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List of acronyms and abbreviations

AC	Associated Countries
AI	Aridity Index
AWC	Available Water Content
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CEC	Cation Exchange Capacity
CLC	Corine Land Cover
DG	Directorate-General (of EC)
EC	Electrical Conductivity
ECa	Apparent Electrical Conductivity
EIONET	European Environment Information and Observation Network
EMI	Electro Magnetic Induction
ESA	European Space Agency
ESDAC	European Soil Data Centre
ESP	Exchangeable Sodium Percentage
EU	European Union
EUSO	European Soil Observatory
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FC	Field Capacity
HE	Horizon Europe
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	International Panel on Climate Change
LUCAS	Land Use/Cover Frame area Survey
MS	Member States
OECD	Organisation for the Economic and Cooperation Development
PS	Proximal Sensing
PTF	Pedo Transfer Function
PWP	Permanent Wilting Point
REA	Research Executive Agency
RS	Remote Sensing
SES	Soil-based Ecosystem Services
SICS	Soil-Improving Cropping Systems
SML	Soil Monitoring Law
SMN	Soil Monitoring Network
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
SOM	Soil Organic Matter
UNCCD SPI	Science-Policy Interface of the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification
UNEP	United Nations Environmental Programme
WFP	Water-Filled Porosity
WG	Working Group
WHC	Water Holding Capacity
WP	Work Package

1. Executive summary

More than ever, the important role that soil plays in sustaining life is recognised. This is, amongst others, expressed in high level objectives at EU scale and in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Achieving these targets and goals is in large part reliant on sustainable land and soil management. As discussed by EEA (2023), soil quality is often described using soil indicators. These are observed and evaluated soil properties, which can indicate the degree to which soils fulfil expected functions as needed for the wellbeing of crops, livestock, and consequently, human society. To be able to use indicators for evaluation purposes, reference values, thresholds and target values are also needed. It is, however, not straightforward to set reference values, thresholds and target values, nor to select appropriate indicators, because such values likely should vary depending on e.g. land use, soil type, climate, degradation type, soil management status.

Several past (e.g. EU soil research projects) and recent initiatives have proposed and published soil indicators and reference, thresholds or target values, including EEA (2023), Soil Monitoring Law (SML, EC 2023) and EU soil dashboard (JRC 2023). This deliverable sets out to review all existing information on indicators and threshold setting, dealing with a range of parameters that can on the one hand inform about soil degradation, and on the other about soil fertility also. A large group of soil scientist from EJP SOIL started from existing literature and recent reviews (such as EEA, 2023) and added its expertise and knowledge in order to provide recommendations for the selection of soil parameters to be used for accounting and mapping soil fertility and degradation changes. Topics like selection of indicators, determining the costs of soil monitoring by using field/laboratory methods as well as Remote Sensing (RS)/Proximal Sensing (PS) methods, scale effects, and modelling were included.

This has resulted in the following main recommendations for specific parameters (for details please consider the respective chapters):

- SOC: organic carbon should be measured for each monitoring campaign together with the texture and the bulk density. Even if detectable changes are not expected within 10 to 15 years, this will allow to calculate the concentration and stock of carbon, as well as the evaluation of results depending on the nature of soils (e.g sand, clay, silt). Based on those results, in combination with modelling and existing data, several indicators can be calculated, such as SOC/Clay ratio (as proposed by the SML), SOC/SOC_{expected} or SOC/SOC_{max}.
- Soil nutrients: total N and available P should be measured for each monitoring campaign.
- ECEC, pH, EC: all those parameters should be measured for each monitoring campaign.
- AWC: with the objective to monitor the soil capacity to reduce the flooding risk the SML proposes to monitor the water holding capacity. We rather recommend monitoring other soil properties such as the infiltration rate and the permeability, at field scale, and the waterflow at the outlet as a percentage of the total rainfall volume for each river basin. Monitoring the structural stability of soils is also suggested as a way to better monitor hydraulic conditions for plant growth.
- Soil biodiversity: not only soil activity (e.g. soil respiration recommended by the SML) should be measured but also the diversity of soil organisms. Thus, we recommend also to sample and identify different groups (e.g. as earthworms, microarthropods, nematodes, bacteria, fungi) for each monitoring campaign. Ecological indicators and indices (e.g., richness, evenness, indices related to trophic levels or soil adaptation) shall be preferred to indicators strictly related to abundance.

- Soil structure: we recommend to evaluate soil structure by using bulk density as requested by the SML. In addition, visual evaluation methods may provide fast semi-quantitative information on the status of physical soil quality and fertility.
- Soil contamination: as recommended by the SML the measurement of trace elements and organic contaminants should be done in soils. The choice of organic contaminants must be defined by each member states depending on history and management. The frequency of sampling can be adapted: not all contaminants need to be measured each 5 years.
- Soil sealing: we recommend to monitor soil sealing with a very high spatial and temporal resolution (every 1 to 3 years). The “sealed area” (percentage of sealed area per total area) should be chosen as the principal indicator.
- Soil erosion: Soil erosion monitoring should be long-term, should take locally important erosion processes into account, and should strive to determine the effects of management practices on erosion. A tiered approach is suitable, and 2 t/ha/yr (as suggested by SML) can be used as a first approximation to judge severity of erosion.

For some parameters/indicators (e.g. SOC, EC, texture) the use of proximal sensing techniques are fairly well developed for estimations and mapping at field scale, while for others their use is still in its infancy (e.g. for biodiversity). But for implementation in large scale monitoring systems, that is for detecting changes, accuracy needs to be evaluated, to determine whether the detected changes in time are significant, given the error of proximal/remote sensing estimations and difficulties in developing general prediction models over large areas. Given the continuous development of such techniques, and the advantages they have over labour-intensive field campaigns and laboratory analyses, the use of proximal/remote sensing in monitoring soil indicators is bound to further increase in the future. Nevertheless, the traditional methods will remain necessary for training, ground-truthing, and for a number of indicators proximal/remote sensing will not be suitable. Using remote sensing for estimations of soil properties also requires bare soils under conditions that are similar and favourable for remote data collection. It should be recognised that the remote sensing techniques only gives information on the surface layer. For proximal sensing this problem is less pronounced.

Costs were collected for each indicator/parameter and show a wide range across EU for most indicators. This assessment provides a good indication of the costs to monitor topsoils: we estimate that to measure all relevant indicators (including organic contaminants and soil biodiversity measurements) would cost between euro 1,000 to 2,500 per location. We also discussed the usefulness of collecting information on deeper soil samples (e.g. for soil organic carbon, trace elements, biodiversity, AWC). This will increase the monitoring costs but as subsoil horizons tend to be more stable than topsoil the monitoring frequency could be lower than for topsoil (e.g. 10 to 20 years).

The best period to sample (either for topsoil or subsoil) may depend on EU regions and on the indicators/parameters to be measured. While certain indicators may be sampled at any time during the year, while others should be done under specific conditions. For example, for soil organisms sampling must be done when they are active meaning in spring and autumn as they may be dormant in summer and winter. Other conditions that can be relevant include soil moisture conditions and soil management practices: sampling should be avoided just after a treatment (e.g. application of a fertilizer or a pesticide, or a tillage operation) because it may drastically change the results. This also means that a contact with the owner and/or the farmer should be taken before sampling to agree on the appropriate date and obtain his/her consent.

Concerning the development of target or threshold values for each parameter/indicator, it was found to be difficult to propose generic and unique values for EU as such values should depend on the local context (e.g. soil type, land use, climate, degradation processes). Hence, we confirm that alternative approaches to setting target and threshold values should be tested. As Matson et al (2023) show, depending on context and data availability, there are several approaches to setting thresholds, ranging from using fixed values from literature for certain spatial units (i.e. soil districts), to comparison with a natural condition set as reference, or defining values based on the distribution within the population in a stratified unit, or even to (percentual) changes occurring over time.

Analysing the different soil indicators, is clear that it will be arduous to define soil districts, as required by the Soil Monitoring Law, which could satisfy the monitoring requirements of all the soil indicators. For example, it is possible to define at least 4 main groups of indicators: 1) indicators linked to chemical/physical properties of soils; 2) indicators linked to hydraulic properties, therefore linked to a management a watershed level; 3) indicators defined by the loss of available soil surface (sealing); 4) soil contamination. Each of these groups may have different monitoring requirements and/or may require different stratification and thus soil districts defined in different ways.

Finally, there is reasonable agreement between our review and the indicators proposed by the Soil Monitoring Law, the EUSO soil dashboard and EEA (2023), except for certain indicators (e.g. biodiversity, soil sealing, AWC) and threshold values that should be rediscussed and adapted to local conditions.

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2. Introduction

Soils are crucial for economic and environmental well-being because they form the basis for agricultural production and also provide a range of other ecosystem services. For example, Hessel et al (2022) mentioned that healthy soils are more resilient to extreme weather conditions (Webb et al 2017), provide better water purification and regulation, buffering and cycling of nutrients (Lori et al 2018), and are more resilient to pests (Bongiorno et al 2019) and climate variability/change (Maynard and Levi 2017). Other ecosystem services provided by soils (O’Sullivan et al 2018) include provision of biodiversity (Rillig et al 2019, Oehlmann et al 2021) and carbon sequestration, cycling and regulation (Bossio et al 2020, Griscom et al 2017). However, these services are affected by soil threats that may lead to physical, chemical and biological degradation of the soil (Attard et al, 2011; Cassman 1999, Gasso et al 2013; Sapkota et al 2012; Hessel et al 2022). These include erosion, compaction, salinization (Cuevas et al 2019), soil pollution (FAO and UNEP, 2021), loss of organic matter (Bolinder et al 2020) and loss of soil biodiversity (Crotty et al 2022). For example, the use of heavy machinery can lead to soil compaction and impaired root growth (Nosalewicz and Lipiec 2014); increased soil cultivation and climate change can lead to soil organic matter decline (Mehra et al 2018); and narrow rotations may cause biodiversity decline and increased incidence of soil-borne diseases (Schneider et al 2014).

More than ever, the important role that soil plays in sustaining life is being recognised, with high level objectives at EU scale (e.g. EU 2020) and meeting the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) reliant in large part on sustainable land and soil management (Bouma et al 2019). Such management should aim at improving the health and resilience of land and soil (Thomas et al 2018).

As discussed by EEA (2023), soil quality is described using soil indicators. These are observed and evaluated soil properties, which can indicate the degree to which soils fulfil expected functions as needed for the wellbeing of crops, livestock, and consequently, human society. Within EJP SOIL, soil quality is seen as an integration of chemical, physical and biological aspects of soil ecosystem structure and function up to, and including, the continued potential delivery of ecosystem goods and services. While soil quality is the potential capability of a soil given soil type and land use, soil health is its actual (current) capacity to deliver goods and services (Faber et al 2022). Whatever the definition, important selection criteria for indicators, and the underlying soil properties, are their responsiveness to management and changed environmental conditions; they must also correlate with soil functions and the environmental processes affected by disturbances and change. As already mentioned by Van Camp et al (2004) the importance of monitoring indicators is that they can give information on how soils are changing over time, e.g. whether the quality of a soil is improving, deteriorating or staying the same under a particular use and management practice. Such indicators are essential to support public policies and assessing their efficiency and success.

To be able to use indicators for evaluation purposes, reference values, thresholds and target values are also needed. The reference is a value for an indicator representing its normal background value for defined local circumstances, usually defined within the state boundaries of a country, and referring in general to a context of soil type, climatic zone and elevation, and land use and management (Faber et al 2022). The target value represents the desired status for a particular indicator or set of indicators given specific ecological conditions, land use and objectives for use (Faber et al 2022). The threshold value could be described as the value that marks the boundary between healthy conditions and degraded conditions.

It is, however, not straightforward to set reference values, thresholds and target values, or even to select appropriate indicators. Several reasons for this can be mentioned:

- For most indicators, factors like soil type, land use, climate, and soil management have an impact on the range of values that can be expected for the indicators (e.g., Faber et al 2022, EU 2020, EEA 2023). This implies that different reference values, thresholds and target values may need to be set for different combinations of these factors.
- Policy considerations may also influence selection of especially target values, meaning that targets for the same combinations of physical factors may be different for different countries or even for different regions within countries.
- Due to the profound human influence that has been ongoing in Europe for centuries, it is often difficult to find undisturbed soils that could be used for setting reference values.
- Evaluation of soil quality and/or soil health is always done with a specific aim or specific use in mind. Often, this aim has been agricultural production, but soil quality will for example be assessed very differently if the aim is e.g. city development or nature conservation. In such cases, not only is the evaluation different, but so is the selection of soil indicators that is needed.
- Similarly, selection of soil indicators should also be adapted to the occurrence of soil threats, as different soil threats necessitate the use of different indicators, see e.g. EEA (2023), Stolte et al (2016). Likewise, different indicators would also be needed for the different ecosystem services.
- Soil quality evaluation may also need to be done differently at different spatial scales. For example, indicators suitable for evaluation of soil quality at local scale may not be suitable for evaluation at regional, national or European scale. This can be due to data availability issues, or to suitability of methods at certain scales, but it can also be due to e.g. the fact that different processes operate at different scales or operate differently at different scales. A well-known example is soil erosion evaluation: at field scale the main process is splash detachment, but at larger scales sediment yield may be determined mostly by rill erosion, gully erosion, streambank erosion and by deposition.

In recent years, several different indicator frameworks have been proposed, illustrating the large emerging political interest in soil indicators. Examples are :

1. EU Soil Monitoring Law
2. EU Soil Mission and related calls
3. The WG on soil monitoring of the EUSO
4. The EU soil experts' proposals
5. The EEA reporting
6. The WG of the new action framework of the GSP-FAO
7. The EJP SOIL projects SIREN, SERENA, and MINOTAUR
8. Other (EC-funded) projects like ENVASSO, ECOFINDER, RECARE, LANDMARK, iSQAPER and SoilCare

The current deliverable sets out to provide an overview of work so far, and to develop guidelines for accounting and mapping soil fertility (including agricultural soil carbon) and degradation changes in cropland. Chapter 3 describes the aims and objectives and summarises previous work, chapter 4 is dedicated to indicators for soil fertility and soil degradation evaluation, and chapter 5 provides conclusions and recommendations.

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3. Objectives and earlier work

3.1 Objectives

Objectives of this deliverable are to:

- Review available methodologies for assessing soil fertility (including agricultural soil carbon) and degradation changes using indicators.
- Develop guidelines for accounting and mapping soil fertility (including agricultural soil carbon) and degradation changes, including:
 - o Selection of indicators
 - o How to determine values for indicators using field/laboratory methods but also Remote Sensing (RS)/Proximal Sensing (PS) methods
 - o How to assess soil fertility and degradation based on these indicators
 - o Examples or showcases clarifying the procedures
 - o How to deal with different climate, soil, land use, nations, scales
- Provide information on reference values, target values and thresholds. If these are not available, suggest ways to obtain them.
- Provide recommendations.

3.2 Earlier work

As mentioned in Chapter 2, several different indicator frameworks have been proposed, illustrating the large emerging political interest in soil indicators. Here, some of the main ones will be briefly discussed, while Annex 1 provides more information on earlier work. The focus in this section will be on the Soil Monitoring Law, the Soil Mission, EUSO, the recent EEA report (EEA 2023) and on earlier work done in EJP-SOIL.

EU Soil Monitoring Law

Introduction

The EU Soil Strategy (published in November 2021) announced a Soil Health Law (due in 2023), which would give soil similar legal protection as air and water (Maréchal et al 2022). The announcement was fulfilled on July 5th 2023, when the proposal for a new Soil Monitoring Law ([Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52023P0201)) to protect and restore soils and ensure that they are used sustainably was published.

The new Soil Monitoring Law (SML) aims to address key soil threats in the EU, such as erosion, floods and landslides, loss of soil organic matter, salinisation, contamination, compaction, sealing, as well as loss of soil biodiversity.

In the impact assessment of the proposal for a SML, the policy options have been described by using five key building blocks:

- (1) definition of soil health and establishment of soil districts,
- (2) monitoring of soil health,
- (3) sustainable soil management,
- (4) identification, registration, investigation and assessment of contaminated sites,

(5) restoration (regeneration) of soil health and remediation of contaminated sites.

The proposed indicators are listed in [ANNEX 1](#) of the SML proposal, as linked to the respective soil threats. For part of those indicators criteria for healthy soil condition are proposed. Table 3.2.1 provides a summary.

Table 3.2. 1 Summary of soil indicators proposed in the Soil Monitoring Law Proposal.

Soil threat	Soil indicator	Criteria for healthy soil condition												
Salinization	Electrical conductivity (deci-Siemens per meter)	< 4 dS m ⁻¹ when using saturated soil paste extract (eEC) measurement method, or equivalent criterion if using another measurement method												
Soil erosion by water, wind, harvest and tillage.	Soil erosion rate (t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)	≤ 2 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹												
Loss of soil organic carbon	Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) concentration (g per kg) evaluated as a ratio to Clay content	For mineral soils: SOC/Clay ratio > 1/13; Adaptation if needed at country scale												
Subsoil compaction	Bulk density in subsoil (upper part of B or E horizon) (g per cm ³)	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Soil texture²</th> <th>range</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>sand, loamy sand, sandy loam, loam</td> <td><1.80</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sandy clay loam, loam, clay loam, silt, silt loam</td> <td><1.75</td> </tr> <tr> <td>silt loam, silty clay loam</td> <td><1.65</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sandy clay, silty clay, clay loam with 35-45% clay</td> <td><1.58</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Clay</td> <td><1.47</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Soil texture ²	range	sand, loamy sand, sandy loam, loam	<1.80	Sandy clay loam, loam, clay loam, silt, silt loam	<1.75	silt loam, silty clay loam	<1.65	Sandy clay, silty clay, clay loam with 35-45% clay	<1.58	Clay	<1.47
Soil texture ²	range													
sand, loamy sand, sandy loam, loam	<1.80													
Sandy clay loam, loam, clay loam, silt, silt loam	<1.75													
silt loam, silty clay loam	<1.65													
Sandy clay, silty clay, clay loam with 35-45% clay	<1.58													
Clay	<1.47													
Excess nutrient content in soil	Extractable phosphorus (mg per kg)	< maximum value (value to be established at country level)												
Soil contamination	Concentration of heavy metals in soil: As, Sb, Cd, Co, Cr (total), Cr (VI), Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, Tl, V, Zn (µg per kg) Concentration of a selection of organic contaminants	Reasonable assurance, obtained from soil point sampling, identification and investigation of contaminated sites and any other relevant information, that no unacceptable risk for human health and the environment from soil contamination exists.												

Soil threat	Soil indicator	Criteria for healthy soil condition
Reduction of soil capacity to retain water	Soil water holding capacity (WHC) of the soil sample (% of volume of water / volume of saturated soil). The estimated value for total soil WHC of a soil district by river basin/sub-basin is above the minimum level (i.e. that mitigates impact of floodings/drought)	The estimated value for the total water holding capacity of a soil district by river basin or subbasin is above the minimal threshold. The minimal threshold shall be set (in tonnes) by the Member State at soil district and river basin or subbasin level at such a value that the impacts of floodings following intense rain events or of periods of low soil moisture due to drought events are mitigated
Excess nutrient content in soil	Nitrogen in soil (mg g ⁻¹)	No criteria
Acidification	Soil acidity (pH)	No criteria
Topsoil compaction	Bulk density in topsoil (A-horizon) (g cm ⁻³)	No criteria
Loss of soil biodiversity	Soil basal respiration ((mm ³ O ₂ g ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹) in dry soil. Member States may also select other optional soil descriptors for biodiversity such as: - metabarcoding of bacteria, fungi, protists and animals; - abundance and diversity of nematodes; - microbial biomass; - abundance and diversity of earthworms (in cropland); - invasive alien species and plant pests	No criteria
Land take and soil sealing	Total artificial land (km ² and % of Member State surface) Land take, Reverse land take Net land take (average per year— in km ² and % of Member State surface) Soil sealing (total km ² and % of Member State surface)	No criteria

EU Soil Mission and related calls

Introduction

The Soil Mission and the Green Deal aim to lead a transition towards healthy soils by 2030 using 100 living labs and lighthouses (EC 2021). The Mission has formulated 8 objectives:

1. Reduce land degradation relating to desertification
2. Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks

3. No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils
4. Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
5. Prevent erosion
6. Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops
7. Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
8. Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

Proposed indicators

The Soil Mission has suggested 8 indicators with the main aim to determine current status of soil health and to track progress towards the objectives mentioned above. The 8 proposed indicators are:

1. Presence of pollutants, excess nutrients and salts
2. Soil organic carbon stock
3. Soil structure including soil bulk density and absence of soil sealing and erosion
4. Soil biodiversity
5. Soil nutrients and acidity (pH)
6. Vegetation cover
7. Landscape heterogeneity
8. Forest cover

The Mission (EC 2021) acknowledges that targets and expected ranges to provide benchmarks for these indicators should be soil-specific showing characteristically different ranges of values for different soil types according to their land use and climate zones. The set of 8 proposed indicators is furthermore intended to be a starting point for discussions with Member State (MS) and Associated Countries (AC) to finally come up with commonly agreed ecosystem types, in which a set of harmonised soil and land use classes with similar properties and sensitivities are defined, and for which an agreed list of indicators will be applied.

‘Once indicators have been measured for a given soil they have to be compared with threshold or standard values that separate healthy from unhealthy conditions. Such considerations are land use and climate specific and cannot be generalized. Work will be needed to define such thresholds or standards for each indicator for each soil type set within a land use and climate context using an agreed standard approach.’ (EC 2021)

In addition to these indicators, it is proposed to track management activities as a proxy for soil health.

Two HE projects working on evaluation of these 8 indicators, as well as on possible alternatives and proxies, namely the Benchmarks and AI4SOIL projects, have started in 2022.

The WG on soil monitoring of the EUSO

Introduction

The European Soil Observatory (EUSO) is intended to become the principal provider of reference data and knowledge at EU-level for all matters relating to soil (Maréchal et al 2022). The EUSO has 5 main functions (Maréchal et al 2022):

1. Support the development of an EU-wide Soil Monitoring System
2. Consolidate and enhance the current European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC)
3. Establish an EU Soil Dashboard that reflects the state of soil health and trends in pressures affecting soil health
4. Support research and innovation through the implementation of the “Soil Deal for Europe”

5. Provide an open and inclusive forum that supports the drive towards a societal change in the perception of soil

The Observatory aims to (Maréchal et al 2022):

- serve all EU policies relevant to soils in partnership with the relevant Commission Services (Different DGs, ESTAT, INTPA)
- closely network with relevant EU Agencies, such as the ECHA, EEA, EFSA and ESA
- build on ESDAC
- build on existing soil data collection projects and initiatives of the Commission (e.g. LUCAS) and closely network with experts in soil monitoring (e.g. Alpine Convention, MS, Regions), soil research (e.g. EJP-SOIL) and soil-related reporting across Europe (e.g. EIONET-Soil), to design and propose a harmonized system of soil data and information collection and diffusion for evaluation at EU scale
- work closely with REA and HORIZON Europe & HORIZON2020 projects on soils
- support citizen engagement and awareness raising actions by promoting the European Green Deal aspirations on soil to society
- interact and collaborate with international organisations such as the FAO, OECD, ESA, UNEP, IPCC, IPBES and UNCCD SPI, to ensure synergies are exploited and data at EU and global levels are consistent.

EUSO established several technical working groups, including one on soil monitoring. This working group aims to set out a roadmap for an integrated soil monitoring system (Maréchal et al 2022). The roadmap (draft due in 2023) will set out concrete ways in which a more integrated monitoring system could be achieved for EU soil data and knowledge, e.g. through the development/deployment of (Maréchal et al 2022):

- Common soil indicators across policies, land uses, countries, sectors, etc.
- Comparison and potential harmonisation of national (MS/AC) and LUCAS soil sampling strategies/schemes
- Comparison of national and LUCAS soil datasets
- Methods to combine national and LUCAS datasets
- Methods to combine existing maps
- Methods to integrate data from RS, citizen data, or private company data willing to collaborate.

Proposed indicators

The WG on soil monitoring has not proposed indicators yet, but as the list above indicates their intention is to come up with common indicators. This will be done in collaboration with MS and a number of the organisations and projects listed above.

An EU Soil Observatory dashboard was developed to present available scientific data about soils in Europe. It includes 16 indicators with proposed thresholds (table 3.2.2). The dashboard will be updated and improved over time.

Table 3.2. 2 EUSO indicators and proposed thresholds

Soil degradation	Indicator	Threshold used
Soil erosion	Water erosion	Erosion rate > 2 tonnes ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹
	Wind erosion	Erosion rate > 2 tonnes ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹
	Tillage erosion	Erosion rate > 2 tonnes ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹
	Harvest erosion	Erosion rate > 2 tonnes ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹
	Post-fire recovery	Recovery rate (RCOVER) < 1
Soil pollution	Copper excess	Copper concentrations > 50 mg kg ⁻¹
	Mercury excess	Mercury concentration > 200 µg kg ⁻¹
	Zinc Excess	Zinc concentrations > 65 mg kg ⁻¹
Soil nutrients	Nitrogen surplus	Agricultural areas where N surplus > 50 kg ha ⁻¹
	Phosphorus deficiency	P deficiency < 20 mg kg ⁻¹
	Phosphorus excess	P excess > 50 mg kg ⁻¹
Loss of soil organic carbon	Distance to maximum SOC level	Distance from 'maximum' SOC > 60%
Loss of soil biodiversity	Potential threat to biological functions	≥ Moderately-High level of risk
Soil compaction	Soil compaction	≥ High susceptibility to compaction
Salinization	Secondary salinization	Areas in Mediterranean biogeographical region where >30% is equipped for irrigation
Loss of organic soils	Peatland degradation	Peatlands under hotspots of cropland
Soil consumption	Soil sealing	No threshold applied (all built-up areas)

EEA report

Introduction

The EEA report (EEA 2023) set out to synthesize the current knowledge about soil indicators in the context of land degradation, ecosystem condition and soil resource use efficiency. The report provides an in-depth discussion of indicators that can be used for the different soil threats. The report notes that *'The development of adequate and broadly applicable indicators and thresholds is challenged by the great diversity of European soils and climate, as well as different political, economic, and social conditions which lead to different priority settings for targets and indicators.'* And *'One reason for not having such a harmonized set of standards is the complicated interconnection between soil functions and site conditions (e.g., climate, soil fertility level), management measures (e.g., fertilizer management) and corresponding soil threats. In addition, views from Member States on targets or endpoints (e.g. water quality, food quality, ecosystem health) to protect, and at what level, widely differ.'* This well illustrates the difficulty in deciding on indicators, as well as on reference values, thresholds and target values for these indicators. Their discussion on indicators for the different soil threats further illustrates this by demonstrating that stratification of indicators needs to be done differently for different indicators and different soil threats. The indicators described in EEA (2023) are

meant to assess condition and functioning of soil, which signal to practitioners and policy makers the success of management practices.

Proposed indicators

Table 3.2.3 provides information on indicators, as well as thresholds.

Table 3.2. 3 Overview of soil threats and threshold investigated by EEA (2023) for cropland.

Soil threat	Indicator	Thresholds	Comments
Soil Organic Carbon	Deceadance of optimal SOC	Sand: 1,5 (1,0-2,0) [% SOC] Silt: 1,9 (1,4-2,4) Loam and clay: 1,6 (1,0-2,8)	Values for extreme summer-dry areas can be lower (< -100 climate water balance) Values for optimal fertilizer management (Wessolek et al. 2008). Proxy: sequestration potential
Nutrients	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	NH ₃ in air: 1 – 3 [mg NH ₃ m ⁻³] NO ₃ in ground water: 50 [mg NO ₃ l ⁻¹] N in surface water: 1.0 to 2.5 [mg N l ⁻¹]	Mineral N: sum of available NH ₄ and NO ₃
	Deceadance of optimal phosphorus	P concentration 25-35 mg/kg (optimal P fertility class)	Extractable P concentration < optimum (value range refers to Mehlich 3-ICP; also available: P-Bray P1 and Olsen P)
Acidification	Critical pH levels	pH < 4.5 - 4.7	
Soil pollution	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metal pollution	Cd, Cu, Pb and Zn by country [mg/kg] (<i>Arsenic could be added; others?</i>)	Country-specific values vary broadly and are not necessarily comparable Stratification by land use and soil texture
Soil erosion	Actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2 [t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹] (soil loss tolerance)	Threshold for shallow soils < 70 cm: 2 t/ha/yr (Switzerland) Soil formation rate: 0.3 to 1.4 t/ha/yr (Verheijen et al. 2009) All erosion types
Soil biodiversity	Loss of soil biodiversity (subindicators)	to be developed: (a) safe minimum standard of conservation (b) Operating Ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	requires sub-indicators by species (functional) group
Soil compaction	Harmful subsoil compaction (subindicators)	Priority (sub) indicators: Saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ks) < 10 [cm/d] Air capacity (AC) < 5 [%]	Exceedance of “action values” (Zink et al. 2011) Secondary subindicators with available thresholds: bulk density, internal soil strength, air permeability and oxygen diffusion
Soil sealing	Sealed area per total area	National targets to achieve No Net Land Take	

The EJP SOIL SIREN project

Introduction

Faber et al (2022) stress that soils, climate and agricultural systems differ significantly between countries and that soil quality assessment would therefore require references and target values tailored at a national or EU region level. Furthermore, developing a system of indicators and evaluation criteria is challenged by the large heterogeneity of European soils and climates, the occurrence of different soil threats, and by region-specific land use and management. Therefore, the authors recommend the use of a tiered approach in which common methods are used at EU level, while leaving freedom to individual countries to implement their specific parameters and protocols of choice and higher tiers. This suggestion is similar to the different levels for monitoring that were suggested by Van Camp et al (2004). Faber et al (2022) also noted that reference values should be differentiated between regions. Faber et al (2022) used a questionnaire to collect information on indicators and thresholds that are currently used in the different MS. The aim of using indicators is to assess soil quality, and to relate this to provision of ecosystem services.

Proposed indicators

Table 3.2.4 provides a list of indicators that are recommended for use at Tier 1 (EU-level).

Table 3.2. 4 Indicators suggested for use at Tier 1 (Faber et al 2022)

Policy Indicator	Soil Quality Indicator
Soil physical condition	Texture Porosity Bulk density
Soil fertility	C concentration Total N P K pH
Erosion evaluation	Based on calculation
Salinity	Electric conductivity
Contamination metals	Heavy metal trace elements
Other contaminants	Recommended to be included
Soil biodiversity	
Water regulation	

Faber et al (2022) provided the following justification for such a tiered approach: *In monitoring and assessment activities a stepwise and tiered approach is a common strategy to break down complex problems and decisions by collecting information in a stepwise approach. This is usually done from an aggregated level down into more detail (as in natural accounting), often triggered by some threshold condition being surpassed and the gravity of the situation and the most likely causes being clarified sequentially by deduction and validation (as in environmental risk assessment). [...] A tiered approach to soil quality monitoring is one that uses the simplest techniques first and advances to more detailed approaches only where necessary. This is aimed to produce information at minimum expense with optimum degree of harmonization across countries to facilitate pan-European comparison and analysis. [...] The essentials of a tiered approach are:*

- *Low tiers are extensive, with few, simple indicators used at relatively low-cost, relatively few sites, and top-soil only;*

- *A 1st tier is harmonised among countries for indicators (not necessarily standardised for methodology, leaving room for continuity in national traditional methods and trend data comparability);*
- *Higher tiers build on lower tier info (related data use), collecting more detailed and specified data, addressing specific national (regional, local) situations, reducing uncertainty, enhancing causality for assessment and decision-making.*

Clearly, for harmonised assessments across EU only 1st tier data may qualify.

As can be seen in Table 3.2.4, Faber et al (2022) also found that some policy indicators are currently not widely used in Europe, and therefore recommended inclusion of soil quality indicators in relation to contaminants (other than metals), soil biodiversity and water regulation. FAO et al (2020) and Maréchal et al (2022) also strongly recommended to include soil biological indicators in soil monitoring.

Faber et al (2022) also investigated the use of reference, target and threshold values for a large number of indicators, using a questionnaire. They noted that: *The reference, target and threshold values that were filled in by the correspondents differed much and were difficult to compare. For example, values can be dependent on soil type, soil layer (topsoil versus subsoil), land use, etc. Ignoring such differentiation, a simple comparison of the values for upper and lower limits of references, target and threshold values as specified by MS for C concentration showed a large variation [...]. The number of MS that have defined reference values for pH and P-availability was also quite high [...]. However, also in these data, differentiations occur. For example, in Wallonia the value for P-availability depends on soil type and pH. Due to these contextual differentiations, we cannot provide reference, target, and threshold values for soil quality indicators based on the collected data. Because of country-specific differentiations, it was also not possible to define reference, target and threshold values per environmental zone (Metzger et al, 2005) or other political or environmental boundaries.*

Synthesis

As demonstrated in the sections above and in Annex 1, various lists of soil indicators have been developed. These lists show similarities but also differences. For example, SOM or SOC is included in almost all of them, reflecting the consensus that exists on the importance of organic matter for soil quality and soil health. As mentioned by several authors, differences in indicators and thresholds can be explained from heterogeneity of conditions in Europe. Different soil threats, soil types, climate, land use, management, policies may all require the use of different indicators and/or different threshold, reference and target values. Faber et al (2022) proposed a tiered approach to make these difficulties manageable. In their proposal, a limited set of indicators would be applied at EU-scale as a first step in evaluation of soil quality. In areas where this evaluation suggests that soil quality may be compromised, furthermore detailed assessments could be done of progressively more local and specialist nature. Given the site specificity at higher tiers, the main opportunities for standardisation are at tier 1, but even so it may not be possible to provide thresholds values for the whole of Europe, as even at tier 1 level thresholds may need to be specified for specific combinations on conditions and/or following different stratifications (see e.g. EEA 2023). For example, SOM or SOC can be stratified based on texture, background values for pollutants vary with parent material, and soil biota is primarily impacted by land use (EEA 2023).

In most cases, it is not possible to select one single reference value, target value or threshold for the different indicators. This because these values should depend e.g. on soil type, climate, land use,

management and geology (parent material), while in addition to these biophysical factors there are also differences between MS. The setting of target values, and to a lesser extent thresholds, is also a political process. In addition, as the different indicators represent different parameters and different processes, which impact the quality of soil in different ways, the way in which indicators should be stratified (e.g. different reference values for different soil types) should be different for different indicators. Finally, indicators, evaluation methods and thresholds may also need to be different for the different soil threats and for different scales. Another difficulty is that reference values can often not be based on original/pristine conditions as such conditions are very difficult to find in Europe. Therefore, several authors have proposed to base reference values and threshold values on the distribution of values that is encountered in the field, using e.g. quantiles or percentages (Bunemann et al 2018). Matson et al (2023) provide an overview of different methods that could be used to set threshold values, distinguishing between fixed value method, using natural reference values, using distributions and using relative change.

Standardization should probably be sought more in the direction of using the same or similar methods to derive reference and threshold values (e.g. Matson et al 2023). Hence, in the following chapters it will be discussed for each indicator:

- What standardisation is possible at EU level
- What reference and threshold values are available at EU level
- Which methods might be suitable for further investigation at higher tiers

Since the total number of indicators that has been suggested is large, a selection of indicators was used in the following chapters. This selection includes:

- Indicators for which literature review shows that they are commonly used
- Indicators that according to the expert opinion of authors of the current report are important
- Indicators proposed by the SIREN project
- Indicators proposed by the Soil Mission
- An important requirement is that indicators should be suitable to detect changes in soil fertility and soil degradation. Hence, indicators that are not expected to show changes over time have been omitted from chapter 5.

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4. Indicators for soil fertility and soil degradation

4.1 Definitions and set-up

Soil fertility and soil degradation can in several cases be seen as two sides of the same coin, as often the same indicators can be used to assess both. If this is the case, soil fertility is the state if indicator values are in the right range, while degradation occurs if they are not. This link between fertility and degradation is illustrated in table 4.1.1. As soil fertility and soil degradation are in several cases evaluated by similar indicators, they will not be discussed separately in this deliverable, but each of the following sections will deal with both of them (see chapter numbers in Table 4.1.1).

Table 4.1. 1 Links between fertility and degradation

Parameter (chapter)	Fertile state	Degraded state	Remarks
SOC (4.2)	Good SOC content	SOC decline, GHG emissions	
Soil nutrients (4.3)	Sufficient nutrients, balanced	Nutrient decline and unbalance	
CEC/ECEC and exchangeable bases (4.4)	Good CEC/ECEC	Sodification	
pH (4.5)	Good pH	Acidification	
Electrical conductivity (4.6)	Good EC	Soil salinity	
AWC (4.7)	Good AWC	Soil aridity	
Soil Biodiversity (4.8)	Good soil biodiversity	Decline in soil biodiversity	
Soil structure (4.9)	Good soil structure	Soil compaction and degradation of soil structure	
Contamination (4.10)		Contamination	No corresponding fertile state
Sealing (4.11)		Sealing	No corresponding fertile state
Soil erosion (4.12)		Soil erosion	No corresponding fertile state

It should be noted that in several cases, degradation processes are not linked to just one parameter, but for sake of simplicity the degradation processes are in this deliverable discussed in connection with their main parameter. Besides, there can also be links between different soil threats, different ecosystem services or combinations of both (i.e. the concept of bundles, which is being investigated in the EJP SOIL-SERENA project). Besides, there can also be correlations between different indicators. However, again for the sake of simplicity, these complex interactions are not considered in this deliverable, and the different indicators are discussed separately.

Each of the following sections is structured as follows:

- Measurement and monitoring with traditional methods (field/lab)

- Measurement and monitoring with PS/RS
- Existing thresholds and target values
- Modelling
- Effects of scale (time/space)
- Degradation processes
- Recommendations

Within this deliverable, it was chosen to describe the parameters/indicators that can be measured from soils and that will inform on their status (e.g., fertile, degraded). Note that a measured parameter on soils, such as pH or organic carbon content, will inform on its current status and if the measure is repeated in time, will also give a trend to decide if soil is improving or degrading.

4.2. Soil organic carbon

SOC (including SOC loss)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Dominique Arrouays, Joost Salomez, Costanza Calzolari, Claudia Cagnarini, Katrien Oorts, Christopher Poeplau, Lubos Borůvka, Maria Fantappiè, Kęstutis Armolaitis, Gabriele Buttafuoco, Johanna Wetterlind, Rudi Hessel, Elisa Tagliaferri, Ialina Vinci, Bo Stenberg, Carlos Lozano-Fondon, Triven Koganti, Emmanuelle Vaudour, Roberto Barbetti, Antonio Bispo ○ Relevant EJP-SOIL projects: CarboSEQ, Steropes, PROBEFIELD, AGROSEQ, SERENA, INSURE
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4.2.1 Measurement and monitoring of soil organic carbon by standard lab analyses

4.2.1.1 Soil organic carbon measurement by wet chemistry methods

Analysis of soil organic carbon by chemical oxidation

The analysis of soil organic carbon (SOC) by chemical oxidation (known also as wet digestion) has long been regarded as the standard procedure since Schollenberger (1927) introduced it. However, the method has undergone several modifications related to the type and concentration of the acids used and whether external heat is applied or not (Chatterjee et al., 2009). In their review article, these authors provided a table, partly adapted from Nelson and Sommers (1996), in which they listed and described the main modifications in wet digestion methods for determining SOC.

Most wet chemistry methods aiming at measuring (total) SOC are a variation of the chromate digestion method. Among the historically most used methods in the Western Countries is the Walkley & Black method (Walkley and Black, 1934; Walkley, 1947). This method uses $K_2Cr_2O_7$, H_2SO_4 and H_3PO_4 , along with the heat generated by the addition of water, to oxidize organic carbon in the sample. A variety of equivalent methods exists, in which either different concentrations and/or different acids are used, at different heating temperatures. In Russia, as well as in several Central and East European and Asian countries, the Tyurin method (1931, 1935) and its modifications, based on the same principle, have been widely used. The also comparable Anne (1945) method (ISO 14235:1998 - Determination of organic carbon by sulfochromic oxidation), has mostly been used in France. All these methods were widespread before the generalization of the use of dry combustion methods and automated C, CHN, or CHNS apparatus, that have been normalized with some standards (ISO-10694:1995 - Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion; EN17505:2023 - Temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon - TOC_{400} , ROC , TIC_{900}). Moreover, wet digestion methods are now banned in some countries because of the deployment of reagents, especially $K_2Cr_2O_7$, which are dangerous for laboratory personnel and the environment. However, due to the relatively high cost of automated dry combustion, wet chemistry methods are still used in many countries, especially in developing countries. Therefore, GLOSOLAN, the Global Soil Laboratory Network of FAO has proposed a standard operating procedure for SOC determination following the Walkley-Black method (GLOSOLAN-SOP-02; FAO, 2019). Automated dry combustion methods require costly instruments, whereas chemical oxidation can be set up with apparatus already present in most laboratories. However, in the case of dry combustion it is possible to analyze many samples with minimal variability due to operator error, while on the contrary, wet methods are time consuming and require careful use of laboratory techniques (Nelson and Sommers, 1996).

The costs of one analysis of SOC by chemical oxidation range 10-30 € (laboratory cost only).

Anyhow, the main drawback of these methods is the incomplete and (highly) variable oxidation of organic matter (Nelson and Sommers, 1996; Chatterjee et al., 2009; Pribyl, 2010). They do not extract the most stable pools of SOC, they are not adapted to high or very low SOC contents, they have different SOC recovery percentages according to soil types, depths, SOC compounds and age, and SOC binding agents. Proposed correction factors are highly variable ranging from 1.0 to 3.7, with 4/3 being typical (Nelson and Sommers, 1996; Pribyl, 2010). Therefore, using a standard conversion factor is a great source of uncertainty. Using old legacy data together with more recent ones to a posteriori estimate changes in SOC, is often biased. Some authors justify continued use of these methods to keep the results comparable with old measurements, but even in this case, the total SOC is not extracted, changes of sampling location might induce changes in SOC recovery, and even changes in SOC compounds themselves may have changed the rate of recovery. Therefore, we do not recommend these methods for future SOC monitoring.

4.2.1.2. Soil organic carbon measurement by dry combustion

Loss on ignition

Loss on ignition (LOI) is easy and relatively cheap to realize. The SOM content is assessed by measuring the weight loss from a dried soil sample (usually at 105°C) after high-temperature ignition of the organic compounds in a muffle furnace. Then SOM is converted into SOC using a factor that is highly controversial (Pribyl, 2010). This method generated many other controversies (Shulte et al., 1991; De Vos et al., 2005; Pribyl, 2010) and suffers from many drawbacks, especially linked to the fact that LOI and the temperature used may involve loss of weight due to other components than SOM. In some cases, however, it may be useful especially in samples mainly composed of quartz and SOM (Jolivet et al., 1998). In the case of O horizons with high SOC contents, this method is still often used. When used for analyses in mineral soils with clay, it is often combined with a correction for loss of structural water from clay minerals (Ekström, 1927). Anyway, because of the problem associated in determining the appropriate factor to convert SOM into SOC, it is strongly suggested to use methods that determine SOC concentration (Nelson and Sommers, 1996), instead of SOM. The equipment and consumables are low cost. The costs for one sample range 5-25€.

Dry combustion and automated carbon analyzer

Automated dry combustion analysis (ADCA) is very accurate, precise, and reliable. It has become the standard method for determining soil carbon (Chatterjee et al., 2009) and it has been normalized (ISO-10694:1995). The sample is mixed with a catalyst and heated in a stream of oxygen to approximately 1000 to 1200°C or sometimes up to 1800°C (Chatterjee et al., 2009; Wright and Bailey, 2001). Total carbon (TC) is oxidized to CO₂. The quantity of CO₂ released is measured and converted to TC. Any inorganic carbon (IC) present in the sample, such as carbonates, must either be measured by a separate procedure and subtracted from TC, or should first be removed by pre-treatment (Kerven et al., 2000). Then, TC equals total SOC. The main advantage of the automated carbon analyzer is that it is rapid and precise and does not have loss of carbon during combustion (Chatterjee et al., 2009). On the other hand, the required apparatus is quite expensive (40-50.000 euro) and special care must be taken in homogenizing the soils (Chatterjee et al., 2009), that should be finely ground in a ball mill. This is due to the size of the sample, which is quite small and there could be a limitation in capacity to measure SOC when it is extremely low, which is rarely the case in soils. Anyway, new instruments have been

developed to perform dry combustion with temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon (see following paragraph), that overcome the problem, allowing to analyze larger samples.

The laboratory cost for one measurement is in the range from 15-30€. The cost of traditional SOC monitoring by standard laboratory analysis (dry combustion) was estimated as 47 euros per soil sample from the organic layer of forest soils in Finland (Mäkipää et al., 2008), though it is not clear which steps this estimation included. The cost of the traditional SOC monitoring campaigns, regardless of the applied analysis method, is greatly affected by the chosen sampling scheme: due to the heterogeneous distribution of SOC and the associated uncertainty, high numbers of samples are needed to detect changes over time, as suggested by power analysis (Smith, 2004).

The Annex 2 (European Commission, 2023a) to the proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law) (European Commission, 2023b), proposes this method as the reference (ISO 10694:1995, Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion – elementary analysis).

Automated temperature controlled dry combustion

Correct and reliable determination of total organic carbon in soil samples is a difficult task because of the numerous problems in correctly separating the organic carbon and inorganic carbon phases. For example, removal of carbonates by acidification could lead to erroneous results in forest soils; furthermore, elemental analyzers are not compatible with elevated acid concentrations (Bisutti et al., 2004). Therefore, a new method has been developed which allows the determination of OC, IC and TC within one single analytical run (Bisutti et al., 2007), that was standardized into the German DIN19539:2016. In April 2023, it was approved as a European Standard (EN17505 Soil and waste Characterization – Temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon - TOC₄₀₀, ROC, TIC₉₀₀) with minor revisions, and it will be published next October. In the last years different companies have developed new instruments that are based on this method, many private and public laboratories have acquired them, analyzing soil and other matrices such as waste and sediment. The advantages of this method are a high degree of accuracy and repeatability and relatively fast analysis, with no toxic reagents involved (Bisutti et al., 2007) as with chemical oxidation methods. The method as specified in EN17505:2023 is for the differentiated determination of the organic carbon content (TOC₄₀₀), which is released at temperatures up to 400 °C, the residual oxidizable carbon (ROC), (including e.g. lignite (brown coal), hard coal, charcoal, black carbon, soot) and the inorganic carbon (TIC₉₀₀) which is released at temperatures up to 900 °C. Basis of the method is dry combustion of carbon to CO₂ in the presence of oxygen conditions using temperatures ranging from 150 °C to 900 °C. If ROC and TIC peaks are not well separated in oxidizing conditions, EN17505 describes also a mixed oxidative/non-oxidative method to better separate ROC and TIC fractions, that is usually not necessary for soils, as ROC fraction should be negligible.

As in ADCA method, the apparatus required is quite expensive, even more (40-70.000 euro), but sample size is larger (x10), thus partially overcoming the issue of sample homogenization. As for the previous method, the advantages are a high degree of accuracy and repeatability and relatively fast analysis, furthermore this method allows to differentiate and determine SOC and SIC, and thus carbonates, in one single analytical run (Bisutti et al., 2004; Bisutti et al., 2007).

Rock-Eval® thermal analysis

The Rock-Eval® thermal analysis technique is often used, as it represents a powerful method for SOM characterization by providing insights into SOM chemistry and thermal stability. The method, first

applied to soil samples by Disnar et al. (2003), is now largely used to characterize thermal properties of SOM (e.g., Cécillon et al., 2018, 2021; Poeplau et al., 2019; Chassé et al., 2021., Delahaie et al., 2023). Briefly, the method involves progressively heating soil samples in a special high-temperature-resistant stainless-steel pod, allowing the transport gas to pass through. It involves pyrolysis and oxidation steps under different atmospheres (pure inert N₂ or containing O₂). Gas emissions are measured by flame ionisation and infrared detectors. Delahaie et al. (2023) recently demonstrated the applicability of this method over the entire French soil quality monitoring network. One major hypothesis of this method is that the thermal stability of SOM products is related to their nature and to their biodegradability. It is therefore not only a measure of total SOC and SIC, but it opens the door to the measurement of numerous indicators of the thermal stability and elemental stoichiometry of SOM. This method is thus not only a measurement of total SOC but enables the identification and characterization of different pools of SOC according to their recalcitrance to biodegradation. We hereafter briefly summarize numerous methods aiming at characterizing different pools.

4.2.1.3. Methods aiming at characterizing different pools of soil organic matter

Numerous methods have been developed trying to characterize soil organic matter (SOM) pools according to their lability, turnover time and recalcitrance to biodegradation. They can be based on physical fractionations, chemical extractions, biological extractions, chemometrics, and numerous other techniques. Several reasons explain the development of these methods:

- The need for better understanding soil processes related to SOM dynamics
- The search for measurable pools that could be incorporated into carbon dynamics modelling (e.g., Balesdent, 1996; Zimmerman, 2006).
- The search for indicators of early changes in SOM nature or dynamics, which may be more sensitive than the measurements of total SOC contents or stocks.
- The search for very stable pools of SOM.
- The search for less-invasive methods of measurement that avoid the destruction of samples.
- The reduction of costs.

Many of them are not yet operational for broad-scale monitoring as not yet standardized (Bispo et al. 2017). However, some of them have been tested on quite a lot of samples and could constitute better and more sensitive indicators of SOM dynamics than total SOC.

Thermal analysis, especially Rock-Eval[®] have been described in the previous section.

Physical fractionation methods

These methods include for example the measurement of particulate organic matter (POM, e.g., Cambardella and Elliot, 1992, 1993, 1994; Gregorich et al., 1994; Pujet et al., 2000), light fraction organic matter (LF, e.g., Arrouays, 1994; Cerli et al., 2012), dissolved organic carbon in water (DOC, e.g. Chantigny, 2003; Akagi et al., 2007; Sharma et al., 2017), hot-water extractable SOC (HWEC, e.g., Ghani et al., 2003; Guigue et al., 2014) or sequential density fractionations (Sollins et al., 2006; Basile-Doelsch et al., 2007).

Almost all physical fractionations are followed by further analyses to characterize the nature, the mineral association or the dynamics of SOM (e.g., Kaiser et al., 2002; Balesdent et al., 1996, 1998;

Chenu and Plante, 2006; Jaddama and Lal, 2010). Density fractionations are often followed by the characterization of organo-mineral complexes both for their mineral phases (X-ray diffraction, elemental analyses) and the nature of organic compounds (e.g., ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance, Basile-Doelsch et al., 2009; Bonnard et al., 2014). Chemical extractions may include treatment of samples by various chemical products such as permanganate oxidizable carbon (POXC, also referred to as Active Carbon, Hurrisso et al., 2016; Bongiorno et al., 2019), K_2SO_4 extractable C, and various acid (H_2SO_4 , HCl ...) hydrolysable C.

Mineralizable SOM

Mineralizable SOM (Franzluebbers et al., 1995) is estimated from incubation experiments. The quantities of CO_2 - that are mineralized from a soil sample, kept at controlled temperature and soil water potential, but under various duration (10- days to 1 year), are measured. It is mainly used together with mineralizable N, to estimate the short time range degradation rate of SOM and the N liberation by newly added organic materials to soil (straw, manure, sewage sludge, etc.). Zimmerman et al. (2006) attempted to relate measured soil fractions to conceptual pools of SOM having different turn-over rates and that are used in a model of SOM dynamics (Roth-C, Coleman and Jenkinson, 1999). Briefly, a combination of physical and chemical methods resulted in two sensitive (particulate organic matter and dissolved organic carbon), two slow (carbon associated to clay and silt or stabilized in aggregates) and one passive (oxidation-resistant carbon) SOM fractions. These fractions were compared with the estimated equilibrium model pools when the corresponding soils were modelled with RothC. Analysis revealed strong correlations between SOC in measured fractions and modelled pools. In 2013, Poeplau et al. (2013) assessed the reproducibility of this method and formulated a modified fractionation procedure. However, according to Poeplau et al. (2018) there is no consensus yet around SOM separation schemes. More recently, Lavallée et al. (2019) proposed to distinguish two main pools, particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) and to separate them based on size and density fractionations (see further in sections 4.2.3 and 4.2.4). However, they stressed the importance of adopting consistent operational definitions of POM and MAOM to streamline interstudy comparison and avoid miscommunication. They showed that density and size thresholds vary a lot among studies.

Chemometrics

Chemometrics includes various methods of laboratory Vis-NIR-MIRS spectroscopy that have been shown to be able to distinguish different SOC pools (Viscarra Rossel and Hicks, 2015). They are described in section 4.2.2.1.

4.2.2 Soil organic carbon measurement and monitoring with PS/RS techniques

4.2.2.1 Soil organic carbon monitoring with spectroscopy and proximal sensing

Laboratory visible, near-infrared and mid-infrared spectroscopy

Constrained by the budget, the number of soil samples is often limited when using standard laboratory analyses, as these are usually expensive and time-consuming. Soil spectroscopic techniques, such as visible-near infrared (Vis-NIR) and mid-infrared (MIR) spectroscopy, have shown great potential in measuring SOC in a rapid and cost-effective way under laboratory conditions (e.g., Grinand et al., 2012; Stevens et al., 2013; Shi et al., 2014; Nocita et al., 2014; Viscarra et al., 2016; Demattê et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020, 2021, 2023). This method is normalized (ISO-17184:2014). Several studies have also

demonstrated the feasibility of predicting the C content in fractions (Zimmermann et al., 2006; Baldock et al., 2013), as well as fractions and chemical composition of the SOC using measurements on the bulk soil sample (Viscarra Rossel and Hicks, 2015; Wetterlind et al., 2022). Thus, Vis-NIR and MIR spectroscopy-based approaches are a promising way for an efficient estimation of SOC fractions, SOC monitoring and modelling (Nocita et al., 2015). Another advantage of Vis-NIR-MIR spectroscopy is that it allows us to capture many other soil characteristics that may be linked to SOC or considered as “noise” for SOC prediction.

However, the quality of SOC contents estimated by these techniques varies, and often has a lower precision when compared with ADCA and their mean errors or root mean square errors which may constitute a limit to detecting small/early changes in SOC. Clairotte et al. (2016), for example, presented the standard prediction error of regression models using visible or IR spectra as predictors of SOC concentration of around 2.6 g C. kg⁻¹ soil for MIR spectroscopy, 4.4 g C. kg⁻¹ soil for NIR spectroscopy and 4.8 g C. kg⁻¹ for soil Vis-NIR spectroscopy on the French Soil Quality Measurement Network, i.e. for concentrations ranging mainly between 10 and 25 g C. kg⁻¹ soil. Higher errors are especially common when using large-scale models (e.g., national, regional) for smaller scales (farms or fields). However, this magnitude of errors can be reduced by using local information and “localise” the models (e.g., Guerrero et al., 2016; Shen et al., 2022). **Because of the sometimes rather large errors, the technique might not be suitable for monitoring small changes.** Nevertheless, for broad-scale SOC mapping and assessment, adding new point data of such measurements to ADCA measurements can be useful, on the condition that they fall within the validity domain of the spectral library used to calibrate their relationships. Furthermore, it should be realised that there is a trade-off between the number and the location of these new measurements, and their uncertainty compared to ADCA data (Chen et al., 2023).

From the point of view of costs, the combination of spectroscopy, the associated collection of spectral libraries, and the modelling of SOC, represents a set of techniques to take under consideration when the number of samples is large, or in long-term monitoring cases. Li et al. (2021) concluded that the cost-effectiveness of spectroscopy would be a good choice for accurately determining SOC on 100–200 soil samples per day with four or more replicates. In addition, the local characteristics spectroscopy associated with monitoring activities allows to track changes in SOC with reduced investment on soil sample analysis. The costs of one SOC laboratory spectroscopic measurement ranges between 10 and 20€. This analysis is thus about one third less expensive than dry combustion. On the one hand, spectroscopy is less precise than dry combustion for measuring total SOC, but on the other hand, the full spectrum may allow to estimate some specific soil organic compounds/pools together with many other soil parameters.

Li et al. (2021) quantified a cost-effectiveness index (E) of soil spectroscopy. Considering both the accuracy of measurements and the capacity of the laboratory on soil carbon content analysis, they proposed the following equation.

$$E = \left(\frac{U_r \cdot C_r}{U_s \cdot C_s} \right) \cdot n \log \alpha \left(\frac{\alpha_s \cdot \beta_s}{\alpha_r \cdot \beta_r} \right)$$

Where E= cost effectiveness of spectroscopy; n is the number of samples; β is the maximum number that can be measured by the method; α= quantity or capacity of laboratory to prepare samples for analysis or spectroscopy; U is MSE in %; C is Total cost; r refers to Lab method (i.e., Dry combustion); s refers to spectrometer. From this study, the portable vis–NIR on the ≤2 mm samples was the most

cost-effective for estimating SOC because it is cheap, accurate and has a large capacity for measurements.

Proximal sensing for estimating and monitoring SOC in field with portable instruments.

In the previous paragraph we have described spectroscopy instruments used in laboratory, but proximal sensing (PS), in strict meaning, is commonly referred to the sensing of soil with field-based sensors that are in close proximity with the ground, i.e., within a maximum distance of two meters (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2011). There are many different types of proximal sensors, based on different techniques and measuring different signals (e.g., Electromagnetic sensor measuring electrical conductivity, electrochemical sensors using ion selective electrodes, and several different sensors measuring different parts of the electromagnetic spectrum such as gamma radiation, x-ray and microwaves; Adamchuk et al., 2011). Most of them, however, only have indirect relationships with SOM and SOC.

Spectroscopy using the visible, NIR and MIR (as mentioned in the section above) holds information about SOM and SOC and is therefore one of the most often used proximal sensors for estimating SOC. In field spectroscopy for measurements of SOC is rapidly developing (Cambou et al., 2016; England and Viscarra Rossel., 2018; Barthès et al., 2019; Angepopoulou et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2020). Compared to lab measurements, in field spectroscopy measurement precision is hampered by the temporal variability of other soil surface characteristics (moisture, coarse elements, rugosity, solar incidence, etc.) and has generally a lower precision than lab measurements (e.g., Franceschini et al., 2018). Mathematical techniques exist by which it is possible to effectively remove moisture effects from Visible–Near-Infrared–Shortwave-Infrared soil spectra (Knadel et al., 2022) The main advantage of in field spectroscopy is obviously its low cost and the possibility to get a very high density of information at the field or rather small areas level. Another advantage is the possibility to reduce time lags between measurements.

Another field of in field PS in relation to SOC monitoring is the use of on-the-go field PS sensors. Priori et al. in 2016 found that coupling Gamma-Ray on-the-go field PS sensing and laboratory Vis-NIR spectroscopy was a cost-effective tool to interpolate SOC stocks within arable fields, limiting laboratory analysis. An advantage of the use of on-the-go field PS sensors is that it may allow to delineate homogeneous areas that can be used as strata for a design-based sampling (de Gruijter et al., 2016) optimizing both the number and locations of samples to collect and analyze by laboratory in order to get unbiased estimates of SOC mean over a given area. The main disadvantage is that it requires bare soil, and that its precision is not good enough to monitor small changes in SOC. It is, however, a very promising tool for low-cost farm- or field-scale SOC monitoring.

4.2.2.2 Soil organic carbon monitoring with remote sensing

Remote sensing (RS) for soil property measurements and monitoring was reviewed in several articles (e.g., Angelopoulou et al., 2019; Tziolas et al., 2021; Vaudour et al., 2022; Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023), in particular for SOC, either from whatever sensor and platform (Angelopoulou et al, 2019), or focusing on satellites (Vaudour et al., 2022). A recent trend is that the availability of RS data, and those derived from satellite (Dvorakova et al., 2023), airborne or unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) imagery, has increased significantly. Ustin and Middleton (2021) identified and described 48 instruments and 13 multi-instrument platforms that collected data since the 2000s, were recently launched, or are expected to be launched in this decade. Some of these, notably derived from multispectral time series, are now being considered as a direct measurement of some targeted soil properties (Demattê et al., 2020; Heiden et al., 2022). They have shown potential for deriving SOC maps from the sole spectral

information (Vaudour et al., 2021; Castaldi et al., 2023; Dvorakova et al., 2021, 2023) or in combination with other spectral layers (e.g., Zizala et al., 2022; Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023). For SOC, most approaches have been conducted on bare cultivated soils: the larger the scale, the lower the accuracy (Vaudour et al., 2022; Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023).

The advantages of new RS products are numerous:

- The weekly revisiting time of new multispectral satellites enables the temporal mosaicking of bare soil pixels to extend the coverage of bare soils. Their increased spectral richness encompassing shortwave infrared spectral bands that cover specific soil features is likely to improve the precision of RS predictions of SOC compared to previous multispectral satellites. Moreover, recently launched hyperspectral satellite sensors such as PRISMA show even more accurate SOC predictions (Mzid et al., 2022).
- Sentinel-2 time series provide improved spatial resolution (10 m) compared to Landsat8 or currently available hyperspectral PRISMA and EnMAP satellites (30 m). A spatial resolution of <10 m together with weekly revisit frequency is expected from forthcoming hyperspectral satellites such as BIODIVERSITY (Brionnet et al., 2022) but covering “hot spots” rather than large areas. For multispectral satellite time series, large areas of thousands km² might be covered with a myriad of image spectra of bare soil surface, while areas are less extended (~hundreds km²) from hyperspectral acquisitions.
- Shorter revisit periods allow for better detection of changes in soil properties over shorter time periods and better capture of soil management effects.
- Merging data from RS products generally provides better predictions than using a single RS product (e.g., using time series to increase both the prediction accuracy and map coverage, using synergistic information to retrieve soil information, or fusing products to increase both spatial and temporal resolution).
- RS can be used to delineate soil sampling strata to improve the cost and the quality of total SOC unbiased estimates on a given area, based on optimizing sampling strategy as described by De Grujter et al. (2016).

There are, however, some severe limitations.

- RS imagery for measuring SOC is especially efficient on bare soils, thus many land covers are missing; the spectral relationships that might be established with vegetated cover are less straightforward.
- RS imagery generally provides information only on the very first 1mm-depth of soil surface, thus the performance of the prediction may strongly decrease with topsoil layer depth, according to the ploughing frequency in the topsoil. The sole RS imagery does not enable to predict SOC in the soil layers below the ploughed topsoil.
- The prediction performance varies according to the type of soil (Vaudour et al., 2019a, 2022), the date of acquisition, the soil moisture, and roughness (Vaudour et al., 2019b) and the presence of crop residues on the surface (Castaldi, 2021; Castaldi et al., 2018, 2019, 2023).

Note that most of these limitations also apply for proximal soil sensing. The precision in SOC by RS estimations is still usually worse than for PSS and especially for laboratory measurements.

However, neither PSS nor laboratory measurements cover extents as large as RS. Furthermore, “bottom-up” approaches combining laboratory spectral libraries and RS might be developed to map SOC (Castaldi et al., 2018; Castaldi, 2021), provided spectral libraries are available at a sufficient spatial density over a given area.

Many satellite products are freely available, the main costs are in gathering in situ soil samples and lab analyses for the calibration, and time for assembling, processing the data, and running the prediction models.

4.2.3 Existing thresholds/target values for SOC or SOM

The question of SOC or SOM threshold or target values, either in concentration or in stock, is very complex. Besides SOC stock threshold values, SOC stock changes can also be targeted. However, the relevance of universal values is highly disputable.

The European Environmental Agency (EEA, 2023) reported that an often-mentioned SOC threshold is 2% (Kemper and Koch, 1966; Greenland et al., 1975, both cited from Loveland and Webb, (2003) and Huber et al., 2008), below which potentially serious degradation (compaction, crusting, erosion) of soil would occur. Note that according to the maps and statistics from LUCAS-Soil, almost 60% of the EU arable soils are already below this 2% SOC. Loveland and Webb, 2003, wrote that for chemical fertility many papers suggested that 1% seems more appropriate.

The EEA report (EEA, 2023) suggested that any typical SOC content can only be determined if specific soil, management, and climatic conditions are considered. Given the diversity of soils and growing factors, one universal value for a critical minimum SOC level may not be appropriate (Goulding et al., 2013). For example, the EEA report suggested that thresholds must consider textural classes and shows an example in which the values presented could provide orientation to evaluate the SOM measurements from monitoring. Note that there is a discrepancy between the minimum threshold values SOC and SOM which were expressed in SOC% in the previous § and are expressed in SOM% in Table 4.2.1.

Table 4.2. 1 Examples of various aggregations of SOM thresholds for Germany. Extracted from EEA (2023).

Soil groups	% clay/fine silt	Koerschens et al., 1998		BMLFUW, 2017
		% SOM in sandy soils	% SOM in loamy soils	Minimum SOM threshold*)
		Upper threshold (range)	Upper threshold (range)	
Light (<15% clay)	4-7	1.0-1.5		> 2.0
	8-14	1.5-2.0	1.6-2.3	
Medium (15-25% clay)	15-22	2.0-2.5	2.2-3.0	> 2.5
	23-25	2.2-2.8	2.5-3.3	
Heavy (>25% clay)	25-32		3.0-4.0	> 3.0
	> 32		3.5-4.4	

Note: *plot specific optimal humus contents

Source: Trombetti et al. 2019

According to Faber et al. (2022), the number of EU Member States that use reference, target and/or threshold values is limited. Among 16 respondents, about half of them have defined a reference value for SOC-concentration (Table 4.2.2). Upper and lower limits for SOC are less often defined, and threshold values are very rare. For SOC stocks, SOM quality and SOM decrease, all these values are almost inexistent.

Table 4.2. 2 Number of EU Member States (out of 16 respondents) that have defined reference, target or threshold values for soil organic matter (SOM) or soil organic carbon (SOC) (after Faber et al., 2022).

SOM or SOC	Reference values	Target values	Threshold values
SOC-concentration	9	4	2
SOC Lower limit	5	3	2
SOC Upper limit	7	3	2
SOC-stock (topsoil)	2	2	1
SOC-stock (subsoil)	0	0	0
SOM quality	0	0	0
SOM decrease	0	0	1

Faber et al. (2022) showed that a simple comparison of the values for upper and lower limits of references, target and threshold values as specified by MS for C-concentration showed a large variation (Fig. 4.2.1).

Figure 4.2. 1 Boxplots of upper and lower limits of the reference, target and threshold values for SOC-concentration as implemented by countries in the SIREN consortium (extracted with permission from Faber et al. 2022).

It seems obvious that one cannot define single and homogeneous threshold or target values for SOC concentration. The values should depend on soil type, clay content, land cover, climate, land use, and several other controlling factors (pH, soil depth, rockiness, CaCO₃ content, mineralogy, etc.). They also depend on the targeted soil functions (chemical fertility, crop rootability, soil structure stability, SOC storage, SOC sequestration), and soil threats (erosion, compaction, decline in organic matter, nutrient imbalance, acidification).

Several approaches can be used to try to define threshold values or target values.

Some approaches use **data-driven statistics**. A rather simple one was defined by Verheijen et al. (2005) for England and Wales by using 2,448 arable and ley-arable sites in the 1980 England and Wales National Soil Inventory (NSI). ‘Indicative SOC management ranges’ were estimated for different physiotores, that is, landscape units for which the environmental factors, namely soil clay content and precipitation were similar. These authors wrote “that these SOC ranges for an arable soil in a given physiotope have potential to support approximate targets for the SOC of arable soils and for estimating upper and lower limits for sequestered soil carbon in arable systems”. We think that these ranges indicate upper and lower limits for SOC storage rather than SOC sequestration. Even simpler target values can be used such as, for example, a given percentile of reference land-use (e.g., forest or permanent grasslands) under similar soil type and climate conditions.

Carbon storage potential may be also estimated by using a **data-driven approach on similar “clusters” of controlling factors** (e.g., clay, decomposition indexes, NPP indexes). Then, a target value is fixed to reach a given percentile of this carbon storage statistical distribution (Chen et al., 2019). This approach can offer advantages from an operational point of view, as it enables us to set targets of SOC storage considering both policy makers' and farmers' considerations about their feasibility. Barré et al. (2017) suggested that this approach could be also realized using mechanistic models. The EU Soil Observatory dashboard recommends using as threshold a value equal to 60% of the maximum observed value.

For **SOC sequestration**, upper limits for organo-mineral soils may be defined by using estimates of the mineral associated OC (MAOC), or mineral associated OM (MAOM) using, for instance, the Hassink (1997) equation. Angers et al. (2011) estimated and mapped the carbon sequestration potential of agricultural soil in mainland France using this technique. Similarly, Chen et al. (2018) estimated C sequestration potential for top- and subsoil for all land-covers provided fine resolution maps at a national scale. The regression Kriging approach performed successfully in mapping C sequestration potential using environmental covariates. This potential, however, may not be reachable everywhere. This means that it could not be a target value but rather an upper threshold for stable SOC.

Martin et al. (2021) combined a SOC map, an inverse **RothC modelling** and the SOC saturation concept to estimate the amount of SOC inputs necessary to reach a given target. They compared these amounts with models of NPP, human appropriation, and estimates of exogenous C inputs. This approach has the advantage of being more realistic concerning the feasibility of reaching a given target under various land uses, exogenous OC availability, and pedo-climatic conditions.

Recently, using a dataset from Germany, Begill et al. (2023) argued that the **saturation concept** might not exist. Their study questions if MAOM can help to estimate the SOC sequestration potential of soils. Their findings “challenge the notion that MAOM accumulation is limited by soil fine fraction content per se”. However, their study is limited to German soils, and they include some samples that are very high in SOC. One can also wonder if different conclusions about the effect of soil fine fraction may come from different laboratory dispersion methods. Previously, Vogel et al. (2014) showed that only a limited proportion of the clay-sized surfaces (“rough surfaces”) contribute to SOM sequestration. They showed that “clusters” of MAOM exist and pointed to the necessity for careful identification and quantification of the reactive mineral complexes that are responsible for SOM sequestration and that control the SOM saturation capacity of soils. They suggested that “such data could be incorporated into current models for estimating the carbon sequestration capacity of soils and can be expected to considerably improve the predictive power of such models”. However, to our knowledge, no cheap and generic measurements have been developed and applied on a large set of samples.

There is still a debate about **accumulating large SOC stocks under forest O horizons**. Some studies argue that it contributes partially to mitigate climate change and that these SOC stocks contribute to C sequestration when part of them is slowly transformed in more stable SOC that can contribute to increasing sequestration in topsoil or deeper layers. Other studies argue that these O horizons stocks are highly sensitive to extreme events like some forest management practices i.e., clear-cutting, or to droughts and fires. From a forest fertility and C sequestration point of view, it might be better to have O horizons SOM with a rather high turnover and quicker incorporation in deeper layers by decomposition and/or higher biological activity. This choice, however, cannot be managed everywhere

by foresters. Some controlling factors such as acidity, waterlogging, or very low temperatures are not manageable in many parts of Europe.

Considering **peats**, a commonly voiced target is to stop their conversion into pastures/croplands and their exploitation as fuels, and, when already converted, to manage the water table level so that SOC stocks remain as stable as possible and/or to stop cultivation and artificial drainage. This last option is hardly economically and socially possible for some countries where many cultivated areas are located on peats.

If the objective is to reach the optimal physical organo-mineral soil properties, especially for agricultural soils, **thresholds based on SOC/Clay ratio** have been proposed in France, Poland, Switzerland and England and Wales, based on laboratory experiments, visual soil assessments, or farmers enquiries (Dexter et al., 2008; Johannes et al., 2017; Prout et al., 2021; Pulley et al., 2023). Dexter et al. (2008) showed a rather constant increase in desirable soil physical properties until a plateau of about 10. They defined this value as the optimal one to get satisfactory physical soil properties. The other authors defined scales of this ratio, most often from less than 7 to more than 13 to define various classes of soil structural “quality”. Note that the threshold value of 10, although not always qualified as optimal, is classified by all studies as rather satisfactory. Most of these studies, however, are from rather similar contexts, and there is a need to adapt these thresholds under different climate and mineralogical contexts. It might also be that these thresholds depend on land use, and they may not be applicable to soils with very low or very high clay or SOC content.

Note that the Mission Board’s proposal to the European Commission for a mission in the area of Soil health and food (European Commission, 2020) recommended that **current carbon concentration losses on cultivated land** (0.5% per year) are reversed to an increase by 0.1-0.4% per year. This % should be interpreted as relative to current SOC content, not as absolute SOC content values. The EU Soil Observatory dashboard recommends that a threshold for SOC is fixed as 60% of the observed maximum SOC. However, the spatial and feature spaces used to define this maximum SOC remain to be defined, whereas the value of 60% can also be adapted to agro-pedo-climatic conditions and to the feasibility to implement practices aiming at reaching and/or staying above this threshold.

Concerning peat soils, the Mission Board’s proposal to the European Commission for a mission in the area of Soil health and food (European Commission, 2020) recommended that the **area of managed peatlands losing carbon** is reduced by 30-50%. There is no real scientific basis to recommend a given percentage of reduced area of managed peatlands. It seems more linked to an expert judgment about the feasibility of implementing this measure. Moreover, estimating the area of managed peatlands currently losing carbon is far from easy, and the proposals for monitoring soil properties may not be efficient to achieve this estimation.

Annex 1 to the proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law) (European Commission, 2023a) proposes for mineral topsoils (0-30 cm) a **target value of SOC/Clay ratio > 1/13**. This annex specifies that Member States may apply a corrective factor where specific soil types or climatic conditions justify it, considering the actual SOC content in permanent grasslands. This ratio of 1/13 comes from rather few studies cited above (Johannes et al., 2017; Prout et al., 2021; Pulley et al., 2023) and there is no scientific evidence that this ratio has a generic signification. We assume that this is why the proposal for a Directive

specifies that corrective factors can be applied. Note, however, that the scientific way to derive these corrective factors is neither explained in the Directive, nor scientifically obvious. Considering the actual SOC content in permanent grasslands makes the hypothesis that grasslands have the most favorable soil structure and SOC/Clay ratio. This might be true. Nevertheless, the value of SOC/Clay ratio to reach in cultivated soils can hardly be deduced from the values under grasslands.

4.2.4 Soil organic carbon modelling

SOC modelling has traditionally been carried out by means of process-based models, that are capable of projecting SOC trends into future scenarios and differ for the scale of application. Most used SOC models, such as RothC, Century, DNDC, and EPIC (Jenkinson et al., 1977; Parton et al., 1988; Li, 1992; Williams et al., 1983; 1984), have been developed and calibrated at the field scale based on long-term experiments. They are multicompartment, linear kinetic models of SOC decomposition, that were originally built upon the concept of SOC humification but were later adapted to the litter chemical preservation theory (Lehmann and Kleber, 2015). While mainly applied at the field scale, the same and similar-structure models have been incorporated in land surface models (LSM), the land compartments of the earth surface models (ESM), and represents a major source of uncertainty in the global predictions due to the still unsatisfactory representation of SOC spatial distribution and SOC pool turnover times (see Varney et al., 2022 for the CMIP6 ESMs ensemble). To overcome these issues, several model variations have been proposed, that aim at describing not only the chemical but also the environmental and biological controls of SOC persistence (Schmidt et al., 2011). Among the models attempting to describe measurable (and amenable to calibration) SOC pools derived from distinct protection mechanisms we cite the MEMS model (Robertson et al., 2019), and the Millennial model (Abramoff et al., 2018), although their application is still limited; the MIMICS model (Wieder et al., 2014), with SOC pool second-order kinetics and microbial functional types, was recently introduced in a LSM. At the microscale, the models focus on the pore network and spatial distribution of resources and decomposers, as in Kaiser et al. (2014), in which microbes are described with an individual-based approach; however, such models are not up-scalable. How to connect the microscale, where processes occur, with the macroscale, where observations are available, is still an active field of research; some proposals go in the direction of integrating models, with the finer-scale models informing the broader-scale models (Lehmann et al., 2020). The traditional SOC models can be a viable tool for SOC prediction, provided that suitable boundary conditions are available: land use and land cover maps are now sufficiently resolved thanks to the Copernicus mission, while soil depth and soil properties are not yet uniformly characterized on the EU territory. More importantly, there is a lack of knowledge in the quantification and fate of litter inputs – leaf and root litter and root exudates – to the soil (Sokol et al., 2019).

Machine-learning models are increasingly used for SOC spatialization from remote sensing hyperspectral and multispectral data (Guo et al., 2021) and process-based model initialization (Sun et al., 2023), suggesting that they might undergo progressive integration with the process-based models in the future.

SOC modelling could be exploited for tracking SOC changes in the EU, and to this end we suggest the development of a common platform for boundary condition mapping as well as model integration, comparison and verification. Note that some models now include crop modelling to estimate organic inputs to soils. Most of the models do not take clearly into account all the mechanisms governing SOC

protection to mineralization, except for adding a clay content effect on the SOC compartments kinetics. These models have several interests and can be used for simulating past changes or forecasting changes under future scenarios such as land-use, organic inputs, or climate change. Several attempts to better quantify the relative size of their compartments either recalcitrant or labile have been made (e.g., Falloon et al., 1998; Balesdent, 1996; Balesdent et al., 1998; Poeplau et al., 2013; Zimmerman et al., 2006).

4.2.5 Effects of scale (time/space) on changes of soil organic carbon

Wiesmeier et al (2019) discussed the different indicators that can be used for SOC storage, and indicated the range of scales for which these indicators would be applicable, from micro-scale to global scale. O'Rourke et al. (2015) stated that "Mechanistic understanding of scale effects is important for interpreting the processes that control the global carbon cycle". They reviewed the mechanisms of SOC dynamics and stabilization at a wide range of scales, from mineral to biosphere. They advocated for a framework integrated across a continuum of scales to optimize SOC management. In their conclusion they outline that "A desirable outcome for SOC management is to be able to prescribe the most beneficial management to achieve desirable crop yield, quantify how much SOC is sequestered per cropping cycle, determine how stable the sequestered SOC is in soil, and estimate how long it will take to utilize the sink potential of that specific soil and arrive at SOC saturation. This calls for better integration of scientific knowledge across scales for effective SOC management".

This conclusion also applies to monitoring schemes and reporting. We need to know how much SOC is stored and/or sequestered in soils, how stable it is, how long it will take to arrive at SOC saturation and/or at a new equilibrium. Furthermore, we need to know if there are threshold values for crop yield or for other services. All the responses to these questions are related to scale and time, and the indicators and thresholds that SOC monitoring should be provided to the decision-makers too.

The typical time interval to detect large changes in mean or total national topsoil SOC stocks using existing national soil monitoring networks in EU Member States has been estimated to be about 10 years or more (Saby et al., 2008). The minimum detectable change depends mainly on the density of sites and on the variance of SOC. At national scale, the variance of SOC stocks depends on the size of the country but also mainly on latitude and range of SOC and temperatures. In other words, the variance of SOC is much higher in the northern countries. In addition, patchy land use at fine resolution may induce the need to increase the density of monitoring sites needed in a country. Overall, the questions of time and scale also depend on what the objective of the monitoring is:

- Do we want to estimate the magnitude of changes (e.g., mean value, total stocks and on a geographical area and/or under a given land –cover or land use?
- For which end-users?
- Do we want to map where the changes occur to put in place more targeted actions and at which resolution?
- Do we want both?
- Do we want to monitor early changes?
- Do we want to monitor only SOC? Or do we want to put in place a "generic" strategy that will enable us to monitor other changes or threats?

Obviously, repeated sampling and archiving and repeated DSM predictions is a potential solution. This strategy is already in place in numerous countries of the world, especially in the EU (Morvan et al., 2008; Orgiazzi et al., 2018). Note that the time step of 5 years proposed by the recent law on soil monitoring and its annexes (European Commission, 2023a, 2023b) to monitor changes in total SOC

seems not realistic because the magnitude of expected changes is very low compared to the variances at time t and time $t+5$ (Smith, 2004; Saby et al., 2008).

Targeting global indicators such as assessing mean or total changes over large areas may require much less sampling effort using a soil monitoring sampling design-based approach (Brus, 2021). Here, previous DSM estimates of SOC, or classification by land cover or land use, or agro-pedo-climatic zones can provide a basis for stratification when optimizing a sampling design-based model.

This design-based sampling can be very useful and save a lot of money and time if the aim is to monitor SOC on long-term observation sites such as the ICOS sites, for instance (Arrouays et al., 2018). If we have no idea about a relevant stratification scheme, an equal area stratification combined with a random sampling in each stratum can be efficient and enables to calculate unbiased statistics in a straightforward way (Brus, 2021). However, we must keep in mind that unbiased statistics do not guarantee that we will detect changes more rapidly. Here also, the time necessary to detect changes will depend on the number of samples, the variance within the plot, and the magnitude of the changes.

If we aim to monitor **and map** SOC changes over larger areas, then we must take advantage of the existing SMN in the EU Member States and at the EU level, and look for how to harmonize and combine them, and for which additional sampling would be most efficient. This strategy has the advantage of making use of past measurements, soil archives, and many other measurements already available. From a pure logistic point of view, it allows us to sample and archive soils for many other threats than SOC decline. Thus, it saves a lot of money for sampling in the field.

Some well-known space effects are the effect of the density of measurements over the feature and spatial space, and the effects of the support used to provide prediction maps of changes. Predicting a value at point scale generally results in much more uncertainties than predicting mean or median values at block scales which may range from 100 m² to several km². There is a trade-off between the size of the block, the variability range within the block, and the targeted end-users of the map. For example, patchy land use at fine resolution strongly increases the variability of soil organic carbon stocks within blocks of medium resolution so that for those landscapes or countries, maps at fine resolution are needed.

The effects of scale (time/space) on changes in soil SOC should obviously be considered for designing sampling in time and space for monitoring SOC.

For the choice of the sampling design, Annex 2 to the proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law) (European Commission, 2023) stipulates that:

- 1. The sample survey shall be designed from a complete sample frame containing the best available information on the soil properties distribution, including but not limited to information resulting from previous national measurements and measurements under the LUCAS-Soil programme.
- 2. The sampling scheme shall be a stratified random sampling optimized on the soil health descriptors.
- 3. The size of the national sample shall meet the requirement of a maximum percent error (or Coefficient of Variation) of 5% for the estimation of the area having healthy soils.

- 4. The Commission sample for the survey set under Art 6(4) may contribute to a maximum of 20 % of the size of national samples.
- 5. The allocation and size of the sample shall be determined by applying the Bethel algorithm (Bethel, 1989) accounting for the required maximum estimation error.

It is out of the scope of this chapter on SOM to detail the consequences, the feasibility, the clarity, and the contradictions between these five bullets. However, some bullets are still rather vague or unclear and even sometimes contradictory. Overall, this proposal does not really take advantage of all the existing national soil monitoring networks, except for bullet 1.

4.2.6 Decline in soil organic carbon: effects on soil fertility, soil degradation and climate change

Conversion of grasslands and forests to intensively cultivated soils have shown a decrease in SOC for many decades in numerous countries and regions of EU (e.g., Arrouays et al., 1995; Bellamy et al., 2005; Saby et al., 2008). This decline after conversion is generally higher during the first decades and slows down thereafter (e.g., Arrouays et al., 1995; Jolivet et al., 2003; Balesdent et al., 1998; Besnard et al., 1996; Smith, 2005). This decline is hardly reversible, as the rate of decline is generally two times higher than the rate of increase if the symmetric change in land use is adopted (Smith, 2005; Chenu et al., 2009). This decrease is detrimental for several soil functions and services which we detail in the following sections.

4.2.6.1. Soil organic matter, plant growth and yields

An increase in SOM is generally a desirable objective for plants, mainly in cultivated lands. Loveland and Webb (2003) wrote: "Better plant nutrition (N, P, S, micronutrients), ease of cultivation, penetration and seedbed preparation, greater aggregate stability, reduced bulk density (BD), improved water holding capacity at low suctions, enhanced porosity and earlier warming in Spring have all been associated with increased amounts of SOM (Carter and Stewart, 1996)." There are clear relationships between these different perceptions of SOM and some views of soil quality for plants net primary production. The effect of SOC on soil water available capacity has been recently discussed by Minasny and McBratney (2018), who showed that, except for very sandy soils, the increase in SOC has a small effect on soil water content. They concluded that arguments for sequestering carbon to increase water storage are questionable. Thus, a better extraction of soil water by plants in SOC rich soils is likely because of the effect of SOC on soil structure, porosity, and plant rooting density and depth. In other words, increasing SOC does not improve the intrinsic soil available water capacity. It improves its use by roots. Therefore, SOC sequestration helps reduce climate induced yield variability (Pan *et al.*, 2009) by improving water availability to plants. For tropical soils, Soussanna et al. (2019) showed a weak but significant positive relationship between SOC and crop yields. Under these conditions, however, the use of mineral fertilizers is often very limited. Thus, SOC might have acted as a source of nutrient supply.

In a recent opinion paper, Moinet et al. (2023), reviewing more than 21 meta-analyses, found that observed yield effects of increasing SOC are inconsistent, ranging from negative to neutral to positive. Hijbeek et al. (2017), when studying a wide range of crops in Europe, found that the mean additional yield effect of organic inputs was not significant, except for some specific crops, and for crops on very sandy soils or in wet climates. Nevertheless, most of the studies advocate for a positive effect of increasing SOC for agricultural adaptation to climate change (Chenu et al., 2019). Loveland and Webb (2003) noted that there is some suggestion from cropping data that a threshold, in relation to N-supply from plant residues, might be at ca. 1% SOC. At this point, decomposition of SOM is in equilibrium with

OM additions from plant residues, and thus SOC remains almost constant. Under these conditions, yields will not be maintained without adequate supplies of inorganic fertilizers. This is important, especially in the contexts where the access to inorganic fertilizers is limited (i.e. sub-Saharan Africa, many low-income countries) and/or when limiting the use of inorganic fertilizers is an objective in order to reduce their impacts on the environment (N_2O emissions to air, water quality protection, energy and fossil fuels emissions impact of inorganic fertilizers production).

4.2.6.2. Soil organic matter and soil physical properties

Significant effects of organic matter on a range of soil physical properties have been reported. These include compaction risk (Soane, 1990; Ball et al., 2000), tillage effects (Watts et al., 2006), stability in water (Golchin et al., 1995) and soil physical quality in general (Dexter, 2004a, b, c). These effects are usually such that an increased content of organic matter results in “improved” soil physical properties. Examples relating SOC content to various measurements of soil structure “quality” (bulk density, aggregate stability, textural porosity) are numerous.

A decrease in SOC can lead to a consequent reduction in aggregate stability in cultivated soils generally and to soil degradation problems such as crusting, runoff and erosion (Monnier, 1965; Tisdall and Oades, 1982; Elliot, 1986; Sullivan, 1990; Guerra, 1994) in particular. The decrease in aggregate stability, however, is not always directly proportional to the change in organic carbon content, and the relation may vary with the method used to measure stability (Grieve, 1980; Haynes, 1990). In loamy soils of southwest France, Le Bissonnais and Arrouays (1997) tested the aggregate stability and the infiltration rate of topsoils ranging from 4 to 30 g C kg⁻¹. The relation between organic carbon content and infiltration rate showed that aggregate stability was maintained if organic carbon content is greater than 1.5-2%. Below this threshold, the infiltration rate of the crust decreased with decreasing organic carbon content. On the same soil samples, Chenu et al. (2000) showed a significant shift at SOC<1.5% for the wettability of natural clay-organic matter associations and its relation to soil aggregate stability.

Davidson (2000) and Kemper and Koch (1966) indicated that many soils in the western United States and Canada suffered significant decline in structural stability if SOC is less than 2%. Similarly, Greenland et al. (1975) concluded that soils in England and Wales with <2% SOC were prone to structural deterioration. Under Australian conditions, Malinda (1995) found that soil loss from 10-year plots under wheat, was strongly controlled by SOC content, with a steep increase in amounts of soil loss at SOC contents <1.6%. It is obvious that SOC is not the only controlling factor of aggregate stability, crusting, run-off and soil loss. Most of the literature, however, suggests that it is one of the controlling factors together with other components (clay, iron, etc.) at the aggregate or ped scale. However, many other factors, often not related to the soil properties, can become much more important at larger scales from field to landscape and globe, e.g., slope, soil coverage by vegetation, rainfall intensity, connectivity between fields, barriers to run-off concentration (hedges, ditches, etc.).

Dexter et al. (2008), using samples and measurements from France and Poland defined the concept of Complexed OC (COC) as the ratio of the clay content divided by SOC (Fig. 4.2.2).

Figure 4.2. 2 The concept of complexed organic matter (COC). Clay content (expressed as clay/n) is shown by the open bars and organic carbon content is shown by the hatched bars. Situations for which (clay/n) > OC are shown in A (top) where, in these cases, COC is proportional to the OC content. Situations for which (clay/n) < OC are shown in B (bottom) where, in these cases, COC is proportional to the clay content. From Dexter et al. (2008).

Using measurements such as bulk density, aggregate stability, micro-porosity, and dispersible clay, they suggested that COC was the main driver of soil physical properties. Based on a large set of French and Polish samples, they suggested that an optimal value is reached when $n = 10$. Using various methods, among which visual soil assessment and farmers' surveys, this concept of the Importance of COC for the structural quality of soil was further demonstrated by Johannes et al. (2017), Prout et al. (2020) and Pulley et al. (2023) on Swiss and English soils.

4.2.6.3. Soil organic matter for climate change mitigation and adaptation

Soils are the largest pool of organic carbon (Post et al., 1982; Eswaran et al., 1993; Batjes, 1996). Most of the SOC comes from the decomposition of plant residues that are themselves linked to the capture of atmospheric CO_2 by vegetation photosynthesis. The SOC is then stored in a myriad of various forms and molecules, that have different residence time, or turnover rates in soil, and return to the atmosphere, mainly by CO_2 emissions. Therefore, small relative changes in world SOC stocks could aggravate or mitigate the global greenhouse gas (GHG) effect, as earlier suggested by Balesdent and Arrouays (1999) and developed in many recent articles (Chambers et al., 2016; Lal, 2016; Minasny et al., 2018, 2017; Paustian et al., 2016; Soussana et al., 2019; Chenu et al., 2019). The latter stressed that SOC storage (i.e., an increase of soil organic carbon stocks) should be clearly differentiated from SOC sequestration, as sequestration assumes a net removal of atmospheric CO_2 , at least for several decades.

SOC sequestration implies that part of the SOC is stabilized and protected from microbial degradation through various mechanisms, whereas other forms of SOC are more rapidly degraded and have a quicker turnover. These conceptual pools may have exchanges in soil, as some products of SOC degradation can enrich the sequestered SOC pools, whereas part of the protected SOC can become more easily degraded through various processes (deprotection by tillage, priming effect, etc.). This vision is of course simplistic, as SOC is stored in a continuum of forms and molecules, and different locations in the soil matrix, that can have different residence times and turnover.

It is generally acknowledged that the main controlling factors of SOC storage and sequestrations are governed by inputs of organic material to soil and their subsequent mineralization rates. At the global scale, the main driving factors are climatic (P, ETP and T) because climate both influences C inputs through the net primary productivity (NPP) and the activity of SOC decomposers through soil moisture and temperature (Batjes, 1996; Stockmann et al., 2013; Minasny et al., 2017; Wiesmeier et al., 2019). At more regional scales, very important controlling factors are land cover, and land use, with a general trend of SOC storage higher under forests and permanent grasslands, and lower in cultivated lands (e.g., Arrouays et al., 2001; Chen et al., 2019a; van Wesemael et al., 2010). Other important controlling factors are clay or clay+fine silt content (e.g., Arrouays et al., 2006; Angers et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2018, 2019b; Wiesmeier et al., 2019) and mineralogy (Barré et al., 2014), SOC loss/redistribution by water or wind erosion, soil water regime (Eglin et al., 2008). SOC turnover rates strongly depend on the depth where SOC is in soil, with a general trend of SOC stocks decreasing with depth but being more stable in deeper layers than in the topsoil (Balesdent et al., 2018). At local scale, SOC storage and sequestration in agricultural soils strongly depend on soil management practices that control input of organic material and SOC degradation rates (Chenu et al., 2019), e.g., crop rotations, tillage practices, irrigation, fertilization, drainage.

Emission of Green House Gases (GHG), in particular CO₂, is of special concern in peat areas. Many peat soils have been drained for agriculture or forestry, which allows oxygen to enter to soil, resulting in high oxidation rates (e.g., Evans et al., 2021). In addition, the oxidation of the peat results in soil subsidence, which can cause damage to buildings and infrastructure, increase flooding risk and make water management more complex and more costly.

Peat areas are also a special case when it comes to monitoring SOC. First, peat layers are often of considerable thickness, so that when peat in the upper part of the soil profile oxidises, fresh peat from lower down the profile will become exposed to oxygen. This implies that SOC content is not a good indicator for peat soils, as oxidation is not likely to result in a decrease of SOC content. For peat soils, SOC stock is a more appropriate indicator. Second, monitoring is generally not aimed at SOC itself, but rather at quantifying SOC loss by measuring emissions. SOC loss can be quantified in several ways:

- Using chambers in which CO₂ (and potentially other GHG too) concentrations are measured, and emissions are derived from the change in concentration during the period in which the chambers are closed. Advantage of this method is that it is known where the emissions come from (provided there is no leakage), but disadvantage is that the chamber influences the system
- Using Eddy Covariance (EC), which measures GHG concentrations too, but from a larger area. This type of measurement does not influence the system, but the measured concentrations are the sum of everything that happens within the footprint of the measurement. For example, in peat meadow areas the signal is being influenced by emissions from the meadows, from the ditches and from other sources
- Attempts have also been made to determine change in SOC stock over time by repeated soil profiling (e.g. Van den Akker et al., 2021). Markers are used to indicate the depth to which monitoring should take place (this depth will decrease over time due to oxidation). By determining the C-content of the soil, the total C-stock can be estimated. By repeating the profiling changes in C-stock can be determined

Third, in peat soils it is difficult to distinguish emissions that come from vegetation, recently dead plant material and from the peat itself. Besides, to properly establish a C-balance one should also consider C added through e.g., manure, and C extracted through harvesting and/or grazing.

4.2.7. Recommendations for monitoring soil organic carbon changes

As stated by the recent EEA report (EEA, 2023), a universal SOC threshold seems meaningless. First, the thresholds or target values depend on the objectives for maintaining or increasing SOC. These objectives can be different:

- Optimize the soil structure quality to favor root development and avoid soil compaction.
- Optimize the structure stability to avoid slaking, crusting and erosion.
- Optimize the pool of nutrients and their availability to plants.
- Mitigate climate change by SOC storage or SOC sequestration.
- Avoiding large losses of SOC stocks in order not to increase GHG concentrations.

These objectives can be, or cannot be, achieved by changes in land cover, land use, or land management.

The losses of SOC in the most northern latitudes are hardly manageable. They are a consequence of climate change, and they are accelerating it. Thus, in this case, the main response to this threat is to decrease global emissions, not to act on soil. In this case, the only recommendation is to protect peat areas by not using peat as fuel, and by limiting drainage depth. The monitoring can involve the combination of remote sensing, GHG fluxes measurements and modelling. The target objective should be of course no net SOC losses but the way to reach this objective does not involve soil science or management solutions. It is mainly related to the planetary issue of fossil fuel emissions.

For other peat soils, a net zero loss can also be targeted by managing the water regime. We may even imagine possible SOC increases by stopping drainage or cultivation, but in many cases, it will be hardly possible from an economic point of view. Note that the Mission Board's proposal to the European Commission for a mission in the area of Soil health and food (European Commission, 2020) recommended that the area of managed peatlands losing carbon is reduced by 30-50%. There is no real scientific basis to recommend a given percentage of reduced area of managed peatlands. It seems more linked to an expert judgment about the feasibility of implementing this measure. Moreover, estimating the area of managed peatlands currently losing carbon is far from easy, and the new Directive proposal for monitoring soil properties may not be efficient to achieve this estimation.

For non-organic soils, several threshold or target values have been proposed. Recently, the Mission Board's proposal to the European Commission for a mission in the area of Soil health and food (European Commission, 2020), recommended that "current carbon concentration losses on cultivated land (0.5% per year) are reversed to an increase by 0.1-0.4% per year until 2050". This % should be interpreted as relative to current SOC content, not as absolute SOC content values. The feasibility of this objective is still a matter of debate, and our review shows that reaching and monitoring these rates of increase is far from evident. The time interval of 5 years proposed by the Directive is obviously too narrow to detect such changes in total SOC. It may, however, be adapted to implement indicators more sensitive to early changes. The EU Soil Observatory dashboard recommends using 60% of the maximum observed value of SOC as a threshold. We recommend that this maximum value is determined within well-defined pedo-climatic zones and considering soil properties such as clay content. The value of 60% should also be adapted to local conditions and to the feasibility of reaching and/or staying above this threshold.

Annex 1 to the proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law) (European Commission, 2023a) proposes for mineral topsoil (0-30 cm) a target value of SOC/Clay ratio $> 1/13$. This annex specifies that Member States may apply a corrective factor where specific soil types or climatic conditions justify it, considering the actual SOC content in permanent grasslands. This ratio of $1/13$ comes from rather few studies cited above (Johannes et al., 2017; Prout et al., 2021; Pulley et al., 2023) and there is no scientific evidence that this ratio has a generic signification. We assume that this is why the proposal for a Directive specifies that corrective factors can be applied. Note, however, that the scientific way to derive these corrective factors is neither explained in the Directive, nor scientifically obvious. Considering the actual SOC content in permanent grasslands makes the hypothesis that grasslands have the most favourable soil structure and SOC/Clay ratio. This might well be true. Nevertheless, the value of SOC/Clay ratio to reach in cultivated soils can hardly be deduced from the values under grasslands. Applying the SOC:Clay ratio to about 3000 topsoils in Germany, Poeplau and Don (2023) recently argued that this ratio is not a suitable SOC level metric since strongly biased, misleading and partly insensitive to SOC changes. Instead, they proposed to use the ratio between actual and expected SOC ($SOC:SOC_{exp}$), where expected SOC is derived from a regression between SOC and clay content. Note that the definition of this ratio is rather close to the proposal of the EU Soil Observatory dashboard, though the threshold of 60% suggested by this dashboard should be adapted to local conditions. Indeed, the indicators $SOC:SOC_{exp}$ and/or $SOC:SOC_{max}$ should be more relevant than SOC:Clay, especially if they are applied on rather homogeneous pedo-climatic zones. Further research is needed to define the best methods to calculate and apply these indicators and to assess which monitoring efforts and sampling schemes are needed to implement them.

The main conclusion of this chapter is that these threshold, trigger or target values could be defined using different approaches.

- a. Data driven analysis on soil carbon landscape zones that should involve to take into account i) soil types and main soil SOC controlling properties (e.g., particle-size distribution, depth, pH, water-logging, mineralogy), ii) climatic conditions (mainly P and T), iii) land cover, land-use, main soil management practices, availability of exogenous organic material products.
- b. Collection of results from a network of long-time observations and experiments, which should cover as much as possible the situations cited before.
- c. Modelling, on the condition that enough input data is available, that the results of the models are validated, and that their validity domain is clearly defined both in feature and space domains.

Thus, there is no EU widely commonly accepted indicator or threshold values. They might be relevant according to specific strata depending on all the SOC controlling factors defined above. They must be validated using measurements of SOC, of SOC composition, and of turn-over rates of SOC components. Even validated, the use of these threshold values will remain highly arguable. We should consider the possibility of reaching them, and the risk of promoting highly reversible practices. Increasing SOC stocks in the O horizon of forest is a good example: it may have short-term effect on SOC storage, but it is highly at risk if fire occurrence increases with severe droughts. Defining a target value for a given area highly depends on the feasibility of increasing organic matter inputs to soils and on pedo-climatic conditions controlling SOC mineralisation rates.

Whatever the indicators and/or thresholds we must stress that the certification of the laboratories is crucial to guarantee the quality and the comparability of the analysis.

Although many efforts are currently made in the EU to collect data on soils, at local, national or EU level, we still miss some crucial data and knowledge to map and model SOC dynamics in space and time with a satisfactory resolution and precision.

We can of course derive some estimates of SOC changes and their consequences by long-term monitoring, by spatio-temporal analysis or space-time substitution, by improving modeling, and by trying to measure some pools that are sensitive or recalcitrant to changes. We must refine thresholds and target values according to different soil carbon landscape zones.

We can also derive estimates of the uncertainties of the predictions. We know that these estimates can be more or less robust. However, even if we attempt to estimate the uncertainties, they will remain very large, and their spatial distribution will be difficult to assess.

Some will argue that getting estimates with large uncertainties is better than getting nothing. We fully agree on that, however, we should remain very cautious about the results that we deliver and the way we communicate about them.

Increasing the amount of data thanks to national and EU monitoring systems is one key of the solutions. Characterizing SOC by fractionation, thermal, chemometrics, or biological analyses will open the door both to a better understanding of processes, and to operational and measurable indicators. The possibilities offered by sample archives, spectral libraries, proximal and remote sensing are just in their infancy. Increasing and sharing results of long-term observatories and experiments is another complementary way to improve our knowledge and to feed modeling. Comparing models or mixing them is another promising way.

As said previously, the challenges are to progress in data acquisition, in a better characterization of SOC turnover, in new technology developments, in process knowledge, and in modeling.

We should not be discouraged by the high uncertainties that we have at present. We should try to reduce them, and we should come to relevant indicators, threshold, trigger, and target values and assess their local applicability and feasibility.

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4.3 Soil nutrients and nutrient balance

<p>Soil nutrients (including nutrients unbalance)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Bo Stenberg, Johanna Wetterlind, Joost Salomez, Carlos Lozano-Fondon, Ialina Vinci, Karin Blombäck, Emmanuelle Vaudour ○ Relevant EJP SOIL projects: AGROseqC, SERENA
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4.3.1 Soil nutrients measurement and monitoring by wet chemistry methods

What nutrients to monitor and whether total amounts or labile nutrients are what is of most interest depends on the purpose of the monitoring, the land use and maybe even overall management context. For agricultural soils, plant nutrients are interesting as fertility indicators and to assess environmental risks when in excess. In this context labile nutrients that are more or less readily available to plants are of interest. Thus, for fertility and fertilizing purposes, total amounts of nutrients are often not as informative as plant available nutrients. Since it is the excess of labile nutrients not taken up by plants that are at risk of being lost to the environment, plant available nutrients are often also good indicators for environmental risks (Amery et al., 2019). Nutrient availability is largely affected by other soil properties such as pH, organic matter content and soil texture, which is why several of the other indicators discussed in the other chapters are relevant also in relation to soil nutrients.

The most important plant macro nutrients are nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) which are often included in both larger monitoring systems and farmers' farm soil mapping (EJP SOIL D2.13; D6.1; Faber et al., 2022). In agricultural soils, other nutrients, including both macro and micronutrients, may also be of interest as soil fertility indicators (for further discussion of micronutrients see chapter 4.12 about soil contamination). However, N and P are the main concern in terms of environmental risks. A monitoring system including these two nutrients will therefore capture the most important nutrients both in terms of fertility and environmental risks and can be considered as a feasible compromise for a minimum set of nutrient indicators included in a general monitoring system covering a wide range of land uses.

For plant **available P** ammonium lactate (P-AL; Egnér et al., 1960) and Olsen P (Olsen et al., 1954) are the most common extraction methods in agricultural laboratories in Europe according to EJP Soil deliverable 2.13 (Higgins et al., 2023). However, a number of other methods, like Mehlich III (Mehlich, 1984) and Bray Kurtz (Bray & Kurtz, 1945), are also used and quite often with slight differences in the methodology such as pH and soil extraction ratios.

The standard method chosen in a region or a country typically depends on soil type. For example, P-AL is preferred in regions dominated by acidic to neutral soils while Olsen is preferred where calcareous soils are common. Often, but not always (according to Higgins (2023)), the same extraction method as for P is used for other soil nutrients such as potassium, magnesium and calcium, as well as iron and aluminum. The ammonium lactate extraction and Mehlich III are typically used also for other elements, whereas the Olsen method is only used for P. The possibility to use the same extraction method for several nutrients is of course cost effective and an advantage of those methods. Different methods have been standardized by FAO: GLOSOLAN-SOP-09: Bray I and II (FAO, 2021a); GLOSOLAN-SOP-10: Olsen (FAO, 2021b); GLOSOLAN-SOP-11: Mehlich I (FAO, 2021c). ISO 11263:1994 is the standard

method adopted in LUCAS and is a NaHCO₃ extraction to determine the content of soil phosphorus comparable to the Olsen P method.

The methods used in national monitoring systems or provided by the national laboratories are often linked to agricultural fertilization advice based on field trial series reaching several years back in time. Changing from one analysis method to another is therefore not a trivial task. One problem is the difficulties with converting between the different extraction methods. Mehlich III and Olsen P were found to correlate very well over a wide pH range in lowa soils but with substantially lower values for Olsen, as this method uses a weaker extractant (Mallarino, 1997; Steinfurth et al., 2021). P-AL is a stronger extractant than used in both Mehlich III and Olsen, but tends to overestimate available P at higher pH (Steinfurth et al., 2021). Steinfurth et al. (2021) reviewed the conversion of P-tests widely used in Europe. As the most common method used within and outside Europe, Olsen-P was defined as the joint target of conversion (i.e. the aim is to convert results of other methods to Olson) . Conversion coefficients from a range of tests to Olsen varied considerably within each test and the performance of conversion equations also varied considerably. From P-AL conversion factors varied between 0.27 and 0.44. The differences were largely attributed to differences in the pH range covered, but also to clay content. The conversion from Mehlich III to Olsen varied as much but was not as clearly attributed to pH. For all tests the type of equation could also be a factor that can help explain the accuracy of conversion. For example, Ottonbong et al. (2009) found it possible to convert between P-AL and Olsen P with a reasonable high accuracy when accounting for pH and clay content in the conversion equation. Steinfurth et al. (2021) concluded that the conversion from one test to another will always contain a large portion of error and equation parameters will be highly dependent on soil type. Therefore, for changing from one standard to another, such as the harmonization within EU to ISO 11263 as suggested in the Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law; European Commission, 2023a), must involve systematic lab and field trials to synchronize national and regional fertilization recommendations.

Nitrogen is analyzed as both total N by extraction (often Kjeldahl) and as mineral N in the forms of NO₃⁻ and NH₄⁺. Extractions or incubations to estimate mineralizable N also occur (EJP SOIL D2.13 and Higgins et al., 2023). Plants take up most of the N as mineral N and the available forms are mineralized from N-compounds in the organic matter. However, analysis of the mineral N will only give a snapshot in time largely depending on the short-term weather situation, and recent crops and fertilizer management, making those analyses difficult to interpret and include in a large-scale monitoring system.

The Kjeldahl method is a standard method for nitrogen determination described in the GLOSOLAN-SOP-14 (FAO, 2021e) and ISO 11261:1995 is a modified Kjeldahl method to which the Soil Monitoring Law proposal refers to. FAO also proposes the Dumas dry combustion method described in the GLOSOLAN-SOP-13 (FAO, 2021d). As an ISO standard there is ISO 13878:1998 - Determination of total nitrogen content by dry combustion (elemental analysis). For determination of nitrate and ammonium there are three ISO standards: ISO 14255:1998 -Determination of nitrate nitrogen, ammonium nitrogen and total soluble nitrogen in air-dry soils using calcium chloride solution as extractant, ISO 14256-1:2003 - Determination of nitrate, nitrite and ammonium in field-moist soils by extraction with potassium chloride solution — Part 1: Manual method and ISO 14256-2:2005 - Determination of nitrate, nitrite and ammonium in field-moist soils by extraction with potassium chloride solution — Part 2: Automated method with segmented flow analysis.

4.3.2 Soil nutrients monitoring measurement and monitoring with PS/RS techniques

Proximal and remote sensing techniques for soil nutrients is potentially very useful. Especially for plant available fractions as some are very dynamic and estimates would be needed frequently. At present there are, however, few established services in this respect. Remote sensing research on crop nutrient monitoring has focused mainly on biomass and nitrogen (N) estimation from vegetation characteristics (e.g., Mahajan et al., 2017). Indeed, these vegetation indices are implemented in digital decision support systems for precise variable rate nitrogen fertilization (e.g., Plondlot et al., 2005; Söderström et al., 2017). For detailed nitrogen fertilization advice this approach has been more successful than any soil N estimates and several commercial services to farmers are available across Europe and are increasingly implemented. Kashyap and Kumar (2021) reviewed the proximal sensing devices and methodologies for monitoring purposes, but these are mostly based on tedious laboratory-based methods: ion-selective membrane (ISM)-based electrochemical (EC) sensors, other biosensing methods, and electrophoresis-based methods.

Rather than monitoring, studies have dealt with the feasibility of predicting soil nutrients, either from lab measurements (Kuang and Mouazen, 2011; Vaudour et al., 2018), from field measurements (Mahajan et al., 2017), or in a more spatially exhaustive manner from airborne hyperspectral imagery (Gomez et al., 2012) and from spectral satellite imagery (Vaudour et al., 2019; Song et al., 2020; Hengl et al., 2021; Gasmi et al. 2022). Most approaches were carried at a local field or farm scale and few of them dealt with small regions covering some tens or hundreds of km².

Few studies dealt with rapid and portable field measurements of soil nutrients. An et al. (2014) reported on a portable soil nitrogen detector based on near-IR spectroscopy and using Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN). Song et al. (2018) used hyperspectral images of the Chinese Environmental 1A satellite (visible-near-infrared data) for mapping and monitoring total soil N, available P and available K at the regional scale. At a farm scale, UV-Vis fluorescence lab measurements were carried out in conjunction with lab reflectance measurements in the Vis-NIR-SWIR range over a Mediterranean wine estate with contrasting soil types. PLSR predictions from Vis-NIR-SWIR reflectance spectra and/or from a set of fluorescence signals enabled to predict key agronomic soil properties including N tot, CaCO₃, iron, and exchangeable Ca²⁺, K⁺, Na⁺ and Mg²⁺ (Vaudour et al., 2018). At the studied farm the predictive ability of single fluorescence indices or original signals was very significant for topsoil. These results open encouraging perspectives for using miniaturized fluorescence devices enabling red excitation coupled with red or far-red fluorescence emissions directly in the field. However, in this study neither P nor exchangeable K could be accurately predicted.

It must be recognized that the above-mentioned results to an overwhelming degree originate from spectrophotometric measurements, typically in the Vis-NIR-SWIR (~350-2500nm) range from various platforms. In this region soil spectra are mainly affected by absorption in molecular bonds associated to organic matter, clay minerals and some other minerals and water. Salts, as in mineral nutrients, do not absorb and other nutrient complexes that may absorb in this range are present in too small quantities to have a significant influence on spectra. Instead, the relationships that can be found between spectra and nutrient status are to be explained by secondary relationships that are often very local (Stenberg et al., 2010; Wetterlind et al., 2008). Thus, results so far are limited to local studies and generalizations should be made with great care. Occasionally commercial devices for field measurements of a range of soil properties, like soil type, organic matter content and nutrient status

emerge on the market. To what extent these are able to give reliable results is sparsely tested, but before wider use they must be validated and possibly re-calibrated at least regionally.

Ion-selective electrodes and ion-selective field effect transistors detect specific ions (e.g. H^+ , NO_3^- , K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) in a soil solution, either through a sample preparation with a controlled soil:extractant ratio, or directly at a given soil state (Adamchuk et al., 2018). Whereas approaches using a controlled solution ratio require more time and more elaborate sampling, direct measurements need to be combined with other information on the soil.

Another PS technique that allows the monitoring of soil nutrients is X-ray fluorescence (XRF). This is a type of spectroscopy that involves the emission of x-ray photons (photoelectrons) coming from excited atoms that have been primarily exposed to x-rays. The de-excitation process of atoms emits fluorescence (XRF) that corresponds to the transition of electrons throughout atomic orbitals. The energy characterizing the electron transition is unique for each atom and so, a spectrum can be assigned to specific chemical elements. In addition, the intensity of the fluorescence is directly proportional to the number of atoms, which allows the estimation of the element concentration. This last property allows the use of XRF as a quantitative analytic technique; however, it is also possible to assess qualitative and semi-quantitative properties to soil measurements. Common uses of XRF in agronomy are directed to the determination of soil nutrients and soil fertility (i.e., Al^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , and P) with estimation accuracies ranging from $R^2 = 0.14$ to $R^2 = 0.71$ depending on the element (Andrade et al., 2020). Data fusion combining two or more sensor techniques are increasing in research reports (Wang, 2015; Wetterlind et al., 2015).

4.3.3 Existing thresholds/target values for soil nutrients

The amount of nutrients in soil is typically given as either total or extractable (mimicking plant available nutrients). As indicated in 4.3.1 several extraction methods are employed for available nutrients and the analytical results are related to fertilization advice through field experiments estimating the yield response.

From an agricultural point of view the starting-point should be a balanced fertilization for good nutrient use efficiency, which requires education and extension, research and the development of decision support systems. Soil analysis is a very important prerequisite for this. However, the presence and availability of nutrients is largely dependent on other soil quality indicators such as SOM, pH, mineralogy and texture. In addition, crop requirements are crop and climate (weather) dependent. Considering this, fixed, general thresholds for plant nutrients might be difficult to define or even not desired.

For phosphorus, EEA (2023) suggests that a threshold can be identified above which risk for leaching and losses increase and below which risks for yield loss (or increased fertilizer requirements) increase. For phosphorus 25-35 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ as extracted by Mehlich III-ICP is suggested. In agriculture these tests are otherwise used for fertilization recommendations following much more elaborate crop and soil dependent scales. According to the Swedish board of agriculture, as an example, a P-AL of 80-120 mg/kg is regarded as a balanced amount that only requires harvested P to be replaced. With the exception of potatoes, maize and sugar beets, fertilization above this level is not recommended (Jordbruksverket, 2022). EUSO considers soil to have P deficiency below 20 $mg\ P\ kg^{-1}$ (Olsen P) and

excess above 50 mg P kg⁻¹. Taking into consideration also what is included in today's European national monitoring systems, Faber et al., (2022) propose to include both extractable P and K. However, they do not specify a particular extraction method or suggest any thresholds. It must be recognised that nutrient levels in soil depend largely on other soil properties, geology, climate and historical land use in addition to present management. Also, the risk for leaching depends on soil and landscape properties as described in section 4.3.6, rendering some soils more sensitive than others.

Compared to phosphorus, nitrogen is highly dynamic and is by microbiological processes rapidly transferred between organic and mineral states as well as from ammonium to nitrate. Nitrate is easily leached and can be denitrified and lost in gaseous forms. EEA (2023) therefore suggests environmental and health thresholds to be estimated from concentrations of NH₃ in air and NO₃⁻ in water. Whereas the threshold suggested by EUSO is based on N surplus (N input minus N output) instead of N measurements, with a threshold of more than 50 kg ha⁻¹. Faber et al (2022) propose to use total N in the soil, but do not suggest a threshold. Total nitrogen is also included as a descriptor in the proposed Soil Monitoring Law without a threshold. As for P, different soils are differently vulnerable to N losses, as further discussed in section 4.3.6.

Table 4.3. 1 Proposed soil nutrient indicators and thresholds.

Source	Nutrients	Method	Thresholds	Relevant land use
EUSO	N	Total	N surplus > 50kg ha ⁻¹	Agricultural
	P	Extractable Olsen P	P deficiency < 20 mg kg ⁻¹	Agricultural
			P excess > 50 mg kg ⁻¹	Agricultural
EEA, 2023	N	Mineral N, in air and water	NH ₃ in air: 1 – 3 (mg NH ₃ m ⁻³) NO ₃ in ground water: 50 (mg NO ₃ l ⁻¹) N in surface water: 1.0 to 2.5 (mg N l ⁻¹)	Agricultural
	P	Extractable (value range refers to Mehlich III-ICP; also available: P-Bray P1 and Olsen P)	P concentration 25-35 mg kg ⁻¹ (optimal P fertility class)	
Faber et al., (2022)	N	Total	Nothing suggested	Agricultural
	P	Extractable (not specified)	Nothing suggested	Agricultural
	K	Extractable (not specified)	Nothing suggested	Agricultural
SML	P	Extractable ISO 11263: 1994 (~Olsen P)	< Maximum value to be established at country level within the range 30-50 mg kg ⁻¹	All
	N	Total ISO 11261:1995 (a modified Kjeldahl method)	No criteria	

4.3.4 Soil nutrients modelling and nutrient unbalance modelling

As for organic matter and carbon, soil nutrients, especially nitrogen, are traditionally modelled by process-based soil and crop models. Typically, these are built for scientific purposes and calibrated on long- and short-term field experiments. These models tend to be very complex and require large amounts of input data. For practical agricultural decision support purposes simplified models requiring less input data to work satisfactory are developed. A detailed description of such models is found in Cammerano et al. (2023). As advisory tools for agriculture, balance models are more common and practical as they are based on data directly connected to farm management which normally are available at the farm scale. To estimate and monitor unbalances of any nutrient, balances can be calculated at a larger scale as for example reported by OECD at a national scale (<https://data.oecd.org/agrland/nutrient-balance.htm>). According to OECD's definition the balance is the difference between input to the system as organic and mineral fertilizers and output as harvested yield. For mitigation purposes and policy making there are also examples of models and digital tools that estimate risks for leaching and losses to the environment (for example: Martin et al., 2021; Johnsson et al., 2022). These are typically based on soil type, management information and are weather driven. In that sense the actual monitoring required for modelling is for soil and management combined with standard climatic information.

4.3.5 Effects of scale on changes of soil nutrients

In agricultural soils, the practical management decisions are made at the farm and field (or even within-field) scale. To manage nutrients, the key for avoiding nutrient unbalance, is to match nutrient inputs with crop demands (Pavlu et al., 2021). To be able to do that, information is needed at a field and within field scale, which is at a much higher level of detail than possible in a national or even regional monitoring system. Soil types may vary rapidly over short distances and hot spots for nutrient availability may be found as well as critical areas for erosion and phosphorus leaching. The situation known as the 80:20 rule suggests that 80% of lost phosphorus originates from a small part (20%) of a catchment (Sharpley et al. 2009). Similar variability can be found within fields (Gburek et al. 2000). Djodjic & Villa (2015) concluded that these small critical source areas of a catchment could be identified through high-resolution digital elevation modelling combined with soil and land use data. They also concluded that this approach could form the basis for site-specific mitigation actions. Variability at a fine scale in nitrogen availability and leaching has proven to not be readily predicted through detailed soil mapping. Crop requirement of nitrogen is nevertheless well known to vary substantially over short distances as indicated by increasingly implemented variable rate nitrogen application systems as discussed in 4.3.2. Similarly risks for nitrogen losses, both through leaching in gaseous forms, are highly dependent on soil type as discussed in 4.3.6.

The monitoring systems can follow the large trends over time and make sure that the nutrient status in the soil does not decline or accumulate above what is considered to result in increased environmental risks. However, as fundamental features like soil geological origin and landscape play important roles in leaching and losses, changes in parameters reflecting these, like texture, mineralogy and elevation, are not to be expected and repeated monitoring is not relevant, but rather the establishments of target areas for mitigation efforts like for example buffer zones, managing drainage water, catch crops, etc. Monitoring system on the large scale should not be used to guide on farm decisions. Nutrient levels in the soil change slowly over the long term, even if rapid short-term changes can be observed.

4.3.6 Nutrient unbalance: effects on soil and environment

Phosphorous and nitrogen are globally essential for crop production and food security. Resources naturally occurring in the soil and through recycling have been supplemented with mineral fertilizers for at least a century (Sutton et al., 2013). At the same time, both have a history of causing severe environmental impact when in surplus. Both cause eutrophication of surface waters through leaching and runoff. Pollution of ground water is especially a problem in regions with dense animal production with significant feed import and subsequently an unbalanced availability of nutrients in manure. Nitrogen is also lost to the environment as gaseous ammonia (NH_3) and dinitrogen oxide (N_2O). Ammonia has consequences locally both by its toxicity and as an odor problem, and N_2O is a severe greenhouse gas. Nitrogen can also be lost as nitrogen gas (N_2), which is not a problem as such, but reduces nitrogen use efficiency in a cropping system, which, if replaced by mineral fertilizers is costly and requires significant energy input in production and distribution.

To avoid environmental impact of nutrients from agricultural systems a high nutrient use efficiency should be strived for, and high levels of mineral nitrogen and labile forms of phosphorus in the soil avoided (Delin & Stenberg, 2014). The nitrogen fertilizer efficiency varies widely, often with a substantial potential for improvement (Cassman & Dobermann, 2022). Pavlu et al. (2021) concluded that specified single indicators for nutrient unbalance cannot be established, but fertilizer advice based on crop requirements and soil properties like texture and pH is the best possible proxy to overcome unbalance. Soils high in organic matter or excessively fertilized with manure or other organic fertilizers will also have a high total nitrogen content. As long as the nitrogen is bound in organic molecules it is not available for plant uptake or losses, but as decomposed organic matter (humus) in soil will contain more nitrogen in relation to carbon than the degrading microorganisms can make use of, it will be mineralized as ammonia to the soil solution and further nitrified to nitrate. The more organic matter the more nitrogen mineralization. The C/N-ratio is a good indicator to which extent net mineralization of N will occur. The rule of thumb is that with a C/N-ratio of the decomposing organic material above 25, nitrogen will be immobilized (more will be built into the microbial biomass than released), and below 20 the opposite will occur. The humified soil organic matter C/N-ratio varies, but around 10 is common and above 20 is very rare. With fresh organic matter incorporated in the soil both substantial immobilization and mineralization may occur temporarily depending on the nitrogen content of the material. There is a risk that mineralization largely occurs when crop requirements are low and the nitrogen therefore will be more susceptible to losses. Nitrogen is almost entirely leached as nitrate, which is dissolved in the soil water and moves freely. Easily drained coarse textured soils are therefore more prone to nitrogen leaching. Gaseous losses through N_2 and N_2O on the other hand is driven by microbiological processes mainly under oxygen deficient conditions which is more likely to occur in badly drained fine textured soils and peat soils. Phosphorus is mainly lost in particulate forms through surface run-off in slopes with bare soil or in mass flow through vertical cracks (macro pore flow) in the soil profile. Such cracks typically occur in soils rich in swelling and shrinking clay minerals. The lability of phosphorus in the soil solution and its availability is also highly dependent on pH, the binding capacity of iron and aluminum in sufficient concentrations in a rather complex relationship with soil composition at large (Weil and Brady, 2017).

4.3.7 Recommendations for monitoring soil nutrients changes

We suggest to include phosphorus and nitrogen as a minimum set of nutrient indicators in a general monitoring system covering a wide range of land uses. These nutrients are well studied, required in substantial amounts by crops and have significant negative environmental impacts.

Phosphorus

For low levels of phosphorus, indicating low fertility, easily extractable P is a good indicator. Olsen P is a common extraction method in several national monitoring systems and similar to ISO 11263:1994 used in the LUCAS soil monitoring and is proposed as the preferred extraction method. To avoid excessive fertilization and unnecessary risks for losses Olsen P is also a good indicator. Thresholds should, however, be set in a local (regional or national) context considering soil types, crop rotations and climate.

It is more difficult to find a threshold for the risk for losses and negative environmental impact. Using the same extractable P as for the fertility indicator will capture the easily soluble fraction. However, using a weak extraction method like Olsen P will say very little about the total phosphorus storage in the soil, which is important information for particulate phosphorus, lost through surface runoff or macro pore flow. To capture that phosphorus fraction, a stronger extraction method is needed. P-AL, that is included in several national monitoring programs, will extract a larger portion of the phosphorus, but an extraction method like ammonium oxalate will be a good representation of all the amorphous phosphorus. Since soil properties, climate, landscape and agricultural conditions substantially influence risks for losses and define critical source areas, it is not possible to set a relevant phosphorus threshold for leaching. To what extent dissolved P in the topsoil will actually leach is to a great extent also determined by the P sorption capacity of the subsoil. Soils with high sorption capacity in the subsoil will have low losses of dissolved P also at high P contents, while vice versa soils with low sorption capacity can have high losses even at lower P content in the soil. The sorption capacity of a soil is an inherent character determined by the mineralogy of the soil and to a large degree dependent on the aluminum- and ironhydroxide content as well as the calcium carbonate content. It means that also these elements are of interest in a monitoring system used for assessing the risks for P-losses.

The soil monitoring directive proposes using extractable P according to ISO 11263:1994 with maximum values to be set by the member states. This is similar to our suggestions for an indicator for low phosphorus levels and low fertility, but not with what we suggest for indicators for environmental risks. The literature suggests that there is a potential for high-resolution modelling and mapping to establish critical source areas for losses related to erosion and macropore transport and to direct mitigation efforts for these forms of P transport.

Nitrogen

Plant available mineral nitrogen, i.e. dissolved nitrogen, is not suitable for monitoring as soil concentrations change rapidly (within days or even hours) due to plant uptake and microbial activity dependent on moisture and temperature, and therefore weather changes. To capture both the fertility aspects and the environmental risks, nitrogen balance calculations at a regional or national scale could provide rough yearly estimates of changes in the overall nitrogen unbalance regional scale. However, the level of detail in the input data for the balance calculations at a regional scale will be too coarse for down-scaling to mapping units. To support management decisions at the farm scale to achieve a balanced fertilization according to crop requirements and to avoid surplus of nitrate in the soil, an agronomical combination of crop, soil, organic matter degradation, climate and weather aspects need

to be considered locally. At that scale balance calculations play an important role. Monitoring concentrations of mineral nitrogen reaching the recipients as suggested by EEA (2023) will give a more direct indication of the environmental impact of unbalanced fertilization and other sources.

Organic matter or organic C could be used as a rough indicator for nitrogen mineralization capacity, but we also propose to include total N as a long-term indicator, which supports the calculation of the C/N-ratio. This is in line with what is proposed in the Soil Monitoring Law. As total N in general relates well to organic C, total, or organic, N will typically coincide with changes in soil organic matter content.

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4.4 CEC/ECEC and exchangeable bases

CEC/ECEC and exchangeable bases (including Sodification)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Maria Fantappiè, Zsófia Bakacsi, Sándor Molnár, Carlos Lozano-Fondón, Ialina Vinci ○ Relevant EJP SOIL projects: ProbeField, Steropes
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4.4.1 CEC/ECEC and exchangeable bases measurement and monitoring by wet chemistry methods

Surfaces of soil colloid particles, mainly clay particles and organic material, are negatively charged, which allows cations to bind. The cation exchange capacity of a soil is a measure of the quantity of negatively charged sites on soil surfaces that can retain positively charged ions (cations) by electrostatic forces, in exchangeable form. It can be expressed in terms of milliequivalents/100 g of soil (meq/100 g) or centimoles of positive charge per kg of soil (cmol(+)/kg), which is numerically equal to meq/100 g (FAO, 2022).

There are different methods to determine cation exchange capacity (CEC), depending on the type of colloidal material (Nel et al, 2022). One method proposed as standard uses 1 M NH₄OAc buffered at pH 7 (GLOSOLAN-SOP-17; FAO, 2022). CEC can be measured by extraction with an unbuffered salt, which measures the effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC), i.e., CEC at the normal soil pH (Coleman et al., 1958).

The ECEC is the total amount of exchangeable bases (calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium) plus exchangeable aluminum in the soil. Since the unbuffered salt solution, e.g., 1 M KCl, slightly affects the soil pH, the extraction is determined at or near the soil pH and extracts only the cations held at active exchange sites at the particular pH of the soil (Burt, 2004).

Other methods widely used and standardized by ISO, use barium chloride solutions, with solution buffered at higher pHs, as ISO 13536:1995, or with no buffering, ISO-11260:2018 (e.g. LUCAS SOIL 2023 is supposed to have CEC included in analyzed soil parameters, according to ISO 11260:2018). The latter determines CEC at the pH of the soil and determines also the content of exchangeable sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium. This method is quite often used for forest soil, since it gives reliable results in acid soils. In acid soils, exchangeable acid cations and acidity must be determined too, e.g. with ISO 14254:2018. Therefore, both these methods, ISO 11260:2018 and ISO 14254:2018, are the standard methods adopted by the International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests (ICP Forests, 2020). On the other hand, ISO 13536:1995 and other methods that use barium chloride solutions buffered at higher pHs, are quite often used for soils that have neutral or alkaline pHs, i.e. with a saturated CEC.

4.4.2 CEC/ECEC and exchangeable bases measurement and monitoring with PS/RS techniques

Several Proximal Sensing techniques exist that are suitable for the measurement of CEC such as Electromagnetic Induction (EMI), and gamma-ray (γ -ray) spectrometry (radiometrics). Respectively, they reveal the apparent electrical conductivity of soils (EC_a) measured in dS/m, and the natural radiation coming from the decay of radioactive elements (i.e., ⁴⁰K, ²³⁸U, and ²³²Th) measured in counts per second. Combining data collected with radiometrics and EMI sensors, and then coupling them with soil sampling, CEC can be estimated, mapped and monitored. This set of techniques allows to reveal CEC even in the subsoil, producing quasi-3D soil maps. Gamma rays have a depth of penetration of 0-30 cm while the depth of penetration of EMI instruments varies depending on the distance between the components that create the magnetic field, and the configuration of the sensor (McNeill, 1980,

Abdu et al., 2007, Saey et al., 2009). Currently, the maximum depth of penetration of EMI sensors available in the market ranges from the soil surface to six meters depending on the characteristics of the sensor. Li et al. (2018) provided an example of data fusion collected with EMI and gamma-ray instruments to successfully map topsoil and subsoil CEC.

4.4.3 Existing thresholds and target values for CEC and exchangeable bases

The value of the CEC, or the number of cations bound, is the basis for several soil-specific indicators (BS%, ESP, SAR). The dominant ions associated with the CEC are the exchangeable cations, such as calcium (Ca^{2+}), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), potassium (K^+) and sodium (Na^+). These are often referred to as the base cations. The base saturation percentage (BS%), which is the sum of equivalent charges of Ca, Mg, Na and K ions relative to CEC, is a common metric for characterizing soil status. The availability of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and K^+ increases with increasing BS%. The BS% increases with increasing pH, at pH 5.5 most soils have 45–55% BS, whereas at pH 7 BS is $\geq 90\%$ (Hillel et al., 2005). Related to sodicity, the ratio of monovalent (Na, K) over divalent (Ca, Mg) cations is important. The standard presentation of soil sodicity is the exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) derived through using sodium adsorption ratio (SAR). Alternately, ESP can be determined through measurement of exchangeable sodium (ES) and cation exchange capacity (CEC), as follows: $\text{ESP} = (\text{ES}/\text{CEC}) * 100$.

ESP is the amount of adsorbed sodium on the soil exchange complex expressed in percent of the cation exchange capacity in milliequivalents per 100 g of soil. An ESP of 15 is generally recognized as a limit above which the soils are characterized as sodic (alkaline), see Table 4.4.1).

Table 4.4. 1 Threshold values for saline/alkaline classification, according to Richards, 1954.

	saline soils	saline-sodic soils	sodic soils
ECe	>4	>4	<4
ESP	<15	>15	>15
pH	<8,5	>8,5	>8,5

4.4.4 CEC/ECEC and exchangeable bases modelling

This topic is closely related to soil nutrient modelling, so the relevant issues are discussed there (Chapter 4.3.).

4.4.5 Effects of scale (time/space) on changes on CEC/ECEC and exchangeable bases

Beyond the properties of vegetation cover, the plant nutrient turnover processes and nutrient movement (mineralization, immobilization) depend on the climate, soil physical and chemical properties, in which the soil texture, pH, soil organic matter content and cation exchange capacity play a leading role. The organic matter content of the soil, the texture (including the proportion of colloidal clay particles) and the mineralogical type of clay material have a significant influence on the surface area available for cation exchange (Table 4.4.2.). The negatively charged particles of clay and humus are colloids which provide a comparatively large surface area with capacity to potentially hold a large number of cations. Soil with a high clay content or high organic matter will generally have a high CEC and soils with a high number of base cations are considered inherently more fertile. At pH 7 or higher, soil clay mineral and organic matter surfaces are occupied by basic cations, and thus, base saturation is equal to CEC.

Table 4.4. 2 Typical cation exchange capacities of some soil clay minerals and soils of various textures (Kissel, D.E. and L. Sonon (Eds). 2008.).

Soil Components	CEC (meq/100 g)
Clay Type	
Kaolinite	3-15
Illite	15-40
Montmorillonite	80-100
Soil Texture	
Sand	1-5
Loam	5-15
Clay	>30
Organic Matter	200-400

In naturally acid soils (where parent materials are poor in basic cations) and in areas where the acidification process is advanced (see Chapter 4.5) and pH is low, other cations, mainly hydrogen (H^+) and aluminium (Al^{3+}), are more prevalent, resulting in less fertile soils with unfavorable conditions for plant production. Acid soils ($pH < 5.5$) tend to have toxic amounts of aluminium (and manganese).

The balance of cations for a given soil may be more important than the absolute number of the different cations. When the proportion of calcium ions dominates the basic cations, it promotes a favorable, aggregated soil structure, while an increase in the proportion of sodium results in a dispersed, wet smearing, degraded soil structure (see: sodification, solonetz formation).

4.4.6. Sodification

Exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) is considered the main indicator of sodium accumulation, while ESP and SAR (Sodium Absorption Ratio) are the best characteristics for solonetz formation. Sodium occupies more than 15% of the soil's cation exchange capacity (CEC) in sodic soils (Richards et al., 1954). Unfavorable impact of monovalent cations accumulation (mostly sodium) in the liquid or solid phase of soil, resulting in the increase in swelling/shrinkage/cracking characteristics, sometimes radical decrease in infiltration rate, hydraulic conductivity and water retention, which lead to an extreme moisture regime, increasing frequency of waterlogging, floods, or droughts (Várallyay in Huber et al., 2008). The high content of sodium ions causes dispersion of clay and organic matter, which settle on the surfaces of soil particles to give them a brownish black color. The sodic soil horizon, which is predominantly below the surface, prevents the infiltration of water with scattered clay that settles between the soil particles. Consequently, saline soils remain waterlogged for longer periods after rainfall or irrigation. In some cases, dispersed humus and clay may leach into the soil profile as indicated by clay accumulation in the profile. Sodic soils develop slowly but may be very difficult to remediate (van Beek and Tóth, 2012).

4.4.7 Recommendations for monitoring CEC/ECEC and exchangeable bases changes

The monitoring of sodification as a part of the *sensu lato* salinisation degradation process is not included in the SML. The risk of sodification could be monitored by looking at changes in the ESP (exchangeable sodium percentage) as this can indicate the development of unfavorable soil structure degradation that is difficult to restore. The monitoring could be less frequent in areas affected by "harmful" salts (already sodium predominant areas, $ESP > 15$), e.g. every 10 years, but more often in

areas at risk of secondary salinisation (irrigated areas, shallow areas with high dissolved salinity groundwater, where ESP is between 5-15), e.g. every 5 years. Taking into account that the movement of salts is influenced by the moisture content, seasonal fluctuations must be taken into account when monitoring. The recommended period for sampling is the dry, warm period of the year, when the maximum salt accumulation can be assumed.

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4.5 pH

pH (including acidification)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Dominique Arrouays, Maria Fantappiè, Danute Karcauskiene, Johanna Wetterlind, Lubos Borůvka , Rudi Hessel, Bo Stenberg, Joost Salomez ○ Relevant EJP SOIL projects: SERENA
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Soil pH is a measure of the acidity or basicity (alkalinity) of a soil (Thomas, 1996). Soil pH is defined as the negative logarithm (base 10) of the activity of hydronium ions (H^+ or, more precisely, H_3O^+) in a solution. The pH, or potential hydrogen, is also called hydrogen ion concentration or proton concentration in soil. It is measured in a slurry of soil mixed with pure water (or various solutions, such as KCl, $CaCl_2$) and normally ranges between 3 and 10, with 7 being considered as neutral. Under natural conditions, neutral pH values are rather rare, and the statistical distribution of pH is often bimodal, with acidic ($pH < 7$) and alkaline ($pH > 7$) modes corresponding to a different weathering intensity and/or to specific soil parent materials, climates, or topographic conditions (see further, section 4.5.5).

In a critical review of 65 soil quality (SQ) assessment approaches, Bünemann et al. (2018) showed that soil pH ranked second among the most used SQ indicators (81.5%), soil organic carbon (SOC) or soil organic matter (SOM) being the first. Indeed, pH is a cheap and easy to interpret indicator of a large range of physico-chemical and biological properties of soil:

- It has an influence on soil biogeochemistry (Crowther et al., 2019);
- It controls the chemical forms and mobility of a large variety of major nutrients, micronutrients and contaminants;
- It has impact on the ability to grow plants;
- It provides habitats for micro-, meso- and macrofauna;
- It is a controlling factor of bacterial/fungal life in soil and more generally to the global soil organism community.

Furthermore, soil pH is used to classify some soil types (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2014) and as such is a key characteristic related to both qualitative and quantitative soil properties.

4.5.1 pH measurement and monitoring

Though pH is a cheap and easy to interpret indicator, obtaining a 'correct' pH value is not easy: field or laboratory measurements, different dilutions, different solutions and concentrations, different measuring techniques, ... all have an impact on the result obtained.

To have a quick (and dirty) idea about the pH, field observations can do the job:

- Under "natural" vegetation (forest understory vegetation, natural grasslands) a large variety of floristic inventories may provide indicators of soil pH (Gégout et al., 2005). Precision, however, is rather low, as most plants thrive in a relatively wide pH range.
- Various colorimetric methods are used, making use of commercial liquid color indicators or pH-sensitive test strips. These estimations are based on color and are therefore rather subjective. The precision of the estimation is about 0.5 pH units.
- Hand-held pH meters are also available and distributed by various private companies. The precision of the estimation ranges from 0.1 to 0.5 pH units. The accuracy of the measurement is highly dependent on the operator's care and condition of the electrode.

Because of the rather low precision of field measurements, pH measurements are common routine in soil laboratories. But methods are manifold, and their use often depends on regional/national habits.

The first step is the choice of the soil/water dilution ratio. These ratios can range from 1/1 (saturated paste) to 1/10, 1/2.5 and 1/5 mostly being used. However, it's not uncommon to have the dilution ratio changed over time. This has been the case for France in the mid-1990's where the ratio has been changed from 1/2.5 to 1/5. But changing the dilution ratio obviously has an impact on the measurement results. Therefore, results should be taken with caution when interpreting (long time series of) pH measurements in databases (e.g., Kirk et al., 2010; Saby et al., 2017). A noticeable exception to measuring a soil/solution ratio is the pH measurement of a soil saturated paste.

The next step concerns the choice and concentration of the solution. Depending on the solution, either the actual pH (pH in water; pH_w) or the potential pH (pH in KCl, $CaCl_2$, ...) will be measured. The equilibrium in water (pH_w) does not extract all the H^+ and Al^{3+} ions fixed by the soil cation exchange capacity. When using KCl, these fixed ions are exchanged with K^+ . Therefore, pH_{KCl} is generally lower than pH_w , even more so with stronger KCl-concentrations.

Different combinations of dilution ratios and solutions give rise to different results, e.g., increasing the amount of water slightly decreases pH_w , mainly because of a dilution effect (Keaton, 1938; Conyers and Davey, 1988; Aitken and Moody, 1991; Miller and Kissel, 2010; Libohova et al., 2014). This dilution effect can be corrected rather easily.

Changing the solution from H_2O to $CaCl_2$ or vice-versa, results in more complex relationships as various mechanisms can be involved such as, calcium carbonate buffering for high soil pH, displacement and hydrolysis of Al^{3+} from exchange sites by $CaCl_2$ for low soil pH, etc.

Because of all possible, slightly different outcomes, many studies have tried to establish transfer functions between results obtained using different dilutions and/or solutions, in order to harmonize results from different measurements. The *GlobalSoilMap* specifications (Arrouays et al., 2014a, 2014b; GlobalSoilMap, 2015) take pH_w in a 1/5 soil/water mixture solution as a reference,

The *GlobalSoilMap* specifications (GlobalSoilMap, 2015) provide a short list of examples of such functions, mainly those established by Bruce et al. (1989), Aitken and Moody (1991) and Miller and Kissel (2010). Also, Libohova et al. (2014) gave a good overview of non-linear pedotransfer functions, often adapted to specific pedological/mineralogical contexts and using various covariates, and tested several ways to convert H_2O and $CaCl_2/KCl$ pH measurements over a wide range of US soils. They concluded that, from a practical point of view, simple linear regression models using only pH_w 1:1 or pH_{CaCl_2} 1:2 were suitable for predicting pH_w 1:5, as the errors associated with these predictive models were comparable to those associated with the analytical methods alone.

The costs of one analytical measurement of soil pH range between 5-10 € in E.U. countries.

Recently, Bargrizan et al. (2018) developed a spectrophotometric method to determine pH. This spectrophotometric method, covering a pH range of 3 to 9, uses a mixed indicator solution (equimolar bromophenol blue, bromocresol purple, m-cresol purple and thymol blue). The method uses measurements of absorbance of the dye mixture at two wavelengths (434 and 585 nm), chosen to represent the average acid and base peak maxima of the individual dyes within the mixture. The authors showed a good correlation with pH_w in a 1/5 soil:water ratio.

The standard operating procedure worked out by FAO (2021f) details three methods for pH determination: in water with a ratio 1:2.5 (m/v) and 1:5 (m/v) both for pH measured in KCl and in CaCl₂, whereas ISO 10390:1994 proposes the determination, with water, KCl or CaCl₂, in a 1:5 (volume fraction) suspension of soil (ISO 10390:2021 – Soil, treated biowaste and sludge — Determination of pH.). ISO method is the standard to which the proposal for a soil monitoring law refers to.

4.5.2 pH measurement and monitoring with PS/RS techniques

In contrast to many other estimations using proximal sensing techniques, pH can be analysed directly using electrochemical sensors, namely ion-selective electrodes (ISE) or ion-selective field effect transistors (ISFET), by detecting the H⁺ activity (Adamchuk et al., 2018). The technique can be used for in-field on-the-go measurements and there are commercially available sensors for integration on agriculture machinery.

There are also studies showing the possibility to use soil spectroscopy for indirect estimations of pH although results are varying (Stenberg et al., 2010; Metzger et al., 2020). The soil spectra hold information on several soil properties that influence soil pH, often by a direct influence on buffering capacity, such as clay and organic matter content, mineralogy, and carbonate content. However, as for many cases where the calibration models rely on indirect relationships with other soil properties, it can be difficult to transfer models between sites or to make general models that can be largely used (Stenberg et al., 2010). That is, relationships exist and very locally they can be strong, but at a larger scale they cannot support reliable prediction models.

An alternative of proximal sensing of pH is using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy that provides rather good prediction results (Sharma et al., 2014; Teixeira et al., 2020). Recently, Javadi et al. (2021) obtained good prediction results for pH using fusion of Vis-NIR and XRF spectra.

4.5.3 Existing thresholds and target values for pH

The broad pH_w range acceptable for most plants ranges between 5.5 and 7.5. However, many plants have adapted to thrive at pH values outside this range, and adapted management practices allow cultivating many plants at more alkaline values up to pH 8.7. It is generally acknowledged that for most cash crops the optimum pH_w values range between 6.2 and 6.8. In France, an often-used threshold value for soil liming for is pH 6.3. In Belgium, liming recommendations are based on pH_{KCl}, and different threshold values are used according to soil texture (e.g., ±5-5.5 for sand, up to 7.5 for clay soils). A recent report (EEA, 2023) states that for cultivated soils, a pH value below 5 should for sure be avoided while 4.5 is critical in view of Al toxicity. Preferably, the pH stays above 5.5 or even 6. This report gives indicative optimum values for some crops. Neither the “Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on Soil Monitoring and Resilience” nor its annexes provide target or threshold values for soil pH.

Soil pH is a master indicator in soils as it relates to many chemical processes. It specifically affects plant nutrient availability by controlling the chemical forms of the different nutrients and influencing the chemical reactions they undergo. Proton concentration is vital for all living organisms. It also has an impact on soil and soil constituents. Very high (Al³⁺) concentration (**pH<3.5**) in soil solution may attack

soil minerals, dissolve the metal cations out of the crystal lattice, and eventually lead to mineral degradation and irreversible pedogenic changes. Low soil pH affects root growth, and the decomposition of organic matter. Very low pH_w are most often encountered under rather wet climate and acid vegetation such as coniferous forest. To maintain enough cations and nutrient return to soil, small amounts of liming may be applied, and exportation of harvest residues should be avoided.

The presence of Al^{3+} reduces phosphate availability, is toxic to most crops, and can lead to many crops' deficiencies in the main soil nutrients, and deficiency or toxicity of some micro-nutrients for crops. High concentrations of Al^{3+} also increase the mobility and availability of some toxic trace elements. To our knowledge, the most used thresholds of low pH_w for the risks linked to high Al^{3+} concentrations range from 4.5 to 4.8. To a lesser degree, pH_w values under 5.5 may also induce some deficiencies or toxicities mainly linked to the excess of both H^+ and Al^{3+} .

Truog (1946) produced a famous diagram relating pH to nutrient availability in soils. Hartemink and Barrow (2023) commented on this diagram as follows "For the 11 nutrients on the diagram, a pH_w of around 6.5 was most favorable, but did not mean a satisfactory supply; it indicated that as far as the soil reaction was concerned, the conditions were favorable. Likewise, it did not mean that outside the favorable range a deficiency would prevail". On cultivated soils, low pH values are usually raised by liming with calcium-magnesium (Ca/Mg), carbonates and silicates. Though Hartemink and Barrow stated that target values are arguable, it seems, according to the general practices in EU, that a target value to reach for cultivated soils could be approximated to a pH within a 6.2-6.8 range.

Under alkaline conditions above pH 7.5, nutrients such as Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu and B are strongly bound to the soil and their availability is reduced, causing deficiencies. Under calcareous soil, which usually has pH values ranging from 7.6 - 8.6, phosphate fertilizers may be immobilized in a tri-calcic complex. Therefore, P fertilization should be adapted and applied several times in ad hoc quantities rather than once in large quantities. It is quite impossible to drop the pH of calcareous cultivated soils due to their very high quantity of Ca^{2+} . However, many cultivated soils are calcareous and some of them can be very productive, if their management of fertilization for main nutrients and micronutrients is appropriate. Very calcareous soils, especially developed on chalk rocks, can provide interesting soils for well-known vineyards (e.g., Champagne, Saint-Emilion, Cognac) on the condition that the climate is optimal and that chlorosis-resistant rootstocks are used.

Very high pH_w values (**>8.8**) generally occur on saline and sodic soils. These cases are considered in chapter 4.6 related to electrical conductivity.

4.5.4 pH modelling

Soil pH models have mainly been developed for acid soils, especially in the framework of studies about the effect of acid rain on forest and freshwater (Tipping and Woof, 1990; Tipping et al., 1995). These models are not used for agricultural soils the acidity of which is generally controlled by liming. Therefore, they are not relevant for this chapter on monitoring pH in agricultural soils.

4.5.5 Effects of scale (time/space) on changes of pH

4.5.5.1 Natural pH values and rates of changes

At global scale, and without human intervention, soil pH values are mainly controlled by the water-balance. Slessarev et al. (2016), using a large database of worldwide pH measurements, showed that there is an abrupt transition from alkaline to acid soil pH that occurs at the point where mean annual precipitation begins to exceed mean annual potential evapotranspiration. This threshold is explained by the acidity of rainfall water (pH around 5.5), weathering and a net export of cations by drainage. Therefore, the global distribution of soil pH_w in rather natural conditions is bimodal, and clearly follows climatic gradients linked to P-ETP.

Another well-known climatic effect is the effect of low temperatures leading to very slow soil organic matter decomposition and a related increase in acidity. This is typically the case of Podzols of Nordic areas. Most of the peat soils in the northern EU are also acidic, because of the presence of organic acids in the soil solution.

At more detailed scales, many other effects influence pH distribution of “natural” soils. The presence of more acid soils than expected when using the P-ETP threshold, may be due to several factors such as, for instance, soil age and paleo-climate conditions, high seasonal rainfall or snowmelt, or geologic constraints on Ca^{2+} supply. Conversely, alkaline soils may be encountered in regions where annual P-ETP is positive. This may occur in regions where, for instance, (i) carbonate rocks are a major component of bedrock lithology, (ii) active volcanoes may produce easily weathered silicate minerals, (iii) active erosion on steep slopes is able to maintain pH thanks to a high rate of soil rejuvenation.

Soils derived from alluvial deposits may show a large variety of pH because of the origin and nature of these deposits, which may come from far away and from very different climate and geological contexts.

Finally, very local conditions may provide “natural” very acidic soils (e.g., podzolic soils on nearly pure quartz parent material such as in the French “Landes of Gascony”, acid-sulfate soils in water-logged estuaries and deltas), or very alkaline pH (e.g., primary saline or sodic soils in deltas, soils having semi-permanent saline floods or water-table, or soils derived from marine deposits). Indeed, very high pH values (9-10) are observed in saline or sodic conditions. We will not deal with these cases in this chapter as salinity and sodicity are dealt with in the Electrical Conductivity chapter (see section 4.6.).

The natural long-term rates of changes in soil pH are very slow, except for some cases cited above, such as volcanic eruptions, floods, erosion and deposition. Note, however, that an intra-annual change in pH values is often observed and linked to soil pedo-climate, organic carbon inputs, and microbial activity variations with seasons.

Therefore, without human intervention, nearly neutral soils ($6 < pH_w < 7$) are quite rare, especially if there are neither natural process of rejuvenation by erosion or deposition, nor large stocks of Ca^{2+} or silicates in the parent material, that can be provided to soil by weathering or biological activity. In other words, on a global scale, the natural pH distribution is bimodal with an acidic mode buffered by Al^{3+} and an alkaline pole buffered by Ca^{2+} (or Na^+ for saline and sodic soils). Nearly neutral natural soils are much less frequent.

4.5.5.2. pH values and rates of changes due to anthropogenic causes

We distinguish global anthropogenic causes from local human interventions.

Global anthropogenic causes of changes in soil pH include several processes. One process is atmospheric deposition of N and S compounds from human activity. This process favors soil acidification and is more or less intense and changes depending on regions of the world. We will deal with this process in section 4.5.6.

Another process is climate change and the increase of extreme events. Changes in climate are increasing dryness in some regions of the world and the frequency of extreme events. Dryness may favor salinization in arid areas and a subsequent raise of pH. Climate change is also raising the sea level and puts a lot of soil at threat of being more frequently flooded by marine or rather saline water. Extreme events may accentuate erosion events too. These erosion events may rejuvenate the soil in some places and transport exogenous soil materials over short or very long distances. Thus, erosion may provoke changes in pH, though the direction of them is not generalizable and depends on local conditions.

Intra-annual changes in pH exist, especially under temperate climate. The pH values are prone to seasonal variations linked to H⁺ dilution by rainfall water in winter, and by the production of organic acids in spring, summer (if not too dry), and autumn, when the soil biological activity is more intense. These seasonal effects may range from 0.1 to 0.5 pH units, and sometimes even more in some calcareous soils. It is therefore important to consider the season when interpreting pH values.

Human intervention causes of changes in soil pH are numerous. On cultivated soils, many soil management practices may have a direct effect on soil pH:

- To raise pH, a well-known practice is liming, the objective of which is to increase the pH of acid soils. The main objectives of liming are to favor the availability of soil nutrients and micronutrients, and to avoid problems linked to deficiency or toxicity in some elements. Liming amount and frequency should be adapted to the observed pH, the soil buffering capacity, and the objective of pH increase. Liming is most of the time carried out by spreading amendments rich in Ca²⁺ and/or Mg²⁺. Amendment products generally come from mining calcareous or dolomitic rocks or sediments. Spreading silicate minerals or ashes is less frequent but also influences soil pH. The effect of such amendments is quite rapid, and depends on the quantity applied, but also on how fine the particles brought to the soil are. The duration of this effect depends on the capacity of soil to retain these cations (CEC), and on leaching process dynamics. Leaching process dynamics depend on soil texture, porosity, CEC, and on soil drainage conditions. Climate, especially rainfall, is one of the main controlling factors of leaching. Liming also favors the structural stability of aggregates.
- To avoid acidification by leaching, reducing bare soil periods is an option, especially during the wet seasons. The use of cover-crops is thus recommended. Besides, it helps to reduce soil erosion, and to avoid leaching of nutrients.
- Agroforestry may enable the trees to accumulate in their leaves some Ca⁺⁺, taken by tree roots from deep soil or from very-deep calcareous materials, and to recycle them to the topsoil during fall.
- Nitrogen fertilization (either mineral or organic) should be adapted to the crop needs. Excess in N induces an increase in soil acidification. To reduce this acidification effect, better control of N inputs according to the plant's requirements is necessary, which needs to modulate the inputs according to plant's development and to apply N throughout the year.

- Due to calcareous soil buffering capacity, it is nearly impossible to decrease soil pH by human intervention. Some advice is to provide large amounts of organic carbon inputs and to avoid increasing pH by crushing calcareous rocks or increasing tillage depth in shallow calcareous soils.

4.5.6 Acidification

As noted in section 4.5.5.1, soil acidification is a natural process in nearly all soils where the water balance (P-ETP) is positive. Notable exceptions are soils developed on very calcareous parent materials, especially if soils are eroded, ploughed, or disturbed by windthrow in forests. The general effects of the water-balance and the effect of soil organic carbon accumulation in cold or very wet areas are clearly visible in the soil pH map of EU (Fig. 4.5.1, Ballabio et al., 2019). Many soils under Mediterranean climate are alkaline as weathering by rainfall is not intense enough to remove Ca^{2+} ions from soils developed on calcareous rocks. Most of the alkaline soils under wetter climates correspond to soils whose parent materials are very rich in Ca and that are, in general, cultivated. Therefore, no acidification occurs.

Figure 4.5. 1 Topsoil pH map in Europe as derived from LUCAS-Soil measurements. From Ballabio et al., 2019.

The main cause of natural acidification is rainfall. According to Trolard and Bourrié (2018) “the reaction of CO₂ with water is the main source of protons within the soil”. They explain that rainwater is slightly acidic (pH of about 5.5) because it is in equilibrium with the partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂) in the atmosphere. Thus, when rainwater percolates through the soil, the acidity increases by equilibration with a larger pCO₂, due to the respiration of biota. This increase in acidity favors the hydrolysis reactions of minerals subject to weathering and to an export of alkalinity, which is the cause of the general trends for soil acidification.

One human induced cause of acidification is atmospheric deposition of N and S compounds from human activity. This process favors soil acidification and is more or less intense and changes depending on regions of the world. According to Ackermann et al. (2019), humans have, since the beginning of the industrial period, doubled the amount of nitrogen in the biosphere and drastically increased rates of atmospheric nitrogen deposition. Ackermann et al. (2019) used the GEOS-Chem Chemical Transport Model to estimate wet and dry deposition of inorganic nitrogen globally at a spatial resolution of 2° × 2.5° for 12 individual years in the period from 1984 to 2016. They found an 8% increase in global inorganic nitrogen deposition from 86.6 to 93.6 TgN/year, a trend that comprised a balance of variable regional patterns. For example, inorganic nitrogen deposition increased in areas including East Asia and Southern Brazil, while inorganic nitrogen deposition declined in areas including Europe. Applying N fertilizers in excess of crop needs also increases acidification of soils. These two phenomena explain why acidification of cultivated soils is an issue in a large part of China (e.g., Guo et al., 2010, 2018; Chen et al., 2019), due to industrial emissions and depositions, and to high levels of soil fertilization. On the contrary, soil acidification is decreasing in French cultivated soils and in England and Wales (Saby et al., 2017; Kirk et al., 2010) due to a decrease in atmospheric N and S deposition, and a better management of N fertilization.

Excess in N fertilization or N inputs by animals is one major cause of acidification in intensively cultivated soils or on intensively managed grassland soils receiving very high inputs of N.

The proximity to industrial sites and smelters is frequently a cause of local acidification.

Some catastrophic and very rapid changes in pH are sometimes caused by human (but not necessarily only by them) intervention in acid-sulfate soils. These waterlogged acid soils contain iron sulfide minerals. If the soil is drained, excavated, or otherwise exposed to air, the sulfides react with oxygen to form highly toxic sulfuric acid and the pH drops down to 1. Release of this sulfuric acid from the soil can in turn release heavy metals and metalloids (i.e., arsenic) within the soil. These releases create many adverse impacts: killing vegetation, polluting surface- and groundwater, killing aquatic organisms, and degrading some human-built structures to the point of failure (Mosley et al., 2014a, 2014b).

4.5.7 Recommendations for monitoring changes in pH

Long-term changes in soil pH are rather slow. However, it is necessary to early detect soils approaching some critical threshold values below which problems may occur, to prevent soil, plant, and water degradation. This apparent contradiction between the rate of change and the need to detect them early, shows that it is not easy to fix a temporal time step to monitor soil pH. This is even more complicated as soil pH also exhibits seasonal variations, the range of which may sometimes be larger than long-term decadal changes.

The bimodal statistical distribution of soil pH complicates its mapping and may also lead to misleading statistics or maps. Indeed, when mapping a pH value on a spatial support within which the statistical

distribution is clearly bimodal, one may wonder what the meaning of a mean or median value is when such a value may not exist anywhere within this support. This specificity of soil pH (bimodal distribution) is obvious in rather “natural” soils with clear acidic and alkaline poles. Under cultivation and temperate climate, the acidic pole, though present, is less evident and is often smoothed by the liming effect. Therefore, many pH values of cultivated soils are within a 5.8 to 6.5 interval. Nevertheless, the alkaline pole remains and may be accentuated by tillage or erosion on calcareous soils.

Nussbaum et al. (2023) recently proposed a novel approach that is suitable for bimodal distributions and applied it to produce pH maps for Switzerland. Interestingly they stressed that the approach is “model-agnostic”, namely independent from the used statistical prediction method.

Long-term changes in soil pH were detected and mapped using very large databases such as those obtained by collecting pH results from analyses requested by farmers to manage their soils (i.e., Saby et al., 2017). To avoid the peak of alkaline soils, these authors excluded them by pH and CaCO₃ content filtering. Then, to smooth intra annual variations and to get enough samples to run robust statistics, they used multi-annual periods to calculate median pH on areal supports. They showed, however, that areas with rather small numbers of analyses led to non-significant changes. Two recommendations are therefore to work on as large a set of pH samples as possible and to smooth seasonal effects, and even some annual effects due to highly wet or dry years. This sampling and smoothing may be achieved by grouping several years, either in a discrete way, or by using moving time-periods to calculate median or average and variance.

Attention should be paid to changes in methods with time and to the possibility (or the unfeasibility) to apply transfer functions to convert pH values in a unique reference method, and to take into account the uncertainties generated by this conversion. This reference method is pH_w in a 1:5 soil:water mixture.

On a field scale, and especially in long-term experiments, pH can be measured over much shorter time periods. This will require setting up a sampling design taking into account either natural or management zones. The fact that measurements are more frequent does not necessarily imply that it will be easier to detect long-term changes earlier. It may however give some indications about short time changes in pH linked to seasonal or management effects. These indications could be useful to assess short durations during when pH may reach some critical values.

Critical pH_w values for agricultural soils could be set to 4.5-4.8 for high risks of toxicity/deficiencies of some elements for plants, and severe risks for other biota and water. A second threshold could be set to pH_w < 5.5. This warning threshold indicates that there are already some toxicity/deficiency risks and that the soil is under risk of more severe acidification. It could be a warning threshold to decide that a correction by liming is necessary. Finally, target values should depend on the crops. Most of the crops are adapted to slightly acidic soils 6.2 < pH_w < 6.8 but the optimum pH may vary among crops and rotations. It is thus not easy to fix a common target value to all soils and crops. Besides, this target value cannot be reached in calcareous soils which will always have a pH > 7.5. In this case, recommendations should include the choice of adapted crops, the management of fertilization, and the monitoring of possible deficiencies in micronutrients by plant observations and/or analyses.

In summary, there are rather clear thresholds of soil acidity under which action is required. Monitoring soil pH should involve sampling design and statistics taking into account the bimodal distribution of pH, its local and its seasonal variability. At the field or long-term experiment scales, dedicated space-

time sampling designs can be adapted to local and to short-term variations. At larger scales, taking into account the bimodal distribution of pH is also necessary, and many samples and a long-time monitoring period are required to detect long-term evolutions, if any.

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4.6 Electrical conductivity

<p>Electrical conductivity (including Salinization)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Zsófia Bakacsi, Maria Fantappiè, Chiara Piccini, Gabriele Buttafuoco, Carlos Lozano Fondon, Roberto Barbetti, Katalin Takács, László Pásztor, Johanna Wetterlind ○ Relevant EJP SOIL projects: ProbeField
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4.6.1 Electrical conductivity measurement and monitoring with wet chemistry methods

Measuring the electrical conductivity (EC) of the water sample is the most commonly performed procedure to estimate the amounts of soluble salts in the water. The higher the concentration of salt in a solution, the higher the electrical conductivity, expressed in dS/m. Salinity is generally expressed as total dissolved solutes (TDS) in milli gram per liter (mg/l) or parts per million (ppm). No fixed relationship exists between TDS and EC, although a factor of 640 is commonly used to convert EC (dS/m) to approximate TDS. For highly concentrated solutions, a factor of 800 is used to account for the suppressed ionization effect on EC (Mohammad et al., 2018). A practical relationship exists between E_{ce} (electrical conductivity measured in the saturated soil paste) and total soluble salts (TSS), although a factor of 10 is used to convert E_{ce} (dS/m) to TSS (expressed in meq/l) in the EC range of 0.1–5 dS/m (Richards, 1954). The major soluble mineral salts are the cations: sodium (Na⁺), calcium (Ca²⁺), magnesium (Mg²⁺), potassium (K⁺) and the anions: chloride (Cl⁻), sulfate (SO₄²⁻), bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻), carbonate (CO₃²⁻), and nitrate (NO₃⁻).

Electrical conductivity is a function of quantity and nature of cations and anions in the water. EC is commonly measured in 1:5 or 1:2,5 solid:water mixture or in extracts of the water saturated soil paste (E_{ce}). The 1:5 soil:water measurement is easier to perform. The liquid phase is more difficult to yield from the saturation extract but is considered to be more representative of the actual soil conditions as experienced by plants (Van Reeuwijk, 2002), and traditionally applied for classification of salt-affected soils (Burt, 2004).

The determination of EC generally involves the physical measurement of resistance. EC increases with temperature; it should ideally be determined at 25 °C. However, EC can be measured at other known temperatures and corrected to the 25 °C reference using appropriate temperature coefficients (FAO, 2021a).

FAO has approved two standard operating procedures: GLOSOLAN-SOP-07- for soil electrical conductivity soil/water, 1:5 (FAO 2021g) and GLOSOLAN-SOP-08- for saturated soil paste extract (FAO 2021h). In the latter a soil:water ratio is proposed that is thought to be the lowest reproducible ratio for which enough extract for analysis can be readily removed from the soil with common laboratory equipment (pressure or vacuum), also because this ratio is often predictably related to the soil:water content of the field (FAO 2021h). GLOSOLAN-SOP-07, on the other hand, determines the electrical conductivity (EC) of a soil/water suspension in the ratio of one:five (1:5). Aqueous extracts of soil samples can be made at higher than normal water content for routine characterization purposes, as obtaining soil samples at typical field water contents is not very practical. Considering that the amounts of various solutes are influenced by the soil/water ratio at which the extract is made, the soil:water ratio should be standardized to obtain results that can be applied and reasonably interpreted (FAO 2021g). ISO only existing method, in aqueous extract of soil 1:5 (ISO 11265:1994- Soil quality — Determination of the specific electrical conductivity.), is proposed as alternative standard method to the GLOSOLAN-SOP—08 in saturated paste extract by the proposal of SML and is the method currently used for LUCAS samples, probably because of the operating difficulties in obtaining saturated samples.

There are several conversion methods between ECe and other EC values based on different soil:liquid ratios (Richards, 1954, Landon, 1984, Hogg and Henry, 1984; Zhang et al., 2005; FAO, 2006; Ozkan et al., 2006; Sonmez et al, 2008; Chi and Wand, 2010).

4.6.2 Electrical conductivity (soil salinity) measurement and monitoring with RS/PS techniques
 The presence of salt on the soil surface can be directly detected by Remote Sensing (RS) methods (Table 4.6.1). Salt reflectance is affected by the quantity and mineralogy of salt, soil moisture and surface roughness (Metternicht & Zinck, 2003). In general, the reflectance of the soil surface increases with salt content, so that observations in the visible range of the spectrum allow the identification of salt-affected soils (Daliakopoulos et al., 2016). Information acquired in the thermal bands can be used for the discrimination between salt types (Metternicht & Zinck, 2003). Multispectral sensors are preferred for soil salinity mapping and monitoring, but their lower spectral resolution limits the ability to detect specific absorption bands compared to hyperspectral sensors, which provide better identification of surface salt features (Allbed et al., 2013). The major limitation of optical remote sensing methods is that they are unable to provide information on the whole soil profile (Fan et al., 2016), moreover salt features on the surface are difficult to be discriminated from other surface components below 10–15% salt content (Metternicht & Zinck, 2003).

Another approach to obtain information about soil salinity is microwave RS which is based on the measurement of the dielectric properties of soils (Li et al., 2014). The complex dielectric constant is related to conductivity and correlated well with soil salinity (Periasamy & Ravi, 2020). The most suitable bands for soil salinity detection are L and C, respectively (Shao et al., 2003).

Table 4.6. 1 Examples of soil salinity estimations based on satellite data. (DTA: decision tree analysis, MLR: multiple linear regression, PLSR: partial least square regression).

Satellite	Time frame	Method	Study area	Reference
Landsat-5	Single acquisition	DTA	Oregon, USA	Elnaggar and Noller 2009
Landsat-4,5,7,8	Time series	PLSR	Shandong, China	Fan et al. 2016
Landsat-8, salinity index	Single acquisition	MLR	West-UAE	Abuelgasim and Ammad 2019
Landsat-8, bands and salinity indices	Single acquisition	MLR	Korat, Thailand	Shrestha et al. 2021
RADARSAT-2	Single acquisition	Advanced integral equation model	Jilin, Northeast China	Li et al. 2014
Sentinel-1	Single acquisition	Semi-empirical dielectric model	Tamil Nadu, India	Periasamy and Ravi 2020
EO-1 Hyperion	Single acquisition	PLSR, MLR	China	Weng et al. 2008

Some Proximal Sensing (PS) techniques have been specifically developed to monitor soil salinity. For example, Electromagnetic Induction (EMI) sensors can be used. EMI sensors typically consist of a transmitter (Tx) and a receiver (Rx) coil. A primary magnetic field is generated by the transmitter coil which, when passing through the soil, generates eddy currents in conductors. Such an interaction generates a secondary magnetic field which is intercepted by the receiver coil, and differs in intensity from the primary magnetic field. The attenuation depends on the EC_a of the soil, which is caused by soil properties such as mineralogy (CEC), clay content and type, and soil variables such as water and salt content. The sensitivity of EMI instruments depends on the orientation (i.e., horizontal or vertical

co-planar, HCP and VPC, respectively) and the distance between the transmitter and the receiver coils. Depending on those, the penetration depth of the magnetic field will increase as the distance between the Tx and Rx increases. The orientation of the coils influences the penetration depth of the magnetic field, which will be deeper when the instrument is configured in the VCP compared to HCP.

4.6.3 Existing threshold/target values for electrical conductivity

FAO et al (2020), following USDA (Richards, 1954), accepted an electrical conductivity measured in the saturated soil paste (EC_e) of higher than 4 dS/m (at 25 °C) as boundary for saline soils. Threshold values for saline/alkaline soil classification are discussed in Chapter 4.4. (Table 4.4.1.). Saline and sodic soils (characterized by Na accumulation) often occur together and are distinguished by different EC and ESP (Exchangeable Sodium Percentage) values.

For saline soils, not only the quantity of salts (expressed by EC value) and type are important, but so is their vertical distribution (the so-called salt profile) in the soil, therefore, it is not enough to sample the soil surface layer.

4.6.4 Effects of scale (time/space) on changes of electrical conductivity

The spatial and temporal variability of the electrical conductivity closely follows the dynamics of the salinity in the soil. Soil salinity frequently occurs in semi-arid countries in irrigated regions, regions with shallow groundwater, and low-lying coastal areas and deltas (Salama et al., 1999).

Arid and semi-arid regions with evaporative soil water conditions (precipitation < evaporation), are generally low-lying, in-basin areas with shallow groundwater table. Where groundwater may rise up capillary to close to the surface, salts dissolved in groundwater can accumulate in the soil profile, with a peak of salt concentration and associated EC value at or below the surface. There are a number of reasons for the rise in groundwater levels, such as limited drainage due to the impermeable layer, or when deep-rooted trees are replaced by shallow-rooted annuals. In the case of relatively deep groundwater levels within this region, the capillary fringes cannot reach the surface, and salt accumulation can occur in the deeper part of the soil profile. This process can also occur in the steppe transition zone. In coastal areas, significant amounts of salt can precipitate from seawater vapour in coastal soils, regardless of their type.

Saline soils with a high exchangeable calcium ion content have a good soil structure. Calcium ions have a high flocculation capacity in the soil and their presence in the soil tends to support particle aggregation. Some saline soils contain gypsum (calcium sulphate) and lime (calcium and magnesium carbonate) (Skarie et al., 1987).

Unfavourable salt accumulation in the soil due to rising groundwater can develop relatively quickly (even in a few years), but the flux can be controlled by keeping the groundwater deep (proper drainage). Irrigation with fresh water is safe for optimum crop production, but in that case if this water is used over a long period without managing for salinity, a significant quantity of salts will be added into soil (Mohammad et al., 2018).

Within the EU, the major areas with salt-affected soils are found in various regions of the Iberic Peninsula, Italy, Greece, Hungary and Romania (Omuto et al., 2020).

4.6.5 Salinization

The Salinization process leads to an excessive increase of water-soluble salts in the soil. Both terrestrial and coastal salt accumulation can lead to the formation of saline soils. The salinization process can be a primary or secondary one. Primary salinization involves nature-forced processes, like weathering, and dissolved salt transportation. Secondary salinization is caused by human interventions, such as inappropriate irrigation practices, like using salt-rich irrigation water and poor drainage conditions (Várallyay in Huber et al., 2008.).

Salt accumulation in soils takes different forms, depending on the amount of the dissolved salts, the ionic composition and chemistry of the soil solution, resulting in saline, sodic and alkaline soils. *Saline soils* are characterised by elevated salt concentrations in the soil profile, *sodic soils* by an increased proportion of Na⁺ and K⁺ ions relative to Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions, while *alkaline soils* have a high pH value due to the predominance of (bi)carbonate ions. Sodic soils are also alkaline if their pH is above 8.5. Salinization limits the agro-ecological potential of the area concerned and the range of crops that can be grown. Large osmotic value of the saline soil moisture makes the transpiration of most of the plants in such soils difficult. At the same time, the endemic, salt-tolerant vegetation of saline soils often makes its territory an ecologically valuable nature reserve.

4.6.6 Recommendations for monitoring electrical conductivity changes

The monitoring of salinisation as a degradation process is included in the SML, where the proposed limit of 4 dS/m (ECe) is generally accepted and well applicable. Naturally saline land and areas directly affected by sea level rise are planned to be excluded. Taking into account that the movement of salts is influenced by the moisture content, seasonal fluctuations must be taken into account when monitoring. The recommended period for sampling is the dry, warm period of the year, when the maximum salt accumulation can be assumed. Because, the salt profile is an important characteristic of the soil, in the ideal case, the sampling should go down to the groundwater level, or at least below the root zone.

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4.7 Available water capacity

<p>Available water capacity (links with soil aridity)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Isabelle Cousin, Angelo Basile, Maria Fantappiè, Costanza Calzolari, Chiara Piccini, Maria Costanza Andrenelli, Nadia Vignozzi, Sergio Pellegrini, Carlos Lozano-Fondón, Ialina Vinci, Rosario Napoli ○ Relevant EJP SOIL projects: Steropes, ProbeField, SERENA
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The Available Water Capacity (AWC) is an important indicator of soil quality as it represents both the soil's ability to store water and its ability to supply water available for plant roots (Costantini and Priori, 2022). The Water Holding Capacity (WHC) is instead the ability of soils to store water, as a property of soil, which does not consider the ability of soil to supply that water to plant roots.

AWC is an important feature for soil water management, and it is at the basis of the soil water balance calculation in models using the reservoir-like representation. It is, therefore, involved in several issues: soil classification (Hurst, 1951 in Horne and Scotter, 2016), irrigation scheduling (Barker et al., 2018), crop growth and nutrient leaching (Cichota et al., 2013), and it is further considered as the most sensitive parameter in watershed models (Shivhare et al., 2018). In the Soil Monitoring Law (2023) WHC is considered for watershed management, which is put in place to reduce flooding risk or vice-versa to mitigate the drought risk, at river basin scale.

The AWC definition has been proposed about one century ago by Veihmeyer and Hendrickson (1927, 1931), and taken over by the INSPIRE Directive as “the amount of water that a soil can store that is available for use by plants, based on a potential rooting depth. It is the water held between field capacity and the wilting point, adjusted downward for rock fragments and for salts in solution”. The field capacity has been defined as the water content value at which the redistribution process, following water infiltration, proceeds so slowly that the drainage rate becomes negligible (Veihmeyer & Hendrickson, 1927). Another definition of field capacity is "the water content that remains in a soil 2 or 3 days after it has been wetted with water and after free drainage is negligible" (SSSA, 1997). The wilting point is defined as the lowest value of water content at which the plant finally wilts. The WHC is the total potential capacity of a soil to store water, therefore, is the amount of water that a soil can store between the field a capacity and the state of being completely dry.

Both AWC and WHC are mainly determined by the soil depth and the water-retention characteristic of soils, that is, the water content of soils at specific matric pressures (ISO 11274:2019). The most important parameter to be considered remains the soil volume. For AWC the soil volume is determined by the maximum rooting depth, for WHC by the soil depth up to a layer limiting water percolation, the shallowest between bedrock, groundwater table, or a compacted or destructured layer which impedes the water infiltration.

Both AWC and WHC are related to the hydrological behaviour of the entire soil profile; therefore, a proper soil water management should also consider the related soil properties, such as water infiltration rate and hydraulic conductivity, which are in turn related to other soil properties such as soil structure stability, soil porosity, soil compaction, and the propensity of soils to form crusts at the surface (soil crusting).

It is necessary to point out in this introduction that both AWC and WHC are potential soil water contents. In particular, the Veihmeyer and Hendrickson definition for AWC points to a potential capacity of soil to store water combined with the potential ability of plants to absorb it. This is not the actual water content “available” to crops during a growing season. These concepts are properly resumed by Bonfante et al. (2020) who state that the water content is determined by weather conditions during the growing season, type of crop, rooting patterns of a given crop, water fluxes determined by basic hydraulic properties of each soil horizon, such as moisture retention and hydraulic conductivity, and water-table levels.

4.7.1 Available water capacity measurement

4.7.1.1 Determination of the water-retention characteristic of soils

The available water capacity is defined as the amount of water held between two specific soil water contents: at Field Capacity (FC) and at Permanent Wilting Point (PWP) (Ladanyi et al., 2021; Horne and Scotter, 2016). FC represents the matric potential at which the soil can hold the maximum water content, once saturated, and left to drain freely under the sole action of gravity.

AWC is a process-dependent value of the profile water content, thus strongly dependent on hydraulic conductivity; moreover, it assumes the absence of evaporation from the soil surface and, above all, a uniform soil profile (Romano and Santini, 2002). In stratified soil profiles both AWC and WHC should be viewed as a global parameter according to an integrated response of the soil profile. However, despite the aforementioned limitations, for practical reasons the AWC is largely derived from laboratory measurements that provide proxy information of potential field conditions, which are indeed difficult to measure. The laboratory measures are done for soil samples taken as representative of soil layers/horizons.

FC is thus related to a physical process, the gravity drainage, and should not vary among crops for a given type of soil, as demonstrated by Ratliff et al. (1983). It depends strongly on soil characteristics, especially soil texture and structure. Several values of matric potential have been recommended for one century to represent FC, and Kirkham (2005) suggests setting soil moisture tension for FC at -10kPa (pF 2) for coarse texture soils and at -33kPa (pF 2.5) for heavy-textured soils. However, the most commonly used nowadays is -10 kPa. From data of the UNSODA database (Nemes et al., 2001) and the EU-HYDI database (Weynants et al. 2013), FC water content varies from 0.14 (± 0.07) $\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$ for sandy soils and 0.44 (± 0.08) $\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$ for clayey soils (Cousin et al., 2022).

PWP refers to the soil water content at which a plant is permanently wilted (Jiang et al., 2022). The original definition of PWP has been proposed from experiments of plants growth in pots and corresponds to a situation where the leaf wilt due to the water deficit cannot be reversed (Briggs and Shantz 1912). It is then more a biological ability combined with a soil characteristic: it is influenced by the soil/root profile, the plant type and stage, the transpiration rate, and the osmotic conditions in the soils. To enable a simple and accurate evaluation, a fixed matric potential of -1500 kPa (pF 4.2) is being used for decades to represent PWP, at least for annual crops in temperate climates (Ratliff et al. 1983). However, the matric potential at PWP can vary greatly among plant species, ranging from as low as -16,000 to -3,500 kPa for xerophilic species to higher than -1000 kPa for hydrophilic species

(Gobat et al., 2004); these specific conditions must be considered if a reservoir-like model using AWC is used. From data of the UNSODA and EU-HYDI databases, and using a reference potential of – 1500 kPa, PWP water content varies from 0.05 (± 0.04) $\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$ for sandy soils to 0.28 (± 0.07) $\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$ for clayey soils (Cousin et al., 2022).

4.7.1.2 Related concepts to the Available Water Capacity

As a double capacity to store water and making it available to plants, AWC refers to both soil characteristics and plants abilities. It can be evaluated both in laboratory conditions, where equilibrium conditions can be obtained, and from field data where the soil water content is continuously changing due to rainfall/irrigation inputs, evaporation and transpiration processes, that is, under non-equilibrium conditions. Depending on the evaluation methods, AWC does not exactly refer to the same concept (Fig. 4.7.1) (Cousin et al., 2022):

- With "at equilibrium" measurement methods involving only soil samples, AWC does represent the volume of water that soil can store and cede to plants. It is a potential capability for a given soil layer/horizon, whatever the climate and the plant type. This definition simplifies the evaluation and is the most used by pedologists. However, to evaluate the AWC for the whole soil profile there is the need to evaluate also the potential soil rooting depth, and there is a certain level of subjectivity in this evaluation, because it is difficult to determine this potential depth independently from the plant type. Even in the presence of the same soil properties, the rooting apparatus of different plants behave differently. For example, in the case of a parent material constituted by weathered and a relatively soft rock it could be explored by a strong root apparatus; or a soil horizon with high concentration of soil compounds toxic for the majority of plant root could be explorable by the roots of tolerant plant species. The common practice, among pedologists, is to consider the presence of these limiting factors independently from plant species, that is, to set a limit in case there is a limiting factor, independently from the fact that specific plant species have rooting systems apt to explore those impeding layers.
- With "out of equilibrium" soil-plant system measurements, involving both plant and soil, AWC does represent the volume of water, which is really used by plants, that is, a parameter representing the real capacity of the soil-plant system.

Figure 4.7. 1 Different acceptions of AWC depending on the conditions of measurements or evaluation (modified from Cousin et al. (2022))

4.7.1.3. Calculation of AWC

The AWC can be determined either in the field or in laboratory conditions by measuring water contents at FC and PWP separately at the layer/horizon scale, and then subtracting their values (AWC = FC - PWP). AWC of the whole soil profile is then evaluated from integration of the values at the layer/horizon scale according to the following equation:

$$AWC = \sum_{i=1}^{i=maxDepth} \Delta Z_i (FC_i - PWP_i)$$

where *maxDepth* is the maximum soil depth or the rooting depth, ΔZ_i is the thickness of the layer/horizon *i*, and FC_i and PWP_i are the characteristic water contents of the layer/horizon *i*.

Depending on the context, *maxDepth* can represent several items: for a general evaluation of AWC over a large territory, it must be the soil depth, and AWC then represents the effective maximum capacity of the soil to store water. For a local and dynamic use of AWC, in a model-decision tool for irrigation scheduling for example, it should be the maximum rooting depth, or even it should be adjusted in real time to the rooting value, according to the plant development.

As seen here, *maxDepth* is then a very important parameter in the evaluation of AWC and can even be considered as the most important one at the soil profile, as demonstrated in figure 4.7.2. The differences in AWC using different measurement/evaluation methods are smaller compared to the differences considering different soil (rooting) depths: e.g., the AWC evaluated with pedotransfer functions (PTF) it is equal to 105 mm for a 100 cm soil depth, and 133 mm for a 130 cm soil depth; this 28 mm difference between the two evaluations represents about one irrigation event, and demonstrates how precise the evaluation of AWC must be.

Figure 4.7. 2 Evaluation of water contents at FC and PWP using different methods for a soil developed over alluvium with a fine texture (Avignon, France) (a). Evaluation of AWC over the Avignon soil by using 4 different methods (b).

4.7.1.4. Evaluation of AWC from laboratory measurements

Compared to field measurements, laboratory determination relies on small soil samples, collected in each layer/horizon of soil profiles, but is performed in controlled conditions and allows researchers to post-process several soil samples together.

Based on the ascertained relationship between water content and soil matrix tension, the most common laboratory measurements of FC and PWP consist in equilibrating soil samples, at predetermined tensions of -10 kPa or -33 kPa, depending on soil texture or structure, and -1500 kPa, respectively, for several days. Then, the water content is calculated by the differences between wet and oven dried soil sample weights. Soil bulk density value of the samples allows then the conversion of the gravimetric water content into volumetric base. The standard procedure according to the ISO 11274:2019, proposed as standard procedure in the SML, requires to measure FC, on undisturbed

clouds or soil samples which are successively re-saturated before they are placed on the pressure plate or sand-box apparatus to ensure that they reach the required matric potential (see, for example, Dane and Hopmans, 2002). Conversely, due to the small pore sizes involved in water retention at PWP, this can be measured from disturbed or sieved soil samples. The most common lab methods for measuring FC employ the traditional sandbox or hanging water column apparatus (Burke et al., 1986), otherwise the more modern evaporation method (Wind, 1968). With such traditional methods, soil sample volume spans between 110 and 140 cm³; in the latter, the volume is notably larger, typically 250 cm³. With regards to the PWP determination, typically the pressure plate apparatus (Dane and Hopmans, 2002) or the more modern dewpoint water potential meter technique are used. A dewpoint potentiometer utilizes hygrometry to determine water potentials of porous media via a chilled mirror to measure the dew point temperature in the headspace above a sample (Schelle et al., 2013; Fields et al., 2020).

Next to these “at equilibrium” methods used to directly measure FC and PWP water contents, “outside equilibrium” experiments can be conducted: data from experiments on drainage or evaporation in soil column samples, e.g., single or multistep outflow experiments (Vereecken et al., 1997; Vrugt et al., 2001), wind evaporation experiments (Tamari et al. 1993), can be used. The water contents and matric potential dynamics are used to adjust the parameters of a soil-water transfer model which simulates the observations of the system. The water retention curve, represented by a continuous curve parameterised by, for example, the Van Genuchten model (1980) is then estimated by inverse modelling. One can then derive the water content at FC and PWP.

4.7.1.5. Evaluation of AWC from field measurements

In the field, AWC is evaluated from water content monitoring in soil layer/horizons by sensors, such as time-domain reflectometry or neutron probes (Ritchie 1981), from the surface down to the potential rooting depth. For FC, field monitoring must be conducted on bare soil, preferably in winter, to obtain a soil water content high enough to be near the FC and to avoid high evaporation rates (Ottoni et al., 2014). After a rainfall event supposed to have rewetted the soil above field capacity, the water content time series is recorded. The transition between fast drainage and a quasi-steady state of water content usually occurs 48 hours after the rainfall event and corresponds to FC. FC is reached after a few days of free drainage, variable between 1 to 3 days from saturation, when water content reaches a near-constant value and internal drainage becomes negligible (Assouline and Or, 2014). However, the duration of the observations must be adapted to the texture of the soil layer/horizons and to the climatic demand, and the duration of monitoring may need to be much longer (Assouline and Or, 2014).

In the same way, PWP water content could be evaluated by in-situ monitoring of water content in a cropped field till the plant dies. However, such a measurement usually represents the crop lower limit, which can be different from one plant to another plant, and from one year to another year, depending on the climatic conditions. PWP water content is then definitely plant-dependent. PWP measured in the field depends not only on matric potential, but also on other physical elements, for example mechanical resistance which limits the accessibility of water to plants. Some authors (da Silva and Kay 1997; Leao et al. 2006) introduced the concept of “least limiting water range” to aggregate cumulative effects on crop water uptake in relation to soil water and its dynamics, aeration, but also mechanical resistance due to soil type and crop management. This concept should not be confused with the PWP,

and field data then do not systematically correspond to the water content at -1500 kPa measured in the lab.

To overcome these uncertainties with respect to PWP, the wilting point is universally associated with a soil matrix tension of -1,500 kPa, despite its recognized link with the plant variety and soil chemistry, which would make it preferable to determine it by in situ measurements. The use of the standard value of -1,500 kPa makes the determination of PWP in the laboratory as valid as its determination in the field and frees definition of PWP from the actual withering of the crop. At this tension level, the soil has low moisture content, and it is difficult for the roots of most plants (sunflower, wheat, or corn) to extract water.

As outlined by some authors like Parker and Trignani (2021), field observations could be more accurate than laboratory experiments because they can account for the overall *in situ* condition, soil variability included. In addition, field methods overcome the effect of soil disturbance caused by the soil sampling that might distort soil sample volume and increase the margins of error of deformation and swelling upon saturation. Nevertheless, in situ analyses may be very laborious and time consuming because they often require monitoring soil moisture status over an entire growing season. Sensors must be inserted in the soil and AWC of stony soils can hardly be defined by in-situ monitoring. Moreover, the evaluation of AWC by field monitoring can be representative only of one plant species and, rigorously, should be conducted for each plant, which is definitely too expensive. In any case, one has to keep in mind that laboratory and field measurements do not represent exactly the same thing, and that lab and field values may be different, without one or the other being false (Fig. 4.7.1).

4.7.1.6. Effect of rock fragments and salt solution on the AWC evaluation

As porous media, rock fragments in the soil can retain a significant or non-significant quantity of water, depending on their lithological type. According to Tetegan et al. (2011) sedimentary rock fragments can contribute for 2% (for flint) to 60% (for weathered limestone) to AWC at the horizon scale. Under drought conditions, rock fragments then act as water reservoirs (Tetegan et al., 2015) and can significantly contribute to limit the plant water stress (Korboulewski et al., 2020). In forest soils, Algayer et al. (2020) observed a significant increase in the correlation between tree growth and AWC when the rock fragments are taken into account in the evaluation of AWC. At the field scale, ignoring the contribution of rock fragments to the total soil AWC may lead to some overestimations of irrigation needs, up to 30 mm a year in a sedimentary calcareous region (Tetegan et al., 2015).

As mentioned in the definition given by the INSPIRE Directive, salt content in the soil solution should be considered in the AWC evaluation, because it modifies the interfacial tensions in the soil and the osmotic conditions, which should modify the condition for the plants to capture water from the soil. Generally speaking, the general concept of AWC should not be considered valid for saline or sodic soils, and classical AWC laboratory measurements should not be used to parameterise soil-water bucket models in such soil, which requires site-specific studies (e.g., Wang et al., 2011; Abd El-Mageed and Semida, 2015).

4.7.2 Available water capacity measurement with PS/RS methods

The knowledge of the short-range spatial variability of soil hydrological parameters at field scale is crucial for proper crop management, aimed at maximizing income and reducing environmental impacts of agricultural activities. In precision agriculture it is very important to know the hydrogeological variability (Morari et al., 2009; Costantini et al., 2009) of cultivated areas to plan drainage, irrigation, tillage, fertilization etc., as well as to improve the product quality.

The capacity of soils to conduct electricity is obviously linked to their actual water content, and to the salt concentration in soil water. Based on this principle, PS sensing tools have been produced which measure the electrical resistivity/conductivity of soils. Those sensors can be used as an indirect estimation of potential soil water content properties, such as AWC and WHC, but calibration with analytical measurements is needed. A first PS scanning is performed to detect the short-range spatial variability of the electrical resistivity/conductivity of soils, producing detailed field maps, which are then used to elaborate cost effective field-scale sampling strategies (Genere et al., 2015). The targeted soil sampling strategy permits to extract soil samples representative of the micro spatial variation of soil resistivity/conductivity. The soil samples are then analysed in laboratory and digital soil mapping methods are used to interpolate the soil properties, such as AWC or WHC, with the electrical resistivity/conductivity maps as auxiliary variables (Cousin et al., 2022). Since available soil water capacity (AWC) has been shown to be related to soil texture among others (McCutcheon et al., 2006; Saey et al., 2011), there is the possibility of using digital soil mapping (DSM) techniques to provide such information. Other properties that can be related to soil AWC have also been mapped, including cation exchange capacity (CEC) (Zhao et al., 2020), mineralogy (Nagra et al., 2017), and organic matter (Huang et al., 2017). Conversely, Gamma-ray (γ -ray) spectrometry data have also been used to map clay (Arshad et al., 2020), CEC (Li et al., 2018), and infer mineralogical differences (Triantafilis et al., 2013), and therefore could be used to indirectly determine the linked AWC and WHC soil properties.

Two main categories of PS instruments measuring the electrical resistivity/conductivity of soils are the electromagnetic induction (EMI) instruments, which measure the soil apparent electrical conductivity (ECa), and the conductivity contact probe soil scanners, directly measuring the soil electrical conductivity (EC) by introducing a metallic contact probe into the soils.

The estimation of surface soil moisture (SSM) through RS is already a consolidated technique, supported by decennial research in the field. Remote sensors cannot directly measure SSM content, but instead use a proxy variable related to measured signals. RS soil moisture estimation methods can be grouped into: passive microwave sensing, active microwave sensing and optical/thermal sensing (Ambrosone et al., 2020). An example of passive microwave sensors is the Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer (AMSR-E). The estimation of SSM using passive microwave sensors is based on the difference between the dielectric properties of water and of dry soil, measured as variations in the soil brightness temperature of dry and wet soil (Njoku and Kong, 1977). Active sensors transmit information as a series of pulses while the radar antenna traverses the imaged landscape, which are then processed together to simulate a long aperture capable of providing high surface resolution scenes (Ulaby et al., 1996). Bauer-Marschallinger et al. (2018) proposed a data fusion approach combining two different data sources, METOP-ASCAT and Sentinel-1, in order to calculate a Soil Water Index (SWI) providing data on a daily basis at 1-km spatial resolution. The Bauer-Marschallinger et al. (2018) Soil Water Index is available in the Copernicus Global Land Service (CGLS) (<https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/swi>). Optical/thermal sensing of SSM is based on the use of visible, short wave and thermal infrared optical bands (wavelengths ranging between 0.4 and 15

μm) to retrieve surface reflectance (Sobrino et al., 2012; Rahimzadeh and Berg, 2016). The model, hereinafter called Thermal-Optical Trapezoid Model (TOTRAM) (Nemani et al., 1993; Carlson et al., 1994), is derived from the interpretation of the relationship existing between the pixel distribution of Land Surface Temperature (LST), and vegetation indices (VI). Water body indices are RS indexes, such as the NDWI (normalized water index) and LSWI (land surface water index) which can be used to identify land surface water body and to directly estimate surface soil moisture. RS is already applied by Digital Support Systems produced by private companies for irrigation scheduling in precision agriculture. Therefore, the same as for PS, the developed RS techniques are used to continuously monitor the soil moisture, and not for the monitoring of eventual increase of the potential soil water storage (AWC and WHC).

4.7.3 Available water capacity thresholds and target values

To define a threshold or a target value, the object of the monitoring needs to be a property which is changing in time.

Can the capacity of the soil to store water be improved or degraded by some agricultural practices? As reported in the paragraph on modeling, the water content at different matric potentials is mainly linked to soil texture, therefore strongly dependent on an invariant property of soils. A positive relationship of FC soil water content with SOC has been found, which has been explained by the ability of SOC to improve soil structure, reducing compaction and increasing porosity. Consequently, the soil management practices increasing SOC content can increase WHC, although this positive effect is slow in time. Conversely, it has been demonstrated for decades that the addition of organic matter does not significantly improve AWC, except for sandy soils, because it increased both the water content at FC and at PWP (so that the difference between these is not that different) (Rawls et al., 2003, Minasny and MacBratney, 2018). Secondly, the effect of compaction on AWC may appear as counter-intuitive: as demonstrated by Glab (2014), soil compaction modifies the porous system in the range of large pores and fissures, but the pore volume in the range on AWC can then be higher than before compaction (Richard et al., 2001), which may increase AWC.

Can the capacity of soil to provide water to plants be improved or degraded by some agricultural practices? Plants can collect only water in the soil which is extractable by their roots. It is a biological ability combined with a soil characteristic: it is influenced by the soil/root profile, the plant type and stage, the transpiration rate, and the osmotic conditions in the soils. Some soil management practices have demonstrated to improve the ability of plants to absorb soil water, such as: improving the soil structure by increasing SOC content, since a better soil structure increase the soil volume explorable by plant roots, genetic improvement of cultivars adapted to the specific soil conditions (e.g., drought resistant), crops associations, the use of mycorrhizae, decreasing osmotic pressure in soils by desalinization, and so on. Secondly, management can stimulate that plants collect water over the whole soil profile; agronomic systems including species with a deep rooting in the rotation, as well as multi-species crops with different rooting systems (like agroforestry, for example) will enable a larger quantity of water in the soil available for extraction by plants. It is hard to define which soil property is to be monitored to detect these improvements. The structure stability could be one.

But the most important parameter to be considered is the soil volume. For AWC the soil volume is determined by the maximum rooting depth, for WHC by the soil depth up to a layer limiting water percolation, the shallowest between bedrock, groundwater table, or a compacted or destructured layer which impedes the water percolation to deeper depths. Can soil depth or soil rooting depth be improved or degraded by some agricultural practices? Destructured impermeable layers can be

improved by the addition of SOC, while compacted layers can be theoretically cut by ripping, which depends on their hardness. These kinds of practices could also determine a rapid and effective increase in AWC and WHC.

Another important aspect to be considered in the general hydraulic behavior of soil profile is the water movement from the surface to the deepest layers, which is determined by the infiltration rate at the surface and by the permeability through the soil profile. The presence of soil crusts can even impede water infiltration completely. The infiltration rate is known to be improved by addition of organic matter which stimulates biological activity and maintains large pores connected to the soil surface. Adding organic matter is also known to limit runoff and erosion, and a large part of rainfall can be infiltrated into the soil; finally, organic matter at the soil surface limits the evaporation, and the depletion of the soil water content. The runoff can be decreased, waterflow regulated, and infiltration rate increased, also by the establishment of soil water channels parallel to the contour lines (that is perpendicular to the slope).

Finally, to answer to the question on which soil parameter is most appropriate to be monitored to determine an improvement in the ability of soils to store water, we could give the suggestion to monitor soil water infiltration and percolation rate, given by soil permeability, and the structure stability. At a river basin scale, the water flow at the outlets could be monitored, to be evaluated at each rain event considering the rainfall amount. The more water infiltrates and is stored in the soils, therefore, the higher is the WHC of the river basin soils, the lower the percentage of rainwater that would flow out of the river basin. Some soil permeability classes are given by FAO online, differentiated for agriculture and for civil engineering purposes.

4.7.4 Available water capacity modelling

Measuring the AWC by field or laboratory approaches is expensive and time-consuming. It is then efficient to use pedotransfer functions (PTFs) to evaluate AWC, especially over large territories.

The very first pedotransfer functions, calibrated decades before the terms were introduced by Bouma in 1989, aimed to estimate water content at specific values of soil matric potential. In 1907 Briggs and McLane (1907) were the first to present an empirical relation between water content at wilting point and textural fractions. In 1965 Salter and Williams published class PTFs suggesting AWC values for soil textural classes, while in 1977 Hall et al. derived point PTFs to estimate volumetric water contents at FC and PWP, along with AWC and air capacity. Another example for early PTF literature is provided by Gupta and Larson (1979) who developed 12 PTFs to predict soil water contents at soil matric potentials between -4 kPa and -1500 kPa using soil textural fractions and organic matter as input variables. The most efficient soil variables for the AWC evaluation are physical characteristics relevant for water retention (Minasny and Hartemink 2011): texture or particle-size distribution (see for example Rawls et al., 1982), soil organic carbon content (see for example Batjes, 2016), and the bulk density (see for example Al Majou et al., 2008).

Numerous PTFs evaluations are published in the literature and can help the use to select the most appropriate to the context (see for example Abdelbaki, 2021, who compared 30 PTFs for the evaluation of AWC). However, Cousin et al. (2022) made some recommendations regarding the selection and use of a PTF to evaluate AWC:

1. As already explained by Wösten et al. (2001), the PTF should have been developed using soils similar to those to which it is applied, over a common pedo-climatic context;

2. The selected PTF should have been developed at a scale similar to that at which it is applied (Stoorvogel et al., 2019; Van Looy et al., 2017), and a comparison between the texture characteristics of the soils of the area of interest and the soils used for developing the PTF could be useful (Minasny and Hartemink, 2011; Roman Dobarco et al., 2019). In addition, sets of PTFs can be used, for example to estimate soil properties over large regions (Dai et al. (2019). At the EU-scale the Toth et al. (2015) PTF could be used for AWC estimations over the whole European territory;
3. Finally, it would be better to select a PTF published with its uncertainties (Minasny and McBratney, 2002), and to use such uncertainties in the use of the PTF. Finally, if there isn't any proposition fulfilling these recommendations, the best practice would be to develop a specific PTF in the region of interest, whatever the price of such a proposition.

4.7.5 Effects of scale (time/space) on available water capacity

In the paragraph related to thresholds and target values, we have already answered the question: is the ability of soils to store water and make it available for plants varying in time? The answer was that no significant improvement in the time framework could be obtained in relation to the water-retention characteristic of soils, which are strictly related to the invariable soil property soil texture. Improvement, but very slow in time, could be obtained in relation to the soil water content at FC by adding organic matter. Therefore, we concluded that the largest improvements in the timeframe could be obtained in relation to other hydraulic soil properties, such as water infiltration rate and permeability.

The scale considered is strictly dependent on the soil function considered. In relation to plant growth, therefore for agronomical purposes, the scale mostly applied is the field scale, therefore, microvariation of hydraulic soil properties is considered. In relation to soil and water conservation towards the increase in soil water storage, the river basin scale is the most appropriate.

4.7.6 Soil aridity

Aridity is a nature-produced permanent imbalance in the water availability consisting in low average annual precipitation, with high spatial and temporal variability, resulting in overall low moisture and low carrying capacity of the ecosystems (Pereira et al., 2002). As such, this is not a threat directly for soil but it strongly influenced by the quantity of water in soil, say the water really available for plants. Increasing aridity is an important hazard for many ecosystems and economic sectors, including water management, agriculture, forestry and tourism. Unlike drought, aridity describes the long-term average dryness of a region, which leads to limited or low water content in the soil: the lack of rainfall depends on the local climate and represents a permanent or seasonal condition (Colantoni et al., 2015). Aridity can lead to soil erosion, salinisation and other forms of land degradation; it can also set off or exacerbate water-related conflicts in affected regions.

A reduction in SOC associated with increase in aridity and with increase in diurnal temperature variations is usually observed. Thus, aridity is a critical environmental factor in determining the evolution of natural vegetation, also considering the water stress which may occur reducing vegetation cover (Kosmas et al., 1999).

A common method for quantifying the gap between rainfall contributions and water demand is the [Aridity Index \(AI\)](#) which represents a simple but effective tool for scientific investigation, territorial

monitoring and classification. The Aridity Index, representing the average water available in the soil, is calculated by dividing the total annual precipitation (P) by the annual reference evapotranspiration (ET₀):

$$AI = P/ET_0$$

As a rule, AI values below 0.5 define arid or semi-arid areas, while values over 0.65 describe humid and hyper-humid zones, as shown in the table 4. 7.1 (modified from Nastos et al., 2013):

Table 4.7. 1 Classification limits of the Aridity Index.

Aridity Index (AI) values	Climate classification
AI < 0.05	Hyper-arid
0.05 < AI < 0.2	Arid
0.2 < AI < 0.5	Semi-arid
0.5 < AI < 0.65	Dry sub-humid
0.65 < AI < 0.75	Humid
AI > 0.75	Hyper-humid

Drylands cover more than 40% of the global terrestrial surface (Moreno-Jimenez et al., 2019) and are highly vulnerable to human activities, climate change, and land degradation (Huang et al., 2016; Berdugo et al., 2020). In Europe, aridity is currently higher in the southernmost regions, but worse conditions are likely to occur in the future, especially in areas just north of the current ‘aridity hotspots’ (the northern part of the Iberian Peninsula, Turkey and the Balkans). Increasing aridity is a major force of climate change in drylands (Huang et al., 2016).

Recent studies have indicated that multiple ecosystem structures and functions present two stages of abrupt change in the soil with the intensification of aridity, namely, the soil disruption phase with declines in organic carbon, total nitrogen, clay contents and stability of aggregates (Berdugo et al., 2020; Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2013), and the ecosystem breakdown phase, with extreme reductions in plant cover and exponential increases in albedo (Berdugo et al., 2020; Hu et al., 2021).

4.7.7 Recommendations for monitoring available water capacity changes

When considering AWC as indicator for soil (health) state, the difficulty is given by considering different applications. In the SML, the linked soil degradation process is named ‘reduction of soil capacity to retain water’, and analysing the description it is clear that the focus of the directive is on minimising flooding risk, therefore the water availability for plants is not considered.

When analysing the SML, a threshold is proposed and corresponds to the quantity of water which could be stored in the soil under very intense rainfall. The idea would be to limit flooding due to extreme events, by increasing the capacity of soils to store water. However, we would like to stress that this conceptual vision of the role of soil in mitigating extreme rainfall events is limiting the roles of water content in soils. On the one hand, we do think that the capacity of a river basin to store water is much more affected by soil sealing than by soil management at farm scale. Ungaro et al. (2021) estimated for the valley of Po and Veneto region in Italy, that 8.8 Megatons of potential available water capacity have been lost due to soil sealing between 2012 and 2020, with a mean loss of 1.1 Megatons per year, losing the 12.83% of the whole storage capacity of the region (Ungaro et al., 2021).

On the other hand, soil does not behave like an empty reservoir or a lake: the quantity of rainfall water entering the soil does depend on the infiltration capacity of the soil, which can be depleted due to crusting, or just be lower than the rainfall intensity. Depending on the rainfall intensity, and especially in stormy situations, all the rainfall water cannot be absorbed by the soil. Moreover, whatever the rainfall intensity, the soil may be far from its stage at permanent wilting point: the “soil-tank” is then not empty and cannot receive the whole rainfall. Finally, a significant part of the soil porosity is represented by pores larger than the pore size at FC: whereas it is not stored in the soil, rainfall is transferred through these large pores which can act as buffers to receive high rainfalls.

A final technical comment on the SML is that the indicator proposed for the monitoring is quite confusing. The water holding capacity should be expressed in % of volume of water / volume of saturated soil (a percentage in volume) or in tonnes? Is it to be measured for soil samples, for soil profiles, or for river basins? Furthermore, we recommend to consider and monitor other soil properties which could improve the soil capacity to reduce the flooding risk, such as the infiltration rate and the permeability. At river basin scale, the waterflow at the outlet as a percentage of the total rainfall volume for each river basin, is suggested to monitor the increase of WHC. The structural stability is also suggested as a way to monitor better hydraulic conditions for plant growth.

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4.8 Soil biodiversity

<p>Soil biodiversity (including soil biodiversity loss)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Stefano Mocali, Antonio Bispo, Carlo Jacomini, Alessandra Trinchera, Erica Lumini, Johanna Wetterlind, Raja Murugan, Lorenzo D’Avino, Annamaria Bevivino, Markéta Sagova-Mareckova, Cristina Aponte, Jack Faber ○ Relevant EJP SOIL Projects: Minotaur, SERENA, SIREN AGROECOseqC
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Soil represents the link between the air, water, rocks, and biota, and is responsible for many functions in the natural world that are beneficial to human society, called “ecosystem services” (ES). Notably, many of such ES are driven and regulated by soil biodiversity. Recently, it has been reported that soils are likely home to about 59% of the species on Earth, implying soil is the most biodiverse singular habitat (Anthony et al., 2023). The estimation of soil richness currently doubled compared to the previous values (Decaëns et al., 2006, 2008). Besides biodiversity, soil provides an extensive habitat and enormous storage site. Just to give an idea, one gram of soil can contain billions of bacterial cells, kilometers of fungal hyphae, and dozens of microscopic worms (nematodes) (Table 4.8.1). Scaling up, 57 billion nematodes live on Earth for every human (van den Hoogen et al. 2019), and 20 gigatons (Gt) of carbon are contained in the biomass of fungus and bacteria in soils worldwide (Bar-On et al., 2018). Soil holds 1500 Gt of carbon, twice the amount found in the atmosphere, while up to 15 tons of soil organisms can be found in one hectare of soil (Weil and Brady, 2016), including soil fauna (earthworms, collembola, nematodes) and microorganisms (bacteria and fungi).

The body size of soil organisms spans many orders of magnitude, from nanometers (e.g., viral particles) to several decimeters (e.g., earthworms) (Orgiazzi et al., 2016). Thus, the changes in body size width ((microorganisms (<10uM), microfauna (10 - 100uM), mesofauna (100uM-2mm), macrofauna (2-20mm) and megafauna (>20mm)) demands an appropriate choice of biodiversity indicators that reflect these scales (Coleman & Wall, 2015).

Table 4.8. 1 Estimated diversity and abundance of soil taxa according to published literature (Bardgett & van der Putten, 2014, modified).

Taxon	Diversity per amount soil or area (taxonomic units indicated below)	Abundance (approximate)
Prokaryotes	100–9,000 cm ⁻³	4–20 × 10 ⁹ cm ⁻³
Fungi†	200–235 g ⁻¹ ‡	100 mg ⁻¹
AMF (species)	10–20 m ⁻²	81–111 m cm ⁻³
Protists	150–1,200 (0.25 g) ⁻¹ §	10 ⁴ –10 ⁷ m ⁻²
Nematodes (genera)	10–100 m ⁻²	2–90 × 10 ⁵ m ⁻²
Enchytraeids	1–15 ha ⁻¹	12,000–311,000 m ⁻²
Tardigrades	not available	not available
Collembola	20 m ⁻²	1–5 × 10 ⁴ m ⁻²
Mites (Oribatida)	100–150 m ⁻²	1–10 × 10 ⁴ m ⁻²
Isopoda	10–100 m ⁻²	10 m ⁻²
Diplopoda	10–2,500 m ⁻²	110 m ⁻²
Earthworms (Oligochaeta)	10–15 ha ⁻¹	300 m ⁻²

The complexity and the spatial-temporal dynamics of the soil environment and its interactions with soil biota are still poorly known (Costantini & Mocali, 2022). Such lack of knowledge and the complexity of the interactions occurring among organisms and between biota and the soil chemical-physical environment, strongly limits our comprehension of the dynamics and the biological mechanisms driving soil processes, which directly influence ES. The ecological challenges for soil science lie at the research scale of “*functional domains*” to better understand the complex synergistic and antagonistic interactions among organisms and the physico-chemical environment (Lavelle, 2000). Examples of functional domains include the “drilosphere” (influenced by earthworms), “rhizosphere” (influenced by roots), and “detritosphere” (influenced by plant litter) (Beare et al., 1995). Within each functional domain, processes may be different depending on scales of time and space, which currently provide apparently conflicting results. For example, the high spatial and temporal variation of soil properties and processes, even within functional domains, makes generalizations about the impact of tillage systems on soil ecology very difficult (Kladivko, 2001). So, the question is: “is it possible to simplify such complex interactions between soil biota, soil processes, soil functionality and soil quality in such a way that they can be comprehensively described by a minimum set of parameters?”. We argue that the key to capturing the life of soils does not lie in simplification, but rather in **embracing its multifunctional complexity** (see figure 4.8.2).

In order to deal with this complexity, it is important to keep in mind that soil biodiversity possesses certain specificities. First, microbial taxa within the observed community might never encounter each other as they inhabit spatially separated soil pores or microsites (Geisen et al. 2019). Second, soil food webs usually lack trophic specialization due to a greater number of omnivorous and cannibalistic interactions (Thakur and Geisen, 2019) and systematically lower predator–prey body mass ratios (Brose et al., 2019). Third, important non-trophic interactions also occur in soil, mainly due to ecosystem engineers increasing soil structural complexity and thereby constraining direct encounters between predators and prey, also creating resource hotspots with their excrements. Fourth, the physical complexity of soils is a property that results partly from the biological activity of soil organisms, which has consequences in feed-back connections between soil processes. The discrepancy between

structure and function is particularly significant in microbial communities, which are dominated by a few abundant species, while their richness is associated with rare species with largely unknown ecological roles and biogeography.

Although most of the diversity is still unknown, it is widely accepted that most of soil organisms may be classified in three main functional groups according to their dominant contribution to soil processes and ecosystem services (Fig. 4.8.1):

1. **Chemical engineers (Microbes)**: are the smallest organisms in soil. They decompose and mineralize organic matter, transform residues into nutrients and play a key role in bioremediation (Turbé et al., 2010). Harmful bacteria, such as soil-borne pathogens, affect crop health and growth resulting in yield loss, whereas beneficial microbes may promote plant nutrition and protection. So, all these species are engaged in intricate trophic exchange networks among each other and plant rhizosphere (Compant et al., 2019).
2. **Biological regulators (Micro- and Meso-fauna)**: are a diverse bunch which control the activities of the chemical engineers and form a crucial link in the food web by regulating biological dynamics through grazing, predation or parasitism, control of soil-borne pests and diseases; however, they are also able to impact nutrient recycling rates (Gao et al. 2018). Moreover microarthropods belonging to mesofauna have a significant impact in decomposition processes (Coleman & Wall, 2015).
3. **Ecosystem engineers (Macro-fauna)**: spend their lives restructuring the soil matrix, mixing and moving soil as they feed, and creating habitable spaces and conditions for and dispersing other soil organisms. Their indirect contribution to nutrient cycling plays a key role in improving soil fertility and plant production (Jones et al., 1994).

Figure 4.8. 1 Main (simplified) relationships occurring between soil biodiversity and soil processes, ecosystem functioning and services. (modified by El Mujtar et al., 2019). Black arrows and black dashed arrows indicate, respectively, major and minor roles of functional groups on soil processes. Gray arrows indicate the relationships among supporting, regulating and provisioning ecosystem services.

Overall, the organisms belonging to these groups guarantee and support the main soil structures and processes contributing to soil functioning and the provision of associated ES. Soil biodiversity, being the driver of many soil processes, is essential and indispensable for ecosystem functioning and services including food security and human health. Thus, they should be always included in any monitoring initiative aiming to assess soil biodiversity and the provision of ES.

Along similar assumptions, the experience of previous EU-funded projects (e.g. Ecofinders, Envasso, Landmark, etc.) and initiatives (e.g. JRC-LUCAS, SoilBon, National monitoring programmes, etc.) have already suggested that a reliable and effective approach to monitor soil biodiversity shall be done by means of selected indicators which should be evaluated in terms of policy-relevancy, cost-efficiency, scientific robustness, ease of application, level of standardization, etc. **Based on this overview, we conclude that sufficient methodology and experience is available to start EU implementation of a limited set of biological indicators to monitor soil biodiversity and soil health.**

4.8.1 Soil biodiversity measurements and monitoring

In the last two decades several sets of suitable indicators for monitoring soil biodiversity have been proposed for application in soil monitoring at EU scale. For example, the FP6 project ENVASSO selected about 100 potential indicators from a literature review and an inventory of national monitoring programs and came up with a shortlist recommendation (Bispo et al., 2009). The FP7 project EcoFINDERS has elaborated on these and added the then novel molecular approach of metabarcoding. Indicators were also evaluated in terms of policy-relevancy, cost-efficiency, scientific robustness, ease of application, level of standardization, etc. (Faber et al. 2013, Griffiths et al. 2016). However, the inventory of existing monitoring networks showed that only a few biological indicators have actually been implemented in national monitoring (e.g. Bünemann et al., 2018), as recently confirmed by the EJP SOIL deliverable 2.2 “Stocktaking on soil quality indicators and associated decision support tools, including ICT tools” (unpublished EJP SOIL report) and the SIREN project by taking stock of the member states national monitoring frameworks (Faber et al. 2022) (Table 4.8.2).

These studies highlighted that soil respiration, microbial biomass and earthworm communities were the most often used indicators across Europe. However, soil respiration and microbial biomass do not provide any specific information on structural biodiversity but only general information on the overall soil biological activity, which is often difficult to interpret. Although earthworms represent a key actor of the soil biota, they cannot be indicative of the overall structural and taxonomic diversity occurring in soils.

Table 4.8. 2 Implementation of biological indicators as part of national campaigns on soil health monitoring, as reviewed under 24 EJP SOIL Member States in 2021 (source: EJP Soil D2.2). The relative number of countries which implemented biological indicators are reported. Also, the number of countries is specified per indicator that have established a reference value, threshold value, or target value as evaluation criteria. Note that evaluation criteria may be contextually differentiated in relation to soil type and land use.

Indicator	Measurement	Degree of implementation (n. of countries)	Number of countries with evaluation criteria established		
			Reference value	Threshold value	Target value
Biological activity	Soil respiration	7		1	
	Soil enzymes	5			
	Potential Mineralizable Nitrogen	4	1	1	
Microorganisms	C, N microbial biomass	6	1	1	
	Bacterial biomass (various methods)	5	2		
	Bacterial activity (Thy-incorporation)	1	1		1
	Fungal biomass (various methods)	5			
Macro-edaphon	Invertebrate species counts	3	1		
	Earthworms, species composition and biomass, ecological groups	6	3	2	1
Meso-edaphon	Collembola/ Acari species counts, trophic groups	4	1		
	Nematodes species composition, trophic and coloniser-persister groups	5	1		
Micro-edaphon	Protozoa counts	3	1		

It should also be highlighted that both **structural** and **functional** aspects are relevant for biodiversity assessments or for informing on the condition of the soil environment (e.g. in response to soil threats). For purposes of biodiversity assessment (species richness, phylogenetic diversity, community structure, etc.), rare and endangered species may be listed for monitoring, but such species are expected to have little impact on soil system functioning. While the frequently used monitoring indicators such as fungal, bacterial and earthworm biomasses provide limited information on the status and trends in structural biodiversity, DNA-based molecular metabarcoding approaches can do just that. Molecular techniques have become scientifically well established, standardized, and relatively cheap, and are worldwide increasingly applied in soil monitoring initiatives (e.g. JRC-LUCAS, SoilBON, Earth Microbiome Project, etc.). Therefore, it has been proposed to include those approaches as a basis for decisions about near future monitoring (e.g. Labouyrie et al., 2023).

Actually, whereas the definition of a “minimum set” of indicators for the assessment of soil health should be desirable, some authors are proposing to move beyond the quest for a universal minimum dataset to a more flexible approach which indeed considers the context of the assessment and is tailored to the objectives of the user. For example, Creamer and co-workers (2022) proposed and

described a flexible tool, BIOSIS (<https://biosisplatform.eu/>), for the context-specific selection of methodologies for assessing soil functions as well as overall multifunctionality, specifically for agricultural systems. The method selection tool is tailored to the context and resources of the user, thus recommending different methodologies for diverse contexts. On the other hand, from a more practical perspective a minimum dataset might bring benefits, such as comparability of data across a range of applications, thus better facilitating policy intervention and management actions (Creamer et al., 2022). Thus, to select appropriate indicators and to combine practicability and flexibility of the monitoring initiatives, a “**tiered system**” approach is here proposed, following the recommendations of ENVASSO, EcoFINDERS and SIREN projects, meaning that different sets of indicators may be identified depending on the purpose (aim and conditions) of a specific monitoring program:

- **Tier I:** A “minimum set” of indicators is highly recommended for all applications, and, depending on availability of resources and specific requirements, can be extended to include tiers II for additional analysis. A tiered approach uses the simplest techniques first and advances to more detailed approaches only when additional data is needed to better understand state and trend, and to inform management decision making. Tier I is aimed to produce information at minimum expenses which is harmonized across countries to facilitate pan-European comparison and evaluation. The tiered approach allows stakeholders to identify where greater informational effort is required, for instance if basic indicators suggest poor soil conditions and management intervention seems required to improve soil health.
- **Tier II:** additional indicators may be applied for more intensive study of the effects of a particular environmental stressor or the results of remediation measures (or to inform remediation management). These indicators may include organism groups that require expert identification, such as micro-arthropods and nematodes. Such increased effort is only required when specific sites or questions need to be addressed, requiring more detailed information.

Actually, several strategies may be employed in collecting and characterizing the diversity of soil organisms (Geisen et al., 2019). Many methods and protocols for characterizing soil organisms are quite old and have been used for a very long time (by Darwin, Berlese, etc.). The description of the methods for the assessment of soil biodiversity is beyond the scope of this chapter, but a list of methods commonly used for the assessment of both structural and functional diversity of soil fauna and microbial communities is reported here, with references to ISO standards (table 4.8.3). Here we report the biological indices most commonly used to assess or monitor soil health and discuss some of the broader issues associated with their use. We will also provide recommendations to more effectively guide and improve how biological information could be used to yield relevant and actionable assessments of soil health.

Figure 4.8. 2 Indicators and methodologies for soil biodiversity monitoring

Table 4.8. 3 Common methods for measuring soil biodiversity and activity of soil organisms. Note that these methods mainly describe how to sample and extract soil organisms before identification for characterizing diversity.

	Indicator	Group	Standard
Soil fauna	Diversity	Earthworms (sampling and extraction)	EN ISO 23 611-1
		Mesofauna (collembola and acari) (sampling and extraction)	EN ISO 23 611-2
		Enchytreides (sampling and extraction)	EN ISO 23 611-3
		Nematodes (sampling and extraction)	EN ISO 23 611-4
		Macrofauna total (sampling and extraction)	EN ISO 23 611-5
		eDNA	No standard
	Activity	Bait lamina	ISO 18 311
Cast counting		No standard	
Soil micro-organisms	Biomass	Substrate-induced Fumigation-extraction	ISO 14 240-1 / -2
		Molecular biomass (bacteria and/or fungi) based on DNA extraction	EN ISO 11 063
	Diversity	Quantitative PCR (abundance of gene sequences)	ISO 17 601
		Phospho-Lipid Fatty acids	XP CEN ISO/TS 29 843-1 /-2
		Massive sequencing	No standard
	Activity	Respiration	EN ISO 16 072
		Enzymatic measurements	ISO 14 238 ISO/TS 22 939 ISO 23 753-1 ISO 23 753-2

Molecular and “omics” approaches

Apart from microbes, most of the identification methods of the “taxonomic” groups are based on morphological criteria or metabarcoding. The determination is based on keys, whose precision depends on the level of classification (orders or species) and taxon. Consequently, determining all species present is largely time-consuming and knowledge-intensive. Thus, such protocols have recently undergone changes based on DNA/RNA-based as well as other high-throughput techniques that should speed up our knowledge of soil biodiversity and the complex relationships between these organisms. Such advances in the so-called ‘omics’ technologies (i.e. genomics, transcriptomics, metabolomics, etc.) represents a new opportunity to establish the linkage between structure and function of soil microbial community and helped to get a better insight into the ecological processes in the environment, with special emphasis on plant–microbe ecosystems (Biswas & Sarkar, 2018; Bouchez et al. 2016). In fact, given their well-established importance to many aspects of soil health, microbes and microbial-driven processes are often used as metrics of soil health with a range of different microbe-

based metrics routinely used across the globe (Fierer, 2021). Actually, as in clinical settings metagenomic biomarkers have been proposed as potential biomarkers for various disease states (Segata et al. 2011), in agriculture several features of microbial communities can be used as biomarkers of soil fertility and crop productivity.

More recently, environmental DNA (eDNA) has received increased attention as an indirect marker for biodiversity monitoring. The eDNA metabarcoding (simultaneous detection of multiple species) is a noninvasive and cost-effective approach largely based on the use of DNA fragments that are shorter than in the case of DNA barcoding (mini-barcodes). Coupled with the use of DNA barcode reference libraries, this approach makes it possible to obtain the identity of all the species present in the samples and thus to envisage very comprehensive studies of biodiversity on an ecosystem scale (Hajibabaei, 2012). These recent technical advances in sequencing now allow the use of sequences obtained from total DNA in environmental samples, such as soil or water samples, or a set of unsorted invertebrates obtained in a trap (Hajibabaei, 2012; Taberlet et al., 2012). This technique makes it possible to identify all the phyla, classes and orders present or having left genetic 'traces' from an environmental sample (soil, water or unsorted invertebrates). Although restricted to the identification of soil organisms that are alive or have recently entered the decomposition stage at the time of sampling, environmental sequencing of intracellular DNA allows identification at the specific level, enabling a detailed characterization of soil invertebrate communities. One of the first uses of this approach is to compare communities in different habitats. Unfortunately, it is our opinion that many of these measurements are not easy to interpret and may not always necessarily provide credible inferences about soil health status. In fact, such omics technologies are currently susceptible to limitations and biases that are common to all molecular techniques and cannot replace the traditional approaches adopted in soil science, but have to be integrated alongside more holistically, to provide valuable results, especially when linking taxonomic and functional diversity (Mocali & Benedetti, 2010; Myrold and Nannipieri, 2014). Moreover, the focus on particular taxa and components of soil communities fails to capture the complexity of biodiversity responses to land-use because they act simultaneously (Le Provost et al., 2021). Even a simple comparison of all identified ASVs (OTUs) together using the sample's distance matrices, phylogenetic trees or rarefaction curves enables revealing a broader view on communities. For example, the Earth Microbiome Project (EMP) (<https://earthmicrobiome.org/>) is a massive global-scale initiative aiming at characterizing microbial life on earth. A combination of DNA sequencing and mass spectrometry of crowd-sourced samples was successfully used to understand patterns in microbial ecology across the biomes and habitats of our planet (Thompson et al., 2017). Similarly, networks of LC-MS/MS features, FTIR or Raman spectra profiles can be created to identify dominating compounds of soils and their changes due to impacts. More advanced bioinformatics offers possibilities such as network of taxonomic co-occurrence patterns or measurements of general soil functioning such as resilience, which disposes of the potential to recover functional and structural integrity after a disturbance (Ludwig et al. 2018).

4.8.2 Soil biodiversity measurement and monitoring with PS/RS techniques

No straightforward proximal and remote sensing methods are currently being introduced for estimating taxonomic soil biodiversity. Those include even techniques for estimating soil properties related to soil biodiversity, such as for example organic matter and soil texture (see previous chapters).

However, at present, that would need to rely on secondary correlation relationships with imprecise generalization, thus not recommended.

The use of proximal sensors (mainly soil spectroscopy in the near and mid infrared wavelength regions) in connection to soil biodiversity is related to different aspects of soil organic matter quality, microbial biomass, fungal biomass, soil respiration, enzyme activities and N mineralization (e.g. Stenberg et al., 2010; Rasche et al., 2013; Knox et al., 2015; Hutengs et al., 2021; Wetterlind et al., 2022). One of the advantages of soil spectroscopy is the combined information on both the organic and mineral part of the soil. The success in estimating microbial properties or functions is often dependent on the variation in them being related to soil physicochemical properties (Hutengs et al., 2021). These relationships are also often local, and it is difficult and unreliable to transfer one model to a different site (Stenberg et al., 2010).

4.8.3 Existing thresholds and target values for soil biodiversity

With policies being established worldwide to promote sustainable land use and ecosystem health, there is an urgent need for the rapid development of not only targets but also thresholds to assess soil health. However, defining robust targets and thresholds is not a trivial task, as they should account for soil, climate, land-use, management, and history, among others. Faber et al. (2022) conducted a review of existing targets and thresholds for soils used in EU countries, which showed that except for nutrients (e.g., nitrogen, phosphorus) and contamination (e.g., trace elements), such values are not currently widely used or actively developed.

A recent European Environmental Agency (EEA) report (EEA 2023) provides an overview of the challenges in setting targets and thresholds, noting that these are highly site-, management- and climate-specific, and that careful validation in each resulting category would be critical to fully support any given target or threshold system. In the approach proposed by Römcke et al., (2016), thresholds are based on species richness, but other biological endpoints or indices are possible. In fact, in some cases, species determination is reserved only for specialists and may not be suitable for monitoring plans on regional or national territory. From a biological point of view, the limit of unacceptable degradation is not easy to determine, especially when looking at whole communities rather than one species. Figure 4.8.3 indicates the general relationship between soil biological condition (e.g. species richness) and the change in the diversity of soil organism groups at various levels of stress, ranging from an unaffected (reference) site to a site that has been severely affected by (often anthropogenic) stress. The red column indicates the point of unacceptable depletion (Römcke et al., 2016).

Figure 4.8. 3 Baseline and threshold approach for soil biodiversity monitoring (from Rombke et al., 2016)

Setting such values requires collecting biological data across different soil types, land uses, climate areas as it was done for chemical parameters. This step is needed to be able to define normal ranges for groups of organisms. ISO 23 611-1 in its Annex E presents existing data from soil monitoring programmes in EU and suggests for earthworms, depending on soil type (sandy, loamy, clayed) and 2 land uses (cropland and grassland) mean abundances and species numbers for earthworms across 3 countries (table 4.8.4). For those countries, such values may be considered as normal or expected ones for earthworms. For bacteria, Horrigue et al. (2016) developed a model to predict the biomass of the soil microbial community according to the soil physicochemical properties by combining the dataset of soil molecular microbial biomass with pedoclimatic properties derived from the soil samples from the “French monitoring soil quality network”. Such model provides a reference value for microbial biomass for a given pedoclimatic condition, which can then be compared with the corresponding measured data to provide a robust diagnosis at least over the French nation. The collection of existing data should now be a goal to develop threshold or target values for several groups as developed in EJP SOIL Minotaur project.

Table 4.8. 4 Comparison of mean values for earthworm abundance (Ind/m²) (left half of the table) and species number (right half of the table) for four habitat types in the Netherlands (RIVM) and Germany (UBA) and France (RMQS/INRA/University of Rennes) (extracted from ISO 23611-1, 2018).

Habitat classes	Dutch Reference	German Reference	French Reference	Dutch Reference	German Reference	French Reference
	Ind/m ²	Ind/m ²	Ind/m ²	Ind/m ²	Ind/m ²	Ind/m ²
	Mean abundance			Mean species number		
	Ind/m ²					
Crop sites on clayey soils	200	102	259	4,2	4,4	3,2
Crop sites on loamy/silt soils	—	—	224	—	—	3,2
Crop sites on sandy soil	77	32	88	2,8	3,3	3,6
Grassland on clayey soils	793	42	418	8,3	9,1	8,0
Grassland on loamy/silt soils	—	—	383	—	—	8,7
Grassland on sandy soils	64	104	595	4,8	5,1	8,5

In this regard, different target and threshold-setting methodologies, evaluating their advantages and disadvantages through stakeholder perception and three specific case studies, presented a flexible framework for the selection of soil health indicator targets and thresholds as proposed by Matson et al. (2023, submitted). More specifically, four approaches to setting targets and thresholds are introduced and discussed (through theory and stakeholder feedback): a **target** is defined as a value desirable to reach (i.e., a known maximum or achievable value), while a **critical threshold** is the 'minimum criteria,' a value above/below which soils are targeted as needing intervention, without implying that soils that meet these criteria are in a good state. Between these two, there can be **benchmarks**, which identify distinct stages or categories of soil health. Note that, while not specifically addressed in this paper, a **range** (i.e., defined upper and lower values) can also be used as a broad target, or as a set of critical thresholds. Three approaches (not including relative change) are then illustrated using case study examples from Denmark, Italy, and France, which highlight key strengths and weaknesses of each approach. Finally, a framework is presented that facilitates both choosing the most appropriate target/threshold method for a given context and using targets/thresholds to trigger follow-up actions to promote soil health.

4.8.4 Soil biodiversity modelling

Modelling soil biodiversity can be a hard task to achieve due to the vast quantity of organisms that such a concept encompasses. In fact, the vast majority of soil-dwelling species remain to be characterized, and this taxonomic deficit is likely greater than 90% (Decaëns, 2010; Crowther et al., 2019). However, the perspective of soil biodiversity models is to overcome local-scale diversity and focus on broader organism groups that characterize community-level functioning providing a simplified perspective (Crowther et al., 2019). Objects of modelling are often descriptors of the soil communities (i.e., alpha, beta, gamma diversity, biomass, number of taxa, etc.), sets of organisms (i.e., species, groups of species, trophic guilds, functional groups and traits, etc.), and functions associated to soil biodiversity (i.e., C/N mineralization, cycling of nutrients, biopores, etc.), but very few approaches allow to put together all the factors, and when possible, the process needs lots of efforts. Another frequent question that appears before the modelling is what properties of these abovementioned variables are being estimated (i.e., spatiotemporal dynamics, occurrence, extinctions, invasions, etc.). In addition, the outcome of the model will depend on available data and how data has been collected, what decisions have been made during the modelling (e.g., aggregation of data, data itself, conversion factors employed, etc.) so that the outcome strongly depends on the modeler, and finally, on the current scientific background.

Nevertheless, different studies have modelled and subsequently mapped the distribution, abundance and even biomass of soil communities across the world, EU or countries. Quite all groups were modelled, such as bacteria (Horrigue et al., 2016; Terrat et al., 2017; Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2018, Karimi et al., 2018), fungi (Tederesso et al., 2014), nematodes (van den Hoogen, 2019), arthropods (Guo et al., 2020), earthworms (Phillips et al., 2019, Rutgers et al., 2016) and even overall soil biodiversity (Aksoy et al., 2017, Rutgers et al., 2019). The process is the same for each study: a model is built using existing diversity and/or abundance and/or biomass data together with driving factors collected at the sampled site as soil characteristics (e.g. pH, organic matter, texture, soil type) and other information (e.g. dates of sampling, climate variables as mean annual temperature or precipitations, altitude, land use, land management). The resulting model is then able to predict the diversity and/or abundance of the soil organisms from other attributes. Depending on the scale and the modelled group, important

drivers to be included in the model may change: for example, at global scale Phillips et al. (2019) found climate to be more relevant than soil characteristics but within climatic regions (or at the local scale), other variables may become more important. Moreover, Horrigue et al. (2016) found that soil organic carbon content, clay content, altitude, and pH were the best explanatory variables of soil microbial biomass while other variables such as longitude, latitude and annual temperature were negligible. Depending on the covariates included in the models they may be used to understand and forecast evolutions of soil communities in a changing world (e.g. climate change, land use change, contamination) (van den Hoogen, 2019) or to provide reference values for a given pedoclimatic condition, which can then be compared with the corresponding measured data to provide a robust diagnosis of soil quality (Horrigue et al., 2016).

All authors call attention to the uncertainties of the models linked to a lack of soil biodiversity data (compared to physico-chemical analyses) and differences in data quality (e.g. sampling methods, metadata description). Improving such models will require gathering and sharing existing data across (currently done within EJP SOIL MINOTAUR project) and much more important collecting new data through national, EU or global monitoring networks (if possible, by using standardized or harmonised protocols, reporting and data formats).

4.8.5 Effect of scale (time/space) on the measurement of soil biodiversity

Different factors seem to determine biodiversity and soil processes at different scales. Out of those most important in (micro)organism distributions, both soil moisture and pH seem to act at a broad range of scale from continents to meters (e.g. Fierer and Jackson, 2006; Rousk et al. 2010, Sagova-Mareckova et al. 2011). While distance-decay patterns represent a typical large-scale factor (Ranjard et al., 2013), at millimeter scale resources and redox conditions seem to be most important (Samoilova et al., 2023) but also biotic interactions in the form of competition, facilitation and predation, which are likely to feed back to larger scale of both below and aboveground biodiversity (Le Provost et al., 2021). These are however related to soil connectedness through water pathways (Thakur et al., 2019), so micro-geographic considerations of difficult-to observe microbial processes can improve the interpretation of data from bulk soil samples (Bickel and Or, 2023).

For example, Ponge (2003) identified as one key-factor the humus type, being the mull one typical of productive ecosystems, with a high level of heterogeneity and biological activities, and the Mor one associated to less fertile soils, characterized by reduced biodiversity and slow process-rates. Going to local-scale patterns of soil biodiversity, living organisms body dimensions range from centimetres to metres, related to habitat heterogeneity, in terms of structural complexity of the soil environment and chemical complexity of nutrient resources (Ponge, 2003). These factors can affect the ability of living organisms to establish ecological niches and coexist, thus determining an extreme spatial variation in community-level biological properties of the soil (Ritz et al., 2004).

The small scale of soil distribution represents the extreme in terms of spatio-temporal organization due to both its abiotic, three-dimensional structure of fine gradients and biotic, organisms of different size occurring next to each other, composition. Yet similarly to large scale, even at small scale, soil organisms defy the measurable patterns of abiotic factors, but rather occur at their living scale of factor gradients with unpredictable distribution (Geisen et al. 2019). In addition, vertical structure of soil, abiotic but even more biotic, is often neglected despite its great functional impact (Lehmann and Kleber, 2015). Soil biodiversity studies are usually conducted at ranges of 10 cm to global, whereas the

sampling unit varies from millimeters to meters. Most studies, however, use a spatial range of 1–10 cm following the standard protocols for sampling of both soil organisms and chemical traits rather than their “real” distribution or distribution of influencing factors including time scales (Thakur et al. 2020). Above that the common practice of homogenization ensures greater statistical power for larger scales but leaves questions regarding the ecological relevance of observed community dynamics and function as it irreversibly alters in situ microbial distributions and spatial-functional relationships between them (Smercina et al. 2021). If a scale of microbial habitat size in a typical soil sample (e.g. a soil core) is considered, we can see the challenge in relating microscale to macroscale because at 10 cm² surface soil sample may be anywhere from 56 million to 1 billion distinct microhabitats in which microbial function is carried out in response to specific conditions. Thus, not only microbial biodiversity but also quantification of soil processes from a microbial perspective will allow us to more accurately predict soil functions (Smercina et al. 2021) and elucidating typical ranges of bacterial interactions at the cell or colony scales, as shaped by their physical environment, can benefit the interpretation of measurements made at coarser scales (bulk samples or soil profiles) and provide mechanistic insights into the soil microbiome in different biomes.

Recently, hierarchical approaches to studies of soil organisms distinguishing micro (sub-millimeter) from meso and macro (> cm) habitats were recommended to provide data needed to accurately predict interactions that drive soil biodiversity and biogeochemical cycles (Smercina et al. 2021). Therefore, a soil health survey should consider the continuum between all the different soil-dwelling scales, not excluding any of them, and eventually assess possible interactions between them.

Since soil microbial diversity also affects plant-soil interactions by controlling nutrient availability for plants (Weidner et al., 2015), ecosystem functions such as productivity and decomposition (van der Heijden and Wagg, 2013), N-cycle (Nardi et al., 2021; Wagg et al. 2021) and SOC stabilization and accrual (Manici et al., 2019), the **temporal variability** should be also considered when evaluating soil biodiversity. Soil samples may be collected more than one time during the cropping cycle, for example at maximum and at minimum plant nutrient demand (Fontaine et al., 2023). Some authors showed that temporal variability needs to be carefully assessed when comparing microbial diversity across soil types and the temporal patterns in microbial community structure can not necessarily be generalized across land uses, even if those soils are exposed to the same climatic conditions (Lauber et al., 2013).

Currently, it is not yet possible to fully understand the mechanisms involved in the spatial structuring of soil microbial communities, since spatial models capable of describing and explaining their biodiversity are not even available. More recently, some advances have been made through network analysis, capable of determining coexistence patterns in soil microbial communities, and the application of new theories to the stability of food webs in soil. However, it is still very difficult to reconstruct the trophic and functional relationships between the different organisms living in the soil, both due to the structural and chemical complexity of the soil, and due to the impossibility of associating one or more specific functions to each microbial group or species.

When defining a **sampling plan** for evaluating the soil biodiversity in agricultural soils, the high level of spatial variability of bacteria, archaea, fungi and other organisms justifies the need to collect high number of soil samples based on transects, quadrats or pentagonal schemes. Thus, the sampling should take into consideration:

- the objective of the study (effect of soil disturbance, fertilization, crop rotation, introduction of service crops, etc.);

- the soil structural and chemical variability (texture, bulk density, pH, SOC, etc.), using an adequate soil physico-chemical property mapping;
- climatic conditions as dry and cold seasons are not appropriate to sample active organisms

4.8.6 Decline of soil biodiversity

The soil biodiversity decline is defined as “the reduction of living organisms in soils, in terms of quantity and variety” (Tibbett et al., 2020). Where it occurs, soil biodiversity decline may strongly affect soil functionality, by altering biogeochemical cycles and reducing its resilience to perturbations. Such perturbations generate compositional and functional shifts of plant soil fauna and microbial community (Ossowicki et al., 2021).

Despite the important and multifunctional role of soil biodiversity assemblages, thanks to their abiotic and biotic as well as functional interactions, soil organisms face many of the same threats as aboveground organisms but receive far less research, media attention, and legal protection (Bach et al. 2020).

Orgiazzi et al. (2016) developed a process to map threats to soil biodiversity. The main pressures influencing soil biodiversity (e.g. climate change, pollution, soil sealing, land use change, erosion, compaction, intensive human exploitation) were identified and ranked for soil organisms through an expert consultation. Indices for potential risks for microorganisms, fauna and soil functions were derived from the consultation and mapped for EU. This work allows to identify and circumscribe soils potentially at risk and call attention to soil biodiversity but didn't model nor map soil organisms. They found that soil biodiversity is under a moderate-high to high potential risk in 40% of 14 Member States (MS) (EU + UK). In particular, as agricultural practices represent the main threat and 43% of land in the EU is used for agriculture (Eurostat, 2020) the issue of using practices that better counteract the biodiversity loss is very urgent (Köninger et al. 2022). Those include: (a) reduction of pollutants such as pesticides, heavy metals and mineral fertilizers, (b) prevention of soil compaction by avoiding the use of heavy machinery, (c) increasing permanent soil cover through intercropping, mulching, catch crops and non-till/conservation tillage, (d) plan landscape management through hedgerows, grass borders, agro-forestry to improve wildlife reservoirs, name old trees and old growth forest in field's vicinity (Le Provost et al. 2021) (e) use of high quality organic amendments as soil improvers and microbiome-based solutions (Marsden et al., 2020, Köninger et al., 2021, Tabacchioni et al. 2021).

One of the most challenging tasks is to **identify sensitive indicators able to measure the soil biodiversity decline**: this unavoidably requires defining not only the density, but also the hierarchical organization of the soil community, and the ecosystem services supplied by the different group of living organisms involved in the soil food web, by monitoring them at multiple levels of organization (organism, population, community, ecosystem) and at multiple spatial scales, from plot to farm to landscape (Bispo et al., 2009; Pulleman et al., 2012). Referring to C and N cycling processes, they need a certain level of biodiversity, such as a minimum number of specific feeding groups (such as microbes and invertebrates), total biomass of the soil food web, and biomass of the fungal, bacterial, and root energy channel, as reported in Table 4.8.5 (De Vries et al., 2013).

A first indicator of soil biodiversity decline can therefore be associated with the drastic decrease in density of one or more functional groups listed above over time, up to values lower than the minimum reference values. However, the quantification of the density of the different functional groups is only one of the possible indicators of biodiversity decline in the soil: just in 2010, the ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF SOIL FOR MONITORING (ENVASSO) project (European Commission 6th Framework Programme: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/envasso>) defined a set of priority level of indicators of soil functional diversity decline, referred to the main groups of the soil food web: i) abundance, biomass and species diversity of earthworms for macrofauna; ii) abundance and species diversity of *Collembola* for mesofauna; iii) microbial respiration. This set of indicators refer not only to their biodiversity at species level, but also to their ecological functions (Table 4.8.5).

Table 4.8. 5 List of soil taxonomical groups involved in the soil food web, their functions and density in soil (as reference values) (adapted from Baritz et al., EEA ETC/ULS Report, 2021).

Taxonomical group	Main function	Density in soil (reference values)
Earthworms	Soil engineers: consume plant residues and soil	$\leq 1000 \times \text{m}^2$
Enchytraeids	Soil engineers (much smaller than earthworms): consume plant residues	$10^2 \div 10^6 \times \text{m}^2$
Mites	Soil regulators: predators/omnivores (consume fungi, bacteria)	$10^4 \div 10^5 \times \text{m}^2$
Springtails or Collembola	Soil regulators: omnivores (consume fungi), detritivores (involved in litter decomposition, nutrient cycling, and plant growth)	$10^3 \div 10^5 \times \text{m}^2$
Nematodes	Soil regulators: predators/omnivores (consume fungi, bacteria, plants)	$10 \div 50 \times \text{g}_{\text{soil}}$
Protists	Soil regulators: (consume fungi, bacteria, plants)	$10^6 \text{ cells} \times \text{g}_{\text{soil}}$ 10 kg C ha^{-1}
Bacteria, Archaea	Chemical engineers: involved in biogeochemical cycles, in symbiosis	$10^9 \text{ cells} \times \text{g}_{\text{soil}}$ $50 \div 500 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1}$
Fungi	Chemical engineers: involved in biogeochemical cycles, in symbiosis	$1 \div 500 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1}$

Earthworms, the “soil engineers’ able to positively influence its properties, are strongly affected by soil disturbance, such as soil compaction, pesticide use, etc. *Collembola*, as major detritivore mesofauna in soil, significantly affect litter decomposition, nutrient cycling, and plant growth. Unexpectedly, it was found that their abundance increased in tilled soils, although the *Collembola* community composition changes with time: the decomposing litter material favors similar *Collembola* species, irrespective of tillage treatments (Hanisch et al., 2022). Regarding the nematode assemblages, by comparing organic vs conventionally managed soils, and no-tilled vs tilled soils, they appeared as reliable predictors of the trophic composition of functional characteristics of soil mite assemblages. It was verified that nematode-based soil food web indices are useful indicators of mites also, having similar functional roles and environmental sensitivities (Sánchez-Moreno et al., 2009).

The main drivers impacting on soil biodiversity are well summarized in the meta-analysis published by Christel et al., in 2021. Overall, organic fertilization and longer crop rotations are the most favorable practices, whereas pesticides and soil tillage are the most deleterious ones. The review also evidences a lack of studies on soil conservation farming and on bioindicators of the soil fauna.

In a long-term legume-durum wheat crop rotation of the North-Mediterranean Region, the European H2020 Diverfarming project (<http://www.diverfarming.eu/index.php/it/>) verified that continuous tillage at 30 cm depth impacted soil fungal communities, highlighting a higher diversity of saprotrophic fungi in soils with low disturbance and an inverse correlation between the biodiversity of

ectomycorrhizal and saprotrophic fungi (Orrù et al., 2021). A higher spatial variability was observed in no-tilled soils compared to tilled ones, with fungal taxa distributed according to a small-scale pattern, corresponding to micro-niches that, probably, remained undisturbed and heterogeneously distributed. Some fungal species emerged as potential indicator of soil management or of physical-impacting conditions: *Minimedusa polyspora*, overrepresented in the tilled soils, and the yeast *Saitozyma podzolica*, one of the top indicator species of the non-rotated, monocrop soil (Wang et al., 2020).

Results from CoreOrganic – Cofund SureVeg project, where organic intercropped horticultural systems were compared to monocropped ones in different European pedoclimatic Regions (<https://projects.au.dk/coreorganiccofund/core-organic-cofund-projects/sureveg>) showed that monocrop significantly decreases the soil microbial C (C_{mic}) at the end of the cropping cycle, a prompt indicator of the negative impact of reduced plant diversity on microbial population growth and soil C persistence (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2018). Bacterial and fungi α -diversity (e.g., Shannon and Simpson diversity indexes) was not affected by compared cropping systems, although a decrease of *Bacteroidetes* and an increase of *Mortierellomycota* relative abundances were observed under monocropping (Trinchera et al., 2022).

The above-mentioned indicators of soil biodiversity, when referred to a given agro-system, may inform on soil biodiversity decline, as affected by soil physical, chemical, and/or biological disturbance. However, a multi-functional approach is recommended to disclose the relationship between the fluctuation of functional groups abundance in soil and the derived impact on ecosystem services (Labouyrie et al., 2023). For example, the AGROECOseqC project (EJPSOIL – 2nd Internal call- CM5) is based on application of the multifunctional approach to disclose the role played by soil functional biodiversity on ecosystem services, such as SOC sequestration and nutrient balance. The relevance of the project lies in the possibility of building a complete dataset of chemical, physical, biochemical, and biological indicators of soil health, collected in different EU production systems in eight European pedoclimatic regions.

4.8.7 Recommendations for monitoring soil biodiversity changes

The Mission Soil Deal for Europe defined “Soil Health” as “*the continued capacity of soils to support ecosystem services*”. Soil biodiversity supports most of those services, but degradation processes that change the inherent physical, chemical and biological characteristics of soil can inhibit this capacity. Unfortunately, soil monitoring is not undertaken in a systematic, harmonised way (Bispo et al., 2021).

Although a large number of biological indicators has been proposed over the years for assessing soil health (Bünemann et al., 2018; Faber et al., 2013; Pulleman et al., 2012; Cluzeau et al., 2012; Bispo et al., 2009), only few have been applied in monitoring schemes across Europe and no consensus exists on the extent to which these indicators might perform best and how monitoring schemes can be further optimized in terms of policy relevance and scientific robustness. However, in the last two decades several projects evaluated many possible suitable indicators, in terms of policy-relevancy, cost-efficiency, scientific robustness, ease of application, level of standardization, etc. and we **conclude that sufficient methodology and experience is now available to start EU implementation of a first set of biological indicators to monitor soil biodiversity and soil health.**

It is important to state that the huge amount of biodiversity hidden belowground (almost 60% of the species on Earth), the complexity of the interactions occurring among organisms and the soil chemical-physical environment, as well as their spatial-temporal variability cannot be simplified and comprehensively described by just one or few selected indicators. Actually, whereas the definition of a “minimum set” of indicators for the assessment of soil health should be desirable, a more flexible and tailored approach may better address the soil functions and ecosystem services in a specific context scenario. Thus, in order to select appropriate indicators and to combine practicability and flexibility of the monitoring initiatives, a two “**tiered system**” approach is here proposed (following the recommendations of ENVASSO, EcoFINDERS, SIREN and MINOTAUR projects), meaning that **a first set of indicators is highly recommended in all cases** (Tier I group) (table 4.8.6) and, depending on availability of resources and specific requirements, can be extended to include tiers II for additional analysis. All the indicators of the Tier I group should be standardized, scientifically proven and cost-effective. Moreover, they should be applied together, as the measurements made by only one or two of them may be difficult to interpret in terms of “soil health status”.

On the other hand, many other optional indicators may be selected and included in a Tier II group (not reported here) depending on the purpose (aim and conditions) of a specific monitoring program. Both functional and structural bioindicators should be combined for better planning solutions and restoring actions under degradation threats.

Concerning sampling periods, spring and autumn are generally optimal seasons as soil organisms are active (winter and summer should be avoided). Th sampling should be avoided just after any treatment (e.g. tillage, fertilizer or amendment incorporation, pesticide application) as it may stringly influence the results. The top soil and subsoil should be considered as some organisms live in deeper horizons. Finally, concerning the frequency of sampling, from a scienfitical point of view as soil biodiversity may vary quickly depending on climate and management ideally several measurements per year should be performed but from a practical point of view it is recommended to sample for soil biodiversity at each monitoring campaigns.

A **holistic-based integration** of multiple soil health indicators (biological, chemical, physical, ecological, etc.) is also highly recommended. In fact, soil health should be monitored not only with chemical-physical proxy indices, but also with biological and ecological indicators directly related to soil biodiversity and the provision of ecosystem services. Moreover, biological indicators should be contextualized with soil chemical-physical data in a specific scenario (soil type, climate, land use and management). The application of just one indicator such as the soil basal respiration (as reported in the Annex I of the Soil Health Law proposal COM(2023)416, launched on 05-07-2023) does not provide any information related to soil biodiversity loss or to the soil health status but just a general value of the biological activity, thus providing an information difficult to interpret, in particular if not properly related to soil organic carbon and microbial biomass content (Kandeler et al, 2005).

Table 4.8. 6 Tier I group of recommended indicators with a brief description and available standard methods.

Priority level	Recommended indicators	Brief description	Methodology	Cost efficiency	Sensitivity to degradation processes	
Tier I	Functional Indicators	Microbial biomass C	Amount of microbial biomass per gram soil	ISO 14240-1:1997 ISO 14240-2:1997	Easy and cheap	1. Declining of SOC 2. Desertification 3. Erosion 4. Soil sealing and urbanization 5. Pollution and salinization 6. Compaction
		Microbial respiration	Production of CO ₂ per amount of soil	ISO 16072:2002	Easy and cheap	
		Enzyme activity	Measurement of several hydrolase activities in soil	ISO 20130:2018 ISO/TS 22939:2019	Easy and cheap	
	Structural indicators	Macrofauna diversity (Earthworms)	Structural and functional diversity	ISO 23611-1:2018	Easy and cheap	
		Mesofauna diversity	Structural and functional diversity	ISO 23611-2:2006 QBS-ar (Parisi et al., 2005)	Easy and cheap	
		Nematodes diversity	Structural and functional diversity	ISO 23611-4:2006	Easy and cheap	
		Microbiota diversity (bacteria and fungi)	Structural diversity of soil microbiota	DNA metabarcoding (ISO 11063:2020) and Plassart et al., 2012	Costs are reducing, tends to become easy and cheap	

In conclusion, we could provide the following take-home messages:

- A two “tiered system” approach is here proposed: (1) Tier I group, including a first set of indicators highly recommended in all cases (table 4.8.6); (2) Tier II group, including many other additional available indicators that may be selected and included, depending on the purpose (aim and conditions) of a specific monitoring program (not reported here).
- The application of “soil respiration” as unique indicator (as reported in the Annex I of the Soil Health Law proposal COM(2023)416, launched on 05-07-2023) does not provide any information related to soil biodiversity loss or to the soil health status but just a general value of the biological activity, thus providing an information difficult to interpret. Therefore, we recommend using all the indicators of the Tier I group together (table 4.8.6).
- Selected biological indicators should be standardized, scientifically proven, suitable for monitoring campaigns and cost-effective
- Both functional and structural bioindicators are recommended for better planning solutions and restoring actions under degradation threats
- Biological indicators should be contextualized with soil chemical-physical data in a specific scenario (soil type, climate, land use and management).
- Ecological indicators and indices (e.g., richness, evenness, indices related to trophic levels or soil adaptation) should be also considered to reduce the bias due to the high variability of abundance data and the aggregated distribution of life in soil.
- A holistic-based integration of multiple soil health indicators (biological, chemical, physical, ecological, etc.) is recommended.

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4.9 Soil structure

Soil structure (including compaction)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Marine Lacoste, Sevinc Madenoglu, Virginijus Feiza, Žydrė Kadziuliene, Dalia Feizienė, Joost Salomez, ○ Relevant EJP SOIL projects: Steropes, SoilCompac
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4.9.1 Monitoring and measurement of soil structure

Soil structure is defined here as the spatial heterogeneity of the different components or properties of soil (Dexter, 1988), i.e. as the spatial arrangement of solids and voids across different scales without considering the chemical heterogeneity of soil solids (Rabot et al., 2018). Soil structure controls many processes in soils as it regulates water retention and infiltration, gas exchanges, soil organic matter and nutrients dynamics, root penetration and soil susceptibility to erosion. Soil structure is thus known to impacts soil functions such as biomass production, storage and filtering of water, storage and recycling of nutrients, carbon storage, habitat for biological activity, physical stability, and support (Rabot et al., 2018). However, there is no universally accepted way to characterize soil structure (Díaz-Zorita et al., 2002), and a wide number of methods to characterize the soil structural properties are currently used by soil scientists and farmers, from quick field observations to thorough laboratory characterizations, allowing the characterization of soil structure in a large range of spatial scale, from nm to dm (Rabot et al., 2018). Associated to these methods, many indicators are estimated to describe soil structure, some are very common and widely used, such as the soil bulk density, others are in continuous development (e.g. the relative entropy proposed by Kloffel et al. (2022)). These methods can be classified in two main groups: (i) the methods allowing the characterization of the solid phase arrangement, focusing on the composition and the stability of aggregates, and (ii) the methods that allow characterizing the pore space, focusing on the pore structure and the pore-solid interfaces of undisturbed soil samples (Schlüter et al., 2020; Vogel et al., 2022). In the studies relying on the “pore space” approach, the term of “structure” can sometimes be replaced by the term “architecture” to underline the relation between the three-dimensional arrangement of the soil physical component and the related soil functions (Baveye et al., 2018; Lin, 2012 ; Young et al., 2001).

From the solid phase or the “aggregates approach”, the soil structure is considered as the result of mechanisms of soil aggregation leading to a three-size hierarchical organization of the soil solids: primary particles (< 20 µm), microaggregates (20–250 µm) and macroaggregates (> 250 µm). Processes of soil aggregate formation and stabilization involve organic matter content (Christensen, 2001), soil texture (Krause et al., 2018), soil biota activities (Wiesmeier et al., 2019) and soil management. Field and laboratory methods are available to characterize the solid phase arrangement.

Field methods allow the evaluation of the macrostructure (i.e. visible to the naked eye) and can be divided in two groups: the whole profile evaluation, developed from the fundamental methods of field surveys, and the topsoil evaluation, a simplified version requiring less experience and time. The whole profile evaluation method is described in the FAO (2006) guidelines and in most of the national standards (e.g., Ad-hoc-Arbeitsgruppe Boden, 2005 in Germany; Baize and Jabiol, 2011 in France; Schoeneberger et al., 2012 in the USA): soil structure morphology and its variation with depth are evaluated visually as part of the soil profile description. The description of soil structure is mainly related to its grade, and the size and shape of aggregates. Three types of aggregates are distinguished: peds (aggregates formed by natural processes), fragments (small aggregates formed artificially during field manipulations) and clods (aggregates formed artificially by cultivation operations). Description of

the grade is realized by observing whether soil material breaks into fragments or “powder” when disturbed, and to what extent the surface of aggregates differs from their inner part (FAO, 2006). The aggregates can have different shapes and based on this the soil structure can be defined as angular blocky, subangular blocky, granular, platy, prismatic, or columnar. In structureless soils (apedal soils), no aggregates are observed, and the material is either compact or built up by single grains. Other approaches also distinguish soil clods based on a visual inspection of their internal structural porosity (Boizard et al., 2017; Roger-Estrade et al., 2004). Soil structure description in the field depends on soil moisture, especially in swell-shrinking soils, and the FAO (2006) guidelines recommend performing this description when the soil is dry or slightly moist. The whole profile evaluations provide valuable information on the vertical sequence of soil structural properties. However, they are subjective, and since they require the digging of pits, they are also time consuming, and sufficient replication cannot always be done (Mueller et al., 2009).

Methods for topsoil evaluation of soil structure are developed to estimate soil quality and are highly relevant for farmers or land managers, who wish to evaluate the soil quality and their management practices, easily, quickly, and cheaply. Several methods of Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VSS) have been developed, among which the Peerlkamp score (Peerlkamp, 1959) and its more recent VSS adaptations by Ball et al. (2007) and Guimarães et al. (2011) - also been declined for subsoils (Ball et al., 2015), or the Visual Soil Assessment (VSA; Shepherd, 2009). They all include i) recognition and description of soil aggregates (size, shape), porosity and rooting features, visible to the naked eye, ii) evaluation and classification, of visual soil structure, and sometimes iii) conclusions on the functional status of soil. For example, the soil quality scores obtained using the method from Ball et al. (2007) have been correlated with different measured physical qualities including tensile strength, bulk density, resistance to penetration, least limiting water range, hydraulic properties and air permeability (Guimarães et al., 2011, 2013; Giarola et al., 2013; Pulido-Moncada et al., 2014a, 2014b), demonstrating its reliability for assessing soil structural quality. VSS methods also demonstrated a good sensitivity to different management practices and are particularly useful to detect compacted soil layers (Guimarães et al. 2013; Emmet-Booth et al, 2020). An exhaustive comparison of the VSS methods can be found in Boizard et al. (2006) or Emmet-Booth et al. (2016). Some of the main advantages of these methods are speed and minor soil disturbance. However, the description of soil structure in the field highly depends on soil moisture and the scoring frame has potential for subjective errors (Mueller et al., 2009).

Two types of methods are used to characterize the solid phase arrangement: i) the methods based on the soil bulk density measurement and ii) those dealing with aggregate size distribution and stability. One of the most prominent indicators of soil structure is soil bulk density (or dry bulk density), because it does not require any specific expertise or expensive equipment. It is calculated as the ratio of the dry mass of solids to the undisturbed soil volume. Soil bulk density is maybe the easiest to use soil structure parameter, as it allow to assess the respective volumes of solid and pore space in a known soil volume. However, it does not provide any information on the pore network shape (e.g. pore size distribution and connectivity). Several methods can be used to measure soil bulk density (Al-Shammary et al., 2018). The soils are most often sampled using cores. Alternative methods are the excavation and the clods methods. In the excavation method, which is adapted for loose soils or soils where a coherent sample cannot be collected (in soils with rock fragments for example, where soil bulk density estimation is more challenging), the soil volume can be estimated simply by measuring the elevation of the ground surface before and after excavation or by filling the hole with water, sand or other material (Soil Survey Staff, 2014; Frisbie et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2003; Laundré, 1989). New methods are also developed to estimate the sample volume using imaging technics in the field (Coulouma et al., 2021). In the clod method, the clod is first coated or saturated with a water repellent substance (e.g., paraffin), and the volume is then determined by water displacement. Other variants

of volume determination exist, such as the use of a pycnometer (Uteau et al., 2013). All these methods can lead to uncertainties: the clod method gives an inadequate representation of large pores, soil compaction may occur during sampling with the core method, and cores with small diameter may not be representative of the soil (Page-Dumroese et al., 1999). Soil bulk density can also be estimated using regression methods (pedotransfer functions) based on available data, often organic carbon and texture (Al-Shammary et al., 2018). Several descriptors of soil structure can be derived from the bulk density: e.g. the soil porosity, knowing or approximating the particle density, the degree of compactness (Håkansson and Lipiec, 2000), or the packing density (Renger, 1970). Bulk density and its derived descriptors of soil structure are mainly considered to be useful to estimate soil compaction. For soil monitoring dealing with soil compaction, bulk density measurements are often coupled to penetration resistance measurements (Keller et al., 2017; Vaz et al., 2022).

There are many methods and protocols to assess the aggregate size distribution and aggregate stability (i.e., ability of soil to retain its structure under the actions of water and mechanical stress; Dexter, 1988), that can drive to different results (Díaz-Zorita et al., 2002). Aggregates are broken into several size fractions using dry or wet sieving. During dry sieving, air- or oven-dried soil samples are sieved for a given duration or until complete separation. For wet sieving, dried, field moist, or rewetted soil samples are immersed in water or other solvents, and in some cases submitted to oscillations, and sieved. Only one protocol led to an international standard (Le Bissonnais, 1996; ISO 10930, 2012). Once the size fractions are obtained, indices are computed to express the soil aggregates stability (Díaz-Zorita et al., 2002), e.g. the mean weight diameter (MWD, Le Bissonnais, 1996) or the water-stable aggregate (WSA) index (Pavlů et al., 2022). In addition to these relatively accurate but time-consuming laboratory techniques, faster methods are in development for adoption by farmers, students, or the general public. For example, Fajardo et al. (2016) introduced an approach based on a digital camera on a mobile device to record the process of aggregate disintegration. Significant correlations between the aggregate size and macroporosity, number of pores, and pore size were observed, and aggregate size was also observed to influence the emissions of CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄ (Mangalassery et al., 2013). Evidence was also found that stable microaggregates play a decisive role for the long-term stabilization of SOM, whereas less stable macroaggregates provide only a minimum of physical protection (Krull et al., 2003; Six et al., 2002, 2004). Aggregate stability appeared to be significant for the susceptibility to erosion of soils. Reduced aggregate stability increases soil susceptibility to runoff, interrill erosion, and crusting (Barthès and Roose, 2002; Nciizah and Wakindiki, 2015).

Characterization of the pore space is mostly based on direct or indirect laboratory and imaging methods. Depending on their size, pores are classified as macropores, mesopores, and micropores, although there are no generally agreed upon size thresholds between these categories (Christensen, 2001).

Indirect methods use probe molecules to derive information about the pore size, volume, and/or pore-solid surface area. These methods are not spatially resolved and do not characterize the morphology and topology of the pore space. Three molecules are used: mercury, water and gas. Mercury porosimetry is a widely used method used for decades for the characterization of the pore size distribution. It allows studying aggregates size from 2 to 6 cm³, with pore size from 3 nm to 500 μm, and the measurement is achieved in a few hours. Instruments are easily available, and the repeatability of the method is good (Giesche, 2006). Usually, mercury porosimetry is performed in its “intrusion” mode (MIP): mercury (a non-wetting fluid) is forced to intrude a soil sample by applying known increasing pressures, to fill pores of decreasing sizes (van Brakel et al., 1981). The volume of intruded mercury (for a given pressure) is converted into equivalent pore diameters according to the Young-Laplace law, assuming non-connected cylindrical pores, to retrieve the pore size distribution. The pore size distribution, and therefore the macropore, mesopore, or micropore volumes, can also be derived from the water retention curve, i.e., the relation between soil water content (θ) and matric potential

(ψ), using water as the probe molecule (Dexter, 1988; Nimmo, 2005). Several methods are used to measure the water retention curve, depending on the sample size and the range of matric potential investigated (Dane and Hopmans, 2002), differing in the way water is extracted (hanging water column, suction table, pressure plate extractor, or evaporation method). It is also worth noting that a considerable number of pedotransfer functions exist, to estimate the water retention curve from basic soil properties, e.g., texture, BD, and SOM content (Vereecken et al., 2010). Various other soil structure descriptors can be extracted from the water retention curve, such as the S-index (Dexter, 2004; Reynolds et al. 2009), indicative of the extent to which the soil porosity is concentrated into a narrow range of pore sizes. Finally, physical gas adsorption methods are used to derive properties of the soil pore space in the form of adsorption isotherms (Zachara et al., 2016), using N₂ (e.g., Zong et al., 2015), CO₂ (e.g., Echeverría et al., 1999), and water vapor (e.g., Jozefaciuk et al., 2015). The analyzed soil samples are about 1 to 5 mm in diameter, and the pore size investigated usually ranges between 1 and 200 nm, addressing the lower spatial range of the characterization of soil structure. The reproducibility of the method is recognized to be good (Jozefaciuk et al., 2015).

Imaging techniques can be considered as direct method as they allow evaluating the soil pore space by direct geometric visualization. Thin soil sections have been used for decades to provide 2-D and 3-D representations of the soil pore network using optical microscopes (e.g. Pagliai et al., 2004) or scanning electron microscopy in backscattered electron (e.g. Bruand and Cousin, 1995). These methods require sample preparation in thin sections, but alternatives exist to study undisturbed soil samples, based on radiation interacting with the atoms constituting the soil. Examples are X-ray tomography (Cnudde and Boone, 2013; Lucas et al., 2021; Wildenschild and Sheppard, 2013), gamma-ray tomography (e.g., Pires et al., 2005), neutron tomography (e.g. Tumlinson et al., 2008), and nuclear magnetic resonance imaging (e.g. Sněhota et al., 2010). The latter two methods are rather efficient to image the water phase. The size of the soil sample depends on the resolution to be achieved and on the imaging technique used (Wildenschild et al., 2002), and condition the size of the porosity than can be evaluated. Resolution can range, for example, from about hundred micrometres using a medical X-ray scanner on a decimetre sample, to a few micrometres using synchrotron-based X-ray tomography on a few millimetres sample. Stereological methods are used to retrieve 3-D information from 2-D images or descriptors are calculated directly from reconstructed 3-D images. In any case, images always need to be processed and optimized for subsequent analysis (Schlüter et al., 2014; Tuller et al., 2013). Images can be described visually in a qualitative way, by classifying voids with a typology based on their origin, e.g., biogenic pores, cracks, or textural voids (Skvortsova and Utkaeva, 2008). But the interest of imaging techniques rather lies in the quantitative morphological and topological descriptors which can be extracted from the images (Helliwell et al., 2013). Contrary to the indirect methods to characterize the soil pore space, meaningful measures such as porosity, pore size distribution, and interfacial area can be retrieved directly, without any assumptions on the pore shape.

Some other basic descriptors, often highly correlated, are the number, length, shape, and orientation of pores (Horgan, 1998; Skvortsova and Utkaeva, 2008). Descriptors also characterize the tortuosity, connectivity, or percolation threshold (eg. Vogel et al., 2010). By repeating the calculation of a given descriptor on volumes of increasing sizes, it is also possible to evaluate the representative elementary volume of a given descriptor (e.g., Baveye et al., 2002). However, imaging techniques require expensive instrumentation, expertise, and computing power for image analyses. The segmentation step, allowing the differentiation of the soil matrix from the pore space, is particularly sensitive to subjective errors, and its quality directly affects the calculated metrics (Schlüter et al., 2014; Tuller et al., 2013). Many methods exist and can lead to very different results, depending on both the method and operator (Baveye et al., 2010). This lack of standard protocol limits comparisons between studies (Helliwell et al., 2013), but no method appears ideal to be applied to a wide range of porous media (Tuller et al., 2013). But because the soil pore geometry was observed to be more sensitive to changes in management practices than some bulk measurements like bulk density (Skvortsova and Utkaeva,

2008), imaging techniques are attractive tools to assess soil functions. By the way, porosity and pore size distribution were often observed to be affected by management practices such as tillage, amendment application, crop rotation, or land use (e.g. Munkholm et al., 2016, Schlüter et al., 2011). It also appears that imaging techniques can provide a measure of the pore size distribution which is closer to reality than mercury porosimetry (Zong et al., 2015). Connectivity of the pore network is also a key parameter for soil biota including plant growth, as it impacts water and gas transport (e.g. Luo et al., 2010; Negassa et al., 2015; Paradelo et al., 2016).

4.9.2 Measurement and monitoring of soil structure with PS/RS techniques

Most of the methods used to characterize soil structure are time consuming, or require expensive instrumentations, expertise or computing power. The use of proximal or remote sensing techniques can offer an alternative allowing an easier or quicker characterization of soil structure, especially adapted for monitoring purposes. Descriptors of soil structure can be directly derived from these techniques or can benefit from the advances made on the characterization by these methods of other soil properties linked to the structure. The interest in soil structure estimation is most of the time motivated by the fact this parameter is needed to calculate soil carbon storage.

Regarding direct characterization of soil structure, proximal sensing techniques were mostly used to estimate soil bulk density. Several methods were used in laboratory or in the field: spectral reflectance (Demattê et al., 2010), gamma-Ray Spectrometry (Dhingra, 2023), a combination of gamma-ray attenuation and visible–near infrared (vis–NIR) spectroscopy to measure ex-situ the bulk density of 1 m soil cores that are sampled freshly, wet and under field conditions (Lobsey and Viscarra Rossel, 2016), a combination of mechanical resistance, electric conductivity and soil surface images to propose a “vehicle-mounted soil bulk density detection system” (Meng et al., 2023), active geophysical methods such as S-wave velocity (Murad et al., 2021) and electrical conductivity (Grandjean et al., 2009; Romero-Ruiz et al., 2018), or photogrammetry-based approaches (Coulouma et al., 2021; Mohren et al., 2020). A first attempt was also made to monitor soil structure dynamics using passive acoustic emission (Lacoste et al., 2018). Apart from soil bulk density, proximal sensing methods were also developed to estimate soil porosity (total, inter and intra-aggregate porosities) using gamma-ray attenuation (Oliveira et al., 1998; Pires, 2018; Pires and Pereira, 2014), and aggregate stability using Vis-NIR spectroscopy (Chaloux Clergue et al., 2023; Gomez et al., 2013).

Recently, major advancements have emerged concerning optical and microwave remote sensing. Some studies intended to estimate soil bulk density using multispectral satellite imagery as covariate (Aitkenhead and Coull, 2020; Pittman and Hu, 2020).

However, proximal and remote sensing studies addressed particularly the soil parameters that allow indirect estimation of the soil structure: mineralogical composition, soil texture (sand/silt/clay content), soil moisture (volumetric soil water content) and, indeed, soil organic carbon. For example, several proximal sensing techniques, such as radiometrics and electromagnetic induction, are suitable to reveal parameters that are directly related to soil texture (Demattê et al., 2006). In remote sensing studies, soil texture is typically determined using specific absorption features to differentiate between clay-rich and quartz-rich soils (Wulf et al., 2014). Clay minerals have typical hydroxyl absorption at 2200 nm; this feature can be captured with bands 5 and 6 of ASTER, referred to as the SWIR Clay Index (Chabrilat, 2002). As clay has a great impact on soil texture class and soil aggregation ability, proximal and remote sensing methods are of great importance for measuring soil structure.

4.9.3 Existing thresholds and target values for soil structure

“Good” soil structure can be described as one where all the hierarchical orders, i.e. the different components of soil structure at all the spatial scales, are well-developed and stable (Dexter, 1988).

Soils with a good structure enable adequate soil functioning and support ecosystem services. There is no integrated indicator to indicate whether the structure of a soil is “good”, it is rather necessary to consider a set of structural parameters. Additionally, like many other soil properties, what is considered a good structure can vary depending on what the soil is used for. Well-structured cultivated soils present developed network of pore spaces, continuous and well connected, with a large range of pore size, allowing both water drainage and storage. They are generally considered as well aerated, allowing free movement of air and gas; They quickly absorb water and slowly evaporate moisture. Such soils are characterized by a high biological activity (e.g. micro-organisms, earthworms), can be easily tilled (Keller et al., 2007a), and do not prevent plant germination and root growth. When considering the soil aggregates, good structure is characterized by an equilibrium between aggregates sizes, when large aggregates easily break into smaller ones, but when the aggregates also do not reduce to dust or powder when broken.

The methods and indicators used to describe the soil structure, described in the previous section, do not really present thresholds making it possible to distinguish a good structure from a bad one. Attempts have been made to describe such thresholds, but they are often soil dependent and difficult to generalize. For example, Dexter (2004) found that S-index lower than 0.020 were associated with very poor soil physical conditions in the field. However, Reynolds et al. (2009) demonstrated that this value was not applicable for soils of different texture (e.g. for structureless sandy soils) and advised not to use this type of indicator alone but in conjunction with other indicators to be more representative of the soil structure and functions.

Integrative soil description methods such as visual assesment of soil structure, taking into account different soil structure parameters (aggregates size and shape, porosity, presence of roots, etc.), propose scores to assess a good soil structure. A “good” soil structure, according to the visual soil evaluation scores, was associated with a low soil bulk density, low penetration resistance, low tensile strength, low compaction state as estimated with the degree of compactness, or high number of connected pores (Guimarães et al., 2013; Mueller et al., 2009; Pulido Moncada et al., 2014).

Recently, EEA (2023, Table 4.9.1) as well as the Soil Monitoring Law (SML) proposed indicators for monitoring soil compaction. The soil threat soil compaction is closely related to soil structure and is discussed in more detail in section 4.9.6. One of the most prominent indicators of soil structure as well as soil compaction is soil bulk density (BD). According to the SML: i) soil BD should be determined according to ISO 11272:2017 (taking soil cores, measuring dry weight, lab based), and ii) the critical values of the BD in the subsoil (upper part of B or E horizon) on sand, loamy sand, sandy loam, loam textured soil, should be lower than 1.80 g/cm³; on sandy clay loam, loam clay loam, silt, silt loam the BD should not exceed 1.75 g/cm³; on silt loam, silty clay loam the BD should be lower than 1.65 g/cm³; on sandy clay, silty clay, clay loam (with 34-45 % clay) the BD should not exceed 1.58 g/cm³ and on clay soil, the BD should be lower than 1.47 g/cm³. However, it should be realised that the interpretation of BD with respect to soil functions depends on soil type, especially soil texture and soil organic matter (SOM) content. BD critical and threshold values must be defined according to local agro-pedo-climatic conditions and adapted to crops, cropping systems, tillage practices and stages of plant development.

Some other indicators, derived from BD, have also been used to assess soil compaction. Examples are soil porosity, which can be derived from bulk density if the particle density value is known. Critical limit for root growth has been estimated at < 10% air-filled porosity, meanwhile the 12–15% air-filled porosity can be considered as a safe limit (Grable and Siemer, 1968). Another example is the degree of compactness (DC, also called relative BD). This indicator is defined as the ratio of soil BD to the reference BD of that soil type, and is thus less soil-type and site-specific than BD. However, Håkansson (1990) found that DC was not satisfactory for organic soil.

Table 4.9.1 (set I) presents some of the discussed soil structure parameters based on easily measured and available soil data.

Table 4.9. 1 Thresholds for soil physical parameters for detecting harmful subsoil compaction (EEA, 2023).

Parameter	Explanation and thresholds		Soil sensitivity
Parameter set I			
Bulk density	<1.2 g/cm ³ = very loose 1.2 g/cm ³ - 1.6 g/cm ³ = normal 1.6 g/cm ³ - 1.9 g/cm ³ = dense >1.9 g/cm ³ = very impermeable Based on DVWK 1997, 1998; Keller et al. 2019		Soils originating from clay > silt > sand; higher values are due to geological pre-stressing or anthropogenic impacts
Air capacity: air-filled pore volume	A low air capacity impairs root growth, reduces oxygen pressure in soil air and increases the formation of greenhouse gases. Below 5% air capacity at a soil matric potential of -6kPa, aeration or gas diffusion are mostly insufficient. With decreasing particle size, the pore volume increases, and soil aggregation and soil organic matter content increases. Values around 45% total pore volume are at least acceptable while those below 35% are generally defined as very critical irrespective of texture effects).		Soils originating from clay > loam > silt and sandy loam > sandy loess
Visual soil evaluations	Aggregate type and estimated bulk density Root growth/penetrometer Spade diagnosis	The visual assessment of the soil as loose or dense based on aggregate size and strength, pore size and continuity, root density and distribution	Additional assessment for all soils
Parameter set II			
Precompression stress (= internal soil strength)	Low precompression stress includes 'very low' (<30kPa) and 'low' (30-60kPa) internal soil strength, e.g., because of weak aggregation or wet soil conditions; soils are very sensitive to further deformation and decline in physical, biological, and physico-chemical functions. At medium (60-90kPa) or high (90-120kPa) stress levels, sustainable soil management practices are especially necessary and effective.		All soils, but especially loamy, silty, and clayey soils
Ratio of precompression stress to actual stress applied	Values >1.2 define rigid soil structure conditions with no risk to compaction processes, while values ≤0.8 define structure as irreversibly deformed. Values in between classify soil properties and functions as very susceptible to further soil deformation.		All soils, but especially loamy, silty, and clayey soils, at high water contents and weak levels of aggregation
Shear strength	Shear forces due to wheeling result in smearing: the shear strength is lower for less aggregated soils and decreases with increasing water content. Shearing is more pronounced at higher levels of wheel spin, especially when soils are moist.		All soils, but especially loamy, silty, and clayey soils, at high water contents and weak levels of aggregation

Saturated/unsaturated hydraulic conductivity	Low conductivity is typical for stagnic soil conditions: delayed percolation reduces soil aeration and groundwater accumulation and increases surface run-off (critical values are defined as below 10cm/day).	
Air permeability and oxygen diffusion	Low air fluxes coincide with retarded gas exchange and the formation of anoxic conditions through CH ₄ or N ₂ O formation.	All soils, but especially loamy, silty, and clayey soils, at high water contents and weak levels of aggregation due to tillage or soil management
	Critical values for air permeability <math><1\mu\text{m}^2</math> Diffusion coefficient (D _s) <math><1.5\times 10^{-8}\text{ m}^2\text{ s}^{-1}</math> (Bakker et al., 1987) or relative diffusion <math><0.005</math> for loamy soils and 0.02 for sandy soils.	

4.9.4 Soil structure modelling

Soil structure modelling can be approached from different angles: i) direct soil structure modelling, with the aim to model soil structure in itself, eventually by considering its spatial and/or temporal variations, and ii) use of soil structure parameters in models focused on other properties of interest. The fact is that modelling is a valuable and integrated approach to assess soil functions. Crop growth models, biogeochemical models, water dynamics, or erosion models do not explicitly claim that they were designed to assess soil functions, but some of their output variables can be used to assess these. Soil structural properties have the potential of being used as key variables in these models (Rabot et al., 2018). In any case, one important question raised is the choice of the soil structure parameter to consider for soil structure modelling. There is no unique answer, and it often depends on the function of interest.

Direct modelling of soil structure has long been achieved using soil pedotransfer functions (PTFs), i.e. simple to complex knowledge rules that relate easy to measure soil properties to less easily available soil parameters. Different PTFs of various complexity, using databases of different size and covering a large range of spatial scales, were developed to estimate soil bulk density (van Looy et al., 2017), for example from soil texture and organic carbon content (Martin et al., 2017), or involving also CCE and pH (Shiri et al., 2017). Some of these PTFs also used climatic and topographic data, and are adapted to one specific region (e.g. Schillaci et al., 2021).

When PTFs are based on exhaustive available covariates, they can be used for spatial modelling (or digital soil mapping). These PTFs often involve machine learning algorithms based on soil and environmental covariates. Bulk density estimation and mapping was achieved using classical soil parameters (soil organic carbon, texture, gravel and pH; Chen et al., 2018) or remote sensing (Landsat) covariates and environmental covariates such as land cover, monthly mean temperature and rainfall data, and soil and geological maps (Aitkenhead and Coull, 2020). At the global scale, bulk density was also estimated through covariates used to describe the climate, ecology, geology, land use and cover, elevation and terrain morphology, vegetation indexes and hydrography, to which were added raw bands from Landsat and MODIS products (Poggio et al., 2021).

Apart from PTFs, models were developed to simulate soil structure dynamics, in connection with its different variation factors. However, in most cases only one factor of variation at a time is considered. These models include to different extents mechanistic, statistical or empirical descriptions of the soil structure variations, and consider various soil structure parameters. Among the processes covered we

find the impact of: i) soil organic carbon turnover on soil aggregates dynamics (Segoli et al., 2013; Zech et al. 2022), on bulk density dynamics (Robinson et al., 2022) and porosity, pore size distribution layer thickness (Meurer et al., 2020a), ii) biological activity, for example the action of microbes on soil aggregation (Laub et al., 2023) or the proposition of a framework to model soil structure dynamics induced by biological activity (Meurer et al., 2020b), and iii) soil management. Here the most considered factors are tillage (impact on compacted soil clods (Roger-Estrade et al., 2009), aggregate fracture (Foldager et al., 2022), aggregate coalescence (Or and Ghezzehei, 2002) and the dynamics of pore size distribution (Chandrasekhar et al., 2019)) and compaction inducing practices such as agricultural field traffic (Nawaz et al., 2013; Stettler et al., 2010) or livestock treading (Romero-Ruiz et al., 2023), impacting dynamics of soil bulk density, macroporosity and saturated hydraulic conductivity

Finally, many models dealing with other soil processes (crop growth models, biogeochemical models, water dynamics, or erosion models) use static soil structure parameters (often soil bulk density and/or porosity), even if these parameters are known to be variable in time and space, and without considering any feedback between soil properties. This is the case in general for Earth System Models (Fatichi et al., 2020), models of carbon dynamics such as RothC (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996) or crop model such as STICS (Brisson et al., 2003). However, some of these models consider a spatially explicit soil pore network, for example to model organic matter turnover (Monga et al., 2014; Vogel et al., 2015).

4.9.5 Effects of scale (time/space) on changes of soil structure

Soil structure is highly variable in space and time (Bronick and Lal, 2005; Roger-Estrade et al., 2009). Moreover, soil structure can vary with depth, within the different soil layers (Morris et al., 2010). This variability is linked to the various factors that control soil structure state, including other soil properties (such as texture or organic matter quality and quantity), but also external factors such as plant growth, macro and micro-organisms activities, climate, land use and soil management practices, etc. Soil structure may improve or deteriorate over time. It is much affected by mechanical soil disturbance.

4.9.6. Compaction

Along with aggregate breakdown, soil compaction is one of the key factors impacting soil structural vulnerability (Hu et al., 2023). Soil compaction is estimated to be currently affecting 23% of the agricultural subsoils (Stolte et al., 2015). It is primarily related to physical soil degradation, interactions with chemical and biological properties and functions are also clear. Soil compaction arises mainly if the internal soil strength (known as actual precompression stress) is exceeded by additional stress, such as from dense trafficking, heavy machinery and driving in high soil moisture content conditions. This exceedance results in plastic soil deformation, which negatively affects the soil functions and the provision of ecosystem services. Soil compaction, in particular of the subsoil, is primarily triggered by heavy machinery and often accompanied by increasing field area. In addition, seasonal time constraints, operational conditions and limited knowledge of service providers may cause additional pressures.

The following indicators are suggested for soil compaction (EEA, 2023): precompression stress, ratio of precompression to actual stress applied, air capacity, and saturated hydraulic conductivity.

Table 4.9.1 (set II) describes thresholds for the four abovementioned parameters, presenting well-defined physical units which are intimately related to actual water saturation, soil structure, and anthropogenic processes. Hence, this second set of parameters is more appropriate to quantifying and documenting stress-induced changes in soil functions including water, gas and heat fluxes, as well as effects on biodiversity and physico-chemical processes such as changes in redox potential.

For monitoring soil compaction, some methods allow the evaluation of soil compaction including its intensity and distribution in space and time. Besides some practical models using indicators that can be obtained or determined using data in national and international databases, it can be evaluated through *in situ* and laboratory measurements or obtained from pedotransfer functions. The estimation of soil compaction and shear-generated soil deformation through modelling is mainly based on soil properties, land use and climate. A number of models and approaches can produce mechanical soil properties, related soil processes and functioning. These estimations are based on general soil physical parameters and indicators. However, to be able to generate valid and site-specific input data for models, well-outlined parameters for local soil properties and *in situ* matric potential data need to be gathered for these studies. The most common models to monitor soil compaction can be considered as FEM (finite element method) coupled process model (Richards et al., 1997; Gräsle 1999; Richards and Peth, 2006), Socomo (Van den Akker, 2004), Soil flex (Keller et al., 2007b), Terranimo (Stettler et al., 2014), Scale approach (Duttmann et al., 2022) and pedotransfer functions (Horn and Fleige, 2003, 2009; Imhoff et al., 2016; Schjønning et al., 2020; Schjønning, 2021; Schroeder et al., 2022a, 2022b). In addition to these approaches, Zink et al. (2011) developed the compaction verification tool (CVT), which includes stress-dependent changes in soil functions defined as indicators to assess the actual soil stability and the risk of stress-generated soil degradation. The CVT tool mainly rests on measurements or estimates of saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ks) and air capacity (at -60hPa) as a function of actual stress applied within the virgin compression stress range (EEA, 2023).

4.9.7 Recommendations for monitoring soil structure changes

The structure of cultivated soils presents strong temporal variations, in particular because of agricultural practices, and the moment at which the parameters which describe it will be measured will particularly influence their values. That is why it is absolutely necessary, for monitoring purposes, to clearly define the sampling periods. We recommend a sampling period away from machine disturbances (notably away from soil tillage) to allow the structure of the surface horizons to stabilize. Soil sampling could be better just before harvest, as it would allow comparison between different situations (comparison in time to monitor soil evolution, or comparison of measurement in different countries). This question of temporality is especially important for the topsoil layers, directly impacted by the agricultural practices, but is also valid for deepsoil layers, that can be impacted for example by compaction or root growing.

It is in fact necessary to consider the entire soil profile, as the environmental issues are not the same in the top or deep soil layers, and the soil structure changes with depth. Surface horizons are, for example, very important for the establishment of crops, but deep horizons contribute to the storage of carbon and water.

Another crucial point is that the soil structure is highly dependent to the soil texture and organic matter content. The threshold values to identify a "good" or "bad" structured soil should always take into account at least the soil texture. No unique threshold values can be defined, and the indicators values should always be evaluated regarding the pedological context. It is particularly true for the bulk density, which is a very widely used indicator of soil structure and is often used to detect soil compaction. The interpretation of soil bulk density with respect to soil functions depends on soil type, especially soil texture and soil organic matter content. Bulk density and critical threshold values must be defined according to local agro-pedo-climatic conditions and adapted to crops, cropping systems, tillage practices and stages of plant development.

It is also important to specify that soil structure is linked to different soil functions and cannot be described using a single indicator. If the bulk density (or its derived indicator such as the degree of compaction or the packing density) is useful for characterizing, the soil compaction, it is necessary to quantify the porosity and characterize the pore network (e.g. pore size distribution, connectivity) if we are interested in water flows and storage and greenhouse gas emissions. It would be better to use a bundle of indicators. However, there is no so many normalized methods to measure soil structure indicators except for the soil bulk density (standard ISO 11272:2017) and the soil aggregate stability (standard SO 10930:2012). Some very relevant methods are widely used in the field (e.g. VESS method) or in the laboratories (e.g. water retention curves), but common protocols should be established to compare soil structure indicators among countries.

There is thus a need to developed easy to apply standard methods (in terms of time, human and financial resources) to characterize soil structure that should be evaluate soil according to soil functional indicators based on site- and land-use specific critical limits.

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4.10 Soil contamination

Soil contamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Antonio Bispo, Jozef Kobza, Agnieszka Klimkowicz-Pawlas, Claire Froger ○ Relevant EJP SOIL Projects: SIREN
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4.10.1 Monitoring and measurement of soil contamination

Soils may accumulate chemical contaminants that can be inorganic (e.g., trace elements like cadmium) and/or organic (e.g., PAHs, PCBs, pesticides). Whereas most of the organic contaminants have an anthropogenic origin, high concentrations of inorganic contaminants in soils can occur naturally linked to specific geochemical backgrounds. In addition to these "natural" concentrations, there are inputs from human activities. Depending on the source, the contamination can be qualified as "diffuse" if the substance is emitted from moving sources, from sources with a large area, or from many sources (e.g. cars, application of substances through agricultural practices, emissions from town) or as a "point source" if the substance is emitted from a stationary discrete source of definite size (e.g. accidental spills, waste dumps, spills on industrial sites) (ISO 11074, 2015). Generally, agricultural soils are more concerned with diffuse contamination than with point source contamination.

Trace elements of interest in soils include metals and metalloids such as arsenic (As), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb) and mercury (Hg). Those elements can be toxic to human beings, plants and soil organisms (even at low concentrations, depending on the target organism). Part of them (such as Cu and Zn) are also essential micronutrients that may become toxic at higher concentrations. These elements occur naturally in soils and are linked to the parent materials and soil pedogenesis. Those natural concentrations are generally called geochemical background concentrations.

Concentrations, distribution, and speciation of trace elements including heavy metals in soils are mainly controlled by the geologic parent material, pedogenetic processes, and land use (Schwertmann et al., 1982, Wilcke et al., 1998, Andersen et al., 2002). In anthropogenically contaminated soils, the type of heavy metal sources, chemical and physical soil modifications, and co-deposition of other contaminants such as acids and complexing agents such as fluoride play a more important role for the chemical forms and solubility of contaminants in soils (Wilcke et al. 2000, 2005, Totsche et al. 2000, Scheinost et al. 2002). In addition, contaminated soils are mostly situated in the industrial areas, less on agricultural land (anthropogenic impact) and in the areas influenced by geogenic impact (occurrence of geochemical anomalies mostly in mountain and submontane areas) in conditions of Slovakia (Kobza, et al. 2019).

Note that some authors also include in the background concentrations elements originating from diffuse sources as atmospheric deposition or agricultural inputs (see ISO 19258, 2018). This latter definition does not distinguish between pristine pre-industrial levels versus anthropogenically affected soils. For agricultural soils, the main sources of trace elements are: pesticides (e.g., for Cu), mineral fertilizers (e.g., for Cd), animal manure (e.g., for Cu and Zn), liming materials, sludge and composts and atmospheric deposition (e.g., for As, Hg, Pb, Zn) (Belon et al., 2012).

Trace elements in soil samples are measured using various analytical techniques to determine their total concentrations. The measurement process typically involves the following steps (once the sample is in the laboratory):

- **Sample Preparation:** the collected soil sample is air-dried, carefully sieved at 2 mm (debris like roots or stones are removed) and then crushed (e.g., 250 µm). Subsampling is then performed after another sieving step to achieve uniformity.
- **Sample Digestion:** Before quantification, trace elements should be extracted from the soil. A so-called digestion process is performed in open beakers heated on hot plates or in digestion tubes in a block digester or in digestion bombs placed in microwave ovens with the use of concentrated acids, such as hydrofluoric acid (HF), nitric acid (HNO₃), hydrochloric acid (HCl), or a mixture of them (e.g. aqua regia), to dissolve the soil samples and solubilize the trace elements (see ISO 11466, ISO 14869-1,-2-3). Not all acids are able to break down all complex organic and inorganic compounds in the soil during the digestion step, making the trace elements more or less available for analysis. This digestion step can introduce a difference in the results (Gaudino et al., 2007). The addition of HF strongly influences the recovery of the acid digestion of environmental samples as this acid breaks down silicates and minerals better than other acids mixtures (Melaku et al., 2005).
- **Filtration:** After digestion, the resulting solution is filtered to remove any remaining solid particles or impurities and ensure an accurate analysis.
- **Analytical Technique Selection:** Several quantification techniques exist, and the choice depends on the specific trace elements of interest, the detection limit expected and the available resources. Commonly used techniques include Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS), Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF), and Ion Chromatography (IC), among others (see ISO 22036 or ISO/TS 16965). Analytical methods may also influence the results.

Those techniques are generally able to detect and determine the total/pseudo total concentrations of quite all mineral elements in soils. Softer extractants such as diluted nitric acid, ammonium nitrate or EDTA/DTPA can also be used not to assess total or pseudo-total concentrations but so called environmentally available or bioavailable fractions (see ISO 17402, ISO 19730, ISO 22190). As an example, ISO 11466 (1995) standard defines a method for the extraction of trace elements soluble in aqua regia that has been widely used (e.g., for LUCAS soil samples). ISO 17586 (2016) specifies a method of extracting trace elements from soil using a dilute nitric acid solution, that should determine the potential environmental availability as defined in ISO 17402 (2016) but appears to be quite like the former method. To better estimate the availability of trace elements a buffered diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) solution can also be used for the extraction (ISO 14870:2001), with results that differ from ISO 11466 (1995). Methods using chelating agents such as EDTA and DTPA represent extraction methods that likely simulate the processes that occur in the environment, in particular uptake by plants.

Organic contaminants in soils are very diverse, coming from several sources. In agricultural soils, plant protection products (PPP, pesticides) are introduced as being part of major agricultural practices. Consequently, a series of PPPs, can be found in soils, both currently used pesticides, mostly fungicides and herbicides (Froger et al., 2023, Vieira et al., 2023), and banned pesticides such as organochlorinated compounds (Orton et al., 2013). Those banned pesticides being persistent in soils may also be still found because of previous use (Cabidoche et al. 2009). Near urban areas and in regions of intensive animal farming (e.g., cattle, poultry), sewage sludge (also compost) and manure are also considered as sources of organic compounds including PFAS, plastics and medicines. Air deposition may also introduce industrial contaminants such as PAHs (Froger et al. 2021) or PCBs (Motelay-Massei et al., 2004). In addition, for the evaluation of environmental hazards resulting e. g. from high PAH-concentrations, should be considered, not only of whole soil samples but also the smallscale distribution where aggregate core and surface fractions can be identified. Deposited organic

contaminants are preferentially sorbed at the aggregate surfaces or leached from aggregate surfaces. The differences may be used as an indicator for atmospheric deposition and the extent of PAHs-leaching (Wilcke et al. 1996).

As for trace elements the determination of organic contaminants in soil samples requires several steps (after collection of a representative soil sample¹[14](#)):

- Sample Preparation to remove excess moisture: depending on the nature of organic contaminants of interest this can be done by air-drying the sample at room temperature or by freeze drying. Soil samples may also be mixed with a drying agent. Then the sample may be crushed, and debris or rocks are removed. Another subsampling step is performed by sieving the soil to achieve homogeneity.
- Extraction Methods: like for trace elements organic contaminants have to be extracted in a solvent before analysis. As organic contaminants are diverse the proper solvent has to be chosen and adapted depending on the nature of the contaminant. It can be dichloromethane (DCM), hexane, methanol, acetone... or a mixture of those solvents. Various extraction procedures are also available where temperature and pressure may vary (as for accelerated solvent extraction (ASE)). After the extraction procedure where the soil is mixed with the solvent, the resulting mixture is then separated by centrifugation or filtration.
- Cleanup and Purification: depending on the complexity of the soil matrix and the presence of interfering compounds (such as organic matter), additional cleanup steps may be required (e.g. based on gel permeation chromatography or solid-phase microextraction).
- Instrumental Analysis: the extracted and purified sample is then subjected to instrumental analysis to quantify the organic contaminants. Common techniques include gas chromatography (GC), liquid chromatography (LC), or their hyphenated forms such as GC-MS or LC-MS. These techniques separate and detect individual compounds based on their physical and chemical properties.

Measuring all possible organic contaminants in soil samples is quite challenging as each molecule has its own behaviour in soils, reacting differently with soil components (such as organic matter, clays). Generally, measuring many organic contaminants will require the use of several extraction methods (including different solvents) and different measurement methods to be able to detect and quantify all the molecules of interest! As an example, Froger et al. (2023) required 4 different methods to be able to analyse 111 pesticides in soils.

For several families of organic contaminants, ISO methods are available as for hydrocarbons (ISO 16703), PAHs (ISO 13859 and ISO 18287), PCBs (ISO 13876), dioxins and furans (ISO 13914), organochlorine pesticides (ISO 10382 and 23646), explosive compounds (ISO 11916), nonylphenols (ISO 13907) and phthalates (ISO 13913).

New analytical methods called “target screening” and “suspect screening” have been developed recently to detect multiple compounds using one main extraction method (Chiaia-Hernandez et al. 2017). Such technologies might, in the future, allow the detection of new molecules (such as pesticide transformation products) unknown until now.

¹ Note that if volatile contaminants are to be analysed special sampling and conservation conditions should be adopted (ISO/DIS 18400-301).

4.10.2 Measurement and monitoring of soil contamination with PS/RS techniques

It is also possible to measure trace elements and organic contaminants in soils using remote or proximal sensing techniques. Proximal sensing is defined as the use of electromagnetic radiation to quantitative assessment of a given object (e.g., soil) properties. These techniques offer non-destructive and rapid methods for assessing soil contamination over large areas. Several approaches can be used as:

- **Hyperspectral or multispectral spectroscopy:** these techniques measure the reflectance or absorption of light across different wavelengths (radiation across the visible-near infrared shortwave infrared-longwave infrared (VIS-NIR-SWIR-LWIR) region (400–16000 nm)). By analyzing the spectral signature of the soil, it is possible to estimate the presence and concentration of certain trace elements or organic contaminants (Wang et al., 2018, Gholizadeh et al., 2018).
- **X-ray Fluorescence (XRF):** Portable XRF instruments can be used for proximal sensing of trace elements in soil (Milinovic et al., 2023; Padilla et al., 2019). These devices emit X-rays onto the soil surface, which causes the soil to emit characteristic fluorescent X-rays. By detecting and analyzing these emitted X-rays, the instrument can determine the concentrations of various trace elements present in the soil. XRF instruments are effective for rapid field measurements, but they may have limitations in terms of depth penetration and sensitivity to specific elements.
- **Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS):** LIBS is a remote or proximal sensing technique that uses a high-energy laser pulse to generate a plasma on the soil surface. The plasma emits characteristic light, which is analyzed to identify and quantify trace elements. LIBS can provide rapid and real-time measurements of multiple trace elements simultaneously (Ren et al., 2022).

Note that while remote or proximal sensing techniques provide rapid and non-destructive measurements, they often require calibration and validation using conventional laboratory analysis, often with large numbers of samples. Calibration models are developed using ground data to establish relationships between spectral patterns and trace element concentrations. The accuracy and reliability of these techniques depend on factors such as soil type, vegetation cover, and instrument calibration. Therefore, validation and cross-referencing with traditional soil sampling and laboratory analysis are crucial to ensure accurate trace element measurements.

4.10.3 Existing thresholds and target values for soil contamination

EEA's recent report (2023) made a stocktake of existing benchmark values to judge the contamination of soils. EU countries developed different strategies and policies to identify contaminated land based on risk assessments for different targets (e.g., human health, soil organisms, food production), so called soil screening values (SSV) were developed. The EEA report (2023) proposed the following vocabulary for those values (see Fig. 4.10.1), differentiating background, acceptable, warning and action values where:

- **Background** refers to the concentration of an element or a substance characteristic of a soil type in an area or region arising from both natural sources and anthropogenic diffuse sources such as atmospheric deposition or agricultural practices (adapted from ISO 19258, 2018). It is assumed that those values pose no risk or negligible risk and are considered suitable for any type of land use. However, there is known examples that elevated levels of lead and cadmium are measured in agricultural soil influenced by former industries (Douay et al., 2008).
- **Acceptable** generally reflects a negligible risk. Below this acceptable value there are no restrictions on land use.

- *Warning* marks the lower end of the concentration range of what is considered 'intermediate risk'. Concentrations falling between the acceptable value and the warning value mark the range when (minor) restrictions on sensitive land use may be appropriate. The value is also used as a trigger that initiates further soil or groundwater investigations to increase the reliability of the judgement on whether the action value is exceeded.
- *Action* is the lower limit of concentrations above which unacceptable risk can occur. Usually, in the past, exceedance of this action value often meant 'polluted soil' and required some kind of intervention (such as remediation). Currently, most countries have more advanced procedures based on risk assessment frameworks, in which the action value acts as a trigger for further, more detailed site-specific risk assessments. Depending on the urgency of the risk as defined by modelling or experimental testing, action is required or not. The urgency of the risk is also related to the intended land use.

Figure 4.10. 1 Schematic representation of soil screening values and consequences (EEA, 2023)

The EEA report (2023) provides an updated stocktake of the existing soil screening values (see table 4.10.1) in different countries for trace elements. For cadmium across all countries, the critical risk level ranges between 1 mg.kg⁻¹ (in protected areas, Poland) and 30 mg.kg⁻¹ (industrial land use, Brussels and Flanders region, Belgium; Slovakia); for intermediate risk, values vary by up to a factor of 100, between 0.4 mg.kg⁻¹ (Slovakia) and 40 mg.kg⁻¹ (Austria). The same, even worse for copper as the range of variation is similar for the critical risk thresholds (30-1500 mg.kg⁻¹) but much more extreme for intermediate values (factor of 1,500). A similar degree of variation is reported for thresholds for both lead and zinc (the critical values vary by a factor of 50), while the variation in intermediate values is the highest for lead (factor of 4000). Those differences may be explained by the conceptual and methodological approaches used at national level. Additional aspects such as stratification (land use) or correction using specific soil properties, such as pH or organic matter, also need to be considered.

Table 4.10. 1 Screening values (SSVs) for cadmium, copper lead and zinc in soils for intermediate and critical risk (extracted from EEA, 2023)

Country/region	Warning value		Action value		Warning value		Action value	
	Stratum (*)	SSV	Stratum	SSV	Stratum	SSV	Stratum	SSV
Austria	LU	1-40	-	10	LU	100-1,500	-	600
Belgium/Brussels	-	1	LU	2-30	-	40	LU	145-800
Belgium/Flanders	-	-	LU	2-30	-	-	LU	200-800
Belgium/Wallonia	-	-	LU	1.8-20	-	-	LU	53-600
Bulgaria	LU, pH	1.5-3.5	-	12	LU, pH	80-300	-	500
Czechia	LU, pH, text.	1.5-20	-	-	pH	150-300	-	-
Denmark	LU	5	-	-	LU	1,000	-	-
Finland	-	1	LU	10-20	-	100	LU	150-200
Germany	LU	2-20	LU	0.1-20	LU	1 ^(*)	LU	1,300
Hungary	-	1	-	10	-	75	-	1,000
Italy	-	-	LU	1.5-15	-	-	LU	100-600
Lithuania	-	-	-	0.75-3	-	-	-	35-200
Netherlands	-	-	SOM, clay	13	-	-	SOM, clay	190
Poland	-	-	LU, SHC, z	1-20	-	-	LU, SHC, z	30-1,000
Slovakia	LU, text.	0.4-10	LU	20-30	LU, text.	30-500	LU	600-1,500
Slovenia	-	2	-	12	-	100	-	300
Sweden	LU	0.4-12	-	4	LU	100-300	-	1,000
LEAD					ZINC			
Country/region	Warning value		Action value		Warning value		Action value	
	Stratum (*)	SSV	Stratum	SSV	Stratum	SSV	Stratum	SSV
Austria	LU	100-300	-	500	-	300	-	-
Belgium/Brussels	-	120	LU	200-2,500	-	120	LU	300-3,000
Belgium/Flanders	-	-	LU	200-2,500	-	-	LU	600-3,000
Belgium/Wallonia	-	-	LU	120-1,840	-	-	LU	196-3,000
Bulgaria	LU, pH	60-150	-	500	LU, pH	200-450	-	900
Czechia	LU	300-400	-	-	-	400	-	-
Denmark	-	40	-	400	-	500	-	1,000
Finland	-	60	LU	200-750	-	200	LU	250-400
Germany	-	^(*)	-	-	-	^(*)	-	-
Hungary	-	100	-	750	-	200	-	2,500
Italy	-	-	LU	100-1,000	-	-	LU	150-1,500
Lithuania	-	-	LU	50-500	-	-	LU	75-1,200
Netherlands	-	15-590	SOM, clay	530	-	150-720	SOM, Clay	720
Poland	-	-	LU, SHC, z	50-1,000	-	-	LU, SHC, z	100-3,000
Slovakia	-	150	-	600	LU	2-500	-	3,000
Slovenia	-	100	-	530	-	300	-	720
Sweden	LU	80-300	-	800	LU	350-1,050	-	3,500

Notes: (*) Stratified according to: LU, land use, text., texture; SOM, soil organic matter; SHC, saturated hydraulic conductivity; z, soil depth.
 (**) Analysis based on concentrated ammonium nitrate (commonly, extraction with aqua regia is used).

With a few exceptions (as PAHs), organic contaminants are generally linked to human activities (e.g. pesticides). Their pristine background level should then be zero (contrary to trace elements). Then background levels generally include diffuse contamination. As for trace elements, the EEA report (2023) produced a stocktake of soil screening values for industrial and residential use. The latter is reproduced here as there is no value for agricultural soils (table 4.10.2). As for trace elements, differences between countries can be observed, again linked to the different models and approaches used. Note that compared to the huge number of organic molecules found in the environment just a few soil screening values were developed for soils, mainly for quite old well-known contaminants. There is an urgent need to develop values for new emerging contaminants such as medicines, PFAs and non-banned pesticides.

Table 4.10. 2 Screening values for potentially unacceptable risk (residential soil use) for organic contaminants (extracted from EEA, 2023).

Compound	Country/region												
	AT	BE (F)	BE (B)	BE (W)	CZ	FI	IT	LT	NL	PL	ES	UK	DK
Benzene	-	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.1	0.5	1	12.6	1	-	-
Ethylbenzene	-	5	5	28	50	10	0.5	5	50	38	20	41	-
Toluene	-	15	15	33	100	5	0.5	0.1	130	38	30	-	-
Xylene	-	15	15	10	30	10	0.5	0.1	25	18	100	-	-
Naphthalene	-	5	5		60	5	5	5	-	12.5	8	-	-
Anthracene	-	70	70		60	5	5	5	-	12.5	100	-	-
Benzo(a)anthracene	-	10.5	10.5	5	5	5	0.5	-	-	12.5	2	-	-
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	-	3,920	3,920	15	30	-	0.1	-	-	10	-	-	-
PAHs (total)	50	-	-	-	-	30	10	5	40	30	-	-	40
Dichloromethane	-	0.35	0.35	-	-	1	0.1	2	10	-	6	-	-
Trichloroethylene	-	1.4	1.4	-	-	1	1	2	60	-	7	-	-
Tetrachloromethane	-	0.02	0.02	-	-	-	0.1	1	1	-	0.5	-	-
Hexachlorobenzene	-	0.1	0.1	-	-	0.05	0.05	0.5	-	-	0.1	-	-
Phenol	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	10	40	10.25	70	280	-
Cresols (sum)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.1	-	5	10.25	40	-	-
Atrazine (p)	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.01	-	6	3	-	-	-
DDT (sum of DDT, DDE, DDD)	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	4	2.01	-	-	-
PCB	1	-	0.9	-	5	0.5	0	0.1	1	0.55	0.08	-	-
Methyl t-butyl ether	-	9	9	-	-	5	10	-	100	-	-	-	-
1,1,1-Trichloroethane	-	13	13	-	-		0.5	-	15	-	-	-	-
Chlorobenzenes (sum)	-	-	-	-	-		-	-	30	1.05	-	-	-
Benzo(a)pyrene	5	1.5	1.5	4.4	2	2	0.1	0.1	-	7.5	0.2	-	-
PCDD/PCDF (ng ITEQ TeCdd/g)	100	-	-	-	0.5	1×10 ⁻⁴	1×10 ⁻⁵	-	1×10 ⁻³	-	-	-	-

Note: B, Brussels; F, Flanders; W, Wallonia; PCDD, polychlorinated dibenzodioxins; PCDF, polychlorinated dibenzofurans. For countries not represented, see also note for Figure 5-7.

Note that all those screening values are based on the total content in the soil, and it is known that depending on the soil conditions, the nature of the contaminants and the living organism, the amount available and absorbed can be order of magnitude below the total amount. The so-called bioavailable fraction is not yet used in such assessment.

In addition, except for PAH and PCB most screening values are established only for each substance independently, but the mixture of molecules can induce a higher risk for soil biodiversity and

ecosystems which is called the “cocktail effect”. This is particularly the case for pesticide residues, widespread in agricultural soils with up to 30 molecules detected at the same time (Froger et al. 2023, Silva et al. 2019) potentially harmful effects on soil biodiversity (Panico et al. 2022). The inclusion of soil contamination in soil quality evaluation of agricultural soils is a challenge for future policies.

4.10.4 Soil contamination modelling

The accumulation of contaminants in soil and their transfer into the environment can be modelled. Depending on the contaminant models are available and can be used to predict concentrations in time either in soils coming from different sources and/or in plants or/in water. The metal concentration, partitioning and storage in soil as well as its transfer from soil to plant using Freundlich-type functions have been studied in several works (Wilcke, et al. 1999, 2001, Krauss et al. 2002, Lobe et al. 1998, Bigalke et al., 2010). For example, mass balances approaches have been used to predict accumulation of trace elements in soils and transfers in plants for Cu, Zn, Cd (De Vries et al., 1989, Six and Smolders, 2014, Carne et al, 2021). Those models are not so developed for organic contaminants whereas it is even more relevant for most organic pollutants. Only some mass balance models have been developed for PAH but mostly at small scales and watersheds (Gateuille et al. 2014, Peng et al. 2015). Those models may then be used to predict the remaining concentrations in soils with time (Cabidoche et al., 2009).

4.10.5 Effects of scale (time/space) on changes of soil contamination

The concentration of contaminants in soils varies depending on space and time. For trace elements in agricultural soils the main drivers are the parent materials, the distance to local emissions (e.g. roads, factories, cities) and inputs linked to management practices (e.g., fertilizers, pesticides). Each source may be responsible for a different pattern in space and time and makes it difficult to model and estimate the effect on soil contamination. The same occurs for organic contaminants except that the natural origin does not exist except for few contaminants such as PAHs. In addition, soils have received contaminants from various sources for more than a century linked to anthropogenic activities making it difficult to model and estimate their contamination. Having a regular sampling grid, without any predetermined stratification, may help to catch these different patterns but makes it difficult to relate the amount found in soils to a specific origin.

Considering time, the amount linked to diffuse sources modelled over years predicts quite small variations in less than 10 to 20 years (depending on models and contaminants). Carne et al. (2021) calculated based on a mass balance model the cadmium inputs and respective accumulation in soils depending on the amount of cadmium allowed in phosphate fertilizers and management practices. They found that after 10 years the expected increase in a worst-case scenario was less than 10% whereas after 20 years the increase may reach more than 15% of the initial amount. This argues for a delay of monitoring of at least 10 years. Before, apart from an accident, changes may not be detected.

The evolution of organic contaminants through time is difficult to estimate since the interaction with soils could highly affect their fate. For example, PAH can be volatilized from soils or degraded by oxidation or microorganisms (Demircioglu et al., 2011; Haritash and Kaushik, 2009) but they can also be sequestered in soil due to their sorption on organic matter and diffusion through micropores (Bogan and Sullivan, 2003). This process leads to long term persistence of PAH in soils but decreasing their bioavailability. In the particular case of pesticides, recent studies demonstrated the persistence of some compounds in soils far beyond their theoretical degradation time, thus questioning the real behaviour and fate of pesticides in the environment (Froger et al. 2023, Chiaia-Hernandez et al. 2017).

4.10.6 Recommendations for monitoring soil contamination changes

Contamination of soil is considered a serious threat across the world (FAO and UNEP, 2021). In EU the recent Soil Monitoring Law asks for the monitoring of soil contaminants and includes in its list several trace elements (As, Sb, Cd, Co, Cr (total), Cr (VI), Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, Tl, V, Zn) and a selection of organic contaminants to be established by Member States. Those recommendations agree with EEA (2023) where authors also asked to monitor trace elements and focus on persistent organics. It seems also reasonable to include new organic contaminants widely used as pesticides and emerging ones such as microplastics, PFAs or medicines (at least on selected monitoring sites to identify if there is an issue). Pushing non-target approaches may also be an option to identify the occurrence in soils of several organic contaminants and to identify new molecules not yet measured such as specific transformation products.

Considering the delay between 2 consecutive measurements, a 5-year frequency recommended in the Soil Monitoring Law seems too frequent as for agricultural soils, mainly submitted to diffuse pollution, changes or trends may be detected only after at least 10 years (except for an accident). Therefore, a 10-year frequency would be preferred for organic substances already identified as persistent such as organochlorine pesticides (e.g., lindane, DDT, atrazine, dieldrin etc.), PAHs or PCBs and trace elements.

One option may be to monitor a category of those persistent contaminants (e.g., trace elements, PAHs, pesticides) every 5 years and remeasuring it 10 to 15 years after the first campaign. Doing so will optimize the budget and allow resources to measure several contaminants in time. For contaminants that are not considered to be subject to changes, another option might be to preserve the soil samples to measure contaminants in between 2 campaigns or if needed, on a defined question and/or if budget is available. This will require organizing a long-term storage of the soil samples.

For the specific case of currently used or recently banned pesticides, the 5-year frequency might be relevant to evaluate soil contamination by those substances and some of their transformation products newly identified as a threat (e.g. water contamination). Also, given the widespread use and therefore occurrence of pesticides in soils, their impact on soil biodiversity (Beaumelle et al., 2023; Johnsen et al., 2001) and by extension on soil quality, they should be fully considered in soil monitoring and evaluation.

The development of systematic non-target screening methods would indeed be of high interest to capture the chemical footprint of soil contamination. Those techniques allow the simultaneous identification of multiple substances, including unknown substances, and could work as a “soil footprint library”. Those results could then be reused in the future to search for new molecules, avoiding new analysis of the samples. Establishing such database on soil would help anticipate the rising demand for information on soil contamination already needed by researchers and policies to capture the link between environmental health and human health.

Finally, concerning soil screening values, as identified by EEA (2023) and confirmed by other stocktakes (Faber et al., 2022) there is no consensus in EU countries as values may vary by a factor of more than 4000! The unique values proposed for the EU Dashboard (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/euso/euso-dashboard-sources>) may not be adapted to all countries (e.g., for France, the limit value of 65 mg.kg⁻¹ proposed for Zinc is equal to the median of the national distribution based on the French monitoring network). Several options may be proposed and will require to install an EU working group to:

- develop a harmonized method to derive soil screening values (e.g. based on risk approach, considering the same targets, same protection levels, same methodology) that should then be run by each Member State based on national datasets,

- decide based on the national dataset and distributions on a concentration or a centile above which the soil may be considered as contaminated,
- develop scoring functions to rank the datasets (concentrations and analytical methods may be different within countries but the final score may be the same).

The values obtained may be different in each country according to soil types and land-uses but will be obtained in the same way.

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- ISO 11916-1:2013 Soil quality — Determination of selected explosives and related compounds — Part 1: Method using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with ultraviolet detection
- ISO 11916-2:2013 Soil quality — Determination of selected explosives and related compounds — Part 2: Method using gas chromatography (GC) with electron capture detection (ECD) or mass spectrometric detection (MS)
- ISO 11916-3:2021 Soil quality — Determination of selected explosives and related compounds — Part 3: Method using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)
- ISO 13859:2014 Soil quality — Determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) by gas chromatography (GC) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)
- ISO 13876:2013 Soil quality — Determination of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) by gas chromatography with mass selective detection (GC-MS) and gas chromatography with electron-capture detection (GC-ECD)
- ISO/TS 13907:2012 Soil quality — Determination of nonylphenols (NP) and nonylphenol-mono- and diethoxylates — Method by gas chromatography with mass selective detection (GC-MS)
- ISO 13913:2014 Soil quality — Determination of selected phthalates using capillary gas chromatography with mass spectrometric detection (GC/MS)
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- ISO 18287:2006 Soil quality — Determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) — Gas chromatographic method with mass spectrometric detection (GC-MS)
- ISO 19258:2018. Soil quality — Guidance on the determination of background values
- ISO 19730:2008 Soil quality — Extraction of trace elements from soil using ammonium nitrate solution
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- ISO 22190:2020 Soil quality — Use of extracts for the assessment of bioavailability of trace elements in soils
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4.11 Soil sealing

Soil Sealing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Katrien Oorts, Kasper Cockx, Ines Marinosci, Michele Munafò, Costanza Calzolari, Francesca Assenato, Nicola Riitano, Ialina Vinci, Rudi Hessel ○ Relevant EJP SOIL projects: SERENA
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4.11.1 Monitoring and measurement of soil sealing

Soil sealing is a form of land consumption and can be defined as the destruction or covering of soils by buildings, constructions and layers of completely or partly impermeable artificial material (asphalt, concrete, etc.) (Huber et al., 2008; Prokop et al., 2011; Stolte et al., 2015). In case a soil is completely impermeable to water, e.g. when covered by buildings, the material is considered to be **impervious**, preventing infiltration into groundwater.

Sealing by its nature has a major impact on the soil. It is normal practice to remove the upper layer of topsoil, which delivers most of the soil-related ecosystem services, and to develop strong foundations in the subsoil and/or underlying rock to support the building or infrastructure, before proceeding with the rest of the construction. This usually cuts off the soil from the atmosphere, preventing the exchange of gases between the soil and the air. Soil sealing furthermore results in an increased flood risk, reduced water infiltration, loss of ability to absorb and store carbon, higher temperatures in urban areas and biodiversity losses. Hence, sustainable spatial management is crucial to ensure a healthy living environment and address climate change.

The attention for quantifying and mapping the amount of sealed surfaces and its spatial evolution has strongly increased recently. In Italy and Flanders (Belgium), for example, the issues of land take and soil sealing have become increasingly important in the scientific and political debate on sustainable development and urban and land use planning. The following sources have been used for measuring soil sealing at the national or regional level (Foldal & Oorts, 2022; Lu & Weng, 2006, Peroni et al., 2022; Strollo et al., 2020):

- Earth Observation data (satellite and aerial images) (EEA, Hungary, Italy, Spain, Flanders)
- Cadastral data (Austria), building and infrastructure dataset (Flanders), spatial planning documents (Latvia)
- Corine Land Cover multitemporal maps (Czech Republic)
- Field survey, census data or ground-based data collection (e.g. LUCAS program)

For sealing, existing data covering the entire region or country are of course more interesting than an expensive and time-consuming set of field-based samples. Hence, nation-wide land use/land cover maps and administrative datasets have been used for measuring soil sealing. Sealing indices may then be defined for all categories in these maps by deriving average values from multiple sampling. Cadastral data however may be imprecise and lag behind in time (EEA, 2023). The spatial and temporal resolution of existing land use/cover maps (like the 25 ha units of Corine, which is only updated every 6 years) may also be too low to adequately assess a highly heterogenous phenomenon like soil sealing. Existing land use/cover maps also use average values for a limited set of categories, of which the nomenclature in addition may change through time, and likely is an oversimplification. High-resolution

remote-sensing data with high-frequency revisit times are therefore a more reliable source for sealing quantification. They allow spatial and multitemporal analyses on large areas and are often available as open access data (like the Landsat and Sentinel satellite data) (see 4.13.2).

In Italy, annual 10 m-resolution mapping of land consumption, including sealed areas, is produced by ISPRA and the National Environmental Protection System (SNPA), i.e. the network of regional Environmental Protection Agencies, since 2012, and data and derived indicators are available for the public in form of maps and tables². The base map was worked out in 2015 with a semi-automatic classification process (by means of 5 m resolution satellite images), aimed at identifying impervious and artificial areas. Since then the map has been updated, and the land take calculated, annually by means of manual photointerpretation (by personnel of the National and the Regional Environmental Protection Agencies) with the help of indices calculated by ISPRA on Sentinel-2 (NDVI index) and Sentinel-1 data (radar to detect differences in altitude, i.e. new buildings and infrastructures). Every three years, the whole territory is covered by 20 cm resolution aerial images that allow to check the maps, correct the errors and fill the gaps.

The annual soil sealing maps of Flanders are produced by combining the strengths of different types of data³ (Cockx et al., 2022). These maps combine “known” sealing from the administrative Large-scale Reference Database (LRD) with modelled sealing produced by a machine learning model based on aerial images (25 cm resolution). The LRD is a continuously updated and highly accurate vectorial representation of Flanders’ buildings and infrastructure. This dataset partly circumvents the limitations of remote-sensing data caused by vegetation or shadow concealing sealed areas. The aerial images are each year produced by flights organized by Flanders and made publicly available. This results in annual soil sealing maps at a resolution of 1 m starting from 2013.

Indicators

Table 4.11.1 gives an overview of indicators related to soil sealing adapted from EEA (2023: 131), the EUSO Soil Health Dashboard and the proposal for the Soil Monitoring Law (2023). The most important indicators are also discussed below.

Soil sealing

Confusingly, soil sealing indicators are being defined based on imperviousness and actual soil sealing data (Table 4.11.1). Imperviousness only considers soils covered by non-permeable materials, while soil sealing also takes into account soils covered by partly impermeable artificial material, like e.g. railways. For Flanders, railways take up about 0,7% of the total sealed area in 2021. The location and area of other semi-permeable terrains and artificial turf are unknown.

Soil sealing is usually expressed as a) a percentage of a country’s or region’s total area or b) sealed area (per capita) (Table 4.11.1). **Soil sealing expressed as percentage of the total area** is a very relevant indicator, since sealing-specific policy targets could be defined.

² <https://groupware.sinanet.isprambiente.it/uso-copertura-e-consumo-di-suolo/library>

³ <https://www.vlaanderen.be/statistiek-vlaanderen/ruimtegebruik/verharding> and <https://archieff.algemeen.omgeving.vlaanderen.be/xmlui/handle/acd/843715>

Imperviousness

EEA's soil sealing indicator⁴ is based on the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service's Imperviousness Density 2018 map. Since the majority of sealed area consists of completely impermeable artificial material, imperviousness can be a proxy for soil sealing. EEA's use of 'imperviousness' and 'soil sealing' as synonyms is however confusing. In addition, the 100-m imperviousness product of 2018, aggregated from the 10-m 2018 imperviousness data set for analytical performance, is the basis for this indicator. This means that it is a very coarse resolution indicator.

Impervious built-up

EUSO Soil Health Dashboard's indicator for soil sealing⁵ is currently based on Copernicus' Impervious Built-up 2018 map. Since only above-ground, elevated impervious areas are taken into account this way, this indicator does not include flat impervious areas and hence ignores a significant part of soil sealing. Buildings take up 5,5% of Flanders' area, or only 35,8% of its total sealed area, in 2021.

This indicator is interesting as an additional indicator, because limiting additional land take and sealing includes limiting additional buildings. It however cannot be used as an indicator for soil sealing.

Land take

Soil sealing is related to land take. **Land take** provides a broader picture of land development, as it relates to all previously undeveloped land being taken for settlement-related human activities. Different indicators concerning land take are circulating.

Land take indicator 1 based on (settlement) land use

The European Commission in 2012 defined land take as **an increase of settlement areas over time. Settlement areas are described as the areas of land used for housing, industrial and commercial purposes, health care, education, nursing infrastructure, roads and rail networks, recreation (parks and sports grounds), etc.**

In February 2020, the European Environment Agency (EEA) sent out a questionnaire addressing geospatial and/or statistical data regarding land take and land consumption to all EIONET National Reference Centres on Land Use and Spatial Planning (EIONET NRC LUSP) Members. In that survey, 'land take' was defined as 'the change in the area of agricultural, forest and other semi-natural land taken for urban and other artificial land development'. Urban land development can be considered including blue-green spaces like gardens, parks, sport terrains and small water bodies.

In November 2022, the EEA distributed a note to the members of EIONET network about 'land take in functional urban areas', being one of the 8th Environment Action Programme (EAP) headline indicators. In this discussion note, the indicator was defined as follows: *"the land take indicator addresses the change in the areas of agricultural, forest and other semi-natural land taken for urban and other artificial land development. Land take includes areas sealed by construction and urban infrastructure, urban green areas, and sport and leisure facilities"*.

⁴ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/imperviousness-and-imperviousness-change-in-europe>

⁵ <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/esdacviewer/euso-dashboard/>

‘Settlement area’ is part of the EU SDG indicator set and is used by Eurostat to monitor the progress of SDG 11 on sustainable cities and communities ([Settlement area per capita \(sdg 11 31\)](#)). It is described there as follows:

“this indicator captures the amount of settlement area per capita due to land-take, such as for buildings, industrial and commercial areas, infrastructure and sports grounds, and includes both sealed and non-sealed surfaces. The indicator is closely linked to the concept of settlement land use, which comprises physical components of shelter and infrastructure and services to which the physical elements provide support (such as education, health, culture, welfare, recreation and nutrition).”

Also here, ‘land take’ is mentioned as the driver of change in ‘settlement area’, which includes non-sealed surfaces like some sports terrains, parks, gardens and small water bodies.

The concept of ‘settlement’ also appears in the [LULUCF Regulation](#), where it stands alongside other land uses such as forest land, grassland, cropland and wetland.

Land take indicator 2 based on artificial surfaces

Within the EIONET EAGLE concept⁶⁷, land take entails the **conversion of land to artificial surfaces, which impair the valuable ecological functions of land**. Artificial surfaces are all surfaces where landscape has been changed by or is under the influence of human construction activities by replacing natural surfaces with artificial abiotic 2D/3D constructions or artificial materials. These include the artificial parts of urban, suburban and rural areas where mankind has settled with permanent settlement infrastructures. Within artificial areas, a distinction can be made between sealed and non-sealed surfaces:

- **Sealed artificial surfaces and constructions** represent “the sole part of space that is covered with artificial constructions like a building or surfaces like a pavement. Sealed Artificial Surface includes therefore all impervious and sealed surfaces that are covered mainly by buildings and artificial constructions (3D) or impervious surfaces (2D)”.
- **Non-sealed artificial surfaces** include “Any open areas where natural surface material has been replaced by artificial material or removed from its place of origin as result of human activity, forming a non-sealed (non-impervious) and non-built-up surface. Areas belonging here are e.g. logistic and storage areas, waste disposal and dump sites, festive squares, non-sealed roads and parking lots, unvegetated sport fields”.

Under this framework, a specification is made for ‘urban greenery’, which may be artificial, under human maintenance and part of settlements. However, since they are vegetation, urban green areas are not included under artificial areas, but under biotic vegetation, as suggested by the EEA in the frame of EAGLE concept (EEA, 2023), where biotic vegetation is defined as any vegetated land surface, either naturally grown, semi-natural or artificially planted vegetation (e.g. crops, urban parks), with or without anthropogenic influence.

⁶ <https://land.copernicus.eu/eagle/content-documentation-of-the-eagle-concept/manual/content-documentation-of-the-eagle-concept/b-thematic-content-and-definitions-of-eagle-model-elements/part-i-land-cover-components/1-abiotic-non-vegetated-surfaces-and-objects/1-1-artificial-surfaces-and-constructions>

⁷ https://clms-prod.eea.europa.eu/en/technical-library/explanatory-documentation-of-the-eagle-concept-3_2/@@download/file

Land take indicator proposed in the Soil Monitoring Law (2023)

The recently launched proposal of the Soil Monitoring Law (SML) (2023) comes with a new definition for 'land take' as the **conversion of natural and semi-natural land into artificial land**:

- 'Natural land' means an area where human activity has not substantially modified an area's primary ecological functions and species composition.
- 'Semi-natural land' means an area where ecological assemblages have been substantially modified in their composition, balance or function by human activities, but maintain potentially high value in terms of biodiversity and the ecosystem services it provides.
- 'Artificial land' means land used as a platform for constructions and infrastructure or as a direct source of raw material or as archive for historic patrimony at the expense of the capacity of soils to provide other ecosystem services.

The definition of land take proposed in the Soil Monitoring Law is consistent with the EAGLE concept of Artificial Surfaces and Constructions distinguishing the concept of land consumption from that of urbanization (urban growth) and the definitions of land cover set by Eurostat (LUCAS). This means that is in line with the above indicator 2 for land take.

However, the definition used in the proposal of the SML is inconsistent with previous definitions of land take on the basis of (settlement) land use set by the European Commission and the EEA (see above indicator 1). It affects some already existing national policies based on the definition of land take based on (settlement) land use. For example, from 2012 onwards, Flanders coherently implemented the reduction of land take, as described in the Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe¹, starting from the cited definitions on land take based on (settlement) land use. In contrast, since 2013, Italy implemented monitoring activities and policies starting from the cited indicator 2 based on artificial surfaces.

Also, the indicator for land take based on (settlement) land use is important to monitor the European target 'no net land take' by 2050 and is for example published⁸ for Flanders every 3 years (total land take, share of the total area and average additional land take per day).

It would be consistent with all the previous initiatives to adopt the two different indicators for land take (so both indicator 1 as 2) in the new Soil Monitoring Law and make a clear distinction between them by specification of the indicator: land take based on (settlement) land use on the one hand and land take based on artificial surfaces on the other hand.

Ratio of soil sealing to land take

Especially in highly built-up areas, limiting soil sealing is pressing in order to better address the effects of climate change and to improve urban quality of life. This makes the **ratio of soil sealing to land take (with land take as defined in indicator 1 of land take)** a relevant indicator to check if no additional green is removed in heat-sensitive areas.

⁸ <https://indicatoren.omgeving.vlaanderen.be/indicatoren/ruimtebeslag>

Table 4.11. 1 Overview of indicators related to soil sealing adapted from EEA (2023: 131), the EUSO Soil Health Dashboard and the proposal for the Soil Monitoring Law (European Commission, 2023).

Indicator	Explanation	Proposed/reported in
Soil sealing <i>Sealed area (total km² and % of total surface)</i>	Area where soils are permanently covered by buildings, constructions and layers of completely or partly impermeable artificial material (asphalt, concrete, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Commission Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (2023): Soil sealing shall be expressed as a percentage of sealed area per total area.
Imperviousness <i>1) per area: (% of) impervious area</i> <i>2) (per capita)</i>	Area where soils are covered with non-permeable materials .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EEA (2023): proposes stratified (e.g. urban centre, peri-urban, rural). EEA Land and Soil Indicator set (LSI002) (based on the 100 m aggregation of Copernicus' Imperviousness Density Map)
Impervious built-up <i>per area: (% of) impervious built-up area</i>	Built-up areas are the sub-group of the sealed areas with above-ground building constructions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EUSO Soil Health Dashboard (based on Copernicus' Impervious Built-up) (https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/imperviousness/status-maps/impervious-built-up-2018)
Land take <i>1) Total land take: km² and % of total surface</i> <i>2) Average land take per year (km² and % of total surface)</i> <i>3) (per capita)</i>	<p>Indicator 1 based on (settlement) land use: an increase of settlement area, i.e. the area of land used for housing, industrial and commercial purposes, health care, education, nursing infrastructure, roads and rail networks, recreation (parks and sports grounds), etc. In land use planning, it usually corresponds to all land uses beyond agriculture, semi-natural areas, forestry, and water bodies.</p> <p>Indicator 2 based on artificial surfaces and ecosystem services: definition of land take in Proposal Soil Monitoring Law (2023): 'the conversion of natural and semi-natural land into artificial land, i.e. land used as a platform for constructions and infrastructure or as a direct source of raw material or as archive for historic patrimony at the expense of the capacity of soils to provide other ecosystem services.'</p>	<p>Indicator 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe (COM (2011) 571 final) European Commission (2012) Guidelines on best practice to limit, mitigate or compensate soil sealing (2012) EEA (2023): proposed stratified, e.g. by major land cover category, urban protected areas, functional urban areas, urban floodplains EEA (2023): Net land take in cities and commuting zones in Europe (8th EAP) (https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/net-land-take-in-cities) SDG indicator 11 (Settlement area per capita (sdg_11_31)) Categories in LULUCF Regulation <p>Indicator 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EIONET EAGLE concept⁹ European Commission Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (2023)

⁹ <https://land.copernicus.eu/eagle/content-documentation-of-the-eagle-concept/manual/content-documentation-of-the-eagle-concept/b-thematic-content-and-definitions-of-eagle-model-elements/part-i-land-cover-components/1-abiotic-non-vegetated-surfaces-and-objects/1-1-artificial-surfaces-and-constructions>

Indicator	Explanation	Proposed/reported in
Ratio of soil sealing to land take	Quality and quantity of sustainable land use and urban redevelopment 1 = total loss of all soil ecosystem services (except soil as a carrier for construction) 0 = no soil function is affected	• EEA (2023)
Land recycling		• EEA (2023): includes recultivation • European Commission Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (2023): optional indicator
<i>Subindicators:</i>		
Share of undeveloped building land		• EEA (2023)
Sparse urbanization prevalence index	Ratio of low-intensity sealed land to severely sealed land	• EEA (2023)
Sprawl/densification ratio	Ratio of new sparse urban areas to urban densification area (trend in soil sealing change) < 1 = tendency towards more compact urban forms > 1 = tendency to more diffuse urban forms	• EEA (2023)
Cc/Co ratio	Ratio of SOC in built-up land area to SOC in natural soils 0 = unsealed land ≤ 0.5 = low-intensity sealing 0.5 ≤ 2.0 = medium-intensity sealing > 2.0 = high-intensity sealing	• EEA (2023): tested in three Italian peri-urban areas, using multi-temporal SOC stock maps (Villa et al., 2018)
Land fragmentation		• European Commission Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (2023): optional indicator
Land taken for commercial activities, logistic hubs, renewable energies, surfaces such as airports, roads, mines		• European Commission Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (2023): optional indicator
Consequences of land take such as quantification of loss of ecosystem services, change in floods intensity		• European Commission Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (2023): optional indicator

Note: The methodologies chosen shall either be available in the scientific literature or publicly available.

4.13.2 Measurement and monitoring of soil sealing with PS/RS techniques

The most common method for measuring soil sealing is by classifying high-resolution satellite imagery. A wide range of classification methodologies are used for this purpose, including Spectral Mixture Analysis (SMA) and Linear SMA (LSMA), image classification (at the sub-pixel, pixel or object level) and vegetation index analysis (NDVI, NDBI, IBI) (Wang & Li, 2019; Peroni et al., 2022). An example of the latter is the Imperviousness Density Map of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. This map discriminates the different reflective behaviour of impervious and permeable parts through the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) based on Landsat and Sentinel-2 images. The annual soil sealing maps of Flanders are based on a classification of 25 cm-resolution aerial images with the help of additional different sources. The aerial images that are each year produced by flights organized by Flanders and made publicly available. Also for Italy, a yearly map at 10 m resolution is provided for the land consumption, including soil sealing, derived from classification of images mainly from CLMS with additional different sources.

4.13.3 Existing thresholds and target values for soil sealing

Threshold values for soil sealing, e.g. for a defined land use pattern (core city, peri-urban area, rural area), have neither been defined nor implemented (EEA, 2023). Target values have however been set based on policy rather than science, albeit mostly in terms of land take. Mostly (interim) targets at the national or regional level are defined for land take and not for soil sealing itself. Usually, the target value is an average number of 'hectares per day' compared to a reference year. So far, only a few European countries defined baselines and target values for land take. Among these countries, only Flanders, Luxembourg and Switzerland set targets in line with the EU objective of 'no net land take by 2050' (EEA, 2023). Some targets have been set at regional level, as for Italy, with different indicators as progressive reduction of land take to 2050 with respect of the planned consumption and/or taking into account the population variation. Specifically for Flanders, the policy goal is to reduce the average additional land take to 0 ha/day by 2040 (and 3 ha/day by 2025). Furthermore, the Flemish government has formulated three sealing-specific policy objectives:

- decrease sealed areas in open space zoning by 20% in 2050 compared to 2015,
- stabilise (and preferably reduce) sealed areas in zoning meant for land take in 2050 compared to 2015, and
- realise 1 m² of de-sealing per capita from 2021 until 2030.

4.13.4 Soil sealing modelling

Land use models like for example CLUE (Veldkamp & Fresco, 1996) and Metronamica (Van Delden et al 2005; Van Delden & Vanhout 2018) model changes in land use over time as a function of various drivers and processes. Such changes in land use include conversion of other land uses to built-up areas. Such land use change models have also been specifically used in an urban context. For example, de Silva et al (2014) applied Metronamica to simulate land uses changes in Colombo, Sri Lanka.

4.13.5 Effects of scale (time/space) on changes of soil sealing

Soil sealing change manifests itself in a spatially highly heterogeneous way and practically on a daily basis. Soil can get covered by a wide range of geographical features: small garden houses, terrace extensions, long linear road infrastructure, detached villas, parking lots, large-scale residential developments, industrial warehouses ... To capture spatial patterns of change adequately, very high

resolution data are required, going from 0,25 to 1 m pixel size (Jensen & Cowen, 1999; Franklin et al., 2003; Rogan & Chen, 2004; Peroni et al., 2022). However, satellite images with a much lower resolution such as Landsat 8 (30 m) and Sentinel 2A/B (10 m) are commonly used for soil sealing monitoring (Peroni et al., 2022). The Copernicus’ Imperviousness Density Maps’ 20 m resolution for the reference years before 2018 may therefore be too coarse for proper detection of the full variety of sealing changes. This is reflected in the differences in the more detailed and realistic 10 m-resolution 2018 map compared to previous years: they not only show actual change, but also reflect improved mapping. Hence, the Copernicus website warns to not draw far-reaching conclusions in terms of the magnitude of the change signal in the 2015-2018 imperviousness change products. For Flanders for example, the large increase in imperviousness based on the Copernicus maps between 2015 and 2018 is indeed unrealistic (Table 4.11.2) **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** Though Flanders’ annual soil sealing maps (resolution of 1 m) also cover semi-impermeable materials, the much less pronounced increase for soil sealing based on these maps is likely a reliable proxy for the change in imperviousness. However, since the share of semi-impermeable land in Flanders’ sealed area remains unknown, it’s not possible to directly compare the Imperviousness Density Map and Flanders’ annual soil sealing maps.

Table 4.11. 2 Imperviousness density for Flanders based on the Copernicus Imperviousness Density Map and soil sealing density based on Flanders’ annual soil sealing map.

	2015 (%)	2018 (%)
Copernicus Imperviousness Density Map	8,9 (20 m resolution)	12,3 (10 m resolution)
Flanders’ annual soil sealing map	14,4 (1 m resolution)	14,8 (1 m resolution)

To monitor if policy measures effectively lead to de-sealing and limited additional sealing, a sufficiently high temporal resolution is necessary as well. Measurements every (two) year(s) allow to detect trends early on and – if needed – may support spatial policy adjustments (Departement Omgeving, 2021). Copernicus’ imperviousness maps are made every three years, which may be too coarse.

4.13.6 Recommendations for monitoring soil sealing changes

In order to be able to adequately capture the detailed spatial patterns of soil sealing change (and thus not underestimate soil sealing), monitoring soil sealing with a very high spatial and temporal resolution is required. We therefore recommend to:

- Use the indicator ‘sealed area (percentage of sealed area per total area)’ as the principal indicator for soil sealing,
- Not use the terms ‘imperviousness’ and ‘soil sealing’ as interchangeable to avoid confusion,
- Adopt in the Soil Monitoring Law both circulating indicators concerning land take in order to be consistent with all the previous initiatives and make a clear distinction between them by specification of the indicator: land take based on (settlement) land use on the one hand and land take based on artificial surfaces on the other hand.
- Increase the spatial resolution of existing open (satellite) data and/or support very high-resolution airborne data in order to be able to derive soil sealing indicators with a sufficient high resolution from them.
- Increase the temporal resolution of existing open (satellite) data (from 3/6 years to 1/2 year(s)).

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4.12 Soil erosion

Soil erosion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Authors: Rudi Hessel, Petra Deproost, Seth Callewaert, Martine Swerts, Gabriele Buttafuoco, Sevinc Madenoglu, Maria Fantappiè, Costanza Calzolari ○ Relevant EJP SOIL projects: SCALE, SERENA
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4.12.1 Introduction

Soil erosion is the detachment of individual soil particles from soil mass by one or more natural or anthropogenic erosive agents (rain, runoff, ice, wind, gravity, tillage, land levelling, crop harvesting, etc.) (Table 5.13.1), their movement to lower elevation areas, and deposition when there is no more energy available for transport (Boardman & Poesen, 2006; Morgan, 2005, 2010). Soil erosion is a natural process and it is critical in soil formation from rock parent material, but in anthropized environments, the detachment and removal of soil particles can increase and reach rates and extent to represent one of the main threats to soil (FAO, 2019; FAO and ITPS, 2015). Soil erosion is classified according to the agent driving the detachment and removal of soil particles (Table 5.13.1). In this chapter, the focus will be on soil erosion in agricultural lands and, therefore, glacial erosion, mass movement and coastal erosion will not be covered, while other types of erosion resulting from anthropogenic action (such as tillage and harvest erosion) will be (Table 5.13.1).

Table 4.12. 1 Types of erosion. Partly based on Lal (1990).

Agent		Erosion type	This chapter
Water	Rain	Splash	Yes
	Water flow	Surface	Sheet Rill Gully Stream bank
		Subsurface	Pipe or tunnel
	Sea	Coastal erosion	No
Wind		Deflation Corrasion	Yes
Ice		Glacial erosion	No
Gravity		Mass movements	No
Anthropogenic		e.g. tillage, harvest	Yes

There are two main ways to quantify erosion rates (Stolte et al, 2016; EEA 2023), namely field-based monitoring and modelling. These methods are discussed in the following sections.

4.12.2 Monitoring and measurement of soil erosion

A large number of measurement techniques have been developed to quantify the erosion processes and types that are shown in Table 5.13.1. These techniques vary in relation to different erosion processes, amount of soil loss, but also in function of spatial and temporal scales. More pragmatic considerations in selecting measurement techniques are the use of the collected data and available resources. Measurement of soil erosion is crucial to determine the severity of the threat, to improve the understanding of erosion processes, to design management plans and strategies, and technologies

for erosion control (Toy et al, 2002; Bhat Shakeel Ahmad and Dar, 2019) and to validate model results. In this section some typical measurement techniques will be discussed. Erosion measurement usually also involves measuring other attributes or properties that are important in explaining erosion, such as rainfall, wind speed, soil moisture content, plant and soil characteristics. Describing these measurements is beyond the scope of this chapter. Here, the description is limited to field measurements, although some erosion processes are often studied in the laboratory using flumes, plots and rainfall simulators.

Water erosion

Rainsplash erosion

The action of raindrops on soil consists both in a consolidating force that compacts the soil and a disruptive force, as water rapidly disperses from the point of impact and returns to it in jets flowing laterally (Morgan, 2005). Rainsplash erosion can be measured in several ways (Fernández-Raga et al 2017). One of the methods that is used most often are splash cups that collect the sediment that has been splashed by the rainfall (see Fig. 4.12.1 for an example). The amount of sediment collected in the splash cup depends not only on splash rate, but also on splash distance (Van Dijk, 2002), making conversion to an erosion rate more difficult (Fernández-Raga et al 2017). As can be seen from figure 4.12.1 splashed sediment is caught on the surrounding cloth that covers a metal mesh to let the water drain. The relatively high edge of the cup is meant to minimise the amount of splashed soil that leaves the splash cup, and to minimise the amount of soil that is splashed into the cup from outside. As the cup is divided in two parts downslope splash and upslope splash can be measured separately, and the difference between them will be net splash erosion.

Figure 4.12. 1 Splash cup, Embu, Kenya. Picture by B.Okoba

Another way to measure splash erosion is by measuring the height of splash pedestals. To convert such measurements into erosion rates the time period over which these pedestals developed must be known.

Sheet erosion

Sheet erosion together with rill erosion are the most common types of erosion by water on upland areas. It is induced by the combined action of raindrops detaching soil particles and shallow overland flows removing a relatively uniform depth (or sheet) of soil. (Flanagan, 2017). For the measurement of sheet erosion two types of methods can be used. On the one hand, denudation measurements can be used to estimate soil loss by sheet erosion. There are several ways to measure the denudation: exposure of tree roots, erosion pins and erosion plots (e.g. Boix-Fayos et al 2006). By measuring the exposure of tree roots an estimate of sheet erosion rate can be obtained, but care should be taken in interpreting the results since certain tree roots might naturally have exposed roots, while for others no roots might be exposed even if there is considerable erosion (Lal, 1990). Repeated measurement of pin lengths gives information about the amount of sediment removed or deposited. The method is cheap and easy and therefore allows for large numbers of measurements. Care should, however, be taken to ensure that the pins themselves are stable. Such pin stability will, for example, be very difficult to ensure on cropland, since land management is likely to disturb the pins. Likewise, pins might move because of frost heave (Toy et al., 2002), because of swelling clays or because of settlement of the plough layer. Other problems with pin measurements include the fact that installing the pins disturbs the soil and that the pins themselves might influence erosion (Toy et al., 2002), while the measurement error can easily be a few mm, which precludes the detection of small changes in surface elevation and results in large uncertainty in estimated erosion per unit area. More sophisticated methods that also determine the elevation of the soil surface include photogrammetry using stereo photos and laser scanning (e.g. Stumvoll et al 2022).

On the other hand, sediment load in run-off water can be used as an estimation of soil loss. For example, by using erosion plots the amount of soil loss from an area of a certain size is measured, but no information is obtained about distribution of erosion/deposition inside the plots. For example, the runoff and sediment collected may derive from a relatively small but unknown part of the plot, usually on the lower part of the plot (Parsons, 2011). Since there is likely to be some deposition on the plot, the measured rates will be lower than the erosion rates, i.e., sediment delivery ratio will be lower than one. The usual procedure is to collect the runoff from a plot of known area, and to measure the amount of runoff as well as the sediment concentration in the runoff. To be able to handle large amounts of runoff a divisor system is often used to collect a known fraction of the total runoff. On smaller plots troughs or barrels can be used. Care must be taken that these collector systems can handle both maximum rate of flow and total quantity of runoff (Hudson, 1993). These plot measurements, however, only give values of sheet erosion if no other erosion processes occur on the plot. Erosion plots of many different sizes have been used, but all have in common that the slope is more or less uniform and that the plot is considerably longer in the downslope direction than in the cross slope direction. In order to convert the measured sediment to erosion rates the area of the plot must be known, which is easy for bounded plots, but might be more difficult for unbounded plots. On bounded plots, however, there is some risk that the boundaries might cause rill erosion. Plot data have been widely used in development of soil erosion models and to evaluate the effect of different crops or soil and water conservation measures on erosion (Fig. 4.12.2).

As shown by Hudson (1993), determining the amount of sediment leaving an area gives potentially a much more precise estimate of soil loss per unit area than areal measures by erosion pins, for example. Nevertheless, Hudson (1993) also pointed to the fact that large numbers of plot studies have been ill-designed, or have given useless data for various other reasons, e.g. overflow, leakage, equipment breakdown, and animal disturbance. Properly designed plots with sufficient replicates are very expensive. A simpler and less expensive alternative can be found in the use of catchpits. These pits can be used to show the assess differences between different crops and conservation measures. Due to their unknown catchment area and the inability to measure the trapped soil, however, these types of experiments do not allow for quantification of the total erosion (Hudson, 1993).

Figure 4.12. 2 Erosion plots used to evaluate different crops and treatments, Ansai Field Station of Institute of Soil and Water Conservation, Shaanxi Province, China (picture R.Hessel)

Rill erosion

Rill erosion is induced by changing overland flow conditions downslope when overland flow breaks up into small channels or microrills, which are also the major pathways for transporting soil particles and sediments detached by sheet erosion (Flanagan, 2017; Morgan, 2005). The usual method of assessing rill erosion is by measuring length, width and depth of the rills, e.g. using tape. To convert to soil loss bulk density of the eroded sediment should be known. If rills are measured on erosion plots, sheet erosion rates can be derived by subtracting rill erosion from total sediment yield for the plot. The results of erosion plots depend on the spatial scale of the experiment, because at different scales different erosion processes dominate. On small plots mostly sheet erosion is measured, while on larger plots rill erosion is likely to increase in significance, and at hillslope scales gully erosion can occur, as well. On small plots, divisor systems are usually sufficient, but for larger plots tipping buckets or flumes may be used to measure discharge. Ciesiolka & Rose (1998), for example, advise to use tipping buckets for plot sizes of up to 600 m².

Gully erosion

Rills are small enough to be levelled out by tillage and do not reform in exactly the same location. Gullies, on the contrary, are deeper and larger erosion channels and are formed by large runoff flow concentration that cannot normally be tilled over. However, ephemeral gullies are small enough to be tilled over but because of the convergent topography in small catchments they tend to re-form in the same location (Flanagan, 2017).

Poesen et al. (2003) mention a number of methods that have been used to measure gully erosion at different time scales. On short time scales, the most usual methods are direct measurement of gully volume, e.g. with tape and the use of benchmark pins around the gully head to determine the headcut retreat. Hudson (1993) also mentions the use of erosion pins driven horizontally into the gully wall, but cautions that inserting the pins might change resistance to erosion.

Another method is to measure the amount of water and sediment that leaves the gully. Such measurements require that water level is measured (preferably at a weir or flume), and that sediment

concentration in the runoff is determined. These methods will be more fully explained in the section on catchment erosion. If these techniques are used for gullies, one should be aware that most gully catchments do not consist of only gullied terrain, so that gully erosion rates cannot be extracted easily from those data.

At medium time scales (aerial) photos or satellite images taken at different moments can be used, while on long time scales historical data (documents and maps) might be available. Recently, Borelli et al (2022) used the 2018 LUCAS survey to assess gully erosion at EU scale. The existence of almost all gullies mentioned during LUCAS survey could be confirmed from satellite images and LUCAS 2018 terrestrial photos. However, authors indicate that ephemeral gullies might have been missed. Besides, it should be realised that identification of current gullies does not give information on gully erosion rates as the age of gullies is not known.

Catchment erosion

Catchment erosion, or more accurately catchment soil loss, can only be assessed by measuring the amount of water flowing at the outlet of the catchment and the sediment concentration in the runoff. For catchments with a lot of bedload, additional structures like sediment traps might be needed. The usual procedure is to build a structure (weir or flume) for which a known relationship exists between water level and discharge. Many different designs are available for such structures (see e.g., Bos, 1989, Herschy, 1995). The water level must be measured just upstream of the structure, for which various methods have been developed, as well. The most low-tech method is to record water levels manually using a staff gage. However, this method suffers from the fact that in that case someone must be present at the structure during high runoff. This can be quite difficult to arrange because in many streams (especially in semi-arid and arid regions) discharge peaks are short lived and can be easily missed. Furthermore, the structure might be difficult to reach under the extreme circumstances of exceptional storms which are likely to cause the highest water levels. To overcome such problems a range of automated methods has been developed to measure water levels. These methods range from simple float recorders that require regular changes of recorder paper, to fully automatic systems with data loggers, like ultrasonic sensors, pressure transducers, capacitive sensors and acoustic sensors. Obviously, such methods require a power source, e.g. provided by batteries in combination with a solar panel. For these automatic measurements the events are also the most difficult periods to measure because of the generally very wet conditions, in conjunction with the risk of physical damage to the sensor. Therefore, it is advisable to use several systems at the same time. Some methods allow for direct measurement of discharge and therefore do not require a structure. One of the best known of these methods is dilution gauging (as done by Herschy (1995)). Like for discharge, samples to determine sediment concentration can be taken manually or using automatic equipment like samplers. By multiplying with measured discharge, soil loss from the catchment is obtained, but one should be aware that concentration gradients often exist in the flow, so that the sample taken might not be representative for the average sediment concentration.

Figure 4.12.3 shows a weir that was used at the catchment outlet of a 2 km² catchment on the Chinese Loess Plateau. It was equipped with several backup systems to reduce the risk that during the extreme conditions of high intensity storms data would be lost.

Figure 4.12. 3 Weir at catchment outlet of a small catchment on the Chinese Loess Plateau. Picture taken by R. Vergouwe during an event on July 20th, 1999.

If reservoirs or lakes are present, longer term catchment erosion rates may be obtained from measuring sedimentation in those reservoirs and lakes. However, not all sediment might be trapped (e.g. Garcia-Ruiz et al 2015), and data on initial water depth as well as on bulk density of the deposited sediments are needed.

Wind erosion

The velocity of moving air is main factor inducing wind erosion (Morgan, 2005). Assessing wind erosion is not easy because the movement of soil particles is related to critical speed values which need to be defined (Morgan, 2005). Wind erosion can be measured by the depth of soil removed (using e.g. erosion pins), or by determining the transport rates on erosion plots. Contrary to water erosion plots, which are usually rectangular, wind erosion plots are often circular because wind can come from any direction. Furthermore, the air entering the measurement plot will already carry a certain sediment load (Toy et al., 2002), which is not the case for properly designed water erosion plots. Therefore, multiple measurement equipment is needed to be able to measure sediment load of wind coming from any direction both when it enters and when it leaves the measurement plot. Furthermore, sediment concentrations must be measured at multiple heights since there is a vertical distribution of sediment load.

Windblown sediment can be collected using traps, which may be placed horizontally (to measure total creep and saltation load) or vertically (to measure saltation and suspension load as a function of height). Vertical traps include mechanisms to rotate the traps into the wind.

Tillage erosion

The net downslope movement of soil resulting from tillage operations is defined as tillage erosion (Morgan, 2005). Tillage erosion is usually determined by measuring the displacement of tracers like numbered metal cubes (e.g. Quine, 2003) which are usually dug into the soil at different depths along transects. These tracers can be counted individually, but it is also possible to use large numbers of smaller tracers and determine their density (weight per volume of soil) instead of counting the individual tracers (e.g. Zhang et al., 2004). In both cases, it is important to recover as many tracers as possible, since tracers that are not accounted for have unknown displacement distance and might be

simply missed during recovery, but they might also have been transported far. Longer term rates of tillage erosion can be determined using tracing (see section on tracing). Fiener et al (2018) compared several techniques for determining tillage erosion rates (including micro-tracers, macro-tracers and laser scanning) in a case study in Germany. Van Oost et al (2009) used a modelling approach and found that mean tillage erosion rate is of the same order of magnitude as the water erosion rate.

Harvest erosion

The loss (or export) of topsoil from arable land during harvesting of crops such as potato, sugar beet, carrot or chicory roots, is defined as harvest erosion (Panagos et al., 2019). Harvest erosion can be measured by washing the harvested root and tuber crops and by weighing the sediment. Crop yield must be known to convert to erosion rates. Panagos et al (2019) analysed crop statistics of sugar beet and potato and found that about 65% of harvest erosion is caused by sugar beet harvesting. They also found that the mean harvest erosion rates for these crops were 5 t/ha per harvest for sugar beets and 2.25 t/ha per harvest for potatoes. This shows that harvest erosion rates can be of the same order of magnitude as water erosion rates. However, as sugar beets and potatoes are grown as part of a rotation, the long-term average rate will be significantly lower, and as sugar beets and potatoes together cover only about 3.8 % of the EU-28 arable land (Panagos et al 2019), the average harvest erosion rate at EU-scale is only 0.13 t/ha/year.

Tracer-based methods

Most of the measurement techniques discussed above are meant to measure current erosion rates. Using radioactive tracers, however, information can be obtained on longer term erosion rates. Several elements have been used for this purpose, the most widely used being ^{137}Cs . ^{137}Cs is a fission product of nuclear weapons tests and has accumulated in the topsoil due to atmospheric fallout, mainly in the 1950's and 60's (Loughran, 1989), but in parts of Europe also after the 1986 Tsernobyl accident. Since it is quickly and firmly adsorbed it is only translocated if sediment is moving. The principle is to determine ^{137}Cs contents in the soil and to compare those contents to that of sites that can be assumed to be undisturbed since the 1950's. Lower amounts than indicate erosion, while higher amounts indicate deposition. Since only the topsoil contains ^{137}Cs the technique is best suited to determine long term erosion rates for processes that erode the topsoil, such as sheet erosion, rill erosion and tillage erosion. Other elements like excess ^{210}Pb , ^{59}Fe , ^{46}Sc and ^7Be have also been used (e.g. Mabit et al 2009). The advantage of tracing with radioactive elements is that a single measurement is needed (contrary to constant monitoring with other methods), that a spatially distributed picture of erosion and deposition can be obtained and that sediment budgets for entire catchments may be developed. Some tracers with short half-lives might also be useful to study event erosion rates. Mabit et al (2009) used ^{137}Cs in a case study in Austria and that ^{137}Cs and runoff plots provide complementary information.

Discussion

The preceding sections have discussed a large number of measurement techniques that can be used to determine erosion. The techniques mentioned are, however, only a part of all techniques that have been developed. Each of them has advantages and disadvantages as well as points of strength and weaknesses. However, it is important using the most suitable in the specific situation and available data or possible measurements.

This review has made clear that all methods have their limitations, and that measurement schemes should be well thought out to ensure that the rates that are being measured are indeed representative for the process (and related scale) one intends to measure. It is inevitable that with technological advances new measurement techniques will also be developed. Although such advances in measuring are highly recommendable in view of what was said above, the consequence is that the erosion data

that have been collected over the years stem from many different techniques and scales. This can pose problems in comparing data sets with each other, since results depend both on technique used and on scale. To minimise such problems, standardised procedures and techniques should be used as much as possible (Garcia-Ruiz et al 2015). Besides, Garcia-Ruiz et al (2015) recommend a monitoring period of at least 20 years to obtain reliable erosion rates.

4.12.3 Measurement and monitoring of soil erosion with PS/RS techniques

In the scope of measuring and monitoring soil erosion, proximal (PS) and remote sensing (RS) techniques can be focused on quantifying:

1. soil erosion processes and their rates
2. soil and environmental factors playing a role (or affecting) in erosion processes.

Each is briefly discussed below.

Erosion processes

Several erosion processes occur at scales too small to be monitored by RS techniques directly. However, soil erosion can result in changes in colour, brightness and structure of the soil, which could be detected with RS (Lukyanchuk et al 2020). In addition, erosion processes operating at larger scale could be investigated directly with RS techniques. In fact, areal pictures have been used in the past to study rill and gully erosion, and possibilities to study rill and gully erosion have increased with the availability of RS images and derived products like Google Earth. For example, Stumvoll et al (2022) used UAS (unmanned aerial systems) to detect erosion features like rills in case studies in Austria. Other erosion processes that could potentially be studied with RS techniques include streambank/channel erosion as well as the location of deposited sediments.

Factors influencing erosion processes

Erosion rates are influenced by various factors that could be monitored with PS/RS. These include e.g., topography, soil properties, land use, plant cover (or presence of bare soil), moisture content and rainfall. Lab analyses of soil properties as well as field investigations of cover and moisture content (among many others) are time consuming and costly. Hence, the use of PS/RS techniques can save time and money, while RS might be the only source of information when the study areas are not accessible. The same is potentially true for rainfall. RS based rainfall data have the advantage that they give spatially distributed rainfall data, which is of high importance as rainfall is known to be highly variable in space, especially for the high intensity storms that are of crucial importance for soil erosion by water. However, RS based rainfall data are currently not yet reliable enough to replace traditional measurement of rainfall with rain gauges.

Some RS based approaches also combine the two categories above. For example, El Jazouli et al (2017) mapped soil erosion in a watershed in Morocco using spectral indices based on soil reflectance, such as form index (FI- a measure for presence/absence of iron oxide and organic matter thought to reflect degradation status), colour index (CI), brightness index (BI), and normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). Here, the first three indices provide information on the occurrence of soil erosion, while NDVI provides info on one of the factors that influence erosion.

4.12.4 Existing thresholds and target values for soil erosion

Because it is hardly possible to stop soil erosion completely, the concept of soil loss tolerance is used to define levels of soil erosion that are considered acceptable. Soil loss tolerance is than the maximum acceptable rate of soil loss, which is supposed to be equal to the natural rate of soil formation (Morgan,

1986). If soil loss remains below this threshold, soil management can be considered as sustainable with regard to erosion. However, natural rates of soil formation are variable and hard to measure. Several authors (see EEA 2023) consider a soil loss rate of more than 1 t/ha/yr irreversible (e.g. Verheijen et al 2009). Panagos et al (2020) used 2 t/ha/yr as threshold for sustainable soil loss, and 11 t/ha/yr as threshold for severe erosion. EEA (2023) considered 2 t/ha/yr a suitable threshold for shallow soils and 4 t/ha/yr for deep soils. The threshold of 2 t/ha/yr is also used in Annex 1 of the proposal for a Soil Monitoring Law and in the EUSO dashboard ([EU SOIL OBSERVATORY \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu/euso/)). As also discussed in EEA (2023), other authors consider 5-10 t/ha/yr as moderate erosion, and >10 t/ha/yr as severe erosion. Thus, the following classes can be defined:

0-2 t/ha/yr: Negligible soil erosion
2-5 t/ha/yr: Slight soil erosion
5-10 t/ha/yr: Moderate soil erosion
>10 t/ha/yr: Severe soil erosion

However, as EEA (2023) also noted the variability of soil type and climate in Europe should be taken into account to define soil erosion thresholds separately for different soil characteristics, land uses and climate zones.

The indicator soil loss rate can also be used to evaluate the sub-indicator area affected by a certain soil erosion rate if maps of soil erosion rate are available. Examples are provided in EEA (2023). These maps are usually made using modelling (see next section), though extrapolation of plot measurements has also been used (Cerdan et al 2010).

It should be realised that the parameters and the scale used in erosion modelling have a significant effect on the absolute value of the modelled soil erosion. Therefore, a threshold can only be used in combination with fixed parameters for models (e.g. RUSLE) and a fixed scale.

4.12.5 Soil erosion modelling

Introduction

As a fundamental premise, it must be stated that any model that describes and/or quantifies erosion is a simplification of reality (e.g. Epple et al 2022), generally based on a small number of locations/conditions, so that its applicability to other locations or conditions is not guaranteed. Hence, modelling can never be a substitute for measuring. However, as detailed field observations are often very expensive, must be carried out over many years (preferably ten or more), and direct measurements have their own issues regarding accuracy and representativeness, erosion modelling is often the most feasible way to quantify erosion rates. Besides, many problems of erosion control and mitigation must be addressed immediately and it is not possible to wait for years until monitoring results become available. The value of existing erosion models is that they can be applied straight away by choosing the one best suited to the case at hand in terms of complexity or simplification, as well as their ability to estimate the impact of different scenarios (e.g. climatic changes, land use changes, implementation of erosion control measures,...) on the erosion rate in a catchment. The starting point of modelling should be a clear statement of objective (Morgan & Quinton, 2001).

The models developed for simulating soil erosion range from simple empirical models to very complicated process based models (e.g., Borelli et al. 2021, Epple et al 2022). Process based models apply as much process-knowledge as is available and use general laws or principles such as

conservation of mass (continuity), Newton's second law of motion (momentum) and the first law of thermodynamics (energy) (Doe & Harmon, 2001). Process-based models may, in principle, be used for conditions outside those tested since the laws on which they are based must be obeyed in all circumstances. Empirical models, on the other hand, do not necessarily model the right process and can only be used for the range of conditions for which they were developed. Which type of model is most suited to any particular situation depends e.g. on what the purpose of modelling is, on time and funds that are available, availability of data and scale. As process based models are more complex, they generally need more input data, which makes them more suitable for smaller spatial scales. Complex process based models do not always give better predictions than simple models (e.g. Alewell et al 2019) for several reasons: 1) Not all processes of soil erosion are sufficiently understood, so that the model structure might be flawed and empirical components are still used. 2) The more complex the model the more input data is required. Since input parameters are often difficult to determine accurately, uncertainty regarding the model input will increase with model complexity (Brazier et al., 2000, Jetten et al., 2003). Favis-Mortlock et al. (2001) showed that for more complex models error propagation becomes more important too. 3) Often, there are no unique input parameter sets, so that different input parameter sets can result in equally good predictions. This is called equifinality. On the other hand, process based models are the only type of model that can help us to better understand the processes that are operating. Besides, if physical processes are correctly incorporated in the model this would increase the reliability of predictions regarding the effects of management and landscape change (Brazier et al., 2000). Finally, though process based models might not give better predictions than empirical models they do give additional information, e.g. regarding the spatial and temporal distribution of erosion (Morgan & Quinton, 2001).

Erosion models can also be subdivided in those that simulate erosion for single events/storms and those that simulate erosion for longer time periods (continuous models). The first type depends on accurate data about model parameters at the start of an event (the initial conditions), while the latter models these parameters in between events. Thus, what happens in between events is not relevant for event based models, as long as the initial conditions for the next event are correctly specified, but should be modelled by models operating on longer time scales. Processes that should be dealt with in continuous models include plant growth, evapotranspiration, percolation and the seasonal change of soil properties. Therefore, continuous models need to simulate additional processes, for which additional data may be required.

Scale issues play a role in soil erosion modelling in several ways. First, it is possible that at different spatial scales different processes are operating, or that they are operating in different ways. For any particular study, a model should therefore be chosen that is relevant to the scale of the problem being studied. Generally, a finer time and space resolution requires more detailed process knowledge, so that modelling at catchment scale is inevitably a compromise between detailed process understanding and reasonable computation times (Kirkby, 1998). At the same time, however, additional processes might appear at larger scales. Gully erosion, for example, does not operate at plot scale, but only on hillslope or catchment scale. Similarly, opportunities for deposition increase with an increase in scale. Secondly, models usually require the use of effective parameter values that are representative values for the spatial units of the model. In most cases, the values of effective parameters are scale dependent. Another problem is that measurement scale of these parameters is often different from model scale. Most measurements of soil characteristics, for example, are point based (King et al, 1998), and might therefore not be representative for the larger model units. Finally, the way in which the actual landscape is represented in the model can also influence the model results. For grid-based models, for example, the results depend on grid size (Bruneau et al., 1995; Doe & Harmon, 2001; Schoorl et al., 2000; Jetten et al., 2002; Hessel 2005).

When considering thresholds for erosion, this scale dependency should be kept in mind, as modelled values will significantly vary with different model resolution. As shown by Callewaert (2023) for the Flanders region, due to the change in resolution of the used dataset, as well as the resolution of the model and the final resolution of the erosion map, a significant difference in erosion rates can be noted. This is especially the case in hilly landscapes such as the southern part of Flanders, where high variability in erosion rates is caused by the heterogeneous topography. In these parts, by broadening the scale, the topography will be averaged out, leading to lower modelled erosion rates and thus seemingly smaller gravity of erosion problems in these regions (Callewaert, 2023). This is less the case for lowland or highland regions, where the topography is often less heterogeneous and drastic changes in environmental factors only occur at bigger scales than used model resolution. Furthermore, not only topography is affected by upscaling datasets, some models prioritise some types of land uses (e.g., infrastructure, waterways, grass strips), which at coarse resolution will overestimate the importance of these features in the landscape and thereby change the modelled erosion in a catchment. Callewaert (2023) recommends to model erosion at the highest feasible resolution and upscale the maps as late as possible in the process in order to better conserve erosion patterns.

Water erosion models

This section will briefly discuss some of the present day water erosion models that have been used for applications at EU scale. The actual number of water erosion models is much larger (see e.g. Jetten et al, 1999; Morgan & Quinton, 2001; Batista et al 2019; Borelli et al 2021).

(R)USLE

The Universal Soil Loss Equation (Wischmeier & Smith, 1978) is an empirical equation developed for the United States. It is based on a large number of Wischmeier plot measurements and predicts average annual erosion for plots or fields. Since the plot scale is not the appropriate scale to study gully erosion the model is not capable of simulating gully erosion, and deposition is also not modelled (e.g. Alewell et al 2019; Borelli et al 2021). The basic equation is a simple multiplication of a number of factors, namely:

$$A = R \times K \times LS \times C \times P$$

where A (Mg or t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) is the annual average soil loss, R (MJ mm ha⁻¹ h⁻¹ yr⁻¹) is the rainfall-runoff erosivity factor, K (Mg or t ha h ha⁻¹ MJ⁻¹ mm⁻¹) is the soil erodibility factor, LS (dimensionless) is the slope length and slope steepness factor, C (dimensionless) is the cover-management factor and P (dimensionless) is the support practices factor.

The individual factors can, however, be calculated in complex ways (e.g. Haan et al 1994, Panagos et al 2015, Benavidez et al 2018, Alewell et al 2019), especially in the revised version (RUSLE, Renard et al., 1997). The USLE has later been adapted to other areas than USA as well and is currently the most widely used erosion model globally (Borelli et al 2021). The RUSLE model has been applied at European scale by Panagos et al (2015a, 2022) and the different factors of the equation have been elaborated in European context (Panagos et al 2015b-e).

RUSLE is also used in the spatially distributed soil erosion and sediment delivery model WaTEM/SEDEM. This model consists of the aggregation of WaTEM (Van Oost et al. 2000), calculating soil erosion by means of the RUSLE, and SEDEM (Van Rompaey et al. 2001), simulating sediment transport to rivers (Verstraeten et al. 2002). Sediment deposition processes are taken into account by means of the sediment transport capacity (TC) of each grid cell. With the WaTEM/SEDEM model a

distinction can be made between gross erosion and net erosion (Verstraeten et al., 2007). Net erosion is calculated by subtracting for each grid cell the deposition rates from the gross erosion rates calculated by the RUSLE. WaTEM/SEDEM has been applied at European scale by Borrelli et al. (2018) They concluded that large-scale net soil loss and deposition modelling connected to sediment transfer and fluxes is crucial to assess holistically the impact of erosion induced soil degradation across landscapes. For application at European scale, the study highlighted the need to further improve the calibration scheme of the model transport parameter and to improve the European database of sediment yield measurements.

PESERA

PESERA (Pan-European Soil Erosion Risk Assessment, Kirkby et al 2008) is a process based, spatially distributed model that combines the effect of topography, climate and soil properties to simulate soil erosion. It simulates (bio)physical processes like above-ground biomass production, soil erosion risk, and soil water deficit, using a monthly time-step. It is more process based than RUSLE, but to allow application to large areas it is not as complex as process based models like WEPP (Flanagan et al 2001), Eurosem (Morgan et al 1998) and LISEM (De Roo et al 1996, Jetten & De Roo 2001). Due to these simplifications, a grid size of at least 100 m is recommended. Nevertheless, the model is based on up-scaling and simplification of principles that have been widely accepted and validated at finer scales (Kirkby et al 2008). PESERA was applied at EU scale by a.o. Kirkby et al (2008) and Baartman et al (2022).

MESALES

The MESALES (Modèle d'Evaluation Spatiale de l'ALéa Erosion des Sols — Regional Modelling of Soil Erosion Risk) method is based on expert knowledge and available data and was described by Le Bissonnais et al. (2002), Grimm et al. (2002) and Hessel et al (2014). The method considers soil erosion by overland flow. Land cover and crust formation on cultivated soils are considered important factors that influence runoff and erosion. The model provides a qualitative assessment of soil erosion sensitivity or risk in 5 classes: very low, low, moderate, high and very high. Expert knowledge is only used to set up a decision tree with rules for calculation of erosion sensitivity/risk, after which a modelling approach is used to assign erosion classes to the mapping units. The decision tree uses 4 parameters (land use, crusting, slope angle, and erodibility) to determine sensitivity to soil erosion. The parameters are used in this order to give priority to factors that can be influenced by humans (Le Bissonnais et al., 2002).

Discussion

Until now no water erosion model can model gully erosion accurately. At the moment, none of these models can model for example mass movements on gully walls or headcut retreat (Poesen et al., 1998). The more recent soil erosion models do, however, perform some sort of rill erosion calculation. It is, however, generally necessary to specify beforehand where the rills or gullies will develop. It seems likely that the trend towards incorporating gully erosion into erosion modelling will continue as field measurements have shown how important gully erosion can be. Gully erosion simulation is complicated by the fact that gully development is a process that operates on several timescales, with different formation processes and spatio-temporal development (Borelli et al 2022). Mass movements on gully walls, for example, generally do not occur on event basis, but might depend on the slow redistribution of water and the slow development on cracks.

It should also be realised that most soil erosion models, at least the process based ones, only simulate suspended load and can therefore underestimate erosion if bedload is important. Similarly, not all erosion models simulate deposition or routing of sediment.

Validation of erosion model results with observations is crucial (Batista et al, 2019), as only with sufficient good quality measurement data is it possible to assess if model predictions make sense. Validation is usually done with observations made at the outlet of the modelled area, but for distributed models the predicted erosion patterns should be evaluated too. Several studies have shown that even if model results at the outlet are simulated well, erosion patterns may not be simulated correctly (Hessel et al., 2006; Jetten et al., 2003; Takken et al., 1999; Vigiak et al., 2005). Often, calibration is needed to improve the performance of erosion models, also for process based models.

Improved quality and resolution of grid based Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and satellite imagery provide a valuable source of information for soil erosion monitoring (e.g. gullies) and modelling (e.g. Epple et al 2022). For example, the DEM can be used to create a map of flow direction, and upstream area can be used as threshold to model concentrated flow erosion. Nevertheless, flow direction is not only determined by slope but also by tillage direction and linear features such as field boundaries (e.g. Ludwig et al., 1996; Takken et al., 1999 and Van Dijck, 2000). Ludwig et al (1996), for example, assume that water is more likely to follow the slope on steeper slopes and more likely to follow the tillage direction on gentle slopes.

Soil erosion modelling has several applications. The most obvious one is prediction of erosion for future rainfall events. However, such prediction remains problematical and 'predictions' are usually much better for past events than for future ones. This is less of a problem with continuous models. A second major application is to simulate the effect of different scenarios concerning e.g. land use, climate change or soil and water conservation measures.

Wind erosion modelling

Development of wind erosion models has not been as prolific as that of water erosion models, though multiple models exist (e.g. Jarrah et al, 2020). The first model to appear was WEQ (Wind Erosion Equation) (Woodruff & Siddoway, 1965). It has similarities to the USLE in that it too calculates erosion as a function of a number of factors that are supposed to influence erosion. In the case of WEQ those factors are: soil erodibility, soil roughness, climate, field length and vegetation cover (Jarrah et al 2020). Unlike USLE, erosion cannot be calculated as a multiplication of these factors because several of the factors interact. Van Pelt & Zobeck (2002) found that WEQ generally underpredicted wind erosion by about 50% for discrete periods of several months. However, predictions were much improved after calibration for local conditions.

RWEQ (Revised Wind Erosion Equation) is an empirical model that makes annual or period estimates of wind erosion and based on a single event wind erosion model (Zobeck et al., 2001). Like WEQ it uses a number of factors: wind, erodibility, surface crust, roughness and ground cover. Zobeck et al. (2001) validated RWEQ for single events and found that RWEQ has the tendency to underestimate transport capacity and soil loss and to overestimate critical field length. However, significant relationships were found between observed and predicted transport capacity and soil loss, showing the potential of RWEQ. RWEQ has been used to determine if residue left on the field is enough to provide sufficient protection, or if additional measures are necessary (Fryrear & Bilbro, 1998). Borelli et al (2017) developed a simplified GIS version of the model called GIS-RWEQ and applied it at European scale. Scheper et al (2021) applied the RWEQ model to a 2319 km² area in Lower Austria.

Another wind erosion model is WEPS (Wind Erosion Prediction System), which is more process based than RWEQ and therefore requires additional input parameters. WEPS uses a daily timestep and operates on field scale (Wagner & Tatarko, 2001). Weather generators are used to calculate the daily

weather, which drives the processes in WEPS, but measured weather data can also be used (Jarrah et al 2020). WEPS was developed independently of WEPP, but some commonality between these models is being sought (Fox et al., 2001). To the best of our knowledge, WEPS has not been applied at large scale in Europe.

Tillage erosion modelling

In the last two decades a considerable number of tillage erosion models has been developed. Most model tillage erosion as a diffusive process using a tillage transport coefficient. WATEM (Water and Tillage Erosion Model) is a spatially distributed model that simulates erosion and deposition by water and tillage processes. The water component of the model uses an adapted version of RUSLE. For tillage erosion a diffusion-type equation is used. SPEROS (Soil Properties and EROsion model, Van Oost et al., 2000) simulates tillage erosion and deposition rates and also allows a much more refined interpretation of 137Cs inventory data (Govers et al., 2003). However, it still depends on empirical relationships between tillage translocation and tillage implement specific properties. Van Oost et al. (2003) used a different approach and modelled tillage erosion with a 2D convolution model which combines a probability distribution of tillage displacement for different tillage implements with a spatial distribution function of soil constituents. However, the convolution model also depends on empirical data to define the probability distribution of tillage displacement. To overcome such dependency, Torri & Borselli (2002) used a more fundamental approach in their SETi (Soil Erosion by Tillage model) model, which is based on fundamental principles of clod movement and therefore theoretically has a wider application range than the other models. SETi might for example be used to design new tillage implements and to determine values of the tillage transport coefficient for untested tillage implements (Torri & Borselli, 2002). At present, however, SETi can only simulate single cells (Torri & Borselli, 2002). On the other hand, as Van Oost et al. (2003) state, complex physical descriptions as those in SETi are less suitable to model the spatial and temporal evolution of soil properties in an agricultural field. To model such spatial redistribution at field scale it is not necessary to model the displacement of individual clods. This shows that, like for water erosion, different models serve different aims and should be seen as complementary to each other.

4.12.6 Effects of scale (time/space) on changes of soil erosion

Different erosion processes operate at different scales, and therefore different methods should be used to determine erosion rates at different scales (e.g. Boix-Fayos et al 2006). At the smallest scale, the impact of raindrops causes detachment of soil particles, but as progressively larger areas are considered other erosion processes become more prominent, with e.g. rill erosion at field/slope scale, gully erosion at small catchment scale and riverbank erosion in river basins. As the area that is considered increases in size, deposition of eroded material also becomes more prominent, so that generally with increasing scale the sediment delivery ratio decreases, as does observed erosion rate (Batista et al 2015). Soil erosion modelling should therefore also take scale into account.

There can also be scale-effects in the modelling of erosion itself, as discussed in section 4.12.5. For example, results of soil erosion models may depend on the pixel size and time step length that was used, as e.g. shown by Bruneau et al. (1995); Doe & Harmon (2001); Hessel (2005; Schoorl et al., 2000; Jetten et al., 2002. Besides, the chosen pixel size and time step should be consistent with the erosion processes that are being modelled.

4.12.7 Recommendations for monitoring soil erosion changes

- As soil erosion rate is related to weather parameters and can be determined to a large extent by a few extreme events long term monitoring is needed to obtain accurate average erosion rates.
- As there are several erosion processes that can vary in importance for different parts of Europe (see e.g. EEA 2023) and at different scales, monitoring should be context specific by addressing the right processes and the right scale. Processes like wind erosion, tillage erosion or harvest erosion can be as important as water erosion. Thus an understanding of processes and driving factors in the local context is required.
- One of the main aims of soil erosion monitoring is to monitor the effects that different management practices have on soil erosion, as this provides information on how soil erosion rates could be reduced. Hence, there should be a focus on monitoring these effects. This is, however, complicated by the fact that before-after studies are influenced by weather conditions, while in paired studies soil management may not be the only factor that is different between plots. Hence, ways should be sought to deal with such uncertainties.
- As already recommended by others (e.g. Van Camp et al 2004, Faber et al 2021) a tiered approach can be used for soil erosion monitoring. At the first tier (EU scale) modelling and/or satellite imagery could be used to identify potential problem areas, which could then be investigated in more detail in lower tiers.
- Different methods to determine erosion rates give different results (e.g. Garcia-Ruiz et al 2015); therefore, standardisation of methods and reporting is necessary to allow comparison. However, flexibility should also remain to take full account of local context.
- We consider that soil erosion rate is a good indicator for soil erosion in Europe, and that a threshold of 2 t/ha/yr is a useful first approximation to judge severity of soil erosion. However, as mentioned before locally relevant erosion processes and conditions need to be taken into account.

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5. Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the previous chapters main recommendations from EJP SOIL partners are grouped in table 5.1. and summarized hereafter.

Soil Monitoring

As shown in table 5.1, there is reasonable agreement between our review and the indicators proposed by the Soil Monitoring Law, and also the EUSO soil dashboard and EEA (2023), with the exception of the soil sealing subindicators regarding land take (see chapter 4.11.1) and the AWC indicator, for which the SML focusses on the storage function considering WHC and does not consider the water availability for plants. We also recommend that other hydraulic soil properties are monitored as well, such as infiltration rate and permeability which are more affected by soil management practices. Though there is generally agreement between our review and SML, there are differences in the thresholds that are proposed. Generally, our review shows that more flexibility is needed in thresholds to take sufficient account of local conditions (see also previous point). Another aspect of monitoring is frequency. Several chapters (SOC, contamination) indicated that the 5 year monitoring frequency that is proposed by the SML is too short to expect significant changes. For a number of parameters/indicators, not only frequency should be considered, but also the time of the year, as for example ECEC, pH, EC, biodiversity and biological activity show seasonal fluctuation. Furthermore, for several parameters the sampling should also consider the last management practice before sampling (e.g. avoid sampling for biodiversity after soil tillage or for pesticides just after a treatment). This means that not only information on land use but on management of the monitoring sites should be collected.

Finally, from the analysis of the different soil indicators, is clear that it will be arduous to define soil districts, as required by the Soil Monitoring Law, which could satisfy the monitoring requirements of all the soil indicators. For example, it is possible to define at least 4 main groups of indicators: 1) indicators linked to chemical/physical properties of soils; 2) indicators linked to hydraulic properties, therefore linked to a management a watershed level; 3) indicators defined by the loss of available soil surface (sealing); 4) soil contamination. Each of these groups may have different monitoring requirements and/or may require different stratification and thus soil districts defined in different ways.

Soil depth and scale

The Soil Monitoring Law recommends measuring the different soil parameters/soil indicators only on topsoil, with the exception of soil compaction (where measurements on the B horizon are requested). However, we suggest for soil organic carbon, phosphorus, available water capacity, trace elements and biodiversity to consider not only topsoil (e.g. 0-30 cm) but also deeper soil layers as this will provide information on the nature of soils and their capacity to fulfill several ecosystem services like storing carbon and water or hosting biodiversity. Such knowledge on different soil layers can also be used to distinguish contaminated areas from areas that are naturally rich in some elements.

Table 5. 1 Main recommendations.

	Indicator(s)	Threshold/limit value(s)	Frequency	Period to sample/measure (season, crop cycle, status of the soil)	Type of sampling	Top soil only?	Measurements methods	Estimated costs/sample (sampling not included)
SOC	SOC:Clay Proposed in SML. Not in EUSO dashboard	To adapt to agro-pedo-climatic conditions. Written in the SML but without defining how. The reference to grasslands in SML may be misleading or too ambitious.	about 10 y vs 5 y for SML	Avoid recent OC incorporation to soil	several cores within a plot. Agreement	Agreement with SML	dry combustion: ISO 10694:1995. Particle-size analysis: ISO 13320:2009. Agreement with SML	10 to 30€ sample if SOC only 50 to 80€ if SOC and particle-size analysis
	SOC/SOCexp Not proposed in SML neither EUSO dashboard	To adapt to pedo-climatic conditions	about 10 y	Avoid recent OC incorporation to soil	several cores within a plot.	No. Not defined in SML	dry combustion: ISO 10694:1995. Particle-size analysis: ISO 13320:2009. + regression or statistics at the scale of pedo-climatic conditions	
	SOC/SOCmax Not proposed in SML, Proposed by the EUSO dashboard	To adapt to pedo-climatic conditions	about 10 y	Avoid recent OC incorporation to soil	several cores within a plot.	No. Not defined in SML	dry combustion: ISO 10694:1995. Particle-size analysis: ISO 13320:2009. + statistics at the scale of pedo-climatic conditions	
	SOC content Proposed in SML	No decrease. Target increase to adapt to agro-pedo-climatic conditions. Target unclear in SML.	about 10 y vs 5 y for SML	Avoid recent OC incorporation to soil	several cores within a plot. Fixed depths or horizon-based depths down to 1 m.	no for EJPSoil recommendations, yes for SML	dry combustion: ISO 10694:1995. Agreement with SML. Particle-size analysis: ISO 13320:2009 may be necessary to fix target/threshold values. Not included in SML.	
	SOC Stock Not proposed in SML	No decrease. Objective of increase to adapt to pedo-climatic conditions	about 10 y	Avoid recent OC incorporation to soil; avoid recent tillage	several undisturbed cores. Fixed depths or horizon based depths down to 1 m	No	dry combustion: ISO 10694:1995. Dry Bulk density: ISO 11272: 2017 + coarse fragments	

	Indicator(s)	Threshold/limit value(s)	Frequency	Period to sample/measure (season, crop cycle, status of the soil)	Type of sampling	Top soil only?	Measurements methods	Estimated costs/sample (sampling not included)
Nutrients	total N included in the SML	No recommended threshold, but monitor changes; Same in SML	10 y; 5 y in SML	Same as for SOC content.	Composit sample made up of several cores from one plot	yes; Same in SML	Kjeldahl or Dumas dry combustion; Kjeldahl in SML	10 to 25€ (80 as an extreme) by sample
	available P Extractable P in the SML	Locally (region, country) adopted thresholds; Similar as SML, but SML suggest an upper threshold within the range of 30-50 mg kg ⁻¹	5-10 y; 5 y in SML	Avoid period directly following fertilisation. Autumn is usually a good time.	Composit sample made up of several cores from one plot	yes; Same in SML	Olsen extractable P or ISO 11263:1994; Same in SML	Very often together with other nutrients. A range of extraction methods. 10-40 Euro
	P storage	No P threshold suggested for risk of leaching, but important knowledge possibly in combination with models to establish critical source areas for losses and direct mitigation efforts; Not included in SML	10 y	Same as for the Olsen extractable P	Composit sample made up of several cores from one plot	no, subsoil is also important	preferred: ammonium oxalate extraction, option 2: P-AL	Not specified, but supposedly 10-80 Euro as for total macro nutrients
CEC/Exc Bases	ESP Not included in the SML	for ESP 5 and 15%	ESP >15: 10y ESP 5-15: 5y	Summer or early autumn, dry period	Bulk sample	No. Not defined in SML	CEC: 1 M NH ₄ OAc buffered at pH 7 (GLOSOLAN-SOP-17; FAO, 2022); Exchangeable Al: unbuffered 1 M KCl solution	20-60€

Indicator(s)		Threshold/limit value(s)	Frequency	Period to sample/measure (season, crop cycle, status of the soil)	Type of sampling	Top soil only?	Measurements methods	Estimated costs/sample (sampling not included)
pH	pH in water 1:5 soil:water mixture Soil acidity as generically mentioned pH in the SML	4.5-4.8, 5.5	5 y	Sensitive to season	several cores within a plot	yes		10-30€
Electrical conduct	ECe Included in the SML	4 dS/m		Summer or early autumn, dry period	Bulk sample	No	saturated soil paste extract (eEC) measurement method (or: other soil extracts; 1:n mix; and calculate transfer) = soil:water mix)	5-15€
AWC	WHC is proposed in the SML. We suggest , other indicators: waterflow at the outlet of river basins in relation to rainfall intensity, soil water infiltration rate and permeability, soil structure stability	Thresholds have no sense for AWC. Good drainage with Permeability between 2 to 6 cm/hour (FAO online)	10 y	Any time	Field measurement	no	ISO 11274:2019	13-65 €/sample AWC

Indicator(s)		Threshold/limit value(s)	Frequency	Period to sample/measure (season, crop cycle, status of the soil)	Type of sampling	Top soil only?	Measurements methods	Estimated costs/sample (sampling not included)
Biodiversity	Soil respiration Included in the SML	No recommended threshold, but monitor changes	5 y	Spring and autumn are generally good. Avoid sampling/measurements after soil treatment.	Composite sample made up of several cores from one plot	no, if possible subsoil is also important	ISO 16072:2002	20-30€
	Microbial biomass Included as optional in the SML						ISO 14249-1:1997; ISO 14249-2:1997	20-30€
	Enzyme activity Not included in the SML						ISO 20130:2018; ISO/TS 22939:2019	20-80€ for each enzyme
	Microbial communities (Bacteria, Archaea, Fungi, Protists, Animals) Included as optional in the SML						DNA metabarcoding	75-100€ for each target group
	Microfauna (Nematodes) Included as optional in the SML				ISO 23611-4:2006	30-40€		
	Macrofauna (earthworms) Included as optional in the SML				Sampling on site	ISO 23611-1:2018	30-140€	
	Mesofauna Not included in the SML				3 cores (10x10x10cm) from each plot	yes	ISO 23611-2:2006; QBS-ar method (Parisi et al., 2005)	75-140€

Indicator(s)	Threshold/limit value(s)	Frequency	Period to sample/measure (season, crop cycle, status of the soil)	Type of sampling	Top soil only?	Measurements methods	Estimated costs/sample (sampling not included)	
Contamination	Traces Elements included in SML	No general agreement across EU countries. EUSO dashboard proposed 3 threshold values for Cu (> 50 mg kg ⁻¹), Zn (> 65 mg kg ⁻¹) and Hg (> 200 µg kg ⁻¹) that may not be convenient for all countries. A common methodology should be defined, e.g. based on the national background.	SML asks for a monitoring every 5 years whereas modelling studies predict no detectable change before at least 10 years.	Whole year is the soil can be sampled!	Generally several cores are taken and mixed.	Top soil is generally sampled but sampling the subsoil will help to identify if there is a pollution.	Several are implemented in EU countries, based on ISO methods. Comparisons should be made.	Around 80 € for a set of trace elements (e.g. Cd, Cr, Zn, Pb...). Determination of As and Hg may not be included (20 to 50 € more)
	Selected organics - Common methodology for selection Included in the SML	Common methodology to be defined taking into account background values and risks for several organic contaminants.	SML asks for a monitoring every 5 years whereas modelling studies predict no detectable change before at least 10 years.	Whole year is the soil can be sampled!	Generally several cores are taken and mixed.	Top soil is generally sampled as organic contaminants tend to accumulate at the surface. Sometimes to increase the detection limit of the methods, 0-5 and 0-10 cm may be preferred. As not yet fully implemented at EU scale a common method should be defined.	Several are implemented in EU countries, based on ISO methods. Comparisons should be made.	Depends on the group of organics to be determined as PAHS (100-250 €), PCB (100-250 €), organo chlorinated pesticides (100-250 €), other pesticides (depends on the number to be determined, may cost between 500-1000 €)

Indicator(s)		Threshold/limit value(s)	Frequency	Period to sample/measure (season, crop cycle, status of the soil)	Type of sampling	Top soil only?	Measurements methods	Estimated costs/sample (sampling not included)
Soil structure	Dry bulk density	On sandy soil BD lower than 1.80, on silty soil- lower than 1.65, on clayey soil lower than 1.47 g/cm ³ .	According to need of the experiment. Normally twice per year is sufficient (in spring and in autumn)	whole year, if soil moisture content for core sampling is suitable	Taking undisturbed soil cores, measuring dry weight, lab based	In subsoil (upper part of B or E horizon)	ISO 11272:2017	It depends on travelling distance, number of samples, number of technicians involved. Price starts from about 9 € per sample.
	Included in the SML							
Sealing	Soil sealing expressed as a percentage of sealed area per total area	No threshold/limit value	We recommend 1 to 3 years	All year based on satellite data or airborne data.	No sampling	Not relevant	The methodologies chosen shall either be available in the scientific literature or publicly available. Increase the spatial resolution of existing open (satellite) data and/or support very high-resolution airborne data in order to be able to derive from them soil sealing indicators with a sufficient high resolution.	Costs are variable as depending on the method used, resolution needed and the area of the region.
	Included in the SML							

Indicator(s)		Threshold/limit value(s)	Frequency	Period to sample/measure (season, crop cycle, status of the soil)	Type of sampling	Top soil only?	Measurements methods	Estimated costs/sample (sampling not included)
Erosion	Soil loss rate	0-2 t/ha/yr: Negligible soil erosion; 2-5 t/ha/yr: Slight soil erosion; 5-10 t/ha/yr: Moderate soil erosion; >10 t/ha/yr: Severe soil erosion	total amount per year	whole year, especially if cover is low & after heavy rainfall	no sampling unless density needs to be determined	Topsoil for splash erosion and rill erosion, but other types of erosion may involve subsoil too	Depends on erosion process and on scale	Field studies are very labour intensive and thus expensive
	Included in the SML							

In addition, there are also differences in the scale at which monitoring should be performed, as can be seen in Table 5.2. For most parameters this is the site/field scale, but AWC and erosion can better be monitored at river basin scale, while sealing is also usually evaluated at larger scale (national or regional). These differences in scale reflect the different processes that are relevant. However, the methodology that is chosen will also have an effect on the scale of monitoring. Classical soil sampling methods are site/field based, while for example RS and modelling consider larger areas.

Use of RS/PS

All chapters have shown that RS/PS can be used at least to some extent for estimating included parameters. For some parameters/indicators extensive use of such techniques is fairly well developed for estimations and mapping at field scale (e.g. SOC, EC, texture). For implementation in large scale monitoring system for detecting changes, accuracy need to be evaluated, to determine if the detected changes in time of the soil parameters are significant, given the error of PS/RS estimations, and difficulties in developing general prediction models over large areas. For several other parameters the technology is now still in its infancy. Given the continuous development of RS/PS techniques, and the advantages they have over labour-intensive field campaigns and laboratory analyses, the use of RS/PS in monitoring soil indicators is bound to further increase in the future. Nevertheless, the traditional methods will remain necessary for training, ground-truthing, and for a number of indicators RS/PS will not be suitable. Using RS for estimations of soil properties also requires bare soils under conditions that are similar and favourable for remote data collection. It should be recognised that the RS techniques only gives information on the surface layer. For PS this problem is less pronounced.

Threshold setting

Most chapters have shown that setting figures for reference values, thresholds and target values is not easy, as such they should depend on the local context (e.g. soil type, land use, climate, management, degradation processes). Hence, our results confirm what was written about setting thresholds by e.g. Faber et al (2022) and EEA (2023). Different parameters/indicators might also need to be stratified in different ways. As Matson et al (2023) show, depending on context and data availability, there are several approaches for setting thresholds, ranging from using fixed values from literature for certain spatial units (i.e. soil districts), to comparison with natural conditions as reference, or defining values based on the distribution within the population in a stratified unit, or even to (percentual) changes occurring over time. Which approach is most suitable depends for example on data availability, but also on which condition or situation that can be considered as reference. Although it is beyond the scope of the present document to discuss this in detail, it should be realised that this complexity may need to have implications for monitoring too. For example, different indicators may require different sampling schemes, or the local context may influence what can be considered an area that is homogeneous enough to assume that the threshold for a certain indicator is constant within that area.

Modelling

Similar to RS/PS, at least some modelling is done for all parameters/indicators, but with variations in the degree to which modelling is currently used for monitoring. For some soil threats (e.g. erosion) modelling is already the most commonly used method for monitoring, although ground-truth data should be still used for validation, while for others modelling is used less and/or does not directly address the soil threat. For example, the focus of nutrient modelling is on loss to the environment rather than on changes in the soil itself, and the focus on pH modelling is on acid soils rather than agricultural soils. It should, like for RS/PS, be realised that field and lab studies will remain needed, e.g. to provide input data for models and/or data to validate and calibrate models.

Costs and prioritization

Cost information that has been collected for this deliverable shows a range for most indicators. Main reasons are 1) that prices may differ between countries, and 2) that pricing of commercial lab is different from that of research labs. Nevertheless, for most indicators, the range that was found

provides a good indication of the costs involved. Using the data we collected we estimate that to assess all relevant indicators would cost between euro 1,000 to 2,500 per location for the complete set of indicators (including organic contaminants and soil biodiversity measurements). To decrease costs, prioritization of some indicators over others is possible, but no general rules on prioritization can be given as the importance of different indicators will differ between MS. Nevertheless, a short list of common indicators (i.e. tier 1 indicators) would allow to pinpoint which parameters/indicators should be evaluated in more detail in specific MS. Besides, such a common list would also allow for at least some comparison between MS.

Table 5.2 provides an alternative short-list of indicators that could be monitored in all MS. This table is a summary of information provided in Table 5.1, focussing on the frequency of monitoring. Apart from prioritization of some indicators over others, another option to reduce monitoring costs would be to reconsider the 5-year frequency proposed by the Soil Monitoring Law. As most soil indicators may not change that quickly due to soil management, we recommend not to measure all parameters every 5 years. As Table 5.2 shows a 10 y frequency would be sufficient for a number of indicators, although there are also indicators that should be determined more often (as proposed by SML). From a scientific point of view some indicators as those monitoring soil biodiversity or soil structure may vary more quickly and may ideally require even several measurements per year but from a practical point of view they should be measured at each monitoring campaigns. For indicators for which a frequency of once every 10 years is sufficient, measurements could be alternated (e.g. for contamination, measure trace elements during the 1st campaign, then organic contaminants during the second campaign, and trace elements again during the 3rd campaign).

Table 5. 2 Potential indicators for common set of soil parameters.

Soil parameters	Soil Quality Indicator	Frequency	Depth and scale
SOC	SOC:Clay	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	SOC/SOCexp	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	SOC/SOCmax	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	SOC content	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	SOC Stock	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
Nutrients	total N	10 y	Topsoil/Field
	available P	5-10 y	Topsoil/Field
	P storage	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
CEC/ECEC/Exc Bases	ESP	ESP >15: 10y ESP 5-15: 5y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
pH	pH in water 1:5 soil:water mixture	5 y	Topsoil/Field
Electrical conductivity	ECe	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
AWC	waterflow at the outlet of river basins in relation to rainfall intensity	10 y	Basin

	soil water infiltration rate and permeability	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	soil structure stability	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
Biodiversity	Soil respiration	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	Microbial biomass	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	Enzyme activity	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	Microbial communities (Bacteria, Archaea, Fungi, Protists, Animals)	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	Microfauna (Nematodes)	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	Macrofauna (earthworms)	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	Mesofauna	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
Contamination	Trace Elements	10 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
	Selected organics - Common methodology for selection	10 y	Topsoil/Field 0-5 and 0-10 cm may be preferred.
Soil structure	Dry bulk density	5 y	Topsoil and subsoil /Field
Sealing	Soil sealing expressed as % of sealed area per total area	1-3 y	Not relevant
Erosion	Soil loss rate	Calculation per year	Depends on erosion process

Annex 1: Examples of earlier work on indicators

This annex provides examples of earlier work on soil indicators and soil indicator framework, without attempting to review all existing indicator frameworks. A distinction is made between 1) EJP-SOIL projects, 2) Literature and 3) other projects.

A1: EJP SOIL projects

SERENA

Introduction

SERENA is working on evaluation methods (cookbooks) for assessing soil threats and soil based ecosystems (SES) at different scales (local-EU), with specific attention to bundles of soil threats and SES. The project contains several reviews of indicators, and also builds on results of the SIREN project and other EJP SOIL work. The project develops harmonized methodologies to evaluate soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services at different scales. Results of evaluation are not yet available.

Indicators

SERENA has worked on indicators in two main ways:

- By investigating which indicators have already been used in the different countries taking part in SERENA (D3.1.1, Michel & Niedzwiecki, 2022; D3.1.2, Michel & Niedzwiecki, 2023)
- By selecting indicators that are to be used for evaluation of different soil threats, soil-based ecosystem services and bundles within SERENA (D2.3, Montagne et al 2023). In this a distinction has been made between ideal indicators and realistic ones. Ideal indicators are those that would allow the best evaluation, but these may not always be possible to apply, e.g. because of lack of data. Realistic indicators are the ones that could be applied. Table A1.1 provides an overview of which ideal and realistic indicators have so far been identified.

Table A1.1: List of "ideal" and "realistic" indicators of soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services selected for a harmonisation of assessment of soil threats and services at the European level (Montagne et al 2023)

Soil threat / Soil Ecosystem Services	Ideal indicator	Realistic indicator
Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) loss	Change in SOC stocks	
Soil erosion	Soil loss	Soil loss by water
Soil compaction	Change in bulk density	
Soil sealing	Change in soil sealing	Soil sealing
Primary biomass production		
Greenhouse gas and climate regulation		Net ecosystem productivity
Erosion control	Non-eroded soil	Non-eroded soil by water

A2: Literature

Arshad and Martin (2002)

Introduction

Twenty years ago Arshad and Martin (2002) summarised research into soil quality that was conducted in the 1990's, and provided principles for soil quality evaluation that are still relevant today. They explained how key indicators can be used to determine trends in soil quality for various ecosystems.

They defined soil quality indicators as measurable soil properties that influence the capacity of soil to perform crop production or environmental functions. As the intention is to use indicators to evaluate effects of management, one of the most important requirements for indicators is that they are sensitive to management. They defined threshold values as values which must be maintained for normal functioning of the soil. Thresholds are needed to monitor changes (direction, rate, magnitude, extent, etc.), and determine trends in soil quality.

Changes in soil quality can then be assessed by comparing values of appropriate indicators with desired values (critical limits or threshold level), at different time intervals, for a specific use in a selected agro-ecosystem.

For the reference/baseline value they suggested an approach based on the distribution of values encountered within the agro-ecosystem in question. For example, the reference value could be the average value of an indicator used for a specific ecological zone. Critical limits could, for each indicator separately, be defined in terms of % change compared to an original condition. Such an approach avoids having to look for undisturbed sites to obtain reference values.

Indicators

Arshad and Martin (2002) suggested the following key soil indicators for soil quality assessment: organic matter, topsoil-depth, aggregation, texture, bulk density, infiltration, pH, electrical conductivity, suspected pollutants, soil respiration. Forms of N and extractable N, P and K.

Van Camp et al (2004)

Introduction

Van Camp et al (2004) discussed the state of soil monitoring in member states (MS), and provided advice for integration of soil monitoring work in Europe. They noted that not all soil parameters might be useful to monitor in all MS, and that thus considerable flexibility will be needed in selecting parameters that most clearly reflect local problems and concerns. They, on the other hand, also recommended a basic list of parameters to be measured in all Level-1 sites. More detailed investigation on e.g. specific soil threats or specific problems could then be done at Level-2 and Level-3 sites.

Indicators

The proposed list of parameters to determine at Level-1 sites is:

- Soil profile description according to an agreed International System, including observations on e.g. soil structure, evidence of compaction, status of the soil surface, depth the impermeable layers, stoniness;
- Soil classification according to an agreed International System, such as the World Reference Base;

- Identification of soil parent material;
- A sampling design that allows for long-term, robust assessment, that allows inherent variability of the site to be separated from long-term change;
- Site characteristics, such as slope, aspect, historical and current land use and land management;
- An agreement on sampling depth (by horizon, by fixed depth or both; when sampling by depth steps, information on the limits of the relevant horizon is necessary)
- Soil bulk density;
- Stone content and stone size;
- Particle size distribution (sand, silt, clay);
- Soil pH (water, an electrolyte);
- Soil cation exchange capacity
- Soil water holding capacity;

This is seen as an initial list of basic parameters that need to be determined when soil monitoring is started, which explains why many of the parameters listed above are strictly speaking not indicators as they are not responsive to e.g. management. Separate lists of indicators to monitor for different soil threats at different levels are also provided by Van Camp et al (2004).

Vogel et al (2019)

Introduction

Vogel et al (2019) studied methods to quantify the 5 soil functions production, climate control, water quantity and quality, nutrient cycling and habitat provision for soil biodiversity. In order to evaluate soil functions, indicators are needed. Vogel et al (2019) compared the intrinsic potential (based on inherent soil properties) with the current status (based on manageable soil properties). They considered both inherent properties and manageable properties as indicators, but following our definition of soil indicators only the manageable properties would be considered indicators. These manageable properties are assumed to be at optimal state in the evaluation of potential soil quality, and the difference with current soil quality is then determined by the manageable soil properties. The difference between potential soil quality and actual soil quality then indicates what effect proper management can have on soil quality.

Vogel et al (2019) also noted that there are different motivations for soil function evaluation, which result in different concepts for evaluation. They distinguished the following 4 dimensions:

- the target functions (i.e., which soil functions are considered and how these are defined),
- the purpose of evaluation (i.e., do we want to know actual state of a soil or its potential to fulfill a certain function),
- the spatial scale (i.e., evaluation of a local soil or mapping of soil functions across landscapes);
- the target group (i.e., farmers, authorities, environmental agencies and the public).

Indicators

Vogel et al (2019) used the following manageable soil properties:

Physical: bulk density, air capacity, plant available water, hydraulic conductivity

Chemical: SOC, pH

Biological: earthworm abundance, species diversity

For these indicators, continuous scoring functions were used to transform the indicator value to a value between 0 and 1. For production of wheat, plausible optimal and critical thresholds are given for a central European humid climate (i.e. as in Germany) with a silty loam soil. For other climatic conditions, cropping systems and soils scoring would need to be different. Although this means that no generally valid thresholds can be set, this also provides flexibility to optimize the general concept of using scoring functions for local applications.

Panagos et al (2020)

Introduction

In 2020, JRC published a report (Panagos *et al.* 2020) on ‘Soil related indicators to support agro-environmental policies’ that proposed to include the following issues: soil erosion (based on modelling), soil carbon changes and soil nutrients (based on LUCAS database measurements of C, N, P, and K) (Faber *et al.* 2022). Soil erosion and organic carbon were proposed because they are the most relevant indicators to monitor the impact of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) on soil.

Indicators

The CAP indicator on soil erosion, consists of two sub-indicators, namely (a) estimated rate of soil loss by water erosion ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$), and (b) estimated agricultural area affected by a certain rate of soil erosion by water (ha). A threshold of $11 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$ is applied to map the agricultural areas under severe erosion, while erosion rates of less than $2 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$ are considered sustainable as this equals the generally accepted soil formation rates (Verheijen *et al.*, 2009).

In addition, a soil fertility index was proposed for which the following physical–chemical indicators were selected: available water content (AWC), water-filled porosity (WFP, ratio between water content at 33 kPa and total porosity), pH, soil organic carbon (SOC), cation exchange capacity (CEC), Olsen phosphorus (Pav) and exchangeable potassium (Kex) (Panagos *et al.* 2020). A pedotransfer function, using texture and SOC as independent variables, was applied to estimate AWC and WFP. The proposed soil fertility index is based solely on soil properties and therefore does not include the influence of climatic conditions and management practices.

A3: Other (EC-funded) projects

ENVASSO

Introduction

ENVASSO (Huber *et al.* 2008) was one of the first projects looking at which indicators to use for evaluating different soil threats. The purpose was to propose a well-defined set of indicators for each soil threat, based on sound science and using literature review.

Indicators

ENVASSO selected 3 indicators for each soil threat, as shown in Table A3.1. These TOP3 indicators were selected by expert judgement on the basis of the following criteria: relevance for assessing the soil threat, ease of application (focused on thresholds), linkage to policy aims and applicability in a pan-European context.

Table A3.1. TOP3 indicators proposed by ENVASSO (Huber et al 2008)

	Indicator 1	Indicator 2	Indicator 3
Soil Erosion	Estimated soil loss by rill, inter-rill, and sheet erosion	Estimated soil loss by wind erosion	Estimated soil loss by tillage erosion
Decline soil organic matter	Topsoil organic carbon content (measured)	Soil organic carbon stocks (measured)	Peat stocks (calculated or modelled)
Contamination	Heavy metal contents in soils	Critical load exceedance by sulphur and nitrogen	Progress in management of contaminated sites
Sealing	Sealed area	Land take (CLC)	New settlement area established on previously developed land
Soil compaction	Density (bulk density, packing density, total porosity)	Air-filled pore volume at a specified suction	Vulnerability to compaction (estimated)
Decline soil biodiversity	Earthworms diversity and fresh biomass	Collembola diversity (Enchytraeids diversity if no earthworms)	Microbial respiration
Salinisation	Salt profile	Exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP)	Potential salt sources (groundwater or irrigation water) and vulnerability of soils to salinisation/sodification
Landslides	Occurrence of landslide activity	Volume/weight of displaced material	Landslide hazard assessment
Desertification	Land area at risk of Desertification	Land area (forest and other non-agricultural land use) burnt by wildfires	Soil organic carbon content in desertified land

RECARE

Introduction

Within the FP7 RECARE project a review of soil threat was undertaken (Stolte et al, 2016). In this review, the following information was provided for each soil threat: description of soil threat, state, drivers/pressures, key indicators, methods to assess status and effects on other soil threats and on soil functions. In the section on indicators, use was made of the ENVASSO work but other literature was taken into account too, resulting in a list that shows similarities with the one from ENVASSO.

Indicators

Table A3.2 gives the list of indicators proposed by RECARE.

Table A3.2. Indicators proposed in RECARE

Soil Threat	Indicators
Soil erosion by water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • area affected by soil erosion (km²) and/or extent of area affected by soil erosion (%) • magnitude of soil erosion/deposition or sediment delivery (tons)
Soil erosion by wind	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • measured soil loss by wind (t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) • annual/periodic estimates of wind erosion • soils' susceptibility to wind erosion <p><i>Proxy indicators</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • soil resistance (Ohms) • surface roughness (%) • wind velocity (km hr⁻¹) • soil moisture content (%) • soil cover (% , ha)
Decline OM peat soils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • peat stocks (Mt) <p><i>Proxy indicators</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • water table (m) • soil moisture content (%) • (soil) temperature (°C) • vegetation type (species)
Decline OM mineral soils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • total carbon stocks to 1 m depth ((t ha⁻¹) • clay/SOC • TOP2 indicators by ENVASSO
Soil compaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • relative Normalized Density, • air-filled pore volume (%) • penetration resistance (Mpa)
Soil sealing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sealed area (ha, %) • transition index (TI) • sealed to green areas ratio
Soil contamination	TOP3 indicators by ENVASSO
Soil salinisation	TOP3 indicators by ENVASSO
Desertification	TOP3 indicators by ENVASSO
Flooding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • seasonality, magnitude and frequency of precipitation/rainfall intensity • extent of inundated area (ha) • flood frequency (number per year) • loss of crops due to inundation of fields (ha, Euro)
Landslides	TOP3 indicators by ENVASSO
Loss of soil biodiversity	TOP3 indicators by ENVASSO

LANDMARK

Introduction

LANDMARK was a European Research Project (H2020) on the sustainable management of land and soil in Europe. It aimed to quantify the current and potential supply of **soil functions** across the EU, as

determined by soil properties (soil diagnostic criteria), land use (arable, grassland, forestry) and soil management practices.

Indicators

LANDMARK has proposed indicators to assess five main soil functions: primary productivity, water purification and regulation, climate regulation and carbon sequestration, soil biodiversity and habitat provisioning, and provision and cycling of nutrients (Faber et al 2022). For example, for soil biodiversity (Van Leeuwen et al 2019) an indicator system was used that incorporates four integrated attributes: (1) soil nutrient status, (2) soil biological status, (3) soil structure, and (4) soil hydrological status. For cropland a total of 31 attributes were used; these included inherent properties but also indicators.

iSQAPER

Introduction

As part of the iSQAPER project, Bunemann et al (2018) reviewed soil quality. Like other authors they noted that factors like parent material, climate, topography and hydrology may influence potential values of soil properties to such a degree that it is not possible to establish universal target values in absolute terms. Like Arshad and Martin (2002) they recommend the use of a minimum dataset, because with larger numbers of indicators complexity increases, and so do interrelationships between indicators. Indicators should fulfill a number of requirements:

- They must be related to a given soil threat, function or SES
- Sampling and measurement should be easy
- They should be cost-effective (reliable and not too expensive)
- They should be practical (e.g. the need for undisturbed samples makes an indicator less practical)
- They should be sensitive to changes in management
- Comparability with other (often earlier) campaigns should be ensured
- It should be possible to interpret measured values unequivocally
- Reference values and target values should be available. With regard to target values Bunemann et al (2018) noted: *‘Obviously, acceptable target ranges of soil quality indicators need to be soil- and land use-specific, and they depend not only on targeted soil functions, but also on both spatial and temporal scale of soil quality assessments [...]. In addition, acceptable ranges of a soil quality indicator for one property or process are often highly dependent on the value of another soil property or process, e.g. dependence of microbial biomass or soil organic carbon on soil texture (Candinas et al., 2002; Johannes et al., 2017). [...] A comparative approach in which indicator values or scores of a given sampling point are put in relation to other sampling points may be the most intuitive and flexible basis for interpretation, since it gives a relative assessment (e.g. top 25%) and allows continuing evolution of the system.’*

iSQAPER proceeded to develop an app called SQAPP (Soil Quality App)¹⁰ that allows users to evaluate soil quality in the field based on global datasets. The app allows users to adapt values suggested by these datasets if users have more precise local information. This finally results in advice regarding soil management.

Indicators

Bunemann et al (2018) provided information on the frequency of use of different indicators within soil quality assessments. They found that the 5 most used indicators are total organic matter/carbon, pH, available P, water storage and bulk density, with the first three being chemical indicators and the last

¹⁰ [SQAPP \(isqaper-is.eu\)](https://isqaper-is.eu)

two being physical indicators. Biological indicators were only used by a few assessments. Bunemann et al (2018) recommended to include biological indicators as literature indicates that soil biota are the most sensitive indicators of soil quality as they respond quickly to changes in environmental conditions. Physical and chemical indicators often respond much slower.

SoilCare

Introduction

The H2020 project SoilCare aimed to identify soil-improving cropping systems (SICS) that are sustainable and profitable (Hessel et al 2022). To do this potential SICS were selected and implemented for testing in 16 study sites distributed throughout Europe, in collaboration with stakeholders. Within these study sites SICS were investigated to determine whether they resulted in improved sustainability and profitability. Indicators were used to determine whether SICS had an effect on sustainability and profitability.

Indicators

To facilitate the evaluation of SICS, Alaoui et al (2022) developed a framework to assess the effects of SICS on soil quality, profitability and sustainability. The framework was based on monitoring environmental dimension (physical, chemical and biological soil properties, see Table A3.3), socio-cultural dimension and economic dimension. Indicators were used in a decision tree to be able to use a combination of quantitative and qualitative data, and to be able to give different weights to different indicators.

Table A3.3. Indicators used for the environmental dimension in SoilCare

physical	Infiltration Aggregate stability Bulk density Penetration resistance
chemical	Mineral nitrogen SOC pH
biological	Earthworm density Crop yield Yield quality Crop cover characteristics Pests Root diseases Weed diseases

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